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Adoption Level of Recommended Agricultural Practices by Punjab Farmers

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ABSTRACT

Punjab is predominately an agrarian state and largest contributor of food grains to the central pool. In current scenario, though we have achieved great success in agricultural production and productivity and became not only self reliant but rather surplus producer of many agricultural commodities, but at the same time, we are facing a sort of crisis on many fronts. The rising cost of cultivation, stagnating yields, dwindling underground water reserves, pest resistance, resurgence of new weeds etc. are some of the concerns. To counter balance these issues farmers in the state were resorting to higher doses of nutrients, pesticides, irrigations etc. than the recommended levels. Then there are certain practices regarding residue disposal, seed treatment, soil testing etc. which also have a bearing on sustainability of state agriculture. It was found that though having good farming experience and education level, farmers of the state were not sticking to the recommended practices and resource use levels. Some constraints were cited by the sampled farmers regarding this aspect. These included higher doses of fertilizers and number of irrigations to enhance the productivity, spurious quality of pesticides leading to higher doses, stubble burning due to lack of viable alternative and low awareness about recommendation of soil testing etc. So it was found that farmers equipped with education and expertise in farming were by and large aware about the issues concerning agricultural development, but the constraints emerging mainly due to on-going mono-culture in agricultural production were posing a threat to sustainable growth in the state.

Key Words: Adoption, Agricultural practices, Irrigation, Paddy, Pesticides, Variety, Wheat

INTRODUCTION

In developing nations like India, agriculture still holds the key to reducing poverty and increasing the security of livelihoods. Human resource is one of most important inputs for development of agricultural and allied sectors. Agriculture being the backbone of Indian economy, the human resource needs to undertake various activities related to agricultural development which is critical to attain country's goals towards rural development, employment generation and host of related fields leading to sustainable growth. Indian agricultural sector has shown spectacular achievement from deficit to surplus since the inception of 'Green Revolution'. However, over the years, the scenario has changed. The growth in agriculture sector has slowed down

and the job opportunities have declined in wake of mechanization leading to increased unemployment. To deal with these issues, the importance of training cannot be underestimated. The skills to improve productivity, increase adaptability to deal with change and crisis, and facilitate the diversification of livelihoods to manage risks are at a premium in rural areas (Collette and Gale, 2009). Providing these skills effectively is one of the key challenges of rural development.

Punjab agriculture has made tremendous achievement, due to its human resource who could harness the rapid developments in science and technology. No one can undermine the enthusiasm of the state's zesty farming community in adoption of new technologies. The growth achieved by the

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state agriculture in sustaining food security of the nation and various activities related to agricultural development can be attributed to the concerted efforts of available skilled human force.

Some concerns have emerged in the state agriculture in the last two decades or so, in terms of depleting natural resources in wake of intensive agriculture like stagnating yields, rising costs and shrinking profit margins, high indebtedness of farmers leading to suicides. So, there is urgent need to sustain the livelihood of rural masses especially the marginal and small farmers of the state.

Human activities have always had significant impact on the environment. It is a paradoxical situation that the very development achieved by man in different fields that led to his welfare, now poses threat to present and future generations (Nagarajan and Nagarajan, 2000). With the market forces at the helm of affairs, the demand for natural resources and environmental services to support resource intensive development has grown infinitely (Sengupta, 2001). This issue has gained importance in the present context as many natural resources, which were once regarded as free goods, have now become scarce resources on one hand and on the other; there is immediate need to prevent depletion/degradation of these resources to make the sustainable growth feasible. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to study the awareness as well as adoption level of recommended agricultural practices by Punjab farmers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study is based on primary data collected from farm households of randomly selected 10 blocks from three agri-economic zones viz. sub-mountainous zone (Zone I), central plain zone (zone II) and south western zone (zone III) of the state. At second stage of sampling, two villages from each selected block and 25 farm households from each village were selected. Based on size of the operational holding, farmers were classified into three categories i.e. small, medium and

large. Thus, the ultimate sample consisted of 495 farm households in proportion to the size holding structure existing in that particular village. The data were collected about inputs use pattern including fertilizers, pesticides, irrigations, soil testing practice, seed treatment etc. from selected sample of farm households across the state through especially structured and pre-tested questionnaire using personal interview method. Awareness along with adoption was sought regarding various agricultural practices as well as the constraints faced by farmers in following the recommended practices. Statistical techniques like percentage, average etc. were worked out for the variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Educational status

Education plays an important role in determining the socio-economic status and level of awareness of the respondents. As far as this knowledge parameter was concerned, majority of the farmers i.e. 51.21 per cent in the study were found to be matriculates and 17.37 per cent were illiterate (Table 1), where as 14.17 per cent farmers have studied beyond matriculation but were under graduates followed by 10.12 per cent who have acquired education up to primary level. Further, 7.08 percent were graduates and above. Statistical analysis has shown that large farmers were more educated may be due to their sound financial status. Education and size of holding were found to be directly related to each other. Sampled farmers of zone III were found to be significantly less educated than farmers of zone II and zone I, respectively.

Farming Experience

It was found that average experience of the sampled farmers in state was 27.47 yr. in agriculture production (Table 2). In zone I, 65 per cent of the farmers were having farming experience of more than 25 yr. followed by 58 per cent in zone II and 50 per cent in zone III in the state. The measure of variability showed that variation was more in zone III. Medium farmers were found to be more

Recommended Agricultural Practices by Punjab Farmers

Table 1. Educational status of sampled farmers (zone wise and category wise). (Number)

Zone	I				II				III				State	
	Small	Medium	Large	Total (%)	Small	Medium	Large	Total (%)	Small	Medium	Large	Total (%)	Total Punjab	%age
Illiterate	3	1	1	10.87	24	12	12	16.11	11	12	10	21.85	86	17.37
Upto Pri- mary	5	0	0	10.87	17	8	8	11.07	4	4	4	7.95	50	10.10
>5" upto Matric	17	8	5	65.22	61	32	38	43.96	42	22	29	61.59	254	51.31
>10" and under graduation	2	0	2	8.69	22	18	17	19.13	4	0	5	5.96	70	14.14
Graduation and above	0	0	2	4.35	8	6	15	9.73	2	1	1	2.65	35	7.08
Total	27	9	10	100	132	76	90	100	63	39	49	100	495	100

experienced than others as they were also older in age as compared to small and large farm categories.

Table 2. Average farming experience of the respondent's zone wise and category wise (Year)

Zone	Category	Average	S.D	C.V
I	Small	30.66	15.96	52.07
	Medium	30.33	15.83	52.20
	Large	28.00	18.04	64.43
II	Small	26.76	15.93	59.53
	Medium	28.78	15.18	52.73
	Large	29.41	16.79	52.11
III	Small	23.41	14.39	61.49
	Medium	29.20	13.47	46.14
	Large	24.22	13.13	54.21
	I	30.02	16.06	53.52
State	II	28.08	16.00	56.99
	III	25.17	13.88	55.15

Important resources and practices followed

Soil type

It is the basic requirement for most of human or natural activities and is also the major resource available on earth as a bounty. Primary activities like agriculture depend only on the availability and suitability of land. Land of Punjab is mainly formed of the alluvium deposited by rivers of Indus system. It varies widely across the state. The agricultural production depends on the soil texture and composition of the soil of that particular region.

In Punjab, paddy is grown over wide range of soil with pH varying from 5.0 to 9.5 and texturally varying from sandy loam to clay loams. Silty to clayey loam soils with low permeability, free of sodicity and water logging are considered best for paddy cultivation. Majority of the soils are deficient in nitrogen, 52 per cent medium to high, in available phosphorus and 90 per cent medium to high in available potassium. Micronutrients such as iron, zinc, sulphur and manganese are becoming critical due to intensive cultivation.

Soil testing

The profitable combination of rice-wheat crops has led to higher doses of inputs like chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Excessive use of these chemicals, mechanical operations, lesser use of farm compost as well as non-cycling of crop residues in the soil has created deficiencies of nutrients in the soil. Shukla *et al* (2014) has reported that in Punjab, 16.6, 6.2, 3.6 and 15.2 per cent soil samples were found deficient in zinc, ferrous, copper and manganese, respectively. Similarly, Singh *et al* (2016) reported that organic carbon (OC) status of majority of soil samples analysed ranged between low to medium in district Kapurthala which falls under zone II. The Punjab soils were already having low organic carbon content, which has further declined. Thus soil testing becomes important to supervise the indiscriminate application of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. The data (Table 3) showed that from the total sampled farmers across the zones, only 23 per cent farmers got their soil tested at some point of time. Zone I showed highest proportion (33%) followed by zone II (22%) and zone III (22%), farmers responded in positive for undertaking soil testing. Category-wise, it was found that 30 per cent of the medium farmers, 27 per cent of large farmers and 17 per cent of small farmers have reported to get the soil tested.

Table 3. Soil testing undertaken by farmers' zone wise and category wise

(Number)

Zone	Small	Medium	Large	State
I	7 (25.92)	4 (44.44)	4 (40.00)	15 (32.60)
II	19 (14.39)	24 (31.57)	24 (26.66)	67 (22.48)
III	12 (19.04)	9 (23.07)	12 (24.48)	33 (21.85)
State	38 (17.11)	37 (29.83)	40 (26.84)	115 (23.23)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total

Seed treatment

It is a recommended practice to undertake seed treatment with application of fungicides and insecticides to control the seed born diseases of the crop. Out of total sampled farmers (Table 4),

about 96 per cent reported following this practice. In zone I, 98 per cent of the farmers, 96 per cent in zone II and 94 per cent in zone III were found to be following this practice. It was found that the cost of the practice was not much, but prevention of suspected diseases can go a long way with this treatment. Category wise, 92 per cent of the small farmers had undertaken the seed treatment, where as about 98 per cent of the medium and large farmers have gone with it while sowing the crops. The small farmers were found to be less concerned about this practice as compared to medium and large farmers probably due to the expenses involved in the activity.

Table 4. Seed treatment undertaken by sampled farmers zone wise and category wise (Number)

Zone	Small	Medium	Large	Total
I	26 (96.29)	9 (100)	10 (100)	45 (97.82)
II	125 (94.69)	73 (96.05)	89 (98.88)	287 (96.3)
III	56 (88.88)	39 (100)	48 (97.95)	143 (94.7)
State	207 (92.34)	121 (97.58)	147 (98.65)	475 (95.95)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total

Fertilizer Use

Intensive cultivation in the wake of increased cropping intensity in state agriculture puts stress on soil fertility. The natural capacity of the soil to produce gets depleted with nutrients being extracted from it. The soil has to be replenished continuously to maintain its fertility level. With decline in practices like keeping fallow land, diversified crop rotations, less availability of organic matter, the dependence has increased on chemical fertilizers in the growth of state agriculture. To overcome the nutrient deficiencies caused by intensive agriculture, the use of chemical fertilizers has increased in the state over time. Per hectare use of NPK was 762 thousand tons in 1980-1981 which has increased to 2270 thousand tons in 2015-2016. Judicious application of fertilizers fulfils the nutrient requirement of the crops but overuse of it could result in degradation of soil, water and crop quality. Punjab has emerged as highest user of fertilizers per hectare of cropped area in the country. This not only adds to the cost

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of cultivation thus squeezing the profit margins, but also creates stress on environment.

The farmers were enquired about the doses of fertilizers used for the crops. In zone I, 77 per cent each of small and medium farmers and 70 per cent of large farmers were found to be using recommended doses of fertilizers (Table 5). In all 76 per cent of the total sampled farms were using recommended levels of fertilizers. In zone II, 22.7 per cent of small farms, 9.21 per cent of medium farms and about 8 per cent of large farms were using the fertilizers as per the recommended levels. So, only 14.76 per cent of the sampled farms were adding the fertilizers as per package of practices in this zone. In zone III i.e. cotton belt of the state, 40 per cent of small farmers, about 8 per cent of medium farms and 16 per cent of large farmers were applying fertilizers doses as per recommended levels. So, in this zone 33 per cent of sampled households were using recommended doses of fertilizers. For the state as a whole, 34 per cent of small farms, 13.7 per cent of medium farms and 14.8 per cent of large farms were found to be using recommended fertilizers levels and overall 23 per cent of the farms in state were at this level.

Thus, it was evident that farmers in sub-mountainous zone (zone I) were using fertilizers according to recommendation, followed by zone III and lastly by zone II. Zone II is the central plain

zone, where farmers were using higher fertilizers than the recommended package of practices. Manan *et al* (2016) reported that in Kapurthala, 63 per cent of farmers were adding higher quantity of phosphatic fertilizer (DAP) than the recommended dose in growing spring maize. Further, Manan *et al* (2015) also reported that adoption of cultivation practices such as application of urea fertilizer at the time of sowing and recommended dose of di-ammonium phosphate fertilizer by the farmers was 19.0 and 38.4 per cent, respectively in wheat crop.

It was also noticed that category-wise, small farmers were using fertilizers more optimally than medium and large farmers in the state. The scenario was found to be same in all the zones. The reason could be the financial constraint of the small farmers which is limiting them to the recommended doses of fertilizers for crop cultivation.

Table 5. Use of recommended fertilizers zone wise and category wise (Number)

Zone	Small	Medium	Large	Total
I	21 (77.7)	7 (77.7)	7 (70.0)	35 (76.08)
II	30(22.7)	7 (9.21)	7 (7.8)	44 (14.76)
III	25 (39.7)	3 (7.7)	8 (16.3)	36 (33.29)
Total	76 (34.23)	17 (13.70)	22 (14.76)	115(23.23)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total.

Table 6. Varieties of Paddy and other Kharif crops grown by sampled farmers zone wise and category wise. (Number)

Zone	Particulars	Paddy				Other kharif crops			
		Small	Medium	Large	Total	Small	Medium	Large	Total
I	Recommended	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (10)	1 (2.17)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	Non-Recommended	7 (25.93)	5 (55.56)	4 (40.0)	16 (34.78)	26 (96.3)	9 (100)	10 (100)	45 (97.83)
II	Recommended	16 (12.12)	23 (30.26)	14 (15.56)	53 (17.78)	5 (3.78)	6 (7.89)	22 (24.44)	33 (11.07)
	Non-Recommended	97 (73.48)	66 (86.84)	69 (76.67)	232 (77.85)	13 (9.84)	3 (3.94)	11 (12.22)	27 (9.06)
III	Recommended	18 (28.57)	9 (23.08)	27 (69.23)	54 (35.76)	9 (14.29)	6 (15.38)	17 (34.69)	32 (21.19)
	Non-Recommended	15 (23.81)	17 (43.59)	19 (48.72)	51 (33.77)	27 (42.86)	20 (51.28)	29 (59.18)	76 (50.33)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total.

Table 7. Varieties grown of wheat crop by sampled farmers zone wise and category wise.**(Number)**

Zone	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Total
I	Recommended	27 (100)	9 (100)	10 (100)	46 (100)
	Non-Recommended	4 (14.81)	2 (22.22)	2 (20.00)	8 (17.39)
II	Recommended	94 (71.21)	51 (67.10)	38 (42.22)	18 (61.40)
	Non-Recommended	40 (30.30)	23 (30.26)	29 (30.22)	92 (30.87)
III	Recommended	28 (44.44)	32 (82.05)	50 (33.11)	110(72.85)
	Non-Recommended	37 (58.73)	22 (56.41)	25 (51.02)	84 (55.63)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total

Varieties Sown by sampled farmers

Different varieties of crops vary not only in nutrient requirements and yield levels but also have difference in resistance to pests, diseases etc. Varieties are recommended by the research institutions according to technical feasibility in a particular area/region but some times farmers do not stick to these varieties due to their own constraints like failure to sow it on time, inadequate yield in particular zone, more pest/disease attacks etc. therefore, they also grow unrecommended varieties. It was found that in zone II, 78 per cent farmers growing non-recommended varieties of the paddy followed by zone I (35%) and zone III (34%). Considering other kharif crops, 98 per cent of zone I farmers were growing non-recommended varieties of maize such as hishell and DKC 7074 followed by 50 per cent in zone III of cotton hybrids such as RCH 650, SP 7007 and SP 7010.

Data in Table 7 revealed that in wheat crop, 56 per cent of the farmers were growing non-recommended varieties such as HD 2733 in zone III followed by zone II (31 %) and zone I (17 %), on contrary to it, data also showed 61-100 per cent adoption of recommended wheat varieties indicating overlapping responses from the farmers following both types of wheat varieties (recommended and non-recommended) on some area.

Pesticides usage in Punjab agriculture

The high yielding varieties under the plant protection umbrella with higher energy subsidies

in fertilizers and irrigation has aggravated the pest problems. This has led to increased use of pesticides to get higher yields but this practice has caused the imbalance in natural control in crops like cotton, which have become vulnerable to minor disturbances in a biotic factors leading to frequent losses. This resulted in emergence of new pest problems and development of resistance to pesticides (Dhaliwal *et al*, 2000). On the other hand, farmers use higher levels of non-recommended pesticides as they find difficulties in adaptation to cultural practices, non-availability of resistant varieties with good yield potential, lack of quality control in available pesticides as well as lack of efficient bio-control measures.

Table 8. Use of recommended doses of pesticides zone wise and category wise.**(Number)**

Zone	Small	Medium	Large	Total
I	25 (92.6)	8 (88.9)	6 (60.6)	39 (84.78)
II	40 (30.3)	9 (11.8)	5 (5.5)	54 (18.12)
II	41 (65.08)	14 (18.4)	21 (42.8)	76 (50.33)
Total	10 (47.74)	31 (25.0)	32 (21.47)	169 (34.14)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total.

In the survey, sampled farmers (85 %) in zone I responded that they do not indulge in indiscriminate use of agro-chemicals. However, in zone II, only 18 per cent were found to be sticking to recommended doses and rest was using higher levels of agro-chemicals. In zone III 50 per cent of

Recommended Agricultural Practices by Punjab Farmers

the respondents reported that they use the pesticides as per the recommended application. Majority of small farmers were using recommended doses and least proportion of large farmers were adhering to norms (Table 8). For the state as a whole, about 48 per cent of small farms, 25 per cent of medium farms and 21 per cent of large farms were found to be following the practice of recommended doses of pesticides. In all, 34 per cent of the total sampled farmers were quoted as sticking to the practice.

Application of irrigations

This aspect is directly related to environment as Punjab Agriculture is mainly dependent on utilisation of underground water reserves for irrigation with shrinking canal irrigation network and erratic pattern of rainfall. More is the number of irrigations applied, more is the indirect cost to the state in the form of power subsidy as well as water. The analysis of this aspect showed that more than 99 per cent of the sampled farmers in the state were following the recommended number of irrigations for wheat crop, however, the case was not same for paddy as is evident from the following table.

There was significant difference in water usage of three categories of farmers and directly related to size of the holding i.e. small farmers were using water more economically as compared to medium and large farmers. There was significant difference

in number of irrigations applied to the wheat crop across the zones. It was found to be more in zone I followed by zone III and zone II. Significant difference was observed in number of irrigations during *kharif* season as well in three zones of the state. It was higher in zone II due to the fact that paddy was the main *kharif* crop in this zone followed by zone III and zone I where the area under paddy cultivation was least.

Residue Disposal

With 28 lakh hectares under wheat and paddy cultivation in the state, a total of 47.2 million ton of straw is generated every year. This included 25 lakh tonnes of wheat straw and 22 lakh ton of paddy straw. Out of this 95 per cent of paddy straw and 25 per cent of wheat straw is burnt each year (GOP, 2014). The mechanized harvesting of these crops has further added to the quantity of residue. At the time of manual harvesting, the straw was chopped into small pieces and ploughed back into the soil to improve its content. Though, a ban was imposed on stubble burning by the state government way back in 2005, but the practice is still going on due to non- implementation of the ban. The problem has been highlighted by the United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and Supreme Court of India has also taken a serious note of it, but of no avail.

Table 9. Irrigations applied by sampled farmers, zone wise and category wise

(Number)

Zone	Paddy (Higher)				Wheat (Recommended)			
	Small	Medium	Large	Total	Small	Medium	Large	Total
I	7 (25.92)	5 (55.56)	4 (40.0)	16 (34.78)	27 (100)	9 (100)	10 (100)	46 (100)
II	126 (95.45)	76 (100)	90 (100)	292 (97.98)	130 (98.48)	76 (100)	90 (100)	296 (99.33)
III	42 (66.66)	26 (66.67)	33 (67.35)	101 (66.88)	63 (100)	39 (100)	49 (100)	151 (100)
State	175 (78.82)	107 (86.29)	127 (85.23)	409 (82.62)	220 (99.1)	124 (100)	149 (100)	493 (99.6)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total.

Table 10. Sampled farmers not resorting to residue burning zone wise and category wise**(Number)**

Zone	Small	Medium	Large	Total
I	26 (56.52)	8 (17.39)	10 (21.73)	44 (95.65)
II	88 (29.53)	43 (14.42)	42 (91.30)	173 (58.05)
III	52 (34.43)	30 (19.86)	33 (21.85)	115 (77.48)
Punjab	168 (75.67)	81 (65.32)	85 (57.05)	334 (67.47)

It was found that 96 per cent of sampled farmers of zone I were not indulged in the practice of stubble burning, whereas in zone II, this proportion was minimum i.e. 58 per cent, while 77 per cent of the respondents denied this practice in zone III. Overall for the state, 67 per cent sampled farmers in the study were found to be not resorting to residue burning, with maximum number of small farmers and minimum number of large farmers thereof.

Constraints of farmers pertaining to recommended level of resource use and agricultural practices

It was found that though having good farming experience and educational level, farmers of the state were not sticking to the recommended practices. Lack of knowledge regarding the soil testing aspect as well as lack of the facility to undertake it near the village emerged as the reasons for not following this practice by the respondents.

Paddy emerging as major *kharif* crop in all the agro climatic zones of the state and it being the water intensive crop has led to the grim ground water situation in the state. Erratic rainfall pattern, fear of loss in yield with less number of irrigations has caused the higher application of irrigations in paddy. The situation was found to be as per recommendations in case of wheat crop. The prominent reason cited for higher levels of fertilizer application was to enhance the crop yields followed by maintenance of soil fertility and to cope with deficit rainfall/ water availability. Lack of knowledge did not emerge as a reason for over fertilization in the state. Only 2 per cent of the farmers showed ignorance about proper knowledge regarding fertilizer doses.

The spurious quality of pesticides emerged as the main reason for higher usage of pesticide by the sampled farmers, followed by increased incidence of pest/disease attacks on the crops in recent times. The recommended doses were found to be ineffective by them. Regarding cultivation of non-recommended varieties mainly in paddy crop, constraints cited by the farmers were inadequate yield of recommended variety in a particular zone, more pest/disease attacks, delay in sowing etc. But by and large, sampled farmers were sowing the crops on recommended times and there was not much variation across the zones.

Residue disposal especially the paddy stubble has emerged as a major problem for the farming community as well as the society as a whole. Lack of state assistance and technical support, high cost of machinery to manage the residue, shortage of time for the next crop and lack of any viable alternative leads to stubble fires. All the sampled farmers were found to be against the burning of crop residue, but due to the above cited reasons the practice was going on.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that majority of farmers equipped with knowledge parameters of education and good farming experience were by and large well aware about the issues posing threat to sustainable growth of agriculture in the state, but were tied due to constraints emerging mainly on account of mono-culture being followed in the cropping pattern of the state. Different suggestions were put forward by the respondents to tackle these concerns, involving government action whether co-operative or coercive.

Policy intervention and good price remuneration with assured market for alternative crops is the only key. Though each state government has its own agricultural policy, it is largely the Central government funds and policies which define a state's focus. The need of the hour is to diversify to other crops, especially pulses and horticulture.

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Alternatives to wheat and rice have to be either at par or above in terms of price and profits.

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Adoption of Scientific Farm Innovations Towards Enhancing Nutritional Security in Selected Areas of Kalimpong, West Bengal

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ABSTRACT

Among the four pillars of nutritional security *viz.* food availability, access, utilization, and stability, first one is the most important pillar. Agricultural technologies have a special role in developing countries, boosting the growth of the agricultural sector, hence driving the overall growth and lowering food prices. Agricultural technologies can also directly contribute to alleviate food insecurity: they can improve crops productivity allowing for higher production both for self-consumption and for increased household income, reduce risks of crop failure in case of physical shocks, such as drought or floods. In this backdrop, the present study was undertaken in Kalimpong Hills of West Bengal to assess the adoption level of agricultural technologies. Education being the most dominating factor towards adoption of farm innovations, the present study also analyzed the association of education with adoption of innovation. The study revealed that the farmers of Kalimpong hills adopted different production technologies with varied levels. It was also found that literacy level has profound effect on adoption of different scientific farm innovations.

Key Words: Adoption, Agricultural innovations, Education, Food security, Hill farming.

INTRODUCTION

Food security is to ensure that all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life (FAO, 1996). Among the most important causes of food insecurity, extended periods of poverty and lack of adequate productive or financial resources are the most severe, especially in rural areas of developing countries (Barrett, 2010). About the productive resources, agricultural technologies have a special role in developing countries, boosting the growth of the agricultural sector, hence driving the overall growth and lowering food prices. In developing countries, multidimensional welfare impacts are expected through adoption of improved varieties, including poverty reduction, food security enhancement, and

better nutrition outcomes. At the farm household level, welfare impacts of agricultural technologies primarily occur through adoption, a decision made by the farmer. Agricultural technologies can also directly contribute to alleviate food insecurity: they can improve crops productivity allowing for higher production both for self-consumption and for increased household income (Kassie *et al*, 2012), and can reduce risks of crop failure in case of physical shocks, such as drought or floods (Hagos *et al*, 2012).

Scientific research in agriculture is moving fast and generating numerous new innovations for addressing the farm situations. Numbers of institutional and non-institutional communication sources are actively engaged in transmitting this technical know-how to the farmers. Despite all these efforts, it has been estimated that only 26

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Fig.1. Socio-economic profile of respondents

per cent of the available technology have been adopted so far. It has been found in this connection that knowledge gained through word-of-mouth communication cannot be retained much longer to put in actual practice. A literate farmer is less prone either to fall back on his memory or depend on the advice of his fellow member at the proper time for application of improved technology. Instead, he would be inclined to consult the literature and then act accordingly (Lepcha, 2015).

With this backdrop, the present study was undertaken in Kalimpong Hills of West Bengal to

assess the adoption level of agricultural technologies (scientific farm innovations) and its association with education level of farmers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in four villages selected randomly in the Kalimpong -I block of undivided Darjeeling district during the year 2015. Twenty five farmers from each of the four selected villages were randomly selected, hence the total number of farmers were 100. The data were collected through a structured interview schedule by individual interview.

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Fig.2. Socio-economic profile of respondents

Level of adoption of different production technologies were assessed through Adoption Index (AI) and Overall Adoption Index (OAI). The expression for AI and OAI are as follows:

$$AdoptionIndex(AI) = \frac{n}{N}$$

Where, n = number of farmers adopted the technology and N = total number of farmers

and,

$$Overall\ Adoption\ Index(OAI) = \frac{\sum_i^k = ni}{k, N}$$

Where, ni = number of farmers adopted the ith technology; k = total number of technology and N = total number of farmers

To assess the association between adoption and education χ^2 (Chi-square) were calculated as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$$

Where,

f_o = observed frequency, and
 f_e = expected frequency calculated

Table1. Adoption levels of improved agricultural technologies.**N=100**

Technology	Adopter class	Frequency				Adoption Index	Chi-Square (p-value)
		Illiterate	Up to primary	High school	Above high school		
Quality seed (HYVs)	Adopter	7	20	31	6	0.64	31.22; p<0.001
	Non-adopter	11	20	5	0		
Seed treatment	Adopter	10	16	16	5	0.47	7.15; p>0.41
	Non-adopter	8	24	20	1		
Nursery management	Adopter	9	16	21	5	0.51	7.34; p>0.39
	Non-adopter	9	24	15	1		
Method of sowing	Adopter	6	19	18	4	0.47	2.69; p>0.91
	Non-adopter	12	21	18	2		
Method of irrigation	Adopter	10	14	19	4	0.47	4.59; p>0.70
	Non-adopter	8	26	17	2		
Commercial manures	Adopter	4	12	18	5	0.39	14.71; p<0.04
	Non-adopter	14	28	18	1		
Fertilizers	Adopter	5	16	22	6	0.49	14.36; p<0.05
	Non-adopter	13	24	14	0		
Plant protection chemicals	Adopter	4	15	22	5	0.46	16.60; p<0.03
	Non-adopter	14	25	14	1		
Post harvest measures	Adopter	9	16	17	4	0.46	1.89; p>0.96
	Non-adopter	9	24	19	2		
Overall adoption Index = 0.48							

(Figures expressed in percentage)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic profile of the respondents

Socio-economic profiles are depicted in Fig.1 (A to D) and Fig.2 (E to H). Figures are giving information about the respondents' age, education, caste, major occupation, land holding, family size, income and social participation.

It was seen that majority of the respondents (37%) were under the age group between 36 – 45 yr and only 5 per cent were under the age group between 66 and above. Sixty two per cent of total respondents were engaged in farm practices and rest 18 and 20 per cent were in different services (govt./non govt.) and business respectively. Among all the respondents, 47 per cent belonged to general category, whereas scheduled cast (SC), scheduled tribe (ST) and other backward castes (OBC) were 17 to 24 per cent and 12 per cent, respectively. A

good many number of families (64%) was having medium sized operational holding whereas 36 per cent were under small holding category. The study areas were dominated by small families with 5 or less number of family members (78% of total) and only 22 per cent families had family members of more than 5. It is a matter of concern that only 28 per cent of families were engaged with social organizations or groups (SHGs or Farmers' club). Eight per cent families crossed Rs. 60,000/- income per annum. The whole group was dominated by low education group with more than 50 per cent respondents having no formal education or only up to primary level of education.

Adoption levels of agricultural technologies

The data (Table1) presented the adoption levels of different agricultural technologies. To know the association between adoption and education

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the adopters are distributed according to formal educational class. It was observed that only quality seed viz. the high yielding varieties and nursery management practices could cross the 50 per cent earmark of adoption rate (Index value = 0.64 & 0.51 for quality seed & nursery management, respectively) ranking first and second in respect level of adoption among all the technologies. Commercial manures i.e. vermi-compost or other types were least adopted by the Kalimpong farmers (Index value = 0.39). Others levels were 0.49 for fertilizers, 0.47 all for seed treatment, improved method of sowing and improved method of irrigation, whereas 0.46 both for plant protection chemicals and post harvest measures. The Overall Adoption Index (value = 0.48) depicts a moderate level of technology adoption.

It was also revealed (Table 1) that there was an association between adoption level and education in case of quality seed, commercial manures, fertilizers and plant protection chemicals with p-value <0.05 in all cases. So, it can be said that there was an increase in adoption with the increase of education among the farmers. However, non-significant relationships between the literacy level of the farmers and adoption were also found in case of seed treatment, nursery management, method of sowing, method of irrigation and post harvest measures in all these cases. Although, it is contradictory to general trend of education vs. adoption, but in the present case, it may be that the educated farmers are although eager to adopt these technologies but they may not have training facilities or financial capacity or awareness to adopt these technologies. These findings were in agreement with those reported by Sharma (2016).

Perceived constraints towards adoption of technologies

It was observed (Table 2) that the land topography was the most severe constraint faced by the farmers towards adoption of technology. Eighty seven per cent of total respondents were facing this problem. Hill areas had very steep to terrain type of topography which may hinder to cultivate. lack of scientific knowledge, financial

scarcity, transportation and marketing were also considered as potential constraints towards adoption of technology. Hill farmers rely mostly on family labour for cultivation, so, it was perceived as a moderate level of constraint by them.

Table2. Extent of constraints faced by the hill farmers (N=100)

Sr. No.	Constraint	Percent farmers
1.	Land Topography	87
2.	Lack of scientific knowledge	72
3.	Financial	70
4.	Transportation and marketing	69
5.	Labour	53

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that the farmers of Kalimpong hills adopted different production technologies with varied levels. It was evident from the study that literacy level has profound effect on adoption of different scientific farm innovations. So, it is suggested that to enhance household nutritional securities, farmers should be encouraged to adopt new agricultural technology.

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Changes in Biochemical Parameters in Healthy and Root-Knot Nematode Infested Varieties of Ridge Gourd

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ABSTRACT

Ridge gourd (*Luffa acutangul* (Roxb.) is important Cucurbitaceous vegetable and susceptible host crop facing considerable yield loss due to pest and diseases. The biochemical analysis was carried out in resistant, moderately resistant, susceptible and highly susceptible varieties of both healthy and root-knot nematode infested roots to know the accumulation and variations in biochemical constituents with regard to total phenols, total amino acids, reducing sugar and total sugar. The infested roots of variety Arka Sumeet (830 mg/g, 0.097 mg/g) recorded significantly higher amount of total phenol and amino acids compared to healthy roots and all other varieties studied. Whereas, reducing sugar content was more in infested roots of variety Ridge gourd PN (15.00 mg/g) when compared to healthy roots (10.00 mg/g). Wherein, non-reducing sugar content was higher in healthy roots of variety Ridge gourd PN (12 mg/g) compared to that of infested roots (9.00 mg/g) of same variety. Whereas healthy roots of Ridge gourd PN (9.50 mg/g) recorded more of non reducing sugar compared to 6.75 mg/g in infested roots of same variety.

Key Words: Ridge gourd, Root-knot nematode, Phenols, Sugars and amino-acids

INTRODUCTION

Ridge gourd (*Luffa acutangula* (Roxb) L) is more popular vegetable in the south and east India. Among the production constraints, plant parasitic nematodes are one of the major limiting factors to production. The root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) are cosmopolitan pathogens of plants and cause crop losses worldwide. The host range of Root-knot nematode is extensive with more than two thousands of plant species (Bird *et al*, 2009). Four common *Meloidogyne* species (*Meloidogyne incognita*, *Meloidogyne javanica*, *Meloidogyne hapla* and *Meloidogyne arenaria*) comprise up to 95 per cent of all root-knot nematode populations. *M. incognita* is the most common species accounting for 64 per cent of total population and infects almost all cultivated plants, which makes it perhaps the most damaging of pathogens (Abad *et al*, 2007). At present, only

limited information is available on variation in biochemical changes taking place in healthy and root-knot nematode infested ridge gourd varieties of resistant, moderately resistant, susceptible and highly susceptible during the nematode attack in a pot experiment. This study helped to understand to know biochemical constituents *viz.*, phenols, sugars and aminoacids involved in resistant, moderately resistant, susceptible and highly susceptible reaction of variety to *Meloidogyne incognita*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The screened ridge gourd varieties were taken for analysis of biochemical constituents' *viz.*, phenols, sugars and amino acids in resistant (Arka Sumeet), moderately resistant (RNR), susceptible (US-6001) and highly susceptible Ridge gourd PN seedlings. Seedlings were raised in pots with three kilograms sterilized soil. Three replications were

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maintained for each variety. After seven days of seedling germination, freshly hatched second stage juveniles (J2) of *M. incognita* (2 J2/ g soil) were inoculated into four holes made in the soil around the base of each plant near the rhizosphere. Regular watering, manuring and weeding were followed. The plants were carefully depotted 60 d after nematode inoculation and were carefully washed, cleared of soil.

Total amino acids in root were determined by the ninhydrin method described by Spies (1957) using leucine as standard citrate buffer and ninhydrine solution as reagent. Reducing sugar of the powdered roots was estimated by Simogyi-Nelson method (Nelson, 1944) using reagent A, reagent B (Nelson Chromogenic reagent) and Arsenomolybdate colour reagent. Total sugars estimated by Loomis and Shull (1957) method by using anthrone reagent. Total phenol was estimated in the roots by following the method of Swain and Hills (1959) using Folin Denis reagent (FDR), saturated sodium carbonate solution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phenol content

The study indicated that resistant variety Arka Sumeet (685 mg/g) recorded higher amount of total phenol than moderately resistant variety RNR (660 mg/g), susceptible US-6001 (590 mg/g) and highly susceptible ridge gourd PN (440 mg/g). The infested roots of variety Arka Sumeet (830 mg/g) recorded significantly higher amount of total phenol followed by RNR (798 mg/g), US-6001 (638 mg/g) and ridge gourd PN (460 mg/g) compared to healthy roots (Table 1).

Phenol content and its enhancement during disease progress were least in susceptible varieties. This was in agreement with the findings of Sireesha *et al*, (2015) and Gopinath (2001) who had reported phenolic content was higher in galled (infested roots) than in healthy tissue. Mohanta and Mohanty (2012) reported that, there was an increase in phenolic substances by 36.92 per cent during

post infection period compared to healthy check. In both resistant and highly susceptible varieties sequential development of chitinase, Peroxidase and acid phosphatase takes place but level of these compounds was much higher in roots of resistant variety compared to susceptible variety (Mohamed and Hasabo, 2005).

Table 1. Effect of root-knot nematode, *M. incognita* on phenol content (mg/g).

Sr. No.	Variety	Reaction	Phenol content (mg/g)	
			Healthy	Infested
1	Arka sumeet	R	685	830
2	RNR	MR	660	798
3	US-6001	S	590	638
4	Ridge gourd PN	HS	440	460

Amino acid content

Amino acid content more in Arka Sumeet (0.089 mg/g) compared to ridge gourd PN (0.042 mg/g). Further, the amino acid content more in infested roots of Arka Sumeet (0.097 mg/g) compared to healthy roots (0.089 mg/g) and least in ridge gourd PN (0.049 mg/g and 0.042 mg/g) of infested and healthy roots respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Quantitative estimation of amino acid (mg/g) fresh weight of ridge gourd root infested by root-knot nematode

Sr. No.	Variety	Reaction	Amino acid content (mg/g)	
			Healthy	Infested
1	Arka sumeet	R	0.089	0.097
2	RNR	MR	0.050	0.057
3	US-6001	S	0.040	0.048
4	Ridge gourd PN	HS	0.042	0.049

Similar results were obtained by Sharma and Trivedi (1996). Nayak and Mohanty (2010) opined that, brinjal variety Pusa Purple Long inoculated roots contained higher amino acids than healthy roots. Gautam and Poddar (2014) reported

Changes in Biochemical Parameters of Ridge Gourd

Table 3. Effect of root-knot nematode, *M. incognita* on Sugars (mg/g).

Sr. No.	Variety	Reaction	Total sugars content		Reducing sugars		Non reducing sugars	
			Healthy	Infested	Healthy	Infested	Healthy	Infested
1	Arka Sumeet	R	11.50	12.00	7.00	9.50	4.50	2.50
2	RNR	MR	15.25	16.75	7.25	10.25	8.00	6.50
3	US-6001	S	18.00	21.0	8.50	14.25	9.50	6.75
4	Ridge gourd PN	HS	22.00	24.0	10.00	15.00	12.00	9.00

maximum quantity of total amino acids in root-knot nematode infested brinjal susceptible variety compared to resistant variety.

In the present investigation, (Table 3) total sugars and reducing sugars contents were more in infested roots of variety ridge gourd PN (24 mg/g and 15 mg/g) than resistant variety Arka Sumeet (12.0 mg/g and 9.50 mg/g) compared to healthy roots. Further, the healthy roots of ridge gourd PN (12.0 mg/g) recorded more non-reducing sugars as against resistant variety Arka Sumet (4.50 mg/g) compared to infested roots.

Similar results were obtained by Nayak and Mohanty (2010) and Mohanta and Mohanty (2012) who opined that 41.21 per cent increase in total sugar contents in the inoculated roots of okra variety LBH-55 compared to healthy roots. Senthilkumar *et al.*, (2007) found the increased amount of total and reducing sugar content in *M. graminicola* infested susceptible varieties compared to resistant varieties. The infestation of plant parasitic nematode caused increase in sugar content and it was also observed that increased sugars helpful for the survival of nematodes. The increase in sugar in infected plants may be alteration in host metabolism due nematodes, so that the respiratory substrates move towards the site of infection from the other parts of plant in order that more carbohydrates are available for respiration and release of energy.

The increase in phenolics in resistant plants was due to high activity of α -glucosidase, which converts non-toxic phenolic glycosides to toxic phenolics which are inhibitory to the pathogen. The increase in

Amino acid concentration in infected plants may be either due to the synthesis of new enzyme proteins or the contributions from nematodes (Nayak and Mohanty, 2010). The complex plant nematode interaction may cause the hydrolysis of sucrose and the utilization of simple sugar by the nematode and may be the reason for higher sugar level in infected tissues.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation indicated that *M. incognita* played key role in altering the normal biochemical processes of the ridge gourd. Further, opinion that the basic information provided in this investigation will certainly helpful to understand the complicated areas of the biochemical mechanisms of plant nematode-interaction in ridge gourd relating to root-knot and other plant parasitic nematodes.

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Comparative Analysis of Market Led Initiatives by Producer Groups in Odisha

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out during 2013 to compare range of market-led initiatives (MLIs) pursued by 88 producer groups, covering 9 districts in the state of Odisha. Producer groups have been evolved under 5 different programs viz. Agriculture Technology Management Agency (ATMA), Swarna Jayanti Sworojagar Yojana (SJSY), Orissa Tribal Empowerment Livelihoods Project (OTELP), Farmers' Club (FC), Western Orissa Rural Livelihoods Project (WORLP). Based on the empirical observations on collective action undertaken by the producer groups, the range of MLIs has been classified into 5 categories viz. input aggregation, access resources (credit), access technology, value addition and marketing. Highest proportion of producer groups under ATMA, SGSY, OTELP, FC and WORLP had been reported to access technology (30.20%), access resources (30.00%), access resources (25.76%), marketing (30.13%) and access technology (29.04%) respectively. The project wise comparison of range of MLIs by X2 test recorded significant difference at 1% level. Thereafter, the enterprise-wise comparison of range of MLIs yielded that highest proportion of producer groups with agriculture/ horticulture, livestock/ fisheries, mixed system, agri-processing and others (off-farm) enterprises undertake MLIs such as input aggregation (26.21%), access technology (28.00%), input aggregation (27.72%), marketing (28.13%) and access resources (27.17%) respectively. The X2 test conducted to compare the results of enterprise-wise comparison of range of MLIs resulted in significant difference at 5% level. No significant difference was observed between MLIs when compared agro-climatic zone wise. Therefore, facilitators engaged in formation, supporting and strengthening of producer groups should inherently align the purpose of group formation with that of range of MLIs undertaken, so as to accomplish the desired outcomes.

Key Words: Collective marketing, Fund, Input aggregation, Market-led initiatives, Producer group, Technology access, Value addition,.

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural growth is the most effective route to inclusive growth, especially when the share of agriculture in the Gross Value Added (GVA) is just above 17 per cent (2014-15) which is contributed and shared by more than half of our population. Further, within agriculture sector, the inequitable distribution of landholdings *i.e.* 85 per cent of small and marginal farmers are cultivating in 45

per cent of land area; which makes the small and marginal farms as the poverty hotspots of the country. The Government of India announcement of doubling the farmers' income by 2022, comes as an endorsement of multiple strategies aiming for a sense of income security to farmers in a time bound manner. Amongst all, the engagement of farmers in market has been vouched as one of the key drivers of income change (NABARD, 2016).

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Under various developmental projects and programmes the State Government with support from Govt. of India and/or donor agencies is attempting to improve the livelihoods of rural people in general and farmers in particular. In order to improve the agricultural productivity and market access in impacting the livelihoods, farmer groups have been promulgated. The overarching objective of evolving farmers' groups has been; the social capital compounded with economic capital of otherwise resource poor and disadvantaged farmers would make the agricultural system more competitive with effective management of resources in production and marketing.

Although group approach has remained the cornerstone of development in all of the programmes but there are subtle differences relating to objectives and approaches of programme planning and delivery. The producer groups had been promulgated as a mean to usher in social capital to enable the groups to pursue appropriate high-value crops, livestock and/or other agri-enterprises that would increase farm household income (Mishra and Swanson, 2009).

Fundamentally, market-led initiatives (MLIs) are set of interventions specifically designed to garner more profit and in the process bringing out better efficiency in production and delivery of goods and services. In the same parlance, the developmental projects usher in different MLIs for the farmers' groups in triggering higher economic return to the member farmers. Typically, the MLIs adopted for the producer groups would include one

or multiple activities viz. collectivize agri-inputs and/or outputs, higher technological uptake, better handling of produce (transportation, cleaning, grading, sorting, packaging etc.) change in form (or not change in form), contractual arrangement, certification or quality standards, accessing distant market, accessing market information and consumer's demand, promoting local brands etc. Under this study, attempt has been made to compare the 'range of MLIs' pursued by 88 producer groups, covering 9 districts in the state of Odisha, India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was undertaken during 2012-13, wherein 88 farmer groups were studied supported by 5 different programs viz., Agriculture Technology Management Agency (ATMA), Self Help Groups (SHGs) under Swarnajayanti Gram Sworojagar Yojana (SGSY), Orissa Tribal Livelihood Empowerment Project (OTELP), Farmer's Clubs of National Bank for Agricultural and Rural Development (NABARD) and Western Orissa Rural Livelihood Project(WORLP), in 9 districts of Odisha state. Each group leader (President / Secretary / Treasurer) and 4 group members from each group were interviewed individually to assess the range of MLIs pursued by their farmer group. Altogether, 440 farmers hailing from 88 farmer groups were interviewed with pre-tested questionnaire. They were asked to rank the 'range of MLIs' based on the priorities with which their group pursue these MLIs. Each farmer was asked record his/her preference by giving 'highest rank'

Particulars	Abbreviation	Formula
Range of Market-Led Initiatives (farmer wise) :	RMLIF =	$RMLI_i + RMLI_{ii} + RMLI_{iii} + RMLI_{iv} + RMLI_v$
Range of Market-Led Initiatives (farmer group wise) :	RMLIFG =	$(RMLIF1 + RMLIF2 + RMLIF3 + RMLIF4 + RMLIF5) / 5$
Range of Market-Led Initiatives (Project wise)	RMLIP =	$(RMLIFG1 + RMLIFG2 + RMLIFG3 + \dots + RMLIFG_n) / n$
Range of Market-Led Initiatives (Enterprise wise)	RMLIE =	$(RMLIFG1 + RMLIFG2 + RMLIFG3 + \dots + RMLIFG_m) / m$
Range of Market-Led Initiatives (Agro-climatic zone wise)	RMLIAC =	$(RMLIFG1 + RMLIFG2 + RMLIFG3 + \dots + RMLIFG_q) / q$

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to that MLI which has been perceived as the ‘most important one’, and so on for all other ‘range of MLIs’, keeping in view the overall objectives of the group. As there were five ranges of MLIs viz. input aggregation, access to fund/ credit, access to technologies (for production), value addition, collective marketing; thus, each farmer member had given rank score for each ‘range of MLI’, 5 for the highest rank and 1 for the lowest rank. The mean score for each farmer group was calculated by taking average of the scores obtained for the member farmers. The following formulae were used for calculating the ‘range of MLIs’ (RMLI) score for the farmer member, farmer group, project wise, enterprise wise and agro-climatic zone wise.

Based on the number of observations in the respective ‘range of MLI’, the frequency was calculated as the percentage of the total observations, so as to compare the ‘range of MLIs’ in percentage between 5 projects (ATMA, SGSY, OTELP, Farmer’s Club and WORLP), between 5 agro-enterprises (Agriculture-Horticulture, Animal Science-Fisheries, Mixed Farming System, Agri-Processing and Others) and between 3 broad agro-climatic zones (Coastal Plain, Hilly Terrain and Inland Plain) of the state. In order to assess the test of significance, the chi-square test was conducted as a descriptive measure of the magnitude of the discrepancies, using the formula, as given hereunder;

$$X^2 = (O-E)^2 / E, \text{ where}$$

X^2 = Chi Square value, Σ = Summation, O = Observed frequency, E = Expected frequency

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analyses of range of MLIs across projects

It may be construed that the producer groups used to imbibe primary mandate of the project under which those were groomed and accordingly pursued their MLIs. Citing the case of producer groups under ATMA and WORLP had adopted the access to technologies/ production’ as the principal MLI, similarly producer groups under SGSY and OTELP had identified access to inputs / credit as their primary MLI and the groups promoted as Farmers’ Club subscribed to collective marketing as the most important MLI.. Catholic Relief Services (2007) concluded that independent of the country, the cultural setting or the group formation methodology used, over the 70 per cent of the group of poor farmers visited were proactively trying to acquire three or more of the five skill sets, viz., group organization and management; internal savings and lending; sustainable production (including improved natural resource management); experimentation and innovation (knowing how to access and apply new technology) and basic market skills.

The producer groups undertook focused enterprises as their economic activities but the

Comparison of range of MLIs (Project wise)

Table 1. Range of MLIs in percentage for the 5 projects.

Values in percentage

Sr. No.	Range of MLIs	Name of the Projects				
		ATMA	SGSY	OTELP	Farmer’s Club	WORLP
1	Input Aggregation	24.87	22.87	16.35	18.87	20.15
2	Access Fund / Credit	18.53	30.00	25.76	18.13	14.08
3	Tech Access / Production	30.20	14.13	23.85	11.27	29.04
4	Value Addition	11.40	15.20	11.93	21.60	14.81
5	Collective Marketing	15.00	17.80	22.11	30.13	21.92

The X² value was observed to be 37.98, which was highly significant (P<0.01).

Comparison of range of MLIs (Agro-climactic zone wise)

The range of MLIs in percentage for the 3 agro-climatic zones were calculated as depicted below;

Table 3. Range of MLIs in percentage for 3 agro climatic zones.

Sr. No.	Range of MLIs	Agro-Climate Zone		
		Coastal Plain	Hilly Terrain	Inland Plain
1	Input Aggregation	14.67	27.28	28.40
2	Access Fund / Credit	18.63	27.67	25.37
3	Tech Access / Production	30.31	21.15	21.43
4	Value Addition	14.13	9.81	11.77
5	Collective marketing	22.27	14.09	13.03
	Total	100	100	100

The X^2 value was observed to be 13.19, which was non- significant.

variations existed with respect to the MLIs pursued by different enterprise-groups. An attempt was made to reason out and draw lesson from the observed 'range of MLIs'. The input aggregation was pursued by both producer groups with 'agri-horti' and 'mixed farming' enterprises; it might be due to the fact that the member farmers in these groups intended to procure diversified inputs collectively with an underlying motive of reducing the 'cost of production'. The producer group with 'AH-Fisheries' enterprise primarily pursued 'access to technologies/ production' as its MLI; which might be due to high-end of technologies in production process that could be effectively managed on a collective basis. The producer group undertaking

agri-processing enterprise collectively pursue value addition as the principal MLI. Similarly, Helen and Ruth (2006) compiled the activities ranging from organization around production (potato farmers in Uganda) to processing (dairy groups in Tanzania, dairy and fruit agro-enterprises in Colombia) to trading (cheese makers in Syria). In addition several examples from Africa highlighted that collective activities can be undertaken around bulking, sorting, storage and quality grading. Siddiqui (2008) pointed out that in India, group worked as link to empowerment, providing support, meeting economic needs through income generating etc. The use of group was to form common interest groups or self help groups to help specific clients for

Comparison of range of MLIs (Enterprise wise)**Table 2. Range of MLIs in percentage for the 5 enterprises.**

Values in percentage

Sr. No.	Range of MLIs	Enterprise				
		Agri-Hort	AH- Fish	Mixed	Agri-Processing	Others
1	Input Aggregation	26.21	22.44	27.72	16.4	25.17
2	Access Fund / Credit	22.08	13.44	21.42	14	27.17
3	Tech Access / Production	18.04	28	25.42	18	11.51
4	Value Addition	15.70	15.84	9.14	23.46	9.51
5	Collective marketing	17.96	20.28	16.28	28.13	26.67
	Total	100	100	100	100	100

The X^2 value was observed to be 36.68, which is significant ($P < 0.05$).

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achieving specific needs through collective efforts. Formation of self help groups was major activity thrust in working with poor women in particular, with the objective of promoting income generation or saving and credit groups.

CONCLUSION

It was evident from the study that the producer groups apparently similar in their structural framework but varied in subtle terms with respect to their strategic focus and operational modalities. The groups followed five broad range of MLIs, viz. input aggregation, technology access, access funds/ credit, value addition and collective marketing. The groups' priorities in pursuance of the MLIs varied. The variations could be attributed to the institutional support and approaches ushered in by the concerned projects, under which the groups had been evolved. Further, the type of agri-enterprises also had a bearing on the MLIs pursued by the groups. However, the variation across agro-climatic zones of the state did not affect significantly the range of MLIs followed by groups. This sets forth a strong recommendation to the developmental functionaries to follow group-specific, clientele specific and enterprise-centric market-led interventions (MLIs) that may be adopted

while planning and implementing developmental programmes for the producer groups. Therefore, facilitators engaged in formation, supporting and strengthening of producer groups should inherently align the purpose of group formation with that of range of MLIs undertaken, so as to accomplish the desired outcomes.

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Comparative Performance of Muskmelon (*Cucumis melo*) Hybrids at Farmers' Field in District Kapurthala

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ABSTRACT

The performance of 10 muskmelon hybrids was studied by using an experimental design RCBD at three locations in the district. The results revealed that the fruit diameter was maximum in Farm Glory and Sharda Chand (52.0 cm) followed by Sunny (51.2 cm) and Inthanon (48.5 cm), in case of fruit length, Sunny had maximum value (18.9 cm) followed by Sharda Chand (17.6 cm). Highest fruit weight (1900g) was observed in Sharda Chand followed by Sunny (1870g), Inthanon (1733.3g) whereas, lowest fruit weight (653.3 g) was found in Bobby followed by Kesar (741 g) and MH 27 (783 g). The data revealed that fresh seed weight of different cultivars ranged between 42.7g (Muskan) to 119.7g (Kesar) per fruit. Lowest values of cavity length and breadth were observed with bobby (8.1 cm and 5.9 cm), respectively. The overall seed cavity of Bobby was at par with Muskan, MH 27 and Kesar, which was mainly due to smaller fruit size of these hybrids, as compared to all other hybrids. It was pertinent to note that maximum fruit flesh was found in Sharda Chand (3.2 cm). TSS varied between 9.6° brix to 15.7° brix amongst different muskmelon hybrids. Maximum shelf life was observed for Inthanon and Sunny compared to other cultivars. Higher fruit yield was obtained in Farm Glory (304.2 q/ha) compared to Kesar (171.7 q/ha) followed by Sharda Chand, Sunny and Inthanon (250 to 270.8 q/ha) and Muskan, Golden Glory and Madhu yielded between (218.3 to 245.8 q/ha). Four muskmelon hybrids namely MH 27, Farm Glory, Golden Glory and Kesar possessed typical flavour and flesh colour which were most desirable in muskmelon. Out of 10 hybrids, only MH 27 possessed suture on fruit, whereas, other were having profuse netting (Farm Glory, Inthanon, Golden Glory and Sunny), scattered netting (Muskan, Madhu and Kesar) and minimum netting (Sharda Chand). Two hybrids namely Inthanon and Sunny possessed more shelf life (16.0 and 14.5 d) after harvest and were more suitable for transportation to distant markets compared to other muskmelon hybrids.

Key Words: Hybrid, Kapurthala, Muskmelon, Organoleptic, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the people gorge on mangoes during summer season, another fruit that should be a part of one's summer diet is muskmelon also known as cantaloupe. Its high water content helps to stay hydrated during the hot season. Melons are divided into two groups namely *Citrullus* (water melons) and *Cucumis* (muskmelon-cantaloupe group). The muskmelon is a member of the Cucurbitaceae family, which also includes cucumbers, watermelons and honey dew, Persian, Casaba, and crenshaw melons. Muskmelon (*Cucumis melo*.L) is one of the most important crops grown all over the world. It is

highly relished because of its flavour, sweet taste and refreshing effect. It is a good source of dietary fibre, beta-carotene, folic acid, potassium, vitamins C and A, muskmelon not only helps to stay healthy and is also good for skin and hair. A number of muskmelon hybrids and varieties are grown in different regions of India (Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Punjab, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Bihar, Chattisgarh, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu) which are highly variable in shape, size, colour, netting, sweetness and flavour.

Muskmelon is grown in limited commercial acreage in Punjab and the main muskmelon

producing districts are Kapurthala, Jalandhar and Patiala from where produce is exported to different parts of the country like Mumbai, Kolkata and Jammu & Kashmir. Commission agents as well as traders prefer a cultivar that has less suturing with excellent quality, flavour and good shelf life suitable for long transportation. Melons with profuse netting are usually preferred for the distant markets. Fruit characteristics of melon like netting and rind thickness affect the shelf life and thus transportation. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to compare the yield and postharvest quality of muskmelon cultivars grown under open field conditions by the farmers in district Kapurthala.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Climatic requirements

Muskmelons grow best at average air temperatures between 18 and 24°C but the optimum temperature for germination of the seed is 27-30°C. Temperature above 35°C or below 10°C slows down the growth and maturation of the crop. This crop is very sensitive to cold temperatures and even a mild frost can damage the crop, therefore, should be planted after the last chance of frost has passed. With the increase in temperature, the plants complete their vegetative growth earlier.

Table 1. Monthly rainfall and temperature data of Kapurthala.

Month	Rainfall (mm)	Minimum (°C)	Maximum (°C)
January	41.5	7.2	19.4
February	3.5	11.6	23.0
March	21.0	17.4	27.1
April	10.0	18.9	37.5
May	52.0	23.7	40.7
June	399.0	24.0	37.8

Stormy weather particularly dust storm during flowering reduces fruit setting. Dry weather with clear sunshine during ripening ensures high sugar content, better flavour and a high percentage of marketable fruits. High humidity increases

the incidence of diseases, particularly those affecting foliage. Cool nights and warm days are ideal for accumulation of sugars in the fruits.

The data regarding temperature at Kapurthala during the study period (January, 2017 to June, 2017) on fortnightly basis has been presented in Table 1.

Soil requirements

Muskmelons grow well on a wide range of soil types. Medium-textured soils (loams) will generally produce higher yields and better-quality melons but in order to get early harvesting, lighter soils where there is good air drainage are considered to be the best. It prefers a soil pH between 6.0 and 7.0 but should be above 5.8 and preferably near 6.2. Alkaline soils with high salt concentration are also not suitable. Soil beds should be raised 15 to 20 cm to facilitate soil drainage because well-drained soils that warm up quickly are best suited for muskmelon.

Cultivation practices followed at the farmers' field

The experiment was conducted during the year 2016-2017 at three locations of district Kapurthala where maximum area was under muskmelon crop in order to evaluate different hybrids for yield and quality parameters. The muskmelon hybrids studied were Bobby, Muskan, Kesar, Farm Glory, Golden Glory, Inthanon, Sunny, Sharda Chand, Madhu and MH-27. Sowing of these hybrids was done in first week of March except hybrid Kesar which was sown in first week of February at farmers' field. Experimental design used was a randomized complete block with three locations (environments taken as replications). The soil fertility status of these locations was found to be medium in organic carbon and available phosphorus and high in available potassium (Singh *et al*, 2016).

The fields were prepared for sowing of seed using conventional tillage in early February. Fertilizer was applied at the rate of 250 kg of urea, 187 kg of diammonium phosphate and 125 kg of muriate of potash per hectare before final disking

Performance of Muskmelon Hybrids at Farmers' Field

and leveling. Beds were prepared measuring 2.0 m wide with 2 rows per bed. Row to row spacing of 150 cm and plant to plant spacing of 30cm was maintained while sowing. Seeds were sown at a depth of 1-2 cm with 1 seed /hill. Seed germination took about 10-15 d and gaps noticed were filled up manually with the seedlings prepared in polythene bags.

At the time of sowing Furadon (Carbofuron) @ 5 kg/ha was placed at the base of seed in order to prevent attack of insect pests especially red pumpkin beetle. Similarly, after 30-35 days after sowing, a preventive spray with Indofil M 45 @ 1250g/ha was applied at interval of 7- 10 days repeatedly. Later on, depending upon the severity of disease attack, spray of Ridomil fungicide @ 1250g/ha was also applied. Irrigation was applied in furrows as and when required. A continued watch was kept on the growth and disease incidence appearance on all hybrids grown at farmers' field. Data regarding muskmelon marketable fruit weight was taken from four harvests from first week of May to mid of June and yield was recorded accordingly.

From each location, five average size muskmelon fruits of each hybrid were selected at harvest and data were recorded on different parameters namely, fruit weight (g), fruit length (cm), fruit diameter (cm), seed cavity length (cm), seed cavity breadth (cm), rind thickness (cm), flesh thickness (cm), TSS (^obrix) and pH. Rind and flesh thickness was measured with the help of Vernier Calliper. For total soluble solids content, five mature fruits were chosen and a 1 inch by 1 inch center piece of each fruit was squeezed and the obtained juice was placed on a digital hand-held pocket refractometer (model PAL-1, Atago, Bellevue, WA). Total soluble solids content was measured on 28th May, 2017. After dissecting the fruit into two halves, flesh colour was judged with the help of shade chart (Apolite) developed by Asian paints. Organoleptic parameters like smell, taste, juiciness and look were analyzed by a panel of 5 judges by giving individual ranking between 1 to 10 points scale. Best was given 10

rank and worst 1. The data was analyzed by using OPSTAT (Sheoran *et al*, 1998).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fruit diameter, length and weight

Fruit diameter was observed maximum in Farm Glory and Sharda Chand (52.0 cm) followed by Sunny (51.2 cm) and Inthanon (48.5 cm), which was statistically non significant with each other (Table 2). In case of fruit length, Sunny had maximum value (18.9 cm) followed by Sharda Chand (17.6 cm) and was at par with each other. So, from fruit size point of view, Sunny and Sharda Chand were better options followed by Farm glory and Inthanon.

It is a known fact that fruit weight had a significant effect on the marketing of fruits. It has been observed that earlier cultivars of watermelon were having weight of 10-12 kg/fruit and most of the buyers were reluctant to purchase because needs of the family was found to be less. Hence, scientists developed smaller fruit size and today, in the market one can find watermelon in range about 1-3 kg/fruit. Similar situation exists for muskmelon fruits also. In the present study, highest fruit weight (1900g) was observed in Sharda Chand followed by Sunny (1870g), Inthanon (1733.3g) and the differences in three cultivars was non-significant, whereas, lowest fruit weight (653.3 g) was found in Bobby followed by Kesar (741 g) and MH 27 (783 g) (Table 2). The study revealed that differences in fruit weight of different hybrids were significant. Therefore, this parameter had a major role in marketing of muskmelon fruits.

Seed weight and cavity

Seeds of muskmelon are also sold in the market at very high rate due to its nutritive value. The data revealed that weight of the fresh seed of different cultivars ranged between 42.7g (Muskan) to 119.7g (Kesar) per fruit (Table 2). It was interesting to note that there was no correlation between fruit weight and fresh seed weight obtained, which might probably due to difference in the genetic makeup of different hybrids because research scientists are

eager to develop seedless cultivar of different fruits like Papaya cultivar Red Lady 786 and Grapes.

Small seed cavity is a desirable character in the muskmelon as it affects the fruit flesh. Lowest values of cavity length and breadth were observed with bobby (8.1 cm and 5.9 cm), respectively. The overall seed cavity of Bobby was at par with Muskan, MH 27 and Kesar, which was mainly due to smaller fruit size of these hybrids, as compared to all other hybrids.

Thickness and quality parameters

Rind thickness and tightness of fruits are important parameters that determine the shelf life of fruit. In some cultivars like Inthanon, Sunny rind thickness was found to be 1.3 cm and 1.0cm respectively and fruits were also tighter which adds to their more shelf life. Flesh thickness was found to be maximum in Sharda Chand (3.2 cm) and fruits were more tight although rind thickness was not so good (0.6cm) (Table 2). Due to more rind thickness and tightness of the fruit, there was less attack of fruit fly noticed on Inthanon, Sunny and Sharda Chand, on the other hand, maximum attack of insect pests was noticed in Muskan may be due to scattered netting and less firmness of the fruit. It was observed that shelf life of muskmelon fruit had a very strong correlation with rind thickness indicating that it was desirable character for distant transportation of the fruit.

Total soluble solids (TSS) and Shelf life

This is an important fruit quality parameter because the consumer desires high level of TSS (Table 2 and 3). In the present study, TSS varied between 9.6° brix to 15.7° brix amongst different muskmelon hybrids. The difference in the TSS values of different hybrids was found to be significantly different. Maximum TSS was found in Bobby (15.7° brix) but fruit yield was less, however, its selling price was found to be highest due to higher value of TSS. Therefore, a producer must take into account various fruit quality parameters while selecting a hybrid for its cultivation so that it did not face any difficulty in marketing.

The study indicated that there was large variation in the shelf life of different fruit cultivars, which varied between 2.5 d to 16 d (Table 2 and 3). Similarly, maximum shelf life was observed for Inthanon and Sunny compared to other cultivars. Hence, farmers must pay attention, while selecting the cultivars keeping in view the marketing distance otherwise, whole produce will get damaged during transit period and result in huge loss to the trader as well as farmer.

Fruit Yield

Out of 10 muskmelon hybrids, significantly higher yield was obtained in Farm Glory (304.2 q/ha) compared to Kesar (171.7 q/ha) (Table 2 and 3). Three hybrids namely, Sharda Chand, Sunny and

Table 4. Ranking of different muskmelon hybrids based on organoleptic characters.

Sr. No.	Hybrid	Netting	Suture	Colour (colour code)	Organoleptic rating
1.	Bobby	Less profuse	Absent	Lemon pie (7859)	7
2.	Muskan	Scattered	Absent	Limon (7778)	6
3.	Farm Glory	Profused	Absent	Barley (0572)	5
4.	Golden Glory	Profused	Absent	Barley (0572)	5
5.	Sunny	Profused	Absent	Lime grove (7729)	4
6.	Inthanon	Profused	Absent	Misty vale (0946)	4
7.	MH-27	Less	Present	Orange essence (8009)	3
8.	Madhu	Less	Absent	Mango shake (7960)	2
9.	Sharda Chand	Very Less	Absent	Kesar milk (7962)	2
10.	Kesar	Profused	Light	Orange (8009)	1

Performance of Muskmelon Hybrids at Farmers' Field

Inthanon gave yield between (250 to 270.8 q/ha) where as Muskan, Golden Glory and Madhu yielded between (218.3 to 245.8 q/ha). The difference in the fruit yield was mainly due to the number of fruits per vine and weight of the fruit.

Organoleptic parameters

Four muskmelon hybrids namely MH 27, Farm Glory, Golden Glory and Kesar possessed typical flavor and flesh colour was either Orange (colour code 8009) or barley (colour code 0572). Both these characters are most desirable in muskmelon. However, all other hybrids, possessed flesh colour either green or creamy, are less juicy and crispy (Table 4).

It was noted that 40 per cent of the consumer did not like the Lemon pie colour of hybrid Bobby inspite of its maximum TSS value (15.7⁰ brix). On the same ground, flesh colour of Sharda Chand (Kesar milk), Sunny (lime grove colour), misty vale colour of Inthanon and limon colour of Muskan were not preferred in local market, inspite of good fruit weight and TSS value. Therefore, farmers must take into account the area in which these hybrids are to be sold or marketed.

Netting and suture on fruit

It was pertinent to mention that earlier consumer preferred suture on muskmelon fruits to a great extent (Table 4). But the major disadvantage with this type of fruit was, its shelf life was too poor (2-3 days) after harvest. As a result of which, this type of hybrids did not fetch a good market price in the distant markets due to rapid spoilage during the transit period. Later on, scientists develop more number of hybrids without suture but fruit was lined with heavy netting. This type of hybrids possessed more shelf life (10-16 d) after harvest and was more suitable for transportation purpose. Out of 10 ybrids, only MH 27 possessed suture and light suture on Kesar fruit were also visible, whereas, other were having profuse netting (Inthanon, Sunny, Farm Glory and Golden Glory), scattered netting (Muskan, Madhu and Kesar) and minimum netting (Sharda Chand).

Salient features of the varieties

During the study, it was found that total area in Kapurthala district during the year 2016-17 was found to be 1700 ha under muskmelon crop. Per cent area under different hybrids was found to be Farm Glory (35), Madhu (30), Golden Glory (25), Kesar (7) and Bobby, Muskan, Inthanon, Sunny and Sharda Chand (3). Farmers preferred a particular hybrid due to the following reasons:

Farm Glory – Fruit possessed good colour, netting, fragrance, flesh thickness, suitable for local and distant marketing, takes 70-80 days to mature, ranked 3rd in preference by consumer for organoleptic characters.

Madhu – Fruit possessed more flesh and less rind, minimum wastage during transit to distant markets, mostly preferred in Jammu and Kashmir.

Golden Glory – Fruit were of good size and preferred fragrance, flesh thickness, takes 75 days to mature and suitable for local and distant marketing, ranked 3rd in preference by consumer.

Kesar – Suitable for early sowing during February, fruits are available in market during first week of May takes 65 days to mature, fetches maximum price due to earliness.

Bobby – Maximum TSS value, very sweet, smallest in size suitable for single person, minimum seed cavity, highest pH and crispy texture, suitable for local as well as distant market, ranked 1st in preference by consumer.

Muskan – Fruits are sweet, higher pH, lower seed price as compared to Bobby but TSS value as good as Bobby, ranked 2nd in preference by consumer for organoleptic characters.

Inthanon – Fruit possessed maximum shelf life due to tightness, less insect pest attack, higher fruit weight, ranked 4th in preference by consumer for organoleptic characters, preferred in five star hotels.

Sunny – Tightness, large fruit size, less insect pest attack, ranked 4th in preference by consumer for organoleptic characters.

Performance of Muskmelon Hybrids at Farmers' Field

Table 2. Yield and fruit characteristics of different muskmelon hybrids.

Varieties	Fruit Diameter (cm)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit Weight (g)	Fresh seed weight (g)	Seed cavity (cm)		Thickness (cm)			Quality parameters				Yield (q/ha)
					Length	breadth	Rind	Flesh	Total	TSS	pH	Shelf life (days)		
Farm Glory	52.0	15.9	1300.0	112.3	14.8	9.8	0.9	3.1	4.0	12.1	5.2	7.5	304.2	
Inthanon	48.5	15.6	1733.3	79.7	16.5	6.0	1.3	2.6	3.8	14.0	5.1	16.0	270.8	
Sunny	51.2	18.9	1870.0	77.7	16.7	6.4	1.0	3.1	4.2	14.3	5.2	14.5	270.0	
Sharda Chand	52.0	17.6	1900.0	68.0	16.6	8.7	0.6	3.2	3.8	11.1	5.2	13.5	250.0	
Madhu	38.7	14.6	963.3	82.0	13.1	8.0	0.8	2.9	3.7	11.0	5.1	11.0	245.8	
Golden Glory	45.5	14.6	1133.3	106.0	14.6	9.8	0.7	3.1	3.8	12.3	5.2	7.5	237.5	
Muskan	44.3	15.4	923.3	42.7	9.0	6.5	0.9	3.1	4.0	14.0	5.4	5.5	218.3	
Bobby	42.3	12.5	653.3	87.3	8.1	5.9	0.6	2.5	3.1	15.7	5.5	5.5	204.2	
MH 27	42.7	10.5	783.3	117.7	9.4	6.1	0.3	3.0	3.3	11.2	5.2	2.5	180.8	
Kesar	39.0	11.5	741.7	119.7	8.6	6.5	0.4	2.9	3.2	9.6	5.1	4.0	171.7	
C.D.	4.0	1.6	267.6	4.1	1.1	0.7	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.7	0.1	1.5	32.3	

Table 3. Ranking of different muskmelon hybrids based on yield, TSS and shelf life.

Varieties	Yield (q/ha)	Varieties	TSS	Varieties	Shelf life (days)
Farm Glory	304.2	Bobby	15.7	Inthanon	16.0
Inthanon	270.8	Sunny	14.3	Sunny	14.5
Sunny	270.0	Muskan	14.0	Sharda Chand	13.5
Sharda Chand	250.0	Inthanon	14.0	Madhu	11.0
Madhu	245.8	Golden Glory	12.3	Farm Glory	7.5
Golden Glory	237.5	Farm Glory	12.1	Golden Glory	7.5
Muskan	218.3	MH 27	11.2	Bobby	5.5
Bobby	204.2	Sharda Chand	11.1	Muskan	5.5
MH 27	180.8	Madhu	11.0	Kesar	4.0
Kesar	171.7	Kesar	9.6	MH 27	2.5
C.D.	32.3	C.D.	0.7	C.D.	1.5

Sharda Chand – Good keeping quality, available throughout the year in celebrations, most attractive colour, fetches good price in markets, preferred when no other variety is available in the market.

MH 27 – Most suitable for local market, only variety with suture on fruits, fruits sweet and orange in colour.

CONCLUSION

A large variation was found in the performance of different hybrids regarding yield and various fruit quality parameters like TSS, shelf life, pH and netting etc. This variation was mainly due to the genetic makeup of the hybrids procured by the farmers every year, as well as, management practices followed while raising the crop. Hybrids namely Inthanon, Sunny, Sharda Chand were found to be more suitable for distant marketing mainly due to more shelf life irrespective of flesh colour. It was

noticed that occurrence of rain at the time of crop maturity and virus infestation plays a vital role in the profitability of this crop, as a result of which, the area under both muskmelon and watermelon keep on dwindling every year in the district. Conclusively, it can be said that price of hybrid seed, potential marketing area and consumer preference are the factors responsible for the selection of a hybrid for its cultivation by the farmers.

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Constraints Encountered by the Farmers in Adoption of Drip Irrigation System in District Jaipur

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ABSTRACT

Drip irrigation is basically precise and slow application of water in the form of discrete continuous drops, sprayed through mechanical devices in to the root zone of the plants. Drip irrigation system is profitable as it saves 60-70 per cent water as compared to surface irrigation and other methods, protects the plants from diseases by minimizing humidity in atmosphere. The study was conducted in eight randomly selected gram panchayats of panchayat samiti Jhotwara of district Jaipur. Two villages were selected from each selected gram panchayat having maximum number of drip irrigation sets. Thus in all, 16 villages were selected purposively. Ninety six farmers were selected on the basis of proportional allocation. The study showed that the majority (51.04 %) of farmers were found in to the category of medium constraints level where as 22.92 per cent and 26.04 per cent farmers were found into the categories of low and high constraints levels, respectively, regarding constraints faced by farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system. amongst all the constraints financial constraints (73.30 MPS) were the most intensively perceived followed by general constraints (72.56 MPS), technical constraints (70.74 MPS), educational constraints (69.54 MPS), miscellaneous constraints (69.02 MPS), infrastructural constraints (68.84 MPS) and climatic and geographical constraints (67.15 MPS). Under the financial constraints, high initial cost of installing drip set was observed as the most severe constraint with 86.45 MPS. Difficulty in maintenance of DIS, regularly was most perceived general constraint by the farmers as it was perceived by 85.76 per cent farmers. Problem of blocking the drippers due to salt or other impurities in the water was most perceived technical constraints by the farmers as it was perceived by 85.76 per cent respondents. Inadequate awareness about the advantage of drip irrigation system was most perceived educational constraints.

Key Words:

INTRODUCTION

Drip irrigation system controls the time of application, amount of water and place of application of water. Drip irrigation is far more superior to other traditional methods like surface irrigation because it provides precisely the required amount of water, checks wastage. Secondly, it provides the condition that is created in surface irrigation, due to which there is a gap of 24 hr before plants can actually utilize the irrigation water. This system also permits the use of fertilizers, pesticides and other water-soluble chemicals along with water. It has been

found that fertigation is the most economic method of fertilizer application specially when applied through drip system. It leads to 40-50 per cent savings on nutrients application. Disease spread is also less in those places where drip system is being practiced with application of this technology. The Rajasthan state ranked 6th in terms of coverage of area under drip irrigation system (31203.49 ha.).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Jaipur district of Rajasthan. Jaipur district comprises thirteen

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panchayat samities, out of which Jhotwara panchayat samiti was selected randomly and 8 gram panchayats were selected randomly. Two villages were selected from each selected gram panchayat having maximum number of drip irrigation sets. Thus, a total of 16 villages were selected purposively. Ninety six farmers were selected on the basis of proportional allocation. The responses regarding different constraints like general, technical, infrastructural, financial, educational, climatic and geographical and miscellaneous were recorded on three point continuum viz., most severe, severe and least severe which were assigned scores of 3, 2, and 1, respectively. Total score obtained by farmers as well as for each statement was calculated. The farmers were divided into three categories viz., most severe, severe and least severe on the basis of mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data (Table 1) revealed that 51.04 per cent of farmers were found in to the category of medium constraints level where as 22.92 per cent, and 26.04 per cent farmers were found into the categories of low and high constraints levels, respectively, regarding constraints faced by farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

Table 1. Constraints encountered by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system N=96

Sr. No	Category of constraints	Frequency	Percentage
1	Low constraints (score below 85.66)	22	22.92
2	Medium constraints (score from 85.66 to 113.02)	49	51.04
3	High constraints (score above 113.02)	25	26.04
	Total	96	100.00

$X = 99.34, \quad \sigma = 13.68$

In depth study of constraints was also conducted and the constraints encountered by respondents in adoption of drip irrigation system were categorized into seven categories namely general, technical, financial, infrastructural, educational, climatic and geographical and miscellaneous constraints.

General constraints

The data (Table 2) revealed that difficulty in maintenance of drip irrigation system (DIS) regularly was the most perceived constraints (85.76 %) whereas problem of uprooting due to shallow root technology (57.29 %) was the least perceived by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

Table 2. General constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system. N=96

Sr. No	General constraints	MPS*	Rank
1	Difficulty in maintenance of DIS, regularly	85.76	I
2	Companies/dealers do not provide proper service regarding the drip irrigation sets	83.33	II
3	Irregular supply of electricity in the area	80.90	III
4	Difficult to operate DIS by illiterate people	64.23	IV
5	Spacing varies from crop to crop, so it becomes difficult to change the place to lateral pipes frequency	63.88	V
6	Problem of uprooting due to shallow root technology	57.29	VI

* Mean percent scores

Constraints Encountered in Adoption of Drip Irrigation System

Table 3. Technical constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

N=96

Sr. No	Technical constraints	M.P.S*	Rank
1	Problem of blocking the drippers due to salt or other impurities in the water	89.23	I
2	High technical skill is required in operation and maintenance of drip irrigation system	86.45	II
3	Non-availability of spare parts at village level	78.47	III
4	Problem of leakage of water in the pipe	73.61	IV
5	Uneven distribution of water due to insufficient pressure of water	63.54	V
6	Regular service is not available from installing agency after sale	61.11	VI
7	Lack of technical know-how about maintenance and repairing of drip irrigation sets	61.11	VI
8	Lack of organizing regular trainings on operation, maintenance, repairing of drip irrigation sets	52.43	VII

* Mean percent scores

Technical constraints

The data given (Table 3) revealed that problem of blocking the drippers due to salt or other impurities in the water (89.23 %) was the most perceived constraints whereas lack of organizing regular trainings on operation, maintenance, repairing of drip irrigation sets (52.43 %) was the least perceived by farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

Financial constraints

The data (Table 4) revealed that high initial cost of installing drip set (86.45%) was the most

perceived constraints. The constraint regarding diesel/electrical charges were more expensive (66.31 %) was the least perceived constraints by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

Infrastructural constraints

The data (Table 5) revealed that the services provided by the companies were poor after sale (78.12 %) was the most perceived constraints whereas lower quality of pipe and micro-tubes (57.63 %) was the least perceived constraints by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

Table 4. Financial constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation System.

N=96

Sr. No	Financial constraints	M.P.S*	Rank
1	High initial cost of installing drip set	86.45	I
2	Lack of knowledge about government schemes for installing drip sets on subsidized rates	80.20	II
3	Procedure for getting loan from bank / societies is complicated	76.38	III
4	Lack of knowledge of banking facilities for loan	73.61	IV
5	Lack of timely availability of financial help from government through subsidies	70.48	V
6	Extra tank is needed for high pressure	69.79	VI
7	Spare parts of drip irrigation system are costly	68.75	VII
8	High rate of interest on sanctioned loan	67.70	VIII
9	Diesel/ electrical charges are more expensive	66.31	IX

* Mean percent scores

Table 5. Infrastructural constraints in adoption of drip irrigation system.

N = 96

Sr. No.	Infrastructural constraints	M.P.S*	Rank
1	Poor services provided by the companies after sale	78.12	I
2	Insufficient supply of electricity for irrigating fields	75.34	II
3	Shortage of technical staff in the field	74.30	III
4	Availability of spare parts timely	66.66	IV
5	Monopoly of companies in supplying the drip sets for irrigation	65.97	V
6	Inadequate distribution net work in rural areas	63.88	VI
7.	Lower quality of pipe and micro-tubes	57.63	VII

* Mean percent scores

Table 6. Educational constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

N = 96

Sr. No.	Educational constraints	M.P.S*	Rank
1.	Inadequate awareness about the advantage of drip irrigation system	84.04	I
2.	Untrained farmers feel difficulty in using drip irrigation system	77.77	II
3.	Lack of knowledge about operation of drip irrigation system	73.61	III
4.	Lack of individual's contact with experts related to drip irrigation system for effective adoption	71.52	IV
5.	Adequate number of demonstrations were not arranged to motivate and develop skills for its adoption	63.88	V
6.	Lack of systematic campaign for popularizing the drip irrigation system	59.37	VI
7.	Farmers training are not arranged for its adoption	56.59	VII

* Mean percent scores

Educational constraints

The data (Table 6) revealed that inadequate awareness about the advantages of drip irrigation system (84.04 %) was the most perceived constraint whereas farmers training is not arranged for its adoption (56.59 %) was the least perceived by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

Climatic and geographical constraints

The data (Table 7) revealed that DIS was unsuitable in the areas where water was highly saline which caused choking of emitters (82.29 %) was the most perceived constraints whereas DIS

was unprofitable where land was leveled and ground water available in sufficient quantities (56.25 %) was the least perceived constraints by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

Miscellaneous constraints

The data (Table 8) revealed that lack of trainings to improve skills about operation and repairing of parts of DIS (82.98 %) was the most perceived constraint whereas the constraint like nepotism and favoritism in installation of drip irrigation sets (55.55 %) was the least perceived constraints by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

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Table 7. Climatic and geographical constraints faced by the farmers

N = 96

Sr. No.	Climatic and geographical constraints	M.P.S*	Rank
1	Unsuitable in the area where water is highly saline which causes choking of emitters	82.29	I
2	High temperature reduces the durability of drip irrigation system	69.79	II
3	Inability to minimize temperature of atmosphere	67.01	III
4	Unsuitable for clay soil	60.41	IV
5	Unprofitable where land is leveled and ground water available in sufficient quantity	56.25	V

* Mean percent scores

Table 8. Miscellaneous constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system.

N = 96

Sr. No.	Miscellaneous constraints	M.P.S*	Rank
1	Lack of organizing trainings to improve skills about operation and repairing of parts of DIS.	82.98	I
2	Lack of measurement of water pressure in lateral distributors	78.81	II
3	Lack of extension efforts in popularizing the DIS for getting maximum benefits from DIS	64.23	III
4	Problem of motivation of farmers towards installation of drip irrigation sets. Inability to minimize temperature of atmosphere	63.54	IV
5	Nepotism and favoritism in installation of drip irrigation sets	55.55	V

* Mean percent scores

Overall constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of drip irrigation system. The data given in table 9 revealed that financial constraints (73.30 MPS) were the most intensely perceived constraints followed by general constraints (72.56 MPS), technical constraints (70.74 MPS), educational constraints (69.54 MPS), miscellaneous constraints (69.02 MPS), infrastructural constraints (68.84 MPS) and climatic and geographical constraints (67.15 MPS).

Table 9. Overall constraints faced by the farmers. N=96

Sr. No.	Constraint	M.P.S*	Rank
1.	Financial	73.30	I
2.	General	72.56	II
3.	Technical	70.74	III
4.	Educational	69.54	IV
5.	Miscellaneous	69.02	V
6.	Infrastructural	68.84	VI
7.	Climatic and geographical	67.15	VII

* Mean percent scores

CONCLUSION

The most perceived constraint under general constraints was observed to be difficulty in maintenance of DIS, regularly and problem of blocking the drippers due to salt or other impurities in the water. the most perceived constraint under financial constraints was high initial cost of installing drip set and likewise most perceived Infrastructural constraints was of services provided by the companies were poor after sale. Inadequate awareness about the advantage of drip irrigation system and lack of organizing trainings to improve skills about operation and repairing of parts of DIS was most perceived. amongst all the constraints, financial constraints were the most perceived ones.

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Constraints Perceived by Agricultural Extension Personnel in Using M-Tools

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ABSTRACT

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become a very important feature in the agricultural sector. m-extension is the emerging field of ICT for providing easy access to information at any place and any time. Researchers and Extensionists are important stake holders in the development of agricultural sector. This study examines the constraints perceived by agricultural extension personnel of Kerala in using m-tools. Data were collected using a pre-structured interview schedule. Results showed that majority of the extension personnel opined that non-availability of Malayalam (local language) interface and non-availability of mobile phone networks in remote areas were the major constraints faced by them in using m-tools.

Key Words: Agriculture, Extension personnel, Constraints, m-tools.

INTRODUCTION

Mobile telephony had overcome geographic, economic, social and cultural barriers which unveiled the new 3G and 4G technologies. Mobiles are going to revolutionise agricultural extension might be overstating the facts right now, but so far, within a few years of its introduction in the country, it has changed the mode of agricultural extension and proved to be a great aid to the human resource of the extension system (Sravanan, 2014). This device when lined-up with extension and advisory services improves the livelihood of rural people by providing need based information at affordable price. This so called mobile-based extension and advisory services (m-extension) empowers value-added services such as mobile agro-services and machine to machine services (Stryjak *et al*, 2015) that help farmers in tracking their crops and farm machinery using mobile phones (Sharma *et al*, 2012).

Agricultural extensionists act as direct link between the researchers and the farmers. In order to perform their role effectively and efficiently, they must have steady access to updated agricultural information. Constraints faced by agricultural extension personnel in using m-tools stood as the barrier for making effective use of the information provided by m-tools. Therefore, an attempt was made to identify the constraints that are responsible for restricting the use of m-tools by the agricultural extension personnel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the state of Kerala. Five districts, one each representing each agro-climatic zone in Kerala was selected randomly: Kozhikode (Northern zone), Trivandrum (Southern zone), Thrissur (Central zone), Wayanad (High altitude zone) and Alappuzha-Kuttanad tract (Problem area zone).

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Agricultural Extension Personnel comprising of Agricultural Officers (AOs) and Agricultural Assistants (AAs) from Krishibhavans (grass root level agricultural development officers in Kerala) were selected as the respondents of the study. From each of the selected five districts, 15 Krishibhavans were randomly selected and from each Krishibhavan one AO and one AAs were selected. Thus a total of 75 AOs and 75 AAs were identified, thus constituting a sample of 150 Agricultural Extension Personnel.

Constraints in using m-tools:

Constraints were operationally defined as the limitations or restrictions faced by the respondents in accessing and using various m-tools and services in agriculture. Through gathering relevant literature, discussion with scientists and non-sample extension personnel, a list of 17 constraints were prepared and administered to the respondents. For measuring this variable the scoring procedure followed by Ravikishore (2014) was adopted, in which the importance of constraints were measured on a

five point scale ranging from very important (5), important (4), less important (3), least important (2) and not important (1). The possible highest score was 85 and the least possible score was 17.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The constraints perceived by the extension personnel are presented in Table 1.

Of all the constraints listed, majority of the respondents felt non-availability of Malayalam interface as the important constraint with mean value of 4.22. Malayalam being the local language was preferred by most of the extension personnel for easiness in understanding the content. Unfortunately, m-tools available in Malayalam were very limited.

Non-availability of mobile phone networks in remote areas (4.20) was ranked as the second most important constraint. Though Kerala is blessed with good coverage of networks, some interior remote areas are there where signal tower is not nearby and was with poor connectivity.

Table 1. Constraints perceived by extension personnel in using m-tools (n=150)

Sr. No.	Constraint	Score	Mean	Rank
1.	Non-availability of Malayalam interface	634	4.22	I
2.	Non-availability of mobile phone networks in remote areas	630	4.20	II
3.	Non-availability of user friendly m-apps	627	4.18	III
4.	Lack of exposure to m-education	623	4.15	IV
5.	Low level of e-readiness by extension personnel/organizations	614	4.09	V
6.	Non-availability of mobile phones supported audio-video files on agricultural technologies	593	3.95	VI
7.	Lack of awareness of various options available in the mobile phone	583	3.88	VII
8.	Poor ICT infrastructural development	569	3.79	VIII
9.	Policy inconsistencies by government in both telecommunication and agricultural sectors	568	3.78	IX
10.	Difficulty in loading of data files on mobile phone	544	3.62	X
11.	Limited access to worldwide databases	534	3.56	XI
12.	Certain soft wares are difficult to learn and use	531	3.54	XII

Constraints Perceived by Extension Personnel

Non-availability of the user friendly m-apps (4.18) was the other difficulty faced by the extension personnel which was because of the complexity with the existing apps which were not providing need based and location specific information.

Lack of exposure to m-education and low level of e-readiness by extension personnel/organizations was the next major constraint, as this may be because of lack of relevant trainings conducted for the staff of the Department of Agriculture. All types of mobile phones will not support multimedia files like videos. The compatibility and version of the mobile phone matters in this case, which may be the reason why the extension personnel mentioned non-availability of mobile phone supported audio video files. Some of the extension personnel were still reluctant to use smart phones as they felt that it was difficult to handle smart phones and they mentioned that they use mobile phone only for the purpose of telephone calling. Other constraints include poor ICT infrastructural development and policy inconsistencies by government in both telecommunication and agricultural sectors, difficulty in loading of data files on mobile phone, limited access to worldwide databases and certain softwares are difficult to learn and use.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, if new technologies are not adequately built into the mainstream of agricultural extension system, there is likely to be stagnation in the dissemination, utilization and application of

scientific agricultural information for development of the system. On the other hand the constraints as reported in the study were preventing the effective use of m-tools and its services by the agricultural extension personnel. To mitigate the constraints m-tools in Malayalam (local language) should be made available, extension personnel should be encouraged to use smart phones which provides a way for accessing information easily. As lack of exposure to m-extension and low level of e-readiness among the agricultural extension personnel were found as the other important constraints, training programmes should be organised to make them aware of m-tools and to develop a positive attitude among them.

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Correlation Studies on Fruit Traits of Some Mandarin Genotypes Grown Under Sub-Tropical Conditions of India

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ABSTRACT

The relationships between fruit traits of some indigenous and exotic mandarin cultivars were studied during the year 2015-16. The study revealed highly significant positive correlation ($r = +0.801$) between fruit weight and fruit juice weight followed by fruit weight and segment length ($r = +0.761$); fruit weight and fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.731$); fruit weight and rind weight ($r = +0.634$) and fruit weight and fruit diameter ($r = +0.634$). Highly significant and positive correlations were also observed between fruit diameter and fruit rind weight ($r = +0.505$); fruit rind weight and segment length ($r = +0.785$); fruit rind weight and fruit juice weight ($r = +0.626$). Significant and positive correlations were also observed between fruit rind weight and vesicle length ($r = +0.538$), fruit rind weight and fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.491$), fruit rind weight and number of segments per fruit ($r = +0.481$). However, negative and significant correlation ($r = -0.534$) was observed between diameter of fruit axis and fruit juice weight followed by non-significant negative correlation between diameter of fruit axis and total soluble solids ($r = -0.386$). Total soluble solids showed positive correlations with fruit juice weight ($r = +0.444$) and fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.443$) and negative correlation ($r = -0.227$) with fruit acidity. These correlations among different fruit traits help to understand the relationship between different mandarin genotypes and must be considered before targeting the desired traits in improvement programme.

Key Words: Correlation, Genotypes, Mandarin, Traits.

INTRODUCTION

Mandarin is a most popular fruit in subtropical zone of India. The agro-ecological conditions of Punjab are best suited for the production of Kinnow mandarin. Presently, citrus is being grown in Punjab over 52,836 ha with annual production of 10,49,977. Kinnow mandarin occupies an area of 49,356 ha (93.4 %) with annual production of 10,21,719 (97.3%) (Anonymous, 2016).

No doubt, the fruit characters are generally used for the selection of best genotypes of citrus trees but the farmers pay more attention to the fruit quality than to its size and yield (Paudyal *et al*, 2008). The quality of citrus fruits depends on several factors including the amount of juice, its content

of total soluble solids (TSS), the acidity level and the proportion of vitamin C. Besides introduction of new cultivars, the scope of citrus cultivation, therefore, exists for further expansion of citrus industry through release of early and late varieties. It is very important to select the desired fruit trait in the parentage and more importantly the relationship studies between the important traits must not be ignored.

Only a few varieties of mandarins are available for commercial cultivation under Indian subtropical conditions. Secondly, information about the genotypic variability, correlation studies among important physico-chemical traits is lacking in mandarin. The study on correlation coefficient may

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not only provide the exact insight effect on yield but also indicate the influence of one character on other character. Thus, the present study was undertaken to focus on the correlation studies among different fruit traits in nineteen mandarin genotypes grown under sub-tropical conditions of India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out on 19 mandarin genotypes at Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana (Punjab) during the year 2015-16. The university is at latitude 30° 54' N and longitude 75° 48' E with subtropical climatic conditions. The height above mean sea level is 247 m. The maximum air temperature of area in summer rose up to 41°C whereas minimum temperature in winter went down to 5°C during the period under research. The annual average rainfall and evaporation in research area was about 769 mm and 1564 mm during the period of investigation, respectively.

Nineteen mandarin genotypes grafted on rough lemon rootstock planted at a spacing of 6 x 3 m were used in the research work. Observations were recorded during the years 2015 and 2016 on trees for different morphological characters at various growth and development stages. All the trees received recommended doses of fertilizers and other cultural practices during the course of these investigations. Data were recorded on mature vegetative parts. Reproductive and fruit characters were recorded before the harvesting of fruits. Correlations among fruit physiochemical characters of different mandarin genotypes were carried out with partial correlation method and test of significance was considered at 5 and 1 per cent level of probability ($P < 0.05$) and $P < 0.01$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fruit weight

The data in Table 1 show that there was a highly significant positive correlation ($r = +0.801$) between fruit weight and fruit juice weight which

was followed by fruit weight and segment length ($r = +0.761$); fruit weight and fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.731$); fruit weight and rind weight ($r = +0.634$) and fruit weight and fruit diameter ($r = +0.634$). The correlations between fruit weight and fruit length ($r = +0.524$), and fruit weight and segment length ($r = +0.465$) were positive and significant. Non-significant and negative correlations were observed in fruit weight with fruit rind thickness, diameter of fruit axis and fruit acidity.

The data show that fruit weight influence fruit segment length and breadth, and fruit juice content, however, fruit weight has no effect on fruit rind thickness and fruit acidity. The results were contrary to the findings of Gill *et al* (2002) who reported negative correlations among fruit size and juice content in Kinnow mandarin. Zhang and Gu (2003) also found negative correlation between fruit size and soluble solids.

Fruit diameter and length

Highly significant and positive correlations were also observed between fruit diameter and fruit epicarp width ($r = +1.000$) followed by significant positive correlations in fruit diameter and fruit rind weight ($r = +0.505$) and fruit diameter and vesicle length ($r = +0.488$). Other traits like fruit length, segments per fruit, segment length, segment breadth, vesicle thickness, total soluble solids, fruit juice weight and fruit juice percentage showed positive correlation with fruit diameter but were non-significant ($P < 0.05$). Non-significant and negative correlations were found in fruit diameter with fruit rind thickness, diameter of fruit axis and fruit acidity.

The correlations were highly significant and positive between fruit length and fruit rind weight ($r = +0.641$) and between fruit length and segment length ($r = +0.635$). Fruit traits like fruit epicarp width, areola diameter, segment per fruit, diameter of fruit axis, vesicle length, vesicle thickness, fruit juice weight and fruit juice percentage also showed positive correlations with fruit length but were non-significant. Negative correlations were observed

Correlation Studies on Fruit Traits of Mandarin

between fruit length and total soluble solids and between fruit length and fruit acidity.

Fruit epicarp width

Epicarp width showed significant and positive correlations with fruit rind weight ($r = +0.505$) and vesicle length ($r = +0.488$). Negative non-significant correlations were found in fruit epicarp width with fruit rind thickness, diameter of fruit axis and fruit acidity.

Fruit rind thickness and weight

Fruit rind thickness showed positive correlation with areola diameter, segment length, diameter of fruit axis, vesicle length, and vesicle thickness and fruit acidity while negative correlations were observed with other traits like fruit rind weight, number of segment per fruit, segment breadth, total soluble solids, fruit juice weight and fruit juice percentage.

The maximum positive correlation ($r = +0.785$) was observed between fruit rind weight and segment length, followed by fruit rind weight and fruit juice weight ($r = +0.626$) and these correlations were highly significant. Significant and positive correlations were also observed between fruit rind weight and vesicle length ($r = +0.538$), fruit rind weight and fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.491$), fruit rind weight and number of segments per fruit ($r = +0.481$). However, non-significant and negative correlations were found in rind weight with diameter of fruit axis and fruit acidity.

Areola diameter

Areola diameter showed significant positive correlation with diameter of fruit axis ($r = +0.459$), however negative correlations were observed with number of segments per fruit, total soluble solids, fruit acidity, fruit juice weight and fruit juice percentage.

Segment length and breadth

Segment length was positively correlated with fruit juice weight, fruit juice percentage, vesicle length, vesicle thickness and segment breadth.

However, the correlations between segment length and fruit juice weight ($r = +0.579$); and between segment length and fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.536$) were significant only. Segment length was non-significantly and negatively correlated with fruit acidity. Segment breadth was positively correlated with fruit juice weight, fruit juice percentage, vesicle thickness, total soluble solids and fruit acidity. However, the correlations between segment breadth and fruit juice weight ($r = +0.471$) was significant only. Segment length was non-significantly and negatively correlated with vesicle length.

Fruit axis diameter

Maximum negative and significant correlation ($r = -0.534$) was observed between diameter of fruit axis and fruit juice weight followed by non-significant negative correlation between diameter of fruit axis and total soluble solids ($r = -0.386$). However, significant and positive correlation ($r = +0.465$) was observed between diameter of fruit axis and vesicle thickness. Negative correlation was also reported by Kumar *et al* (2015) in fruit weight and fruit axis diameter (hollowness) in mandarin.

Vesicle length and thickness

Vesicle length showed positive correlation with vesicle thickness ($r = +0.210$), total soluble solids ($r = +0.338$), fruit juice weight ($r = +0.222$) and fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.120$) except fruit acidity which showed negative correlation ($r = -0.342$) with vesicle length. However, all these correlations were non-significant. Positive but non-significant correlations in vesicle thickness were found with total soluble solids ($r = +0.220$), fruit juice weight ($r = +0.039$), fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.072$). However, fruit acidity showed negative correlation ($r = -0.387$) with vesicle thickness.

Total soluble solids and acidity

Total soluble solids showed positive correlations with fruit juice weight ($r = +0.444$) and fruit juice percentage ($r = +0.443$) and negative correlation ($r = -0.227$) with fruit acidity. Non-significant negative correlations were observed between fruit

Table 1. Correlation matrix among mandarin genotypes based on fruit characteristics

Traits	FW	FD	FL	EW	RT	RW	AD	SPF	SL	SB	DFA	VL	VT	TSS	TA	FJW
FD	0.634**															
FL	0.524*	0.433														
EW	0.634**	1.000**	0.433													
RT	-0.194	-0.214	0.003	-0.214												
RW	0.718**	0.505*	0.641**	0.505*	-0.031											
AD	0.179	0.141	0.330	0.141	0.203	0.010										
SPF	0.272	0.410	0.145	0.410	-0.158	0.481*	-0.029									
SL	0.761**	0.389	0.635**	0.389	0.145	0.785**	0.227	0.236								
SB	0.465*	0.051	0.006	0.051	-0.367	0.037	0.291	-0.113	0.343							
DFA	-0.225	-0.125	0.308	-0.125	0.341	-0.006	0.459*	-0.117	0.007	0.063						
VL	0.350	0.488*	0.162	0.488*	0.324	0.538*	0.306	0.233	0.352	-0.201	0.056					
VT	0.234	0.014	0.062	0.014	0.076	0.290	0.278	0.105	0.256	0.403	0.465*	0.210				
TSS	0.432	0.398	-0.122	0.398	-0.118	0.351	-0.101	0.244	0.320	0.267	-0.386	0.338	0.220			
TA	-0.428	-0.393	-0.220	-0.393	0.065	-0.362	-0.212	-0.131	-0.212	0.106	0.097	-0.342	-0.387	-0.227		
FJW	0.801**	0.359	0.280	0.359	-0.322	0.626**	-0.244	0.019	0.579**	0.316	-0.534*	0.222	0.039	0.444	-0.368	
FJP	0.732**	0.332	0.248	0.332	-0.343	0.491*	-0.103	-0.160	0.536*	0.471*	-0.341	0.120	0.072	0.443	-0.371	0.885**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Legend:-FW: Fruit Weight, FD: Fruit Diameter, FL: Fruit Length, EW: Epicarp Width, RT: Rind Thickness, RW: Rind Weight, AD: Areola Diameter, SPF: Segment Per Fruit, SL: Segment Length, SB: Segment Breadth, DFA: Diameter of Fruit Axis, VL: Vesicle Length, VT: Vesicle Thickness, TSS: Total Soluble Solids, TA: Titratable Acidity, FJW: Fruit Juice Weight, FJP: Fruit Juice Per cent

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acidity and fruit juice weight, and acidity and fruit juice percentage.

The positive and significant correlations were found among different characters like fruit weight and juice; fruit weight and diameter; fruit weight and segment length; fruit diameter and fruit epicarp width; fruit diameter and rind weight; vesicle length and vesicle thickness; total soluble solids and fruit juice weight; areola diameter and fruit axis diameter. However, negative correlations were observed between fruit length and total soluble solids; fruit length and fruit acidity; diameter of fruit axis and fruit juice weight. The results were supported more or less by the finding of Khandavi (2012) who reported highly significant and positive correlations of fruit weight with fruit length and fruit breadth in sweet oranges selections and Kagzi lime. Number of seeds positively correlated with length and rind thickness of the fruit in Kagzi lime (Pingle, 2011). Tilekar (2011) reported highly significant and positive correlation with each and negative but highly significant correlation with the fruit acidity. However, negative correlation in acidity and TSS was reported by Pingle (2011). Significant and negative correlation was found in fruit weight, fruit diameter, juice percent and seed number, however significantly positive correlation in fruit pulp, and ascorbic acid, but no significant effect was observed in fruit peel, TSS and acidity in acid lime selections (Shrestha *et al*, 2012).

No doubt, the fruit characters are generally used for the selection of best genotypes of citrus trees but the farmers pay more attention to the fruit quality than to its size and yield (Paudya *et al*, 2008). The quality of citrus fruits depends on several factors including the amount of juice, its content of total soluble solids (TSS), the acidity level and the proportion of vitamin C. Marcilla *et al* (2009) reported that fruit juice yield was independent and poorly correlated with almost all fruit sensory parameters in 'Clemenules' mandarins. Rehman *et al* (1983) also supported our findings of positive correlation between fruit weight and juice content and TSS in sweet oranges. However, their findings were contrary to our finding

where they reported negative correlation between juice content and acidity.

CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that there was a strong positive and negative association between different important fruit traits in mandarin genotypes and hence breeding programme should be planned in accordance with the desired trait association.

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Demographic Characteristics and Constraints Faced by Farmers in West Khasi Hills district

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ABSTRACT

A study on demographic characteristics and constraints faced by farmers in West Khasi Hills district of Meghalaya was undertaken during 2016-17. One hundred and twenty respondents were selected by adopting simple random sampling. Results revealed that 37.50 per cent of the farmers belonged to the age group (31-40yr), 35.83 percent studied up to primary school and 50 percent having large size family. Majority of the farmers (45.0%) had marginal land holding, 82.50 per cent of them had low level of annual income with majority of the farmers (58.3 %) had no extension contact. Majority of the farmers (87.5%) had medium economic motivation and 54.2 per cent of them had high risk orientation with 41.7 percent of them had livestock possession of both poultry + piggery and 65.0 percent of the farmers had low training. The various constraints were non availability of inputs in time (83.33%), lack of credit on marginal interest (83.33%), fluctuations in market price (83.33%) followed by lack of skill for seed and soil treatment (95.0%) in technical and general problems were uncertainty of rainfall (86.2%) and labour shortage (56.66%) .

Key words: Demographic characteristics, Khasi hills, Fluctuations market price, Rainfall, Labour.

INTRODUCTION

West Khasi Hills District lies in the central part of the state of Meghalaya and is situated between approximately 25 degrees 10' and 25 degrees 51' N Latitude, and between 90 degrees 44' and 91 degrees 49' E Longitude. It is bounded on the North-West by Kamrup District of Assam, on the North-East by Ri Bhoi District, on the east by East Khasi Hills District, on the south by Bangladesh and South West Khasi Hills district, the erstwhile Mawkyrwat Civil Sub-Division, on the west by East Garo Hills and South Garo Hills Districts. The district comprises an area of about 5,247 sqkm which is 23 percent of the total area of the state. Nongstoin, covering an area of about 76.00 sq. Km, is the Headquarter of the district.

West Khasi Hills District, presently the largest district of Meghalaya, was carved out of the erstwhile Khasi Hills District on the 28th October, 1976. In the same year, on 10th November, the Mairang Civil Subdivision was inaugurated,

whereas the Mawkyrwat Block was converted into an Administrative unit. With the up gradation of Mawkyrwat into a full-fledged Sub-division on June 26th 1982, the district then comprises of three sub-divisions (including the Sadar sub-division), one Administrative unit viz., Mawshynrut which came into being on the 9th February, 1996 and 6 (six) C & R D Blocks viz., Nongstoin, Mairang, Mawkyrwat, Mawshynrut, Ranikor including Mawthadraishan Block which was created on the 20th March, 2001. The district was later bifurcated into two districts-the present West Khasi Hills District and new South West Khasi Hills District headquarter at Mawkyrwat comprising 2 (two) C & R D Blocks viz., Mawkyrwat and Ranikor C & R D Block. More than 80 per cent of the total population in West Khasi Hills is agrarian as their main backbone of livelihood is basically agriculture. Rice, Maize, potato and ginger are the main crops grown in West Khasi Hills. Agriculture and allied activities provide income and employment for the people in West Khasi Hills. Monocropping in lowland areas

and mixed cropping in upland areas are the features of agriculture in the district. Keeping this in view, the present study was conducted to assess the demographic characteristics and constraints faced by farmers in the West Khasi Hills district.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in West Khasi Hills district of Meghalaya in the year 2016-17. Simple random sampling procedure was adopted for the selection of respondents. Twelve villages were selected from three C& RD Block of four villages each for investigation and 10 respondents from each village were selected. Thus, the total sample for the study constituted 120 respondents. The socio-economic profile and constraints was probed with the help of an interview schedule developed for the study. The various constraints being faced were divided into five categories *i.e.* input based, financial, marketing, technical and general. For quantitative analysis, percentage, mean and standard deviation was used for the study and overall constraints were ranked on the basis of response of the respondents. Interview schedule was prepared for collecting information on demographic characteristics and constraints faced by the farmers. A survey was conducted in these villages and 10 farmers from each village were interviewed personally to note down the different constraints faced by them in agricultural activities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic characteristics of the respondents

A perusal on Table 1 indicated that that 37.50 per cent of the farmers belonged to the age group (31-40 yrs) followed by 29.16 percent under 41-50 yr. which shows that individual indulged more in agriculture activities when his family members started increasing to meet the family demands. Majority of them were married (98.30%) and 50 percent of them had large size family which revealed that early marriage is still prevalent in the district in which the findings were in line with the research results of Fakoya *et al* (2003) and Manay

and Farzana (2000), while 35.83 percent studied up to primary school. This situation might have arisen due to low financial position of the respondents and non-realization of importance of education.

Majority of the farmers (45.00%) had marginal land holding followed by small land holders (33.33%) and it was happened due to lack of ancestral property, family property and increase in family size. Majority of the farmers (82.50%) had low level of annual income and this was due to low land-holding possession, unawareness of improved farm technologies with majority of the farmers (58.30%) had no extension contact. Majority of the farmers (87.50%) had medium economic motivation and 54.20 per cent of them had high risk orientation and this occurred due to higher returns received from the farming activities. A large percentage of 41.70 percent had livestock possession of both poultry + piggery as the farmers depend on these livestock for farm manure on crop cultivation, also majority of them cannot afford to buy manures and fertilizers. Majority of them (65.00%) had no training, as more than 35.83 % had education up to primary school.

Constraints faced by the farmers in agricultural activities

Data from table 2 revealed that the various constraints were divided into five sub components as input supply, financial, marketing, technical and general problems. Non availability of inputs in time (83.33%), non availability of recommended chemicals (68.00%) and non availability of improved varieties (50.00%) were the major constraints in input related problems. This was due to the fact that majority of the farmers depend their seed, fertilizers and chemical requirement from Department of Agriculture which was supplied to the farmers on subsidized rate and at a time cannot fulfill the farmers' needs because the department supplied the inputs as per the allotment sanctioned. The major constraints in financial were lack of credit on marginal interest (83.33%) which were in line with the findings of Joseph and Easwaran (2006) and high cost of chemical fertilizers (57.5%)

Constraints Faced by Farmers in West Khasi Hills

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents n=120

Sr. No.	Variable	Category	Respondents (n)	
			Frequency	Percentage
1	Age (yr)	21-30	24	20.0
		31-40	45	37.5
		41-50	35	29.16
		51-60	15	12.5
		61-70	1	0.83
2	Marital status	Married	118	98.3
		Unmarried	2	1.7
3	Education	Illiterate	1	0.83
		Primary (Class I-III)	43	35.83
		Medium (Class IV-VI)	40	33.33
		High School (VII-X)	31	25.83
		Intermediate (X-XII)	5	4.16
4	Family size	Small size (1 - 3)	21	17.5
		Medium size (4 - 6)	39	32.5
		Large size (7 and above)	60	50.0
5	Land holding	Marginal (0.1-1.0 ha)	54	45.0
		Small (1.1-2.0 ha)	40	33.33
		Semi-medium (2.1-4.0 ha)	14	11.66
		Medium (4.1-10.0 ha)	12	10.0
6	Annual income * (Agriculture +live-stock)	Low income (up to Rs.17,000)	99	82.5
		Semi-medium income (Rs.17,001-34,000)	1	0.83
		Medium income (Rs.34,001-51,000)	20	1.66
		High income (above Rs.51,000)	0	0.00
7	Extension contact	Never	70	58.3
		Regularly	10	8.3
		Occasionally	40	33.3
8	Economic Motivation	Low (<22.8)	10	8.3
		Medium (22.8-24.2)	105	87.5
		High (>24.2)	5	4.2
		Mean: 23.5, SD: 1.7		
9	Risk Orientation	Low (<18.9)	50	41.7
		Medium (18.9-23.3)	5	4.2
		High (>23.3)	65	54.2
		Mean: 21.1, SD: 5.2		
10	Livestock Possession	No livestock	10	8.3
		Poultry	40	33.3
		Piggery	20	16.7
		Poultry + Piggery	50	41.7
11	Training	No training	78	65.00
		Low (<0.62)	3	2.5
		Medium (0.62-1.26)	36	30.0
		High (>1.26)	3	2.5
		Mean: 0.325, SD: 4.5		

Table 2. Constraints faced by the farmers in agricultural activities.(n=120)

Sr.No.	Constraint	Percentage	Rank
a.	Input		
1.	Non availability of inputs in time	83.33	I
2.	Non availability of recommended chemicals	68.00	II
3.	Non availability of improved varieties	50.00	III
b.	Financial		
1.	Lack of credit on marginal interest	83.33	I
2.	High cost of chemical fertilizers	57.5	II
c.	Marketing		
1.	Fluctuations in market price	83.33	I
2.	Lack of storage facilities	75.00	II
3.	Exploitation by the middleman	70.83	III
4.	Lack of market information	66.66	IV
d.	Technical		
1.	Lack of skill for seed and soil treatment	95.00	I
2.	Lack of knowledge for application of manures, plant protection chemicals as per recommended dose	90.00	II
3.	Lack of need based training	85.00	III
4.	Increased resistance of pests and diseases to plant protection chemicals	67.5	IV
e.	General		
1.	Uncertainty of rainfall	86.20	I
2.	Labour shortage	56.66	II
3.	High labour cost	37.5	III
4.	Poor transportation facilities	21.66	IV

which arose because the Department of Agriculture, Government of Meghalaya at present has stopped the subsidy for chemical fertilizers and pesticides and replaced them with organic manures and bio pesticides to promote Organic Agriculture in the state in which the farmers had to buy chemical fertilizers from the local supplier at a very high price. Fluctuations market price (83.33%), Lack of storage facilities (75.00%) were the major constraints in marketing. The findings were in line with the research results of Rao *et al* (2007). The

major technical problems were lack of skill for seed and soil treatment (95.00%), lack of knowledge for application of manures, plant protection chemicals as per recommended dose (90.00%) which were in line with Resmy *et al* (2001) and lack of need based training (85.00%) and this occurred due to lack of extension contact with Agriculture Officers and KVK scientists. The general problems were uncertainty of rainfall (86.20%), labour shortage (56.66%), high labour cost (37.5%) and poor transportation facilities (21.66%).

Constraints Faced by Farmers in West Khasi Hills

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that the farmers of the district need more awareness regarding the value of education so that their children would take interest on education which in turn would help from early marriage. They would require to pay a visit at least once a month to the KVK, Agriculture State Departments and allied Departments for their farm needs. The study also revealed that to tackle the different constraints, the farmers need to have a proper farm management and marketing training skill, proper training skill on different IPM practices and awareness on credit linkage as well as subsidy facilities to buy farm machineries.

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Development of Cow Dung Based Herbal Mosquito Repellent

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ABSTRACT

Mosquitoes are the most important and abundant pest in urban, suburban and rural environment. Although, chemical control provides quick mortality, resistance of mosquito against the use of insecticides have been widely reported. Moreover, chemical mosquito repellents contain toxic synthetic pyrethroids as active ingredients whose exposure to food and water is hazardous to health. In present study, an attempt has been made to develop an eco-friendly mosquito coil containing cow dung, Neem leaves, Saw dust, loban, Tulsi, Maida and Lemon grass oil. This paper deals with selection and optimization of ingredients, their characteristics, medicinal properties and comparison with existing coil.

Key words: Cow dung, Citronella, Pallethrin, Plant extract, Neem, Tulsi.

INTRODUCTION

Mosquito borne disease are major human-health problem in all tropical and subtropical countries. The disease transmitted include malaria, filariasis, yellow fever, Japanese encephalitis and dengue fever *Culex quinquefasciatus*, the potential vector of lymphatic filariasis, is the most widely distributed tropical disease with around 120 million people infected worldwide and 44 million people having common chronic manifestation (Bernhard *et al*, 2003). Controls of such serious diseases are becoming increasingly difficult because of high rate of reproduction and development of resistance to insecticides in mosquitoes (Sukumar *et al*, 1991).

Synthetic pesticides have been extensively used for mosquito control by either killing, preventing adult mosquito to bite human beings or by killing mosquito larvae at the breeding sites of vectors. However its deleterious impact on non-target population and the development of resistance prompted for the search of alternative, simple and sustainable methods of Mosquito control. The need for development of effective insecticides should be

taken in to consideration due to toxicity problems, together with the increased incidence of insect resistance (Miro specos *et al*, 2010). In the most part of the world, synthetic chemical larvicides continue to be applied for controlling mosquitoes but many of these chemicals are toxic to human, animal and plant life and resistance can be problematic in regulating the control. Therefore, researchers are currently exploiting natural substances to be used as insecticides for controlling larval mosquitoes. These formulations are safe, eco friendly, cheap, easy to use and has maximum repellence against mosquitoes. Hence, an effort was made to prepare cow dung based herbal mosquito repellent.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Raw material Selection

Raw material has been selected based on experience, traditional knowledge and practice by ancestors (Duke *et al*, 2002). Cow dung contains plenty of Menthol, Ammonia, Phenol, Indol, Formalin and specifically its bacteriophage eradicate the pathogens and are a recognised disinfectant

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(Mohan *et al*, 2007). Plant products are emerging as a potential source of mosquito control and among them essential oils have special interest due to their insecticidal properties (Benner, 1993).

Lemon Grass Oil (*Cymbopogon flexuosus*)

Lemongrass is an aromatic and medicinal herb. It has been used because of its disinfectant property and good smell.

Tulsi (*Ocimum Sanctum*)

Tulsi is the most sacred and generally used as medicinal plant in Indian homes. It has excellent antiviral and insecticidal property.

Neem (*Azadirachta indica*)

Azadirachta is a powerful insect anti-feedant that disrupt metamorphosis as a moth larvae at extremely low concentration. It has also been proved that besides azadirachtin, salanim, gedunin, azadinone, nimbin, nimbidine, nimbicidine, nimitinolare also important liminods which has excellent effect on insect and pest (Su and Mulla, 1998). Active ingredient of *azadirachta indica* inhibits the growth of insects by interrupting their life cycle.

Maida

It has been used as binder. Maida is found to be more convenient for use and gives excellent binding to all the ingredients and holds it together strongly.

Saw dust

Saw dust will enhance the combustion process while cow dung has large ash content, large volatile content, low carbon content and burning ratio is low.

Loban (sambarani)

It is a resin from a tree (*Styrax benzoin*) and is an excellent repellent of insects and mosquitoes. The fumigation of Loban is a good insect repellent. It has qualities of insecticides, as well as antiseptic. The smoke of loban create soothing atmosphere of serenity.

Method of preparation

The different herbal plants used in the study were collected from our herbal garden of panchgavya research and extension centre. The dried neem leaves (18.22%), tulsi (4.38%) were mixed with Loban (5.82%), maida (6.14%) and saw dust (6.88%), ground well to get a powdered form which was then mixed with dried cow dung (50%). After mixing, pressed in to the desired shapes with the help of a mould which was then dried with the help of drier. Lemon grass oil (8.56%) was sprayed on top of the coil by using a hand spray pump. The coil was dried in the oven at 700c for 6 hr and further kept in the room for half an hour of drying. Finally, these coils were packed in suitable air tight container and kept for 2-3 d for storage so that the essential oil could spread uniformly on the coil.

Table 1. Composition of different ingredients used in herbal mosquito coil.

Sr. No.	Ingredient	Parts (Per cent)
1.	Neem Leaves	18.22
2.	Tulsi	4.38
3.	Loban	5.82
4.	Maida	6.14
5.	Saw Dust	6.88
6.	Dried cow dung	50.0
7.	Lemon Grass Oil	8.56

Smoke toxicity test

Experiments were conducted in glass chamber measuring 140x120x60 cm and a window measuring 60x30 cm was situated at mid bottom of one side of the chamber. Three or four day's blood starved adult female mosquitoes, fed with sucrose solution, were released in the chamber. The experiment chamber was tightly closed. Smoke toxicity was tested with commercial mosquito coil and herbal mosquito repellent from 20 min to 1 hr. intervals respectively (Vineetha and Murugan, 2009).

Cow Dung Based Herbal Mosquito Repellent

Table 2. Comparative efficacy of herbal mosquito repellent with commercial mosquito

Sr. No.	Time (min)	Type of repellent used	Observations recorded
1	5-7 pm	No coil used	Numerous mosquitoes
2	7-9 pm	Commercial coil	100 per cent mosquitoes reduced.
3	9-10 pm	Herbal mosquito repellentHer	85 per cent of the mosquitoes reduced.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was noticed that by 5 to 7 pm when no coil was used, the room was filled with mosquitoes and at 7 to 8 pm, a commercial coil was used to check the repellence activity in that area. It was found that up to 95 per cent of the mosquitoes were reduced. Further, when no coils were used from 7 to 9 pm again, a large number of mosquitoes were gathered. After the burning of herbal mosquito repellent from 9 to 10 pm, it was noticed that up to 85 per cent of the mosquitoes reduced. According to Palanisami *et al* (2014) the death of the mosquitoes increased with the application of the herbal mosquito repellent but as the time of using coils increased, 100 per cent of mosquito died with the application of the commercial coil.

Smoke toxicity effect of herbal mosquito repellent

The smoke toxicity effect of herbal mosquito repellent v/s commercial mosquito coil on mosquitoes was studied and found that after 20 minutes, 54 mosquitoes dropped down and 20 mosquitoes were died due to the burning herbal mosquito repellent while 74 mosquitoes died with the application of commercial coil. The death of

the mosquitoes increased with increase in time interval, 100 per cent of the mosquitoes died with the application of commercial coil. The results were in agreement with Palanisami *et al* (2014). After 20 min. commercial coil killed almost 100 per cent of mosquitoes with deleterious effect on human health while herbal mosquito coil killed mosquitoes 64 to 81 per cent between 20 to 60 minutes (Table 3).

CONCLUSION

It is not only that lemon grass oil showed good mosquito repellent activity in performed tests but it was also strong mosquitocidal agent, Hence, lemongrass, essential oil, alone or in combinations with those obtained from other mosquito repellent plant species, could be potentially used for the preparation of mosquito repellent products. The results of this investigation indicated that the lemon grass oil could be beneficial for the control of vector borne diseases. It provides an herbal repellent with long lasting protection, safe for human life, human and domestic animal skin with no side effect and no feedback of environmental ill effect, as an alternative to synthetic chemical repellents. The formulation was safe, eco-friendly, cheap, easy to use and has maximum repellence against mosquitoes.

Table 3. Smoke toxicity effect of herbal mosquito repellent and commercial mosquito coil.

Sr.No	Time of observation after burning of mosquito repellent	Herbal Mosquito Coil		Commercial Mosquito Coil
		No. of dropped down mosquito	No. of died mosquito	No. of mosquito died by commercial mosquito coil
1	After 20 min	54.00±2.35	20.00±1.45	74.00±0.35
2	After 30 min	102.00±4.65	45.00±2.05	102.00±0.00
3	After 40 min	125.00±5.76	64.00±3.24	100.00±0.00
4	After 50 min	140.00±6.23	73.00±4.50	100.00±0.00
5	After 1hr	152.00±7.85	81.00±4.85	100.00±0.00

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Development of Okra-Cutter-Holder

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ABSTRACT

Okra fruits have an almost hair like bristles and prickly surface exposure to which is uncomfortable to the hands of the harvester. In extreme cases, persons with sensitive skin have developed sores or allergic reactions after a prolonged period of exposure to the pods during a harvest. Therefore to minimize above mentioned problems we developed a suitable low cost tool, okra-cutter-holder. This invention is directed okra cutter to an improved okra-cutter-holder, which permits one to harvest okra pods from a plant without touching the pod. The developed tool was tested in the laboratory as well as in the field. The comparative tests were carried out to compare the performance of the newly developed okra-cutter-holder with the old straight blade okra plucker. The feedback from the workers was taken for ease of operation and the acceptance of the tool for the harvesting of okra. The results shown that the new tool could harvest 297-318 okra per hour (10.0 – 10.9 kg/hr) without damaging pods and also provides better protection to the hands of workers.

Key Words: Cutter, Design considerations, Harvesting, Holder, Okra.

INTRODUCTION

In India, okra is generally harvested without any safety to prevent bruising and after harvesting it is dumped at one place, which results mechanical injuries to the ridges of pods. To reduce the post harvest losses in okra, it should be least handled (Dhall *et al*, 2014). Labourers are usually unwilling to take up okra harvesting work and demand exorbitant wages because the bristles on the okra pods cause injury to the skin during the harvesting operation i.e. in hand plucking method. In order to avoid that, it was suggested to wash hands thoroughly after okra plucking operation or wear gloves throughout operation. Okra growing farmers and labourers do not prefer to wear gloves as the same obstructs the movement of fingers necessary to carry out the harvesting operation efficiently.

The tools available in the market (horticulture secateurs, circular snip, okra plucker) were inefficient for harvesting okra, as reported by earlier workers. Secateurs and circular snip could not

reach the stalk of the pod easily, because of wider in size and shape. Scissors were having effective reach but much care and time is required in opening the scissors and operating them. Moreover their continuous use resulted in a fatigue in the fingers and thumb. Washing of hand thoroughly after picking is also not effective. The pods harvested with minimum handling and field packaging can retain their green colour, crisp texture. The average postharvest loss of okra at production level was 11.5 per cent (Prasad, 2015). Straight blade okra plucker, was not effective because okra pods have been harvested by holding the pod in one hand and cutting the pod from the plant with the other hand using a cutting tool.

Okra pod harvester and cutter were developed in USA which could harvest and hold the pods (Welborn, 1998). Longer pods could not be cut because of straight cutting and short length of arm. Okra pods grow at the bottom of the forks i.e. from where the branches/leaves come out from these stem

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of the plant. Stalk of the pod is tender and requires very little force to break it or to cut it with the help of a sharp tool. There are very small triangular spaces left on the either side of the stalk of the okra pod. The close harvesting of okra therefore needs to be carried out carefully, otherwise the stem of the plant or the petiole of the leaf may get cut or damaged.

Mechanical harvesting of okra depends on physical properties of the okra like uniformity of plant size and other plant characteristics greatly affect the productivity of machine harvested okra (Aminu *et al*, 2016; Salau and Makinde, 2016 and Pawar *et al*, 2017). So there was necessity to design okra cutter-holder which will provide an okra harvesting tool that not only cut the okra pod from the plant but also holds the okra pod. That avoids injuries of hand which are made by bristles on the pod at reduced cost of harvesting of okra to get maximum profit. To overcome these hindrances the okra cutter-holder was developed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Following plant and tool parameters were considered for developing the okra cutter- holder.

Plant parameters

Location of the okra pod on the plant and space available around the pod stalk for inserting the cutting tool, diameter of the pod, stalk diameter and length also the shearing strength were determined and presented in Table 1.

Tool parameters

Size, shape, weight and operational force of tool as well as the size and shape of the blade were major concern while designing the tool.

Safety and comfort parameters

The injuries inflicted on the skin of the palm in general and fingers and thumb in particular along with adaptability, portability and ease of operation of new designed tool were given prime importance while designing.

Constructional details of okra cutter-holder

The harvesting tool was designed based on the physical data of the okra plant at the time of harvesting as described in the Table 1. The tool is having least number of parts for easy operation and low maintenance. It consists fork, blade, pad (with slot) and holder as shown in the Fig. 1. The length of holder was 110 mm to accommodate longest okra length. The width of blade and the holder was 20 mm to cut and hold widest okra pod i.e. 2 cm. the fork length was kept 150 mm to reduce the effort required for cutting. The cutting blade was supported by the nylon pad with slot to help the shearing action of the blade.

The holder with blade and the fork were attached at an angle of 30° on the basis of angle between pod and the leaf. Two screws of 4 mm in diameter were used for connection of each holder plate.

Table 1. Average specifications of okra plant.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Dimensional Range
1	Height of plant	0.5 – 1.6 m
2	Length of okra pod	8 – 11 cm
3	Diameter of okra pod (crown)	1– 2 cm
4	Diameter of the stem of okra pod	6– 8 mm
5	Length of the stem of okra pod	1.5 – 2 cm
6	Angle between stalk of pod and stem of plant	15° – 20°
7	Angle between stalk of pod and petiole of the leaf	20° – 25°
8	Safe angular spacing available for cutting the pod	35°

Development of Okra-Cutter-Holder

Fig. 1 Details of okra cutter-holder

Operation of tool

The tool is held with the help of thumb and other fingers. The stalk of okra pod is then admitted in the throat between blade and pad. The fork ends are then pressed sufficiently so that the blade would come closer to pad (slot), this process cut the pedicel by shearing and separate the pod. At the end of cutting stroke fork ends come closer and the okra pod is caught by the holders. Then cut okra pod could be placed in the basket or bag without touching it. The operation of the tool is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 operation of okra cutter-holder

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Functional and operational performance test of the prototype of okra cutter-holder was carried out in the laboratory of Dr. A. S. College of Agricultural Engineering Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri by using tender branches of ornamental plants grown nearby the workshop and okra pods with long stalk brought for the specific purpose.

Laboratory test of okra cutter-holder showed that it operated properly and satisfactorily.

Adaptability

Before conducting the field trials, labourers were handed over the prototype and were asked to practice okra harvesting by using them for some time. After giving sufficient practice they were asked to express their views regarding the adaptability of the new tool. All of them given a feedback that the tool is quite handy and convenient for okra harvesting. They confirmed their opinion at the end of field trials. These opinions are given below.

Portability and Ease of Operation

Portability of a tool mainly depends upon its weight. The weight of tool is 102 g so handling and transporting is not a problem. The labourers employed for the field trials also expressed the same opinion. The tool was given to different workers and the feedback was taken to assess the ease of operation. Tool was found handy and easy to operate by the workers.

Harvesting Capacity of the Okra Cutter-Holder

Harvesting capacity of the okra cutter-holder is 297-318 okra per hour (i.e. 10.0 – 10.9 kg/hr). Comparative tests results of okra cutter-holder, straight blade okra plucker, hand picking and okra-cutter-holder shown that Okra cutter-holder could harvest more okra per hour than other methods of harvesting okra (Table 2).

CONCLUSION

The angle between stalk of pod and stem of plant varies from 15° to 20°. The angle between stalk of pod and petiole of the leaf varies from 20° to 25°. The Design of the okra cutter holder was based on these two basic parameters. Quantity of okra collected is 297-318 okra per hour (10.0 – 10.9 kg/hr) which is greater than quantity of okra collected by straight blade plucker method and hand picking method (5.2 – 6.1 kg/hr). The okra could be cut properly without damage. The okra cutter-holder can cut and hold okra pod properly and reduce the injuries due to bristles of the pod to

Table 2. Comparative performance of okra cutter and okra-cutter-holder.

Sr. No	Subject	Age	Okra Cutter		Okra cutter holder	
			Quantity harvested No/hr, kg/hr	Remarks from subject	Quantity harvested No/hr, kg/hr	Remarks from subject
1	S1	21	180, 6.10	Scratches on hand, hard to operate. pain at center of palm	318, 10.9	Easy to Operate, no need to hold the okra.
2	S2	25	172, 5.8	Scratches on hand, thumbs pains after 10-12 min, difficult to operate etc.	308, 10.4	Simple in using, less time required, cannot hold large okra.
3	S3	28	169, 5.75	Unable to hold, scratches on hand, large and extra mature are not cut.	297, 10.0	No scratches, easy to operate. But difficult to cut over matured/large diameter okra.
4	S4	34	176, 6.05	Unwilling to operate, hand pains at thumb and center.	314, 10.6	Some time problem in holding the cutter, no scratches.
5	S5	40	158, 5.20	Scratches, hard to cut hard okra, pains on palm.	302, 10.2	Simple to operate, no scratches.

the hand. Tool was found handy and easy to operate by the workers.

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Effect of Citrashine Coating on Post Harvest Quality of Grapefruit Cv. Star Ruby under Ambient Conditions

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to observe the effect of citrashine coating on post harvest quality of grapefruit cv. Star Ruby under ambient conditions. For this, fully mature, uniform, healthy and disease free fruits of grapefruit cv Star Ruby were individually waxed with citrashine wax and kept at ambient temperature (20-25°C) in well ventilated room. The fruits were analyzed for physiological loss in weight, organoleptic rating, spoilage, TSS and total acids after 7, 14 and 21 d of storage. Fruits coated with citrashine wax retained their general appearance and taste after storage. The physiological loss in weight (2.58%) and spoilage (0.0%) were minimum in citrashine treated fruits after 14 d of storage as compared to uncoated fruits where physiological loss in weight was recorded as 7.01 per cent and spoilage was 4.9 per cent. The wax treated fruits showed higher organoleptic rating up to 14 d of storage. Total soluble solids increased up to 14 d of storage interval. However, acidity decreased non-significantly with the increase in storage interval in both the treatments.

Keywords: Citrashine wax, Organoleptic rating, Shelf life, Star Ruby, Weight loss.

INTRODUCTION

Grapefruit is an important citrus fruit which has high medicinal value. It is an excellent source of vitamin C, potassium and dietary fibre. The Star Ruby grapefruit is the benchmark standard of grapefruits regarding colour, flavour and fragrance. The extent of postharvest losses in this crop is comparatively very high. Hence, in order to reduce the postharvest losses, there is need to enhance shelf life of fruits under ordinary marketing conditions. Coating of fruits with shellac wax increase shelf life, besides, improving appearance of the fruits. Application of a physical barrier, such as a wax coating, slows down the permeability of water vapour and other gases (Mahajan *et al*, 2002), retards ripening and also checks the microbial infection. According to Bajwa and Anjum (2007), wax coating reduced the chilling injury, rind staining and physiological loss in weight in mandarins, which limit post harvest shelf life and reduce quality of mandarins. However, very limited information is available with respect to effect of surface coatings on shelf life of grapefruit cv. Star

Ruby. Keeping in view the medicinal importance and increasing market value of this fruit there is an utmost need to evaluate the citrashine wax to enhance shelf life of the fruits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study for the evaluation of wax on the shelf life of grapefruit cv Star Ruby under ambient conditions was conducted in the Department of Fruit Science, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana in 2013, 2014 and 2015. The healthy fruits were harvested in last week of November. The freshly harvested fruits of grapefruit cv Star Ruby were washed in clean water with wet foam, followed by dip in chlorinated water (0.01%) for one minute. These fruits were partially dried under shade and coated with Citrashine wax with the help of foam pad. The waxed fruits were again dried in shade. The treated fruits were stored under ambient conditions (Temp. 20-25 °C) for 7, 14 and 21 d in Corrugated Fiber Board boxes of standard size i.e. 45 x 23 x 18 cm. The physiological loss in weight

(PLW) was determined by subtracting final weight from initial weight of fruits. Spoilage percentage was calculated by counting the fruits that had rotten during the studies. The total soluble solids (TSS) were recorded with hand refractometer and temperature correction applied. The acidity was determined by titrating one ml of juice against 0.1 N sodium hydroxide using *Phenolphthalein* as an indicator. The results were expressed as percentage of anhydrous citric acid. The fruits were rated organoleptically by a panel of 5 judges on 0-10 scale. The statistical analysis was done by using t-test of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physiological loss in weight

The physiological loss in weight (PLW) was recorded to be significantly less in Citrashine coated fruits at all the storage intervals as compared to uncoated fruits (Table 1). On the other hand, the highest mean PLW (12.25%) was observed in control fruits up to 21 d of ambient storage. The

fruits coated with wax retained their weight up to 14 d of ambient storage, but uncoated fruits were highly shriveled after 21 d of storage. After twenty one days of storage, uncoated fruits became unmarketable (PLW > 10%) as physiological loss in weight is directly linked to the shelf-life of any produce. These results were in confirmation with the findings of Jhalegar *et al* (2015) who also reported that the surface coated Kinnow fruits showed lesser loss in weight in comparison to untreated fruits, which indicates that surface coated fruits, can be stored for a longer time than untreated fruits. The wax coatings on fruit surface acted as barrier and prevented water loss and desiccation by affecting the opening of stomata and lenticels, also delayed aging of the rind tissue and reduced rate of respiration (Hagenmaier and Baker, 1993). Manhein and Soffer (1996) and Pal *et al* (1997) made similar observations on the effect of wax emulsions on weight loss in Marsh grapefruit and Kinnow mandarin, respectively.

Table 1. Effect of Citrashine wax on shelf life and quality of Grapefruit cv Star Ruby (pooled mean of three years).

Parameters	Storage days	Treatments		Test of sig. (5%)
		Citrashine wax	Control (Without wax)	
PLW (%)	7	0.95	3.95	S
	14	2.58	7.01	S
	21	5.65	12.25	S
Organoleptic rating (1-9 Hedonic scale)	7	8.0	7.1	S
	14	7.7	6.5	S
	21	6.4	6.1	S
Total soluble solids (0 Brix)	7	9.7	9.2	NS
	14	9.9	8.9	S
	21	10.0	8.5	S
Acidity (%)	7	1.25	1.23	NS
	14	1.21	1.18	NS
	21	1.15	1.13	NS
Spoilage (%)	7	0	0	NS
	14	0	4.9	S
	21	5.04	10.2	S

Effect of Citrashine Coating on Quality of Grapefruit

Spoilage

Both, the fruits coated with citrashine wax and uncoated fruits did not show any spoilage for 7 d of ambient storage but after 14 and 21 d of storage, the mean spoilage (Table 1) in uncoated fruits was 4.9 and 10.2 per cent, respectively, which was significantly higher than citrashine wax coated fruits. Wax coating of fruits prevent fresh inoculation during storage periods and contaminations from the rotting fruits, thus total spoilage was reduced.

Organoleptic rating

The organoleptic rating (Table 1) of wax coated fruits was recorded to be significantly higher than control fruits at all the storage intervals. Considerable reduction in organoleptic rating was observed in uncoated fruits after 14 d of storage as compared to wax coated fruits. After 21 d of storage, mean organoleptic rating of Citrashine wax treated fruits was significantly higher (6.4) than uncoated fruits (Table 1). The observed superior organoleptic rating may be due to the better retention of quality parameters. These results were in confirmation with the findings of Mahajan and Singh, (2014). Uncoated fruits were severely shriveled, showed unacceptable appearance and fruits lose their taste after 7 d of storage.

Total Soluble Sugars

The TSS of wax coated and uncoated fruits did not differ significantly upto 7 d of storage (Table 1). However, after 14 and 21 d of storage, significant difference in TSS was recorded in citrashine treated fruits and uncoated fruits. TSS was recorded to be significantly higher in citrashine treated fruits than uncoated fruits after 14 and 21 d of storage. Mandal (2015) also reported a sharp decline in TSS of uncoated kinnow fruits after 7 d of storage under ambient conditions due to rapid metabolic breakdown in these fruits.

Acidity

The acid content of the wax coated fruits showed non-significant difference with control (Table 1). The acid content was observed to be decreased with the

increase in storage interval from 7 to 21 d. The decrease in titratable acids during storage may be attributed to utilization of organic acid in pyruvate decarboxylation reaction occurring during the ripening process of fruits. When the fruits were coated, the lowering of acidity was delayed, which might be due to the effect of coatings in delaying the respiratory and ripening process (Mahajan and Singh, 2014)

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded that the grapefruit cv Star Ruby fruits treated with citrashine wax prior to storage under ambient conditions can retain their post-harvest quality for about two weeks which may help in extending the marketing period for better economic returns.

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Effect of Different Agricultural Substrates on Yield of *Pleurotus sajor caju*

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ABSTRACT

Oyster (*Pleurotus sajor-caju*) was cultivated on different agricultural viz. wheat straw (*Triticum aestivum*), black gram straw (*Vigna mungo*), sesame straw (*Sesamum indicum*), sarson (*Brassica juncea* (L.) and soybean straw (*Glycine max* (L.) to determine the effect of these agro-waste on spawn running, fruit bodies formation and pinhead formation, yield and biological efficiency. Wheat straw showed significantly highest yield (8.6 % B.E.) and lesser time for spawn run (16.66 d) and pin head appearance (24.33 d). Sarson straw required more time for spawn run (23.66 d) and pin head appearance (30.66 d) and resulted less yield (2.40kg/5.0 kg substrate) with 48.0 per cent biological efficiency. The study revealed that lesser time taken to colonize the substrates is consistent with better yield and highest biological efficiency.

Key Words: Agricultural wastes, Biological efficiency, Cultivation, *Pleurotus sajor-caju*, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

Pleurotus spp. are the most talented group among the cultivated mushrooms, which have ability to degrade many lignocellulosic substrates and are capable to colonize successfully on these substrates (Patrabansh and Madan, 1997). *P. sajor-caju* is one of the most successfully cultivated species of these mushrooms and it is considered to be delicious (Zhang *et al*, 2002). *Pleurotus* species contain high potassium to sodium ratio, which makes mushrooms an ideal food for patients suffering from hypertension and heart diseases. They are also rich source of proteins, minerals and vitamins (Caglarirmak, 2007). The carbohydrate content of mushrooms represents the bulk of fruiting bodies accounting for 50 to 65 per cent on dry weight basis. On a dry weight basis, mushrooms normally contain 19 to 35 per cent proteins where as fat content is very low as compared to carbohydrates and proteins (Wani *et al*, 2010).

Mushroom production gives additional or alternative income to farmers looking for a value-added product and a way to supplement farm income while making use of byproducts or co-

products from other crops. However, development of cost-efficient and alternate substrate to cultivate oyster mushroom without sacrificing mushroom quality is a major focus of many researchers and growers. Therefore, cultivation of *P. sajor-caju* on various agricultural residues offers high value products with nutritional and medicinal properties. Hence, the study was undertaken during March-May, 2016 at Krishi Vigyan Kendra under one of the training programme in Attaining and Attracting Youth in Agriculture (ARYA) project.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The substrates used for cultivation of Oyster mushroom were wheat straw (*Triticum aestivum*), black gram straw (*Vigna mungo*), sesame straw (*Sesamum indicum*), sarson (*Brassica juncea* L.) and soybean straw (*Glycine max* L.). All the substrates were dried and cut into 3-4cm long pieces. The substrates were soaked in water for 8-10 hours in cemented pond to obtained 70-75 per cent moisture level. All the substrates were sterilized by boiling method where the substrates were boiled for one hour at 70-75°C. Then they were stalked on the steep cemented floor so as to

remove the excessive moisture from the substrates to get 65-75 per cent moisture level. The substrates were cooled up to room temperature (25°C). A local method was developed for determination of moisture. In this method moisture was determined by pressing a handful mixture. If there was no water runoff and the material stayed in form indicates that the moisture content was around 65 per cent.

Five kilogram of each substrate was filled in transparent polythene bag (30x45cm and seeded with 150g of *P. sajor-caju*. The pinholes at 10-12cm distance were also done in the bags with help of led pencil after sterilization in 2 per cent formaldehyde solution. The bags were incubated in dark cropping room where ambient temperature ranged between 22-28+10C. The humidity 80 – 90 per cent of the room was maintained by spraying of water twice a day on the floor covered with jute bags. After complete colonization of substrate polythene was removed and bags were put on the bamboo made structure for fruiting. The humidity of the bags was accomplished by spraying of water on them twice a day. The experiment was laid out in complete randomized design (CRD) with three replications and five treatments. Time was recorded in days for the completion of growth of mycelium on substrates, appearance of pinheads and maturity of fruit bodies in different treatments. The data on average values of observations were also recorded

for the yield, number of fruit bodies. Biological efficiency of mushroom on fresh weight basis was calculated by using formula given by Chang and Miles (1989).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spawn running

All the substrates were spawned at the same day. It was evident from the Table 1 that spawn running took 2-3 wk after spawning.

Pinhead formation

The pinhead formation is the second stage of mycelia during cultivation of mushroom. Small pinhead like structures were observed, these pinhead were formed 4-5 days after spawn running (Table1). Our results were corroborated with Ahmed (1986) who stated that *Pleurotus ostreatus* completed spawn running in 17-20 d on different substrates and the time for pinhead formation was noted as 23-27 d.

Fruit bodies formation

This is the third and final stage during the cultivation of mushroom. The fruit bodies appeared 4-5 wk after pinhead formation and took 25-34 d later after inoculation of spawn (Table1). Sharma and Jandaik (1981) reported that *P. sajor-caju* cultivation on wheat straw took 32 d for the first harvest.

Yield of fruiting body (g)

$$\text{Biological efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Yield of fruiting body (g)}}{\text{Total weight of substrate used (g)}} \times 100$$

Total weight of substrate used (g)

Table.1. Days for completion of spawn running, fruiting body formation and pinhead formation on different substrates.

Substrate	Days for completion of spawn running	Days for pinhead formation	Days of fruiting bodies formation	Average number of fruiting bodies
Black gram straw	17.67	26.66	28.33	27.66
Soybean straw	16.67	24.66	26.65	30.55
Sesame straw	20.33	28.33	31.69	22.22
Wheat straw	16.66	24.33	25.66	31.11
Sarson straw (Check)	23.66	30.66	34.33	17.33
CD (P<0.05%)	2.06	2.09	3.12	3.01

Effect of Different Substrates on Yield of *Pleurotus sajor caju*

Number of fruit bodies

The caps of mushroom was also counted in three flushes, average 17.33-31.11 were formed in three flushes (Table1). Highest number of fruiting body (31.11) were produced by wheat straw followed by soybean straw (30.55), black gram straw (27.66) and sesame straw (22.22) whereas least number of fruit bodies (17.33) were harvested from sarson straw. Asraf *et al* (2013) reported that cotton waste took maximum number of fruit bodies 4.33 ± 0.42 followed by wheat straw and rice straw with the number of fruit bodies 3.80 ± 0.30 and 3.53 ± 0.24 , respectively.

Yield of Oyster mushroom

The crop was harvested in three flushes where maximum yield was obtained in first flush than the second and third flush. The results (Table2) showed that out of five substrates evaluated for their potential to produce sporophores of *P. sajor-caju*, wheat straw supported 4.88 per cent higher yield as compared to soybean straw. Other substrates have also proved to be the promising substrates for the cultivation of oyster. Mane *et al* (2007) grew *P. sajor caju* in several agro-industrial residues viz., cotton processing residue, wheat straw, soy straw, pea stalk and peanut stalk. Tupatkar and Jadhao (2006) conducted the similar studies on different substrates including wheat straw, paddy straw, soybean stalks and reported that paddy straw (613 g/kg of dry straw) followed by soybean straw (557 g/kg of dry straw) and combination of soybean straw plus wheat straw 1:1 w/w (508 g/kg of straw) gave optimum yield. The lower performance and yield

of different agricultural wastes might be due to low lignolytic and cellulolytic activity. However, high and significant performance of other substrates ensures the possibilities of utilizing the locally available substrates for *Pleurotus sajor-caju* cultivation.

Biological Efficiency

Considerable variation was found in yield of Oyster Mushroom using different substrates. The biological efficiency was calculated on the dry weight basis of the substrate. It was evident (Table2) that as a substrate wheat straw showed best biological efficiency 86.0 per cent followed by soybean straw 82.0 per cent, black gram straw 78.0 per cent, sesame straw 65.0 per cent and sarson straw 48.0 per cent. Dehariya and Vyas (2013) reported that the soybean straw showed significantly highest yield (with 93.3% B.E.) followed by wheat and paddy straw. *Pleurotus sajor-caju* was found to utilize all the agricultural wastes and were observed suitable for spawn run, yield and biological efficiency (Das et al, 2000).

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that wheat straw showed significantly highest yield (8.6 % B.E.) and lesser time for spawn run (16.66 d) and pin head appearance (24.33 d). Sarson straw required more time for spawn run (23.66 d) and pin head appearance (30.66 d) and resulted less yield (2.40kg/5.0 kg substrate) with 48.0 per cent biological efficiency. The study revealed that lesser time taken to colonize the substrates is consistent with better yield and highest biological efficiency.

Table.2. Effect of different substrates on average yield and biological efficiency of *P. sajor-caju*.

Substrate	Average yield of three flushes (kg)	Biological Efficiency (%)
Black gram straw	3.90	78.0
Soybean straw	4.10	82.0
Sesame straw	3.25	65.0
Wheat straw	4.30	86.0
Sarson straw (Check)	2.40	48.0
CD (p<0.05)	4.83	6.82

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Effect of GA₃ and NAA on Yield and Quality of Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L)

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted at Horticulture Instructional Farm, Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University, Sardarkrushinagar during the *kharif* season 2012 to study the effect of GA₃ and NAA on yield and quality of Okra. Yield parameters like number of fingers harvested per plant, average weight of finger, yield per plant, yield per plot and yield per hectare and quality parameters like total number of pickings, thickness of finger and length of finger were analyzed. The experiment consisted of 16 treatments combination involving two growth regulators with four levels each (0, 25, 50 and 75 ppm). GA₃ and NAA (75 ppm) was found to be the most effective in increasing more number of fingers harvested per plant (15.10), total number of pickings (9.33) and thickness of finger (1.54 cm). Treatment combinations of (GA₃ 75 and NAA 50 ppm) increased average weight of finger (16.28 g) and yield per plant (0.232 g). Maximum length of finger (15.82 cm) was found treatment combinations of (GA₃ and NAA 50 ppm each).

Key Words- GA₃, NAA, Okra, Quality, Yield

INTRODUCTION

Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L) is an annual vegetable crop belongs to family Malvaceae and is grown throughout the year for its tender green fruits. Being a vegetable, it also has medicinal and industrial important. Role of plant growth regulators in crop production is well known phenomenon. Its use promotes growth along the longitudinal area, increase number of branches, early flower initiation; fruit set and subsequently contributes towards higher production when applied at various concentrations. Due to this it is possible to achieve the desirable standards and norms in term of quality for exportable production. Therefore, present investigation was carried out to find out suitable plant growth regulator and its effect on growth and flowering parameters of okra.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An experiment was carried out during the year 2012 at the Horticulture Instructional Farm, Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural

University, Sardarkrushinagar. The design followed was Factorial Randomized Block Design with three replications. The treatments consisted of different concentration of plant growth regulators viz. GA₃ (0 ppm – g₀, 25 ppm – g₁, 50 ppm – g₂, and 75 ppm – g₃) and NAA (0 ppm – n₀, 25 ppm – n₁, 50 ppm – n₂, and 75 ppm – n₃) were applied as foliar spray at 25 days after sowing. Distilled water was sprayed as control.

The recommended dose of fertilizers @ 50:50:50 kg NPK/ha were applied at the time of sowing and remaining half dose of N (50 kg) was applied in the form of urea (top dressing) one month after sowing and other standard cultural practices recommended for okra were uniformly followed for all the treatments. The seeds were dibbled at the spacing of 45 x 30 cm. The observations regarding growth viz. plant height, stem thickness, average length of interned, number of nodes per plant and leaf area per plant and flowering viz. days taken for initiation of first flower, days taken for flower initiation to edible maturity, days taken for sowing

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to first picking and days taken for sowing to last picking of okra were taken and the data subjected to statistical analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data revealed that interaction effect of GA₃ and NAA significantly influenced the yield and quality of okra. Application of GA₃ and NAA 75 ppm were recorded significantly maximum number of fingers harvested per plant (15.10), total number of pickings (9.33) and thickness of finger (1.54 cm) (Table 1). Whereas, minimum fingers harvested per plant (12.50), total number of pickings (7.00) and thickness of finger (1.42 cm) were found control and G₃N₁ treatments. Plant growth regulators were found to have non-significant effect on yield per plot and yield per hectare.

Combined application of GA₃ and NAA also significantly influenced the yield and quality of okra. Maximum average weight of finger (16.28

g) and yield per plant (0.232 g) was recorded with treatment GA₃ 75 ppm + NAA 50 ppm. Whereas, minimum average weight of finger (12.27 g) and yield per plant (0.159 g) was recorded with g₀n₁ and control treatment. The significantly maximum length of finger (15.82 cm) was observed with treatment GA₃ 50 ppm + NAA 50 ppm and it was statistically at par with treatment combination of g₃n₃. While, minimum length of finger (12.78 cm) was recorded with control treatment.

The improvement in growth as a result of GA₃ and NAA might be attributed to their function in stimulation of metabolic activities and hormonal regulation. GA₃ and NAA stimulate the growth of plant tissues there by enhancement in cell multiplication and cell elongation resulting increased growth and flowering of plant. Present results are in close agreement with those of Tyagi *et al* (2008), Patil and Patel (2010), Dhage *et al* (2011) and Jaymala *et al* (2012).

Table 1. Effect of GA₃ and NAA on yield and quality of okra cv. Gujarat Okra-2.

Treatment	No. of fingers harvested per plant	Average weight of finger (g)	Yield per plant (g)	Yield per plot (kg)	Yield per hectare (q)	Total number of pickings	Thickness of finger (cm)	Length of finger (cm)	
T1	g0n0	12.50	12.76	0.159	2.581	119.51	7.00	1.44	12.78
T2	g0n1	13.88	12.49	0.173	2.807	129.97	7.67	1.50	14.18
T3	g0n2	14.74	12.27	0.176	2.897	134.12	8.13	1.48	13.00
T4	g0n3	13.75	13.25	0.179	2.989	138.35	9.08	1.52	13.17
T5	g1n0	14.21	13.06	0.182	3.092	143.16	7.83	1.48	14.00
T6	g1n1	13.71	13.41	0.181	3.226	149.36	8.83	1.49	14.54
T7	g1n2	14.46	14.54	0.199	3.436	159.09	8.29	1.51	13.67
T8	g1n3	14.28	15.83	0.226	3.698	171.23	8.04	1.45	13.28
T9	g2n0	12.59	15.22	0.187	3.086	142.88	7.01	1.50	12.54
T10	g2n1	14.42	14.61	0.201	3.405	157.65	8.33	1.50	14.16
T11	g2n2	14.38	15.24	0.219	3.717	172.10	9.17	1.49	15.82
T12	g2n3	15.00	14.80	0.205	3.762	174.15	8.92	1.52	14.20
T13	g3n0	14.88	12.43	0.183	3.174	146.95	8.92	1.47	14.21
T14	g3n1	14.92	14.88	0.221	3.578	165.67	8.71	1.42	14.26
T15	g3n2	14.22	16.28	0.232	3.723	172.36	8.58	1.48	13.69
T16	g3n3	15.10	14.79	0.223	3.774	174.70	9.33	1.54	14.97
S.Em±		0.38	0.65	0.007	0.139	6.41	0.37	0.02	0.38
C.D.@ 5%		1.08	1.86	0.021	NS	NS	1.06	0.05	1.11

Effect of GA₃ and NAA on Yield and Quality of Okra

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that combined application of GA₃ and NAA significantly influenced the yield and quality of okra. The improvement in growth as a result of GA₃ and NAA might be attributed to their function in stimulation of metabolic activities and hormonal regulation.

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Effect of Integrated Pest Management Practices in Brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L)

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ABSTRACT

For the management of insect pests and diseases of brinjal, farmers are using conventional as well as novel pesticides including carbendazim, cypermethrin 25 EC, spinosad 2.5 percent SC and indoxacarb 15.8 SC. The large scale use of pesticides has caused many environmental problems like pesticide poisoning, insecticide resistance, resurgence of insect pests, effect of non-target organisms and pesticide residue which led to the scientist on alternative methods of pest control in brinjal. The objectives of the study were to minimize the use of chemical pesticides and establish the use of eco-friendly management practices. For this front line demonstrations were organized during 2011-12 and 2012-13 to evaluate the feasibility and economic viability of recommended practices for the management of pests (insects and diseases) of brinjal under real farm condition. On the basis of result obtained from assessment of recommended technology, frontline demonstrations were organized to disseminate the recommended practices. Components of IPM technology used were Seedling root treatment for 3 hour with imidacloprid (1ml/litre) + Soil application of Trichoderma + installation of pheromone traps @ 35/ha + Mechanical removal of infected shoots and fruits + Spraying of NSKE 4 per cent. The recommended technology was found to offer an alternative to pesticides and was feasible, economically viable, environmentally safe and effective for pest management in brinjal.

Key words: Assessment, Impact, Brinjal, Management practices, shoot & fruit borer.

INTRODUCTION

Brinjal or egg plant (*Solanum melongena* L.) is one of the most commonly grown vegetable crop of the country. India produces about 7.8 M mt of brinjal from an area of 0.47 M ha. with an average productivity of 16.3 mt/ha. Brinjal has ayurvedic medicinal properties and white brinjal is good for diabetic patients. It is also a source of vitamins A, C and minerals. Brinjal is commonly suffered by more than a dozen insect-pest species out of which brinjal shoot and fruit borer (*Leucinodes orbonalis* Guenee, Pyralidae: Lepidoptera) is most serious (Sardana *et al*, 2004). In the earlier stages it attacks the terminal shoots and bores inside. Later, it also bores into the young fruits as soon as fruits start setting. *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp.

melongenae, a soil inhabiting fungus responsible for Fusarium wilt of egg plant is very common in the egg plant growing areas and can cause severe yield loss. Egg plant is susceptible to several other diseases particularly Verticillium wilt and Bacterial wilt (Sihachakr *et al*, 1994; Chakraborty, 2005). To manage this, generally farmers use huge amount of pesticides indiscriminately without any proper diagnosis which results into development of resistance and resurgence of the pests as well as environmental pollution.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Assessment and impact of Integrated Pest Management practices in brinjal (Kashi Sandesh) were carried out through on farm trials and

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Table1. Assessment of management practices in brinjal pest (2011-12).

Treatment	Yield q/ha	% yield increase over FP	Shoot Infestation %	Fruit Infestation %	% wilt affected plant	Cost of cultivation Rs./ha	Gross Return Rs./ha	Net Return Rs/ha	B:C Ratio
Recommended Practice	208	51.8	4.3	8.2	3.7	70132	312000	241868	4.5
Farmers Practices Regular spray of carbendazim, cypermethrin 25 EC, spinosad 2.5 percent SC and indoxacarb 15.8 SC.	137	---	18.1	29.5	36.3	73954	178100	104146	2.4

frontline demonstration at village Majhauri of Jaunpur district during 2011-12 and 2012-2013 by Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Jaunpur. For conducting the on farm trials, five innovative and receptive farmers were selected and area under each trial was 0.15ha. The applicable management practices were Seedling root treatment for 3 hr with imidacloprid (1ml/litre) + Soil application of *Trichoderma* @ 1.25 kg/ha + installation of pheromone traps @ 35/ha. starting from 20-25 d of transplanting till final harvest and changing the lures at monthly intervals + Mechanical removal of infected shoots and fruits + Spraying of neem seed kernel extract (NSKE) 4 per cent at 15 d interval after 30 d of transplanting. The existing farmer practices include regular spray of carbendazim, cypermethrin 25 EC, spinosad 2.5 SC and indoxacarb 15.8 SC. Similarly, 6 farmers of the same village were selected for frontline demonstrations (each on 0.25ha land) during 2012-2013. A training to the farmers was imparted with respect to envisaged technological intervention.

Plot-wise data was recorded from recommended practice and farmer's plots. The percentage of infected shoot and fruit was calculated on the basis of total number of healthy shoots and fruits and infested ones. Percentage of disease incidence was also calculated on the same basis. Information of yield and cost of cultivation was also recorded for economic evaluation in terms of net profit earned and the benefit cost ratio.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Average yield performance and economics of five 'on farm trials' of recommended technology and farmers' practice were assessed (Table1). The recommended practice i.e. Seedling root treatment for 3 hr with imidacloprid (1ml/litre) + Soil application of *Trichoderma* + Installation of pheromone traps + Mechanical removal of infected shoots and fruits + Spraying of NSKE 4% was evaluated and assessed over farmers' practice (regular spray of chemical insecticides

Table 2. Impact of frontline demonstration on yield and economics of brinjal (2012-13).

Treatment	Yield q/ha	% yield increase over FP	Shoot Infestation (%)	Fruit Infestation (%)	% wilt affected plant	Cost of cultivation Rs./ha	Gross Return Rs./ha	Net Return Rs/ha	B:C Ratio
Recommended Practice	203	50.4	4.1	7.6	3.5	68986	304500	235514	4.4
Farmer's Practices	135	----	17.7	29.1	37.1	70530	175500	104970	2.5

Integrated Pest Management Practices in Brinjal

i.e Cypermethrin 25 EC, spinosad 2.5 percent SC and indoxacarb 15.8 SC). The yield performance of recommended practice was 208 q/ha which was 51.8 per cent higher to farmer's practice (137 q/ha). The per cent infestation of shoot and fruit by *L. orbonalis* and wilt disease was found 4.3, 8.2 and 3.7 in case of recommended practice while it was 18.1, 29.5 and 36.3 in farmers' practice.

Evaluation of economics clearly revealed that the net returns from the recommended practice were substantially higher than farmers practice. Net returns from recommended practice were observed to be Rs 2,41,868/-ha in comparison to farmers' practice (Rs 1,04,146/-ha), hence an increase in income of Rs 1,37,722/-ha was obtained. These benefits can be attributed to the technological intervention provided in on farm trials. The cost benefit ratio of recommended practice was also higher (4.5) than farmers practice (2.4). Thus, favorable cost-benefit ratio and higher net returns proved the economic viability of the assessed technology and convinced the farmers on the utility of technology provided at real farming situation. Similar findings were reported by Mishra *et al* (2007 and 2012) in onion and cauliflower. Outcome of the 'on farm trials' organized clearly brings out that the dissemination of assessed technology is feasible, economically viable and environmentally safe for containing shoot & fruit borer in brinjal. The assessment could convince on account of its obvious advantages and effective management of shoot & fruit borer in brinjal. These innovative practices showed solving the farmers' problem, decision-making and ability to modify their farming practices. On the basis of out come from OFT, assessment of management practices, 6 Front Line Demonstrations (FLD) were organized and their yield performance and economics of recommended technology and farmers practice were analyzed and presented in Table 2. The yield performance of recommended practice was 203 q/ha which is 50.4 per cent higher to farmer practice (135 q/ha). The percent infestation of shoot & fruit by *L. orbonalis*

and wilt disease was found 4.1 & 7.6 and 3.5 in case of recommended practice while it was 17.7 & 29.1 and 37.1 in farmers' practice. Evaluation of economics clearly revealed that the net returns from the recommended practice were substantially higher than farmers practice. Net returns from recommended practice were observed to be Rs 2,35,514/-ha in comparison to farmers practice (Rs 1,04,970/-ha), hence an increase in income of Rs 1,30,544/-ha was obtained. These benefits can be attributed to the technological intervention provided in front line demonstrations. The cost benefit ratio of recommended practice was also higher (4.4) than farmers practice (2.5). Thus, favorable cost benefit ratio and higher net returns proved the economic viability of the recommended technology and convinced the farmers on the utility of technology provided at real farming situation.

CONCLUSION

The IPM based practices were found effective in comparison to conventional methods, so, the above said management practices must be followed by the brinjal growers.

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Effect of Pre-Harvest Sprays of Ascorbic Acid, Calcium Chloride and Ethephon on Fruit Quality of Grapes (*Vitis vinifera* L.)

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation was conducted to evaluate the effect of pre-harvest sprays of ascorbic acid, calcium chloride and ethephon on hastening maturity and fruit quality of Flame Seedless grapes. The pre-harvest sprays of ascorbic acid (750, 1000 and 1250 ppm) and calcium chloride (0.25, 0.50 and 1.0 %) were given at fruit-set and veraison stage. Ethephon @ 400ppm was sprayed at veraison stage on vines with 75 per cent crop load. The treatment combination of flower bud thinning + gibberellic acid (GA3) 40 ppm was also included for comparison along with water sprays as control. Each treatment was replicated thrice, in which one vine served as a unit treatment. The time of ripening was advanced by 5 d in the treatment 75 per cent crop load + ethephon 400ppm as compared to control, while in the treatment flower bud thinning + GA3 ripening was advance by 3 d. The same treatment i.e. flower bud thinning + GA3 resulted in significantly higher yield (33.54 kg/vine), maximum bunch weight, bunch length and bunch breadth. However, the fruit quality with respect to higher total soluble solids (TSS), lower acidity, higher sugars and anthocyanin content was better in 75 per cent crop load + Ethephon 400 ppm. Also the yield in treatment was at par with flower bud thinning + GA3. Thus, considering yield as well as quality parameters, the treatment 75 per cent crop load+ 400ppm Ethephon was found to be the best.

Key words: Ascorbic acid, Calcium chloride, Ethephon, Flame Seedless, Gibberellic acid.

INTRODUCTION

Although, the grapes are commercially grown in the tropical regions of India, but an early ripening variety can be successfully grown in the regions of northern India too. The grapes grown in this region have higher productivity than grown in commercial region of India. However, very short period (April–June) is available for the ripening of berries in this region which limits the choice of varieties and only early maturing varieties can be grown successfully. Perlette is a leading cultivar of this region which occupies 90 per cent of total area under grapes. To restrict the monoculture of this cultivar recently, coloured Flame Seedless grapes, has been recommended in northern India for commercial cultivation for table purpose (Anonymous, 2009). Flame Seedless is a complex hybrid, whose parents include Sultanina, Cardinal, Malaga and Muscat d' Alexandric, and was developed in early 1960s by

John Weinberger in California (Vander Merwe *et al*, 1991). Uneven colour and small berry size are the primary quality problems in this variety. Previously, various attempts have been made to improve fruit quality of Flame Seedless grapes with use of pre-harvest sprays of chemicals like GA3, ethephon and calcium chloride (Ramteke *et al*, 2002, Fatma and Aisha 2005). Therefore, the present study was conducted to ascertain the effect of ascorbic acid, calcium chloride and ethephon applied as foliar sprays on maturity and fruit quality of Flame Seedless grapes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental details

The present investigation was conducted on 12 yr old vines of Flame Seedless in Fruit Research Farm of Department of Fruit Science at Punjab

Agricultural University, Ludhiana. The different treatments used were ascorbic acid @750ppm (T1), 1000ppm (T2), 1250ppm (T3); calcium chloride @ 0.25% (T4), 0.5% (T5), 1.0% (T6), flower bud thinning + GA3 40 ppm (T7), 75 % crop load + ethephon 400 ppm (T8) and control, water spray (T9).

Each treatment was replicated thrice, in which one vine served as a unit treatment. Thus, Twenty seven uniform vines distributed in the vineyard were selected for this investigation. Application of chemicals was done twice; at fruit-set (pea size) and veraison stage (colour break stage). In treatment T7 which comprised of flower bud thinning + GA3 dips, flower bud thinning is done one week before flowering thereby leaving 100–120 flower buds per panicle followed by GA3 dips when fruit was pea size. For treatment T8 (of 75% crop load), 90-98 bunches were retained on the vines while rest were removed immediately after bunch emergence.

The harvesting was done manually in first fortnight of June. After harvesting, fruits were brought to laboratory at Department of Fruit Science, P.A.U Ludhiana for analysis of various physico-chemical properties.

Evaluation of maturity, yield and physical properties

Date of ripening was recorded as and when vines reached commercial maturity i.e. the checked berries reached maturity stage (16-17 % TSS). Number of bunches were counted at the time of harvest. The bunch weight, length and breadth were measured from 10 randomly selected bunches from each vine and means were worked out. Mean bunch weight was multiplied with counted bunches to record yield. Fifty berries were randomly sampled from ten bunches for the determination of physical and chemical properties. The weight (g) of 50 randomly selected berries was taken with weighing balance and average berry weight for each treatment was calculated. The berry size (cm) and berry pedicel diameter (mm) were taken with digital caliper and

averages for each treatment were calculated. Berry firmness was measured using a Texture Analyzer (TA+HDi ® Stable Micro Systems, UK) equipped with a HDP/90 platform and 5 kg load cell. The measurement was made on the equatorial position of the berry with 4 mm probe at a test speed of 1 mm/s to a constant compression distance of 1 mm. The readings were expressed as resistance force of the skin or flesh in grams (Rolle et al, 2011).

Evaluation of chemical properties

The soluble solids (TSS) content of the fruit was measured with hand refractometer and correction at 20o C was applied and the results were expressed in percent (AOAC, 2000). The acidity (%) of the fruit was estimated by titrating a known volume of juice against N/10 sodium hydroxide. TSS: acid ratio was calculated by dividing the values of TSS with the corresponding values of titratable acidity. Reducing and total sugars were determined as per AOAC (2005).

Total anthocyanin content of berries was determined as described by Ranganna (1986) with the extraction solvent ethanolic HCL and absorbance was noted at 535 nm wavelength by spectrophotometer. For anthocyanin estimation, 5g of sample was taken and macerated using mortar and pestle with small amount of ethanolic HCL (made by 85 parts 95 % ethanol and 15 parts of 1.5 N HCL) and final volume was made 100 ml with ethanolic HCL and kept overnight at 4oC. Following morning the mixture was filtered through Whatman's No.1 filter paper and residue on the filter paper was washed repeatedly with ethanolic HCL and volume was made up to 100 ml with the same solvent. It was again filtered through fine millipore and 10 ml of aliquot was taken and diluted up to 20 ml with ethanolic HCL. It was kept in dark for 2h after that absorbance was measured at 535 nm wavelength by spectrophotometer. The obtained data were statistically analyzed by Randomized Block Design (RBD) described by Singh et al (1998).

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Table 1. Effect of pre-harvest treatments on time of ripening, yield, bunch weight and bunch size of Flame Seedless grapes.

Treatments	Time of ripening	Yield (kg/vine)	Bunch weight (g)	Bunch length (cm)	Bunch breadth (cm)
T1-Ascorbic acid 750 ppm	5/6	29.74	248.62	22.08	11.95
T2 -Ascorbic acid 1000 ppm	7/6	28.56	235.64	21.41	11.89
T3- Ascorbic acid 1250 ppm	8/6	26.42	223.87	20.51	11.75
T4- Calcium chloride (0.25%)	3/6	28.68	263.16	22.37	12.97
T5- Calcium chloride (0.5%)	6/6	25.42	260.42	22.21	12.77
T6-Calcium chloride (1.0 %)	9/6	24.50	254.41	22.14	12.49
T7- Flower bud thinning + GA3 (40ppm)	4/6	33.54	345.57	23.42	14.52
T8 - 75 % crop load + Ethephon (400 ppm)	2/6	31.05	282.57	20.16	12.07
T9- control	7/6	28.29	220.52	19.62	10.98
CD (p=0.05)	--	2.66	2.10	1.95	1.72

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Maturity, yield and physical properties

It was observed that treatment T8 (75% crop load + ethephon 400 ppm) and treatment T7, (flower bud thinning + GA3 40ppm) hastened the harvest maturity in Flame Seedless as compared to control (Table 1). Data indicated that the time of ripening was advanced by 5d in T8 compared to control whereas, in treatment T7, it was advanced by 3d. The advancement of maturity was due to ethylene which accelerated berry ripening. Singla et al (1992) reported that ethephon 750 ppm advanced ripening by 7 d in Early Muscat and by 8 d in cv. Gold. Advancement in maturity in treatment T8 may be attributed to the reduced crop load per vine. Cheema et al (2003) found that cluster-thinning advanced maturity by nine days in Perlette.

The yield was the highest (33.54 kg/vine) in treatment T7 and at par with treatment T8 (Table 1). The results were in conformity with findings of Gowda *et al* (2006). The pre-harvest sprays of ascorbic acid (750 ppm) and calcium chloride (0.25%) increased the fruit yield as compared to control but the differences were non- significant.

All the treatments increased bunch weight compared to control (Table 1). Treatment T7 resulted in higher bunch weight (345.57g) followed

by T8 (282.57g) which was significantly higher than obtained with application of calcium chloride and ascorbic acid. The increase in bunch weight was probably attributed to the availability of more food materials due to decreased crop load and increased cell division with GA3 application. GA3 has been used for seedless grape production to increase berry and bunch weight, and cause thinning of clusters (Omran and Girgis, 2005). Abu-Zahira and Salameh (2012) also found that application of GA3 or GA3+ girdle resulted in heavier berries as well as increased in bunch weight.

The data regarding bunch size revealed that all the treatments reduced the bunch compactness as evident from increased bunch length and breadth over control (Table 1). The maximum bunch length (23.42 cm) was recorded in treatment T7 followed by T 4 (22.37 cm) and T5 (22.21 cm). The treatments in which ascorbic acid was sprayed, bunch length ranged between 20.51 to 22.0 cm and was minimum (19.62 cm) in control vines. Maximum bunch breadth (14.52 cm) was recorded in treatment T7. Similar results with pre-harvest application of gibberellic acid on increasing cluster size in Thompson and Belgrade Seedless grapes has been reported by Dimovaska et al (2011).

The data (Table 2) revealed that the berry weight was the maximum (2.72 g) in treatment T7

Table 2. Effect of pre-harvest treatments on berry weight, berry size and pedicel length of Flame Seedless grapes.

Treatments	Berry weight (g)	Berry length (cm)	Berry width (cm)	Berry pedicel diameter (mm)
T1- Ascorbic acid (750 ppm)	2.21	1.35	1.28	2.32
T2- Ascorbic acid (1000 ppm)	2.16	1.27	1.20	2.27
T3- Ascorbic acid (1250 ppm)	2.09	1.24	1.17	2.24
T4- Calcium chloride (0.25%)	2.34	1.42	1.34	2.59
T5- Calcium chloride (0.5%)	2.24	1.39	1.32	2.42
T6- Calcium chloride (1.0 %)	2.18	1.38	1.31	2.38
T7- Flower bud thinning + GA3 (40ppm)	2.72	1.75	1.67	3.18
T8- 75 % crop load + Ethephon (400 ppm)	2.58	1.44	1.36	2.35
T9- control	1.98	1.33	1.26	2.19
CD (5%)	0.32	0.25	0.20	0.66

followed by treatment T8 (2.58 g) and treatment T4 (2.34g) which was significantly higher than control. Results were in agreement with findings of Zabadal and Dittmer (2000) and Roberto (2002). The observed increase in berry weight with 75 per cent crop load + ethephon 400 ppm might be due to more availability of photosynthates to the left over bunches.

Grapes subjected to flower bud thinning + GA3 (40 ppm) produced larger berries (higher berry length and breadth compared to control). These results comply with those reported by Casanova *et al* (2009) and Kalpan (2011) in grapes. This effect takes place through larger berry growth rate, early uptake of glucose, sucrose and fructose and increased of absolute berry water content.

The perusal of data (Table 2) revealed that the berry pedicel diameter was recorded maximum (3.18 mm) with treatment T7 followed by T4 (2.59 mm) and T5. Casanova *et al* (2009) found that application of GA3 @160 mg/l increased berry peduncle length and berry pedicel diameter. The maximum fruit firmness (182.0 g force⁻¹) was recorded in T4 followed by treatment T5 which had the fruit firmness of 174.0 g force⁻¹. However, the treatment T8 resulted in lowest value of fruit firmness (142.0 gforce⁻¹) as compared to other treatments (Fig.1). The cation Ca²⁺ promotes

the stability of the cell wall by chelating the free carboxylic groups of galacturic units and cross linking the pectic polysaccharide chains forming a firmer tighter structure.

Fig.1 Effect of pre-harvest treatments on fruit firmness of Flame Seedless grapes.

the stability of the cell wall by chelating the free carboxylic groups of galacturic units and cross linking the pectic polysaccharide chains forming a firmer tighter structure.

Chemical Properties

Total Soluble Solids (TSS), Titratable Acidity (TA) and TSS/TA ratio were significantly affected by pre-harvest sprays of ascorbic acid, calcium chloride, gibberellic acid and ethephon (Table 3). The TSS were recorded maximum (19.46%) with treatment T8 followed by treatment T7 (18.98 %). Increase in TSS with ethephon application was in line with the findings of Sharma and Jindal (1983)

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Table 3. Effect of pre-harvest treatments on TSS, acidity and TSS.

Treatments	TSS (%)	Acidity (%)	TSS/acidity
T1- Ascorbic acid (750 ppm)	16.87	0.81	20.83
T2-Ascorbic acid (1000 ppm)	16.62	0.86	19.33
T3- Ascorbic acid (1250 ppm)	16.48	0.89	18.52
T4- Calcium chloride (0.25%)	17.96	0.70	25.66
T5- Calcium chloride (0.5%)	17.67	0.72	24.54
T6 -Calcium chloride (1.0%)	16.72	0.76	22.00
T7- Flower bud thinning + GA3 (40ppm)	18.98	0.71	26.73
T8-75 % crop load + Ethephon (400 ppm)	19.46	0.68	28.61
T9-control	16.32	0.92	17.74
CD (5%)	1.40	0.07	1.82

who reported an increase in TSS by ethrel application in Beauty Seedless grapes. The data (Table 3) revealed that all the treatments significantly reduced the acidity over the control. Minimum (0.68%) acidity was recorded with treatment T8, followed by treatment T7 which recorded 0.71 per cent value of acidity and the maximum acidity (0.92%) was recorded in control. Reduction in acidity as a result of Ethephon application could be due to effect of this chemical in increasing membrane permeability which permits acids, stored in cell vacuoles, to respire at a faster rate.

TSS/Acidity ratio is considered as a reliable maturity index for grapes and sharp increase in TSS/TA ratio indicates the onset of ripening. It was evident from the data given in Table 3 that all the pre-harvest treatments significantly influenced the TSS/acid ratio. Maximum TSS/ acid ratio (28.61) was recorded with treatment T8, followed by the treatment T7.

Anthocyanin content

The data presented in Fig. 2 indicated that all the pre-harvest treatments resulted in significant increase in anthocyanin content as compared to control. The treatment T8 recorded significantly higher (45.36 mg/100g) anthocyanin content followed by treatments T4 (38.54 mg/100g). The treatment in which ascorbic acid was sprayed recorded anthocyanin ranged between 31.47 to 35.72 mg/100g. The minimum anthocyanin content

(27.29 mg/100g) was recorded in treatment T7. Kitamura *et al* (2005) found that controlling crop load resulted in proper colouration of ‘Aki Queen’ fruits through the regulation of anthocyanin concentration in grapes.

Fig. 2: Effect of pre-harvest treatments on anthocyanin of Flame Seedless grapes.

Total and reducing sugars

Effect of pre-harvest treatments on reducing and total sugars are shown in Fig. 3A and 3B. Maximum (12.45 %) total sugar was recorded (Fig. 3A) with treatment T8, followed by treatment T7, (12.19 %). The treatment in which ascorbic acid and calcium chloride were sprayed, total sugar ranged between 11.25 to 12.14 per cent. The control registered lower total sugar (10.92%) as compared to other treatments. The Fig. 3B showed that the maximum (10.72) reducing sugar percentage was registered

Fig. 3A&3B. Effect of pre-harvest treatments on total and reducing sugar of Flame Seedless grapes.

with treatment T8. Gaser et al (1998) reported that ethrel (500 ppm) and hand thinning increased the TSS and sugar content. Ahmad and Zargar (2005) found that Ethephon treatment (500ppm) with or without girdling at veraison stage increased TSS and accumulation of sugars in cv. Perlette.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that retaining 75 per cent crop load + pre-harvest spray of ethephon @ 400 ppm at veraison stage could be an effective treatment for advancement of ripening along with improvement in fruit quality of Flame Seedless grapes.

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Effect of Row Spacing and Level of NPK on Growth and Yield of Fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*)

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted at the Horticulture Research Farm, College of Horticulture, Mandsaur during the rabi season of 2013-2014 to study the effect of row spacing and NPK levels on the growth and yield of fennel. The experiment consisted of 3 levels of row spacing (30 cm, 45 cm and 60 cm) and 4 levels of NPK (0+0+0, 30+20+20, 60+40+40 and 120+60+60 kg/ha) and were evaluated under split plot design with four replications. Among various levels of row spacing tried, 45 cm row spacing exhibited significant higher growth and yield attributes and recorded significant higher seed yield (11.06 q/ha) as compared to 30 cm row spacing. Among the various NPK levels tried, 60+40+40 kg ha⁻¹ exhibited significant maximum growth, yield attributes, yield and quality of fennel. Further treatment observed significant higher seed yield 12.29 q/ha with B: C ratio of 3.45 in comparison to lower NPK levels.

Key Words: Fennel, Growth, Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium, Spacing, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

Fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare* Mill.) is one of the important cash crops of family Apiaceae. The fennel seed is used in the food and flavour industry. The essential oils are used in condiments, soaps, creams perfumes and liquors. Fennel is cultivated in India about 100 thousand hectares area with the production of 143 thousand MT and productivity 1.4 MT/ha (NHB, 2013). Looking to the importance of the crop, its average productivity is less, so the efforts have made to enhance the productivity of the fennel by the management of cultural practices and fertilizer. Macro nutrients such as N, P and K are essential to all crops. Nitrogen is the element that most limits crop yields. Most of the N in plants is in organic form: nucleic acid, some vitamins, hormones, membrane component, coenzymes and pigment. P is an essential component of the energy transfer compounds (ATP and other nucleoproteins), the genetic information system, cell membranes and phospho-proteins. K is serving as an enzyme activator or cofactor for some enzymes.

It also aided in the maintenance of osmotic potential and water uptake. Plant spacing is an important factor in determining the micro environment in the fennel field. The optimization of this factor can lead to a higher yield in the crop by favourably affecting the absorption of nutrients and exposure of the plant to the light (Khorshidi *et al*, 2009). Keeping the above fact in view, the experiment was conducted for knowing the optimum row spacing with the N P K fertilization for achieving the higher growth and yield of fennel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at the Horticulture Research Farm, College of Horticulture, Mandsaur during the year 2013-2014. The soil of the experimental field was light black loamy in texture with low nitrogen (140.0 kg/ha), medium in phosphorus (21.0 kg/ha) and low in potassium (144.0 kg/ha) and alkaline in reaction (pH 7.1). The experiment consisted of 3 levels of row spacing 30 cm (S1), 45 cm (S2) and 60 cm (S3) and 4 levels

of NPK 0+0+0 kg/ha (F1), 30+20+20 kg/ha (F2), 60+40+40 kg/ha (F3), and 120+60+60 kg/ha (F4). These treatments were evaluated in split plot design with four replications. The sowing of crop was done on 10th November, 2013 and harvested on 29th April, 2014. The seeds were treated with carbendazim @ 3 g/kg seed and then sown at a depth of 5 cm in row spaced as per treatment and 30 cm plant to plant using cultivar NRCSS AF - 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of row spacing

It was observed that fennel crop under row spacing 45 cm attained significant higher plant height, number of primary, secondary and tertiary branches, fresh and dry weight of plant as compared to other row spacing. These significant variations may be attributed to vigorous vegetative growth, which resulted from favourable climatic conditions. Thus greater inputs under wider spacing (45cm and 60cm) resulted in profuse branching which in turn might have helped in larger canopy development and delayed plants to attain reproductive phase. Significant improvement in growth with increase in spacing was in close conformity with the findings of Yadav *et al* (2002).

It was observed that increase in spacing significantly improved various yield attributes of the crop. Days to 50 per cent flowering, number of umbels per plant, number of umbellets per umbel, 1000 seed weight, seed yield, straw yield and harvest index were improved due to each increase in spacing and the maximum value for these estimates were obtained at the wider row spacing 45 cm, while least under closer spacing 30 cm. Crop grown under row spacing of 45 cm produced significantly higher seed yield (11.60 q/ha) compared to other row spacing. Marked improvement in yield attributes of the crop with increase in spacing appear to be on account of flowering and adequate supply of metabolites due to the increase in biomass per plant might have helped in retention of flower thereby greater seed formation and seed growth. This was ultimately reflected in increased seed yield. Under the 45

cm row spacing improved overall growth of crop and increased crop yield due to increased biomass resulting in higher seed yield. These findings were in close conformity with Yadav and Khurana (2000) and Yadav *et al* (2002) in fennel.

It was observed that increase in row spacing from 30 cm to 60 cm significantly improved the chlorophyll content of leaves. Significantly higher chlorophyll content of leaves under wider row spacing could be ascribed due to availability of large space per plant resulted in profuse vegetative growth and delayed plants to attain reproductive growth. The similar results have also been reported by Menaria and Maliwal (2007) in fennel.

Effect of NPK

Significantly higher plant height, primary, secondary and tertiary braches per plant at harvest and fresh and dry weight per plant was recorded as a result of higher levels of NPK (60:40:40 kg/ha). Thus, increased endogenous level of N P K in plant by virtue of its increased availability in the soil medium and there after efficient absorption and translocation in various growths by way of active cell division and elongation resulting in greater plant height, number of primary and secondary branches. The improvement in morphological parameters under the influence of NPK application might have resulted in larger canopy development and presumably higher chlorophyll content of leaves as nutrient actively participate in its formation. The findings of this investigation were in close conformity with those of Rai *et al* (2002) in fennel, Krishnamoorthy and Madalgiri (2002), Nath *et al* (2008), Naruka *et al* (2012) in ajowan.

Data on yield components of the crop under influence of NPK application indicate that increasing level of NPK up to 60:40:40 kg/ha significantly improved days to 50 per cent flowering, number of umbels per plant, number of umbellets per umbel, number of seeds per umbel, test weight, seed yield. Levels of NPK application indicates that increasing level of NPK up to (120:60:60 kg/ha) significantly improved straw and biological yield. The faster

Row Spacing and Level of NPK on Yield of Fennel

Table 1. Effect of row spacing and NPK levels on growth and quality of fennel.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)		Branches per plant			Fresh weight/ plant (g)			Dry weight/ plant (g)			Chlorophyll content (mg/g)		
	60 DAS	90 DAS	At harvest	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary	60 DAS	90 DAS	At harvest	60 DAS	90 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	
Row spacing														
30 cm	46.14	136.63	152.18	3.44	11.89	14.45	25.82	116.13	206.72	2.86	14.47	106.08	1.26	1.46
45 cm	48.60	140.59	155.04	3.58	12.13	14.55	27.24	119.72	208.90	3.12	15.26	107.26	1.27	1.48
60 cm	50.80	144.68	159.68	3.64	12.14	14.64	27.80	120.66	209.63	3.33	16.07	107.91	1.29	1.50
S.Em ±	0.63	1.42	1.35	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.18	0.44	0.37	0.06	0.21	0.29	0.01	0.01
CD at 5%	2.19	4.91	4.68	0.10	0.18	0.11	0.61	1.53	1.28	0.21	0.74	1.01	0.02	0.02
Levels of NPK (Kg/ha)														
Control (0,0,0)	45.07	130.93	145.02	3.30	11.79	14.15	25.35	116.46	206.12	2.72	14.39	105.54	1.22	1.40
30, 20, 20	45.98	136.36	150.25	3.53	11.91	14.37	26.93	117.77	207.51	2.94	14.60	105.93	1.24	1.46
60, 40, 40	48.30	143.48	158.78	3.71	12.28	14.81	27.26	119.52	209.67	3.36	15.91	108.41	1.29	1.52
120, 60, 60	54.71	151.75	161.47	3.74	12.43	14.96	28.26	121.60	210.37	3.41	16.16	108.44	1.34	1.55
S.Em ±	0.86	2.20	2.46	0.05	0.11	0.12	0.38	0.80	0.73	0.12	0.41	0.68	0.02	0.02
CD at 5%	2.50	6.38	7.14	0.13	0.32	0.36	1.09	2.33	2.13	0.36	1.19	1.98	0.05	0.04

Table 2. Effect of row spacing and NPK levels on yield attributes, yield and economics of fennel.

Treatment	Umbels/plant			Umbellet/plant			Days to 50% flowering	Seeds / umbel	Test weight (g)	Seed yield (q ha-1)	Straw yield (q ha-1)	Biological yield (q ha-1)	Harvest index (%)	Gross return Rs ha-1	Net return Rs ha-1	B:C ratio
	Pri-mary	Sec-ondary	Ter-tiary	Pri-mary	Sec-ondary	Ter-tiary										
Row spacing																
30 cm	3.42	12.36	11.07	33.5	27.7	12.23	94.17	428.08	7.92	9.34	22.17	31.71	28.86	84015	60158	2.49
45 cm	3.56	12.85	11.26	33.9	28.2	12.63	93.38	506.53	8.08	11.06	22.72	33.59	31.93	99506	75769	3.10
60 cm	3.59	13.14	11.58	34.3	28.4	13.04	95.04	522.06	8.21	11.40	22.90	34.30	32.07	102611	78994	3.30
S.Em ±	0.03	0.09	0.06	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.19	7.73	0.04	0.17	0.14	0.24	0.34	1546	1546	0.07
CD at 5%	0.11	0.30	0.21	0.48	0.43	0.45	0.64	26.76	0.14	0.59	0.48	0.84	1.19	5352	5352	0.24
Levels of NPK (Kg/ha)																
Control (0,0,0)	3.18	12.22	10.33	32.7	27.0	11.65	91.88	343.61	7.41	7.64	14.23	21.62	29.63	68722	49182	2.52
30, 20, 20	3.41	12.40	10.93	33.1	27.5	12.35	92.82	493.20	7.99	9.96	20.93	30.89	32.23	89640	67454	3.04
60, 40, 40	3.64	12.88	11.86	34.5	28.9	13.17	95.52	544.05	8.40	12.29	27.16	39.45	31.15	110610	85777	3.45
120, 60, 60	3.87	13.73	12.09	35.3	29.0	13.36	96.57	562.69	8.48	12.50	28.06	40.55	30.80	112537	84148	2.97
S.Em ±	0.06	0.19	0.15	0.35	0.33	0.23	0.81	11.81	0.12	0.26	0.25	0.36	0.54	2362	2362	0.10
CD at 5%	0.17	0.56	0.44	1.00	0.95	0.68	2.35	34.27	0.36	0.76	0.73	1.04	1.58	6854	6854	0.30

Row Spacing and Level of NPK on Yield of Fennel

growth of plants evidenced from increased biomass per plant at successive stages of crop growth with NPK subscribe to the views that there was better availability of metabolites and nutrients, which synchronized to the demand for the growth and development of each reproductive structure of the fennel plant.

A perusal of results indicated that increasing levels of NPK increased seed yield and straw yield of the crop up to 60:40:40 kg/ha. These increased could be ascribed to its direct influence on dry matter accumulation at successive growth stages while indirect influence seems to be *viz.* improvement in various morphological and yield attributing characters. The present trend of increase in seed yield and straw yield of fennel with the application of NPK were in close conformity with the findings of Rai *et al* (2002), Bagri *et al* (2010) in fennel crop and Krishnamoorthy and Madalgari (2002), Nath *et al* (2008) and Naruka *et al* (2012).

ECONOMICS

The significantly higher gross return of Rs. 99506 and net return of Rs.75769/ ha with a B:C ratio of 3:10 was recorded with row spacing of 45 cm. Similarly significantly higher gross return of Rs. 110610 and net return of Rs. 85777/ha with a B:C ratio of 3.45 was recorded with the application of 60:40:40 Kg N P K/ ha applied to fennel.

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded that 45 cm row spacing and 60+40+40 kg NPK/ha recorded significantly higher growth attributes, yield attributes, yield and quality of fennel as compared to other row spacing and NPK levels tested, respectively.

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Efficacy of Urea Molasses Minerals Block on Milk Production and Reproductive Performance of Zebu Cattle under Field Condition

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ABSTRACT

An on farm trial was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of UMMB on performance of zebu cattle and feed economics under semi arid conditions, during the year 2016-17. Twenty lactating cows in mid lactation with similar age, body weight and breed were selected from dairy farms of the local farmers and divided into two equal groups of ten animals in each group i.e. T1 (control) and T2 (UMMB supplementation). The feeding of animals in control group (T1) consisted of 7 kg dry maize stover with some quantity of local dry grasses and 10 kg green fodder i.e. Lucerne with concentrate mixture @40 per cent of milk yield /day. In the treatment group (T2) in addition to the above, a regular supply of urea molasses minerals block as a lick was offered during the whole period of study, without interruption. The average milk yield was recorded 4.70 ± 0.20 and 6.00 ± 0.21 l/day in control and UMMB groups, respectively. The significant increase in the milk yield by 27.65 per cent in experiment group suggested that the supplementation of UMMB improved the milk yield. Reduction in cost of milk production/ l was recorded 12.12 per cent in zebu cows supplemented with UMMB. The postpartum estrus period and service period reduced in experimental group than the control group. It can be concluded that the feeding of UMMB improved the feed efficiency, milk production and reproductive performance of zebu cattle under semi-arid ecosystem.

Key Words: Feeding, Milk production, Reproductive performance UMMB and Zebu cattle.

INTRODUCTION

The crop residues based system of animal feeding in most of the developing countries of the world is not adequate to meet even maintenance requirements of the animals. The crops residues and grasses which are low in nitrogen and high in crude fibre, lignin, restricts their intake and digestibility. These feed and fodder are insufficient to support nutrients requirements, optimal reproductive performance and sustainable milk production from the dairy animals. Singh and Singh (2003) well documented the importance of urea molasses mineral block (UMMB) as supplement for livestock. UMMB can be offered throughout the year but more beneficially utilized during the dry season when animals are grazing on low quality fodder.

The availability of molasses, urea and minerals as source of energy, protein and minerals respectively through UMMB optimize rumen fermentation and consequently increase utilization of crop residues and results into higher consumption which decrease the requirement of concentrate. However, most of the trials have been conducted on farm station and few work have been done to evaluate the response of UMMB supplementation on milk production and reproductive performance on indigenous cattle under the field conditions particularly in semi arid ecosystem. Keeping the above facts in view, an attempt was made to evaluate the effect of UMMB on milk production and reproductive performance of lactating Zebu cattle under field conditions.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

An on farm trial was conducted during 2016-17 on 20 Kankrej lactating cattle maintained at farmers' flock in the adopted villages of Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Jalore district of Southern Rajasthan. The animals were selected at the same lactation stage, body weight, milk yield and parity and managed under farmers own traditional system of feeding and management. The average body weight of selected crossbreed cows was 351 kg and average daily milk yield was 4.58 l/day during the start of experiment. The animals were randomly divided into two groups of 10 animals in each group i.e. T1 (control) and T2 (UMMB supplementations). The feeding of animals in control group (T1) consisted of 7 kg dry maize stover with some quantity of local dry grasses and 10 kg green fodder i.e. Lucerne with concentrate mixture @40 per cent of milk yield per day. In the treatment group (T2) in addition to the above, a regular supply of urea molasses minerals block as a lick was offered during the whole period of study, without interruption.

The UMMB was purchased from Rajasthan cooperative dairy federation (RCDF) unit Saras dairy, Jalore. The UMMB was kept in front of the animals in the manger to allow optimum intake. All the animals fed individually and clean, fresh water was available free choice throughout experimental period. All the animals were dewormed by Albendazole for control of internal parasites before the beginning of experiment. The data recording of experiment trial was carried out for 120 days. The body weights of the cows were estimated before the

initiation and at the end of the experiment indirectly by measuring heart girth of the cows using a metric tape as suggested by (Sastry *et al*, 1988). The milk was recorded daily at morning and evening. The intake of feed and UMMB was recorded daily. Samples of milk were taken constantly at milking time from each cow and analyzed for fat, SNF, and total solid. Milk fat was determined by Gerber's method (BIS, 1977), SNF by using ISI formula based on estimation of specific gravity using corrected lactometer reading and 4 per cent FCM was calculated by the equation of formula (Gaines,1928). Reproductive performance with reference to onset of post- partum estrus, service period and services per conception were also recorded. The data were analyzed statistically in a completely randomized design and the significances of the difference means was determined by using the student- t test (Snedecor and Cochran, 1989).

RESULTS DISCUSSION

The chemical composition of concentrate mixture, maize Stover and UMMB is given in Table 1. The chemical composition of the concentrate mixture was different to the mixture reported by (Misra *et al*, 2006 and Khadda *et al*, 2014). This might be due to mixing of various ingredients in different proportion to meet the nutritional requirement of the animals. The CP content of concentrate mixture, maize straw and UMMB was 20.78, 3.74 and 41.13 percent, respectively. Supplementation of UMMB significantly improved the quality and nutrient density of the basal diet. Improvement of

Table I. Chemical composition (% DM) of concentrate mixture, Maize straw and UMMB.

Particular	Concentrate mixture	Maize straw	UMMB
Dry matter	90.32	89.57	88.58
Organic matter	88.21	91.10	75.86
Crude protein	20.78	3.74	41.13
Ether extract	2.66	1.62	2.06
Crude fiber	10.69	37.90	1.93
Nitrogen free extract	61.98	61.98	58.20
Total ash	11.79	8.90	24.14

Efficacy of Urea Molasses Minerals Block on Zebu Cattle

Table 2. Efficacy of UMMB on yield and composition of milk of zebu cattle

Parameter	T-1 (Control)	T-2 (UMMB)
Initial body weight(Kg)	350 ±10.75	352 ±10.50
Final body weight(Kg)	363 ±12.50	376 ±6.25
Body weight gain(Kg)*	13a ±1.07	24b ±3.21
Initial Milk yield (l/ d)	4.56± 0.15	4.61± 0.18
Milk yield (l/ d)**	4.70a ± 0.20	6.00b±0.21
4% FCM yield (l/ d)**	4.03a ±0.15	5.40b ±0.20
Lactometer reading**	28.20a± 0.32	30.30b ±0.20
Fat**	2.90a ± 0.01	3.31b ± 0.01
SNF**	7.80a ± 0.08	9.02b ± 0.05
Total solid %	10.70±0.23	12.33±0.15

the basal diet due to UMMB supplementation is well established and may vary widely depending on nature of basal feed and feeding system (Misra et al, 2006). The intake of UMMB ranged from 250 to 350 g with an overall average of 300g/ cow/ day. This variation was due to the variability in taste habits of the animals.

Effect of UMMB on milk yield

Group mean with different superscripts differ significantly * (P<0.05) and ** (P<0.01). The effect of UMMB on milk yield and its composition (Table 2) revealed that the initial milk yield was similar in both groups but average milk yield recorded during the study period was 4.70 ± 0.20 and 6.00±0.21/ day in control and UMMB group, respectively. The significant increase in the milk yield by 27.65 per cent in experiment group suggested that the supplementation of UMMB improved the milk yield. Similarly, it also helped in improving lactometer reading from 28.20 to 30.30 in cows being statistically different. These results were in

agreement with the earlier study by (Ramesh *et al*, 2009 and Khadda *et al*, 2014). The increase in milk production may be attributed to higher availability of crude protein, energy and area specific minerals in the ration supplemented with UMMB which led to a subsequent maintenance of rumen ammonia content and an improved rumen environment for micro-organisms and increased digestibility of the ration (Tiwari et al, 2013 and Sharma *et al*, 2014). Fat and SNF components of milk in animals fed with UMMB improved considerably as compared to control. Similar results were also reported by (Ramesh *et al*,2009).

Reproductive performance

The mean duration of postpartum estrus period and service period was reduced significantly (P<0.05) in experiment group as compared to the control group (Table 3). The average number of service per conception was also significantly (P<0.05) higher in control group than the experiment group. Our results were corroborated with the

Table 3. Efficacy of UMMB on reproductive performance of zebu cattle.

Particulars	T-1 (Control)	T-2(UMMB)
No. of cow	10	10
Post-partum estrus(days)*	130.6a ± 17.54	80.9b±11.66
Service period(days)*	171.4a ± 11.7	115.7b± 8.40
No. Of service per conception*	3.6a± 1.22	1.37b± 0.20

* Group mean with different superscripts differ significantly (P<0.05)

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findings of (Ramesh *et al*, 2009) who reported that UMMB supplementation has a positive effect on reproductive performance of cow maintained on straw based diets due to supply on nitrogen resulting in more intake and utilization of straw. The improvement in reproductive efficiency in the present study may be attributed to the beneficial action of supplemented minerals, crude protein and energy on the neuro-endocrine axis and reproductive function.

Feeding economics of UMMB

A partial budget analysis measures was used in those items of expenditure and income. Therefore, the cost of roughage, concentrate mixture and UMMB have been considered. The cost of labour was not considered for calculation because it was same in both groups as family members were used in management of livestock. The costs of dry fodder, green fodder, concentrate mixture and UMMB was calculated on basis of market rate prevalent during the study period i.e. @ Rs.400/q. for dry fodder, Rs.100/q. for green fodder, Rs.1600/q. for concentrate mixture and Rs. 33/ block of 3Kg for UMMB. Selling price of milk received by farmers

during experimental period was taken Rs. 30/l. The recurring cost which included feeding and income from sale of milk presented in Table 4. The average cost of feeding per liter of milk production in control and experiment group was Rs.14.89 and 13.28, respectively, which showed that dietary supplementation of UMMB under field condition reduced the cost of milk production sizably. The supplementation of UMMB during experimental period indicated that benefit cost ratio 1:2.25 was recorded, which appears to be very lucrative over traditional system of feeding. Significantly higher net return and benefit-cost ratio was also recorded in crossbreed cows (Misra *et al*, 2006) maintained on roughage based diet due to UMMB supplementation under small holder condition.

CONCLUSION

Hence, it can be concluded that the improvement in nutrient intake, milk yield, onset of estrus and lower cost of production in experiment group in cows could easily be achieved as urea molasses minerals block supplied the adequate nutrients for better performance in zebu cows of medium level of

Table 4. Feed economics of UMMB on zebu cattle.

Particulars	T-1 (Control)	T-2(UMMB)
Feed consumed (Kg/ day/ animal)		
Maize Stover	7.0	7.0
Concentrate mixture	2.0	2.4
Lucerne fodder	10.0	10.0
UMMB	-	0.3
Av. Feeding cost Rs. (120 days)	8400/-	9168/-
Cost of UMMB (Rs.)	-	396/-
Total variable cost (Rs.)	8400/-	9564/-
Variable cost of milk production/ day (Rs.)	70.0	79.7
Total milk yield liter (120 days)	564	720
Av. feeding cost/ liter milk production (Rs.)	14.89	13.28
Gross return from sale of milk(Rs.)	16920	21600
Net return (Rs.)	8520/-	12036/-
B:C ratio	2.01	2.25
Additional B:C ratio from UMMB	-	11.81

Efficacy of Urea Molasses Minerals Block on Zebu Cattle

production. It was inferred that the supplementation of urea molasses minerals block to the zebu lactating cows @300g/ day under field conditions improved their milk yield and reproductive performance besides reducing cost of milk production. However, awareness needs to be created among the dairy farmers about usefulness of UMMB.

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Evaluation of Bullock Drawn Drum Seeder with other Rice Establishment Methods under Wet Land Conditions

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ABSTRACT

A bullock drawn 8 row drum seeder has been developed by incorporating suitable modifications in the manual 8 row drum seeder to improve plant population stand under wet land rice cultivation system. The performance of the developed bullock drawn drum seeder was compared with the existing manual drum seeder and four other methods of rice establishment i.e. manual three row mechanical transplanter, line transplanting using rope and guide; often considered as Researcher's method, SRI method and manual random transplanting as control. The performance of bullock drawn drum seeder was found superior to other methods of paddy establishment with respect to labour requirement, cost of operation, plant growth and yield parameters. The highest B: C ratio of 2.26 was found out in case of bullock drawn drum seeder with cost of operation being Rs 1275/- per ha. Among the six methods of paddy establishment under wet land condition, highest grain and straw yield of 51.8 q/ha and 67.3q/ha, respectively were recorded in case of the developed bullock drawn drum seeder. The small and marginal farmers of the state would be substantially benefited by using the bullock drawn drum seeder considering the lower cost of cultivation, labour and drudgery involvement; yet obtaining higher grain and straw yield.

Key Words: Drum seeder, Cost of operation, transplanting, labour requirement.

INTRODUCTION

Paddy is the major cereal crop of Odisha and is grown under wet land condition primarily during *kharif* season and under irrigated conditions in rabi season where conventional manual random transplanting is followed. The high yielding rice varieties have been growing in transplanted condition since their introduction, with a belief that transplanted rice usually produces 10-15 per cent more yield than direct seeded rice.

Transplanting method involves seedbed preparation, nursery growing, care of seedlings in nursery, uprooting of seedlings, hauling and transplanting operations. The preparation of seedbed and sowing are done 30 days before planting. The rice farmers practicing transplanting are facing

problems like shortage of labour during peak time, hike in labour charges, small and fragmented land holdings etc. Use of mechanical transplanter is slowly increasing; but raising mat type seedling has been a major concern for the farmers. The socio-economic conditions of the farmers of Odisha hardly permit them to own mechanical transplanters for line transplanting. In comparison, the drum seeder seems to be an alternative to transplanting under wet land rice cultivation without sacrificing the yield. The farmers are preferring line sowing of pre-germinated paddy seeds by using a 8 row manual drawn drum seeder to line transplanting by conventional hand transplanting method. The major reasons for this are reduction in labour and time requirement and cost involvement and reduction

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in drudgery. The wet seeding of rice is generally followed in irrigated areas. For wet drum seeding the paddy seeds are soaked in water for 24 hr and incubated for 24-48 hr. These sprouted seeds are sown in puddled field 1-2 d after puddling using perforated drum seeder.

Subbaiah and Balasubramanian (2000) cited the advantages of direct wet seeding of rice in comparison to transplanting as faster and easier crop establishment, reduced labour use, lesser drudgery, earlier crop maturity (8-10 d), more efficient water use due to reduced crop duration and increased benefit-crop ratio. They further opined that direct wet seeding has every potential to occupy the place of transplanted rice in command areas of Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh especially under rainfed low land rice ecosystem. Chavan *et al* (2012) evaluated 8 row manual operated drum seeder in the Konkan region for seeding in both *kharif* and *rabi* season with proper irrigation practices. During field test the theoretical field capacity was calculated as 0.2 ha/h, while effective field capacity was observed to be 0.11 ha/h. The field efficiency of the seeder was found to be 55 per cent. The cost of operation of drum seeder is Rs. 32.73/- per hour and Rs.297/- per hectare. Singh and Hensel (2012) reported that the cost of operation for sowing paddy using drum seeder was Rs.800/-ha as compared to Rs.30000/-ha in conventional method. The benefit cost (B:C) ratio of drum seeding was calculated as 4.59 as compared to 3.89 in case of transplanting method. They further emphasized that the dry seeder technology is preferred because of low draft requirement, labour saving, natural resource conservation, better output/profits and less occupational health hazards. Islam and Ahmad (2010) developed a BIRRI modified drum type row seeder incorporating few changes in IIRRI manual drum type seeder for line sowing of pre-germinated paddy seeds and conducted field experiments to compare its performance with hand broadcasted paddy system. It was reported that the BIRRI modified drum type row seeder, with a

seeding rate of 60 kg/ha, performed better for an optimum crop yield.

However, the use of drum seeder is also limited because of improper levelling of puddled field, which results in rotting of seeds. Hence, a bullock drawn ridge type drum seeder was developed by incorporating necessary modifications in manual drum seeder i.e. making a provision for a float to form ridges as it is pulled forward and allowing the pre-germinated paddy seeds to fall on the ridge to ensure the proper plant population apart from timely completion of sowing leading to higher production and productivity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The bullock drawn ridge type 8 row drum seeder has been developed incorporating necessary modifications in the existing manual 8 row drum seeder. This device has got a float on which there is a provision for operator to sit and control the operation. The manual drum seeder is attached at the rear end of the float while the beam is attached to the yoke at the front. The float is so designed that it gives alternate raised surface and furrow during its operation in puddle field. The operator has to press a pedal to lift the drum seeder during the turning and has to release the pedal to allow the rotation of the ground wheels of the drum seeder as it proceeds forward. The drums of the seeder is so arranged that the seeds drop only over the middle of the raised surfaces (ridges) formed by the float and stagnant water if any flow into the furrows.

A field experiment was conducted by using (RBD) 6 treatments with 4 replications to evaluate the performance of bullock drawn drum seeder along with other rice establishment methods during *kharif*, 2016 in Central Farm, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology. The performance of the developed bullock drawn drum seeder was compared with the existing manual drum seeder and three other methods of rice establishment i.e. manual three row mechanical transplanter, line transplanting using rope and guide; often

Evaluation of Bullock Drawn Drum Seeder

Fig 1. Drum seeder details and float with ridge arrangement

Treatments

- T1: Bullock drawn 8 row drum seeder
- T2: Manual 8 row drum seeder
- T3: Manual 3 row mechanical transplanter
- T4: SRI method
- T5: Line transplanting using rope & guide method
- T6: Control-Manual random transplanting

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results on functional parameters, plant growth and yield parameters of different methods of paddy establishment have been presented in Table 1 and 2, respectively. The output of the bullock drawn drum seeder was found to be 0.157 ha/h as compared to 0.165 ha/h in case of the manual drum seeder. The output of the 3 row manual mechanical transplanter was observed to be 0.016 ha/h. The draft and power requirement of the bullock Cost of conventional transplanting: Rs 10900/- per ha [(30 workers/ha for transplanting + 20 workers for nursery uprooting + bullock with plough man 1 day with 2 workers for nursery bed preparation)

considered as Researcher's method and SRI method. Conventional manual random transplanting was included in the field experiment as control. A high yielding variety (HYV), *Rani* was selected for the experiment. Recommended package of practices with references to land preparation, fertilizer and plant protection measure were followed for the experiment. The functional parameters, plant growth parameters and yield parameters were recorded to compare the performance of different treatments under the study.

Table 1. Functional parameters of different methods of paddy establishment.

Treatment	Actual field capacity, ha/h h/ha	Speed of operation, kmph	Draft, kgf	Power, hp	Cost of operation, Rs/ha	Seed rate, kg/ha	Labour requirement, man days/ha	Field efficiency, percent
T1	0.165 6.06	1.602	8.1	0.048	975	30.67	5.02	64.35
T2	0.157 6.37	1.453	45.8	0.246	1275	31.25	5.12	67.54
T3	0.016 62.5	0.290	14.6	0.016	2874	35.12	10.42	61.21
T4	-	-	-	-	12548	5.24	60.24	-
T5	-	-	-	-	11456	40.32	54.78	-
T6	-	-	-	-	11004	40.16	52.52	-

Table 2. Plant growth and yield parameters under different methods of paddy establishment.

Treatment	No of tillers/ sqm at maxi- mum tillering	Plant height, cm	No of panicles /sq m	No of grains/ panicle	1000 grain weight, g	Grain yield, q/ ha	Straw yield, q/ ha	B:C ratio
T1	320	118.2	294	107	23.8	46.8	64.6	2.06
T2r	370	115.0	340	118	24.1	51.8	67.3	2.26
T3	321	107.6	291	105	23.7	46.0	64.4	1.93
T4	360	113.2	332	116	23.4	50.2	60.2	1.65
T5	356	112.8	327	111	23.0	49.5	59.4	1.67
T6	327	111.2	301	109	23.1	45.6	57.1	1.55
CD 0.05%	9.8	6.97	10.22	8.20	0.34	6.11	3.75	

Cost of planting by 8-row bullock drawn drum seeder: Rs 1275/- per ha [(operating cost of drum seeder is Rs 108/h)x 6.25 hrs/ha) + 1 worker for watching 3 days]

Cost of planting by 8-row drum seeder: Rs 975/- per ha [(operating cost of drum seeder is Rs 75/h) x 5 hrs/ha) + 1 worker for watching 3 days drawn drum seeder were found to be 45.8 kgf and 0.246 hp respectively. The average draft requirement for operating the transplanter was found to be 14.6 kgf and operating the manual drum seeder was within 5.3 to 8.1 kgf. Highest cost of operation among the treatments was recorded as Rs12548/- per ha for manual transplanting in SRI method while it was lowest as Rs 975/- per ha in case of manual drum seeder due to the fact that the highest and lowest labour requirement of 60.24 man days/ha and 5.02 man days/ha were observed in SRI method and manual drum seeder, respectively. The cost of operation in case of bullock drawn drum seeder was found to be Rs 1275/- ha.

Among the different paddy establishment methods, maximum and minimum number of plants per square meter at maximum tillering stage were observed to be 370 and 320 respectively, in case of bullock drawn drum seeder and manual drum seeder. The highest and lowest plant heights as 118.2 cm and 107.6 cm were found to be in case of manual drum seeder under puddled condition and

3 row manual mechanical trasplanter respectively. Considering the other plant growth parameters such as No of panicles/sq m, No of grains/ panicle and 1000 grain weight, the performance of the bullock drawn drum seeder was found to be superior to other treatments under the experiment. The highest No of panicles/sq m, No of grains/ panicle and 1000 grain weight in case of the said treatment were 340, 118 and 24.1 g respectively. Highest and lowest grain yield of 51.8 q/ha and 45.6 q/ha were recorded in case of bullock drawn drum seeder and manual random transplanting respectively. The grain yield in case of manual drum seeder, SRI method and manual line transplanting using rope and guide were at par. Similarly the straw yield was found to be highest as 67.3q/ha in case of bullock drawn drum seeder which was at par with manual drum seeder and manual mechanical transplanter. The highest and lowest B:C ratio of 2.26 and 1.55 were found out in case of bullock drawn drum seeder and manual random transplanting respectively. Among other treatments, the B:C ratio of manual drum seeder was observed to be 2.06, followed by 1.93 in case of manual mechanical transplanter. This may be due to the fact that the grain and straw yield were higher in case of bullock drawn drum seeder along with lower cost of operation while the cost of operation in case of manual random transplanting, manual line transplanting and SRI method were much higher in comparison to other methods.

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CONCLUSION

Considering B: C ratio and labour requirement, economic benefit to the farmer and labour involvement in different paddy establishment methods, bullock drawn drum seeder under puddled condition was found superior to other methods. This device can cater to the needs of small and marginal farmers of paddy growing areas of the state.

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Growth and Yield of Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L) as Affected by Date of Sowing and Spacing under north Gujarat Condition

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was carried out during kharif season of 2010- 11 at Dantiwada Agricultural University, Sardarkrushinagar to study the effect of sowing dates and spacing on growth and yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) var. Parbhani Kranti. The experiment was laid out in split plot design with three replications and sixteen treatment combinations consisted of four dates of sowing viz., 15th August (D1), 1st September (D2), 15th September (D3) and 1st October (D4) and four plant spacing 30 cm X 30 cm (S1), 45 cm X 30 cm (S2), 45 cm X 45 cm (S3) and 60 cm X 30 cm (S4). The growth and yield attributes like plant height (cm), stem girth, leaf area index, average length of internodes, flower parameters, number of fruits per plant and fruit yield per hectare were significantly higher under sowing on 15th August with plant spacing 30 cm X 30 cm (S1) but fruit yield per plant was significantly higher on 15th August at 45 cm x 45 cm.

Key Words: Fruit yield, Okra, Sowing dates, Spacing.

INTRODUCTION

Okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench.] belong to the family Malvaceae is one of the important vegetable crops of subtropical and tropical regions of India. Among agronomic factors, known to augment crop yield, the sowing dates and plant spacing are considered to be the most productive inputs. The sowing date is known to influence the performance of genotypes due to interaction with weather conditions that prevail at different period of growth. Birbal *et al* (1995) observed that okra cv. Varsha Uphar was found tallest and maximum number of fruits per plant under closer spacing whereas, number of pods and pod weight per plant was found highest at wider spacing. Thus, to get highest yield and good quality green fruit, okra is required to be sown at optimum plant spacing. With regard to okra cultivation optimum number of plant per unit area is required to utilize efficiently the available production factors such as water, nutrients, light and CO₂. The growth and yield of okra are greatly influenced by sowing dates and plant spacing. Hence, a field experiment was

conducted to study the effect of sowing dates and spacing on growth and yield of okra under north Gujarat conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at the Sardarkrushinagar located at 72.190 East longitudes and 24.190 North latitude during kharif season of 2010-11. The experiment was laid out in split plot design with three replications and sixteen treatment combinations consisted of four dates of sowing viz., 15th August (D1), 1st September (D2), 15th September (D3) and 1st October (D4) and four plant spacing 30 cm X 30 cm (S1), 45 cm X 30 cm (S2), 45 cm X 45 cm (S3) and 60 cm X 30 cm (S4). It is mentioned that for this region, the recommended optimum sowing time for okra was June-July at plant spacing of 45 cm x30 cm with seed rate of 10 kg/ha. in rainy season. In the experiment, well rotted farm yard manure @ 20 t/ha was incorporated 20 d before sowing. The fertilizers were applied as per the treatments. The recommended dose of fertilizers 80-50-50 NPK kg/

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ha applied equally to all treatments. Observations, with respect to vegetative growth and fruit yield characters were recorded. Five plants were selected randomly from each plot for immature fruit yield, plant height, stem girth, leaf area index (LAI) and average length of internodes, days taken to flower initiation and number of fruit per plant, fruit yield per plant and yield per hectare.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of sowing date

Growth yield parameters of okra such as plant height stem girth (cm), leaf area index (LAI) at 30, 60, and 90 DAS and average length of internodes (cm) at 60 DAS days taken to flower initiation (days) and viz., number of fruits per plant, fruit yield per plant and fruit yield per hectare were significantly affected by sowing dates. The data (Table 1) indicated that highest plant height (20.82, 68.72 and 96.40 cm), stem girth (1.82, 4.71 and 6.67 cm), leaf area index (LAI) 0.23, 0.76 1.34 respectively at 30,60 and 90 DAS, average length of internodes/plant (6.09 cm), minimum days taken to flower initiation (36.23 d) and maximum number of fruits/plant 23.03, fruit yield/plant (0.16 kg), and fruit yield (94.54 q/ha) okra were observed in treatment D1 whereas, lowest plant height (12.83, 38.16 and 39.67 cm), stem girth (1.34, 3.65 and 5.07 cm), leaf area index (LAI) 0.15, 0.51 and 0.41 respectively at 30,60 and 90 DAS, average length of internodes/plant (4.75 cm) and maximum days taken to flower initiation (44.95 d) were observed in treatment D4. This might have resulted due to the maintenance of optimum plant population and favorable weather conditions during plant vegetative growth and development. Similar results were reported by Bajpai *et al* (2004), Hussain *et al* (2006) and Firoz *et al* (2008) in okra.

Effect of different spacing

Plant geometry i.e. 30 cm X 30 cm (S1), 45 cm X 30 cm (S2), 45 cm X 45 cm (S3) and 60 cm X 30 cm (S4) significantly influenced the different

growth attributes (Table 1) Maximum plant height (cm) and Leaf area index at 30, 60 and 90 DAS (17.95cm, 63.43 cm and 76.80 cm) and (0.29, 0.98 and 1.18) were recorded, respectively, when crop was sown at 30 cm x 30 cm spacing .However, maximum stem girth (1.89, 4.20 and 6.23 cm) were observed in crop sown at 45 cm x 45 cm at 30, 60 and 90 DAS, respectively and maximum average length of internodes/plant (5.92 cm) at 60 DAS, in crop sown at 30 cm x 30 cm plant spacing. Plant behavior observed under closer plant spacing was in close conformity with the findings of Soni *et al* (2006).

Yield character

It was observed that yield characters of okra such as number of fruit/plant, fruit yield/plant (kg) and fruit yield (t/ha) were significantly affected by plant spacing (Table 2). The maximum number of fruit/plant (21.60) and fruit yield (12.72 q/ha) were recorded with closer plant spacing at 30 cm X 30 cm (S1) whereas, minimum number of fruit/plant (17.08) and fruit yield (3.32 q/ha) were recorded at wider plant spacing of 60 cm x 45 cm (S4) and maximum fruit yield/plant (0.15 kg) was recorded with plant spacing i.e. 45 cm X 45 cm (S3) but minimum fruit yield/ plant (0.11kg) were recorded with closer plant spacing i.e. 30 cm X 30 cm (S1). This might be due to the plant grown at wider spacing comparatively received more nutrition and light for vegetative growth and development crop but number of fruit per plant and fruit yield per hectare might have helped for more vegetative growth and development of crop. Similar results were reported by Poonam *et al* (2006), Soni *et al* (2006).Bharad *et al* (2006) and Moniruzzaman *et al* (2007).

CONCLUSION

From the experimentation, it can be concluded that for securing higher yield okra should be sown on 15th August (D1) with (S1) 30 cm X 30 cm plant spacing in North Gujarat Agro - climatic conditions.

Growth and Yield of Okra

Table 1: Effect of sowing dates and spacing on plant growth attributes of kharif okra

Treatment	Plant height			Stem girth (cm)			Leaf area index			Average length of internodes/plant (cm)
	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	
Date of Sowing										
D1 (15th August)	20.82	68.72	96.40	1.82	4.71	6.67	0.23	0.76	1.34	6.09
D2 (1st September)	16.00	63.28	81.18	1.66	3.84	5.74	0.20	0.66	1.11	5.44
D3 (15th September)	14.39	52.12	62.79	1.58	3.65	5.07	0.17	0.59	0.93	5.36
D4 (1st October)	12.83	38.16	39.67	1.34	3.18	4.51	0.15	0.51	0.41	4.75
S.E.m.±	0.43	1.48	1.66	0.04	0.10	0.16	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.15
C.D. at 5%	1.50	5.12	5.73	0.15	0.34	0.57	0.02	0.06	0.11	0.51
Spacing(S)										
S1 (30cm x30cm)	17.95	63.43	76.80	1.61	3.88	5.70	0.29	0.98	1.18	5.92
S2 (45cm x 30cm)	16.44	57.86	73.38	1.56	3.80	5.26	0.21	0.70	1.04	5.50
S3 (45cm x 45cm)	15.82	52.99	66.75	1.89	4.20	6.23	0.15	0.49	0.83	5.34
S4 (60cm x45cm)	13.81	48.00	62.62	1.34	3.49	4.79	0.11	0.36	0.74	4.88
S.E.m±	0.42	1.45	1.49	0.06	0.10	0.14	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.13
C.D. at 5%	1.21	4.21	4.34	0.18	0.29	0.41	0.02	0.05	0.08	0.39
Interaction										
S.E.m±	0.83	2.89	2.99	0.12	0.20	0.28	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.27
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.03	0.10	0.15	NS
C.V. %	9.01	9.01	7.39	13.26	8.85	8.86	9.53	9.35	9.54	8.50

Table 2. Effect of sowing dates and spacing on fruit yield (kg/ plot) and fruit yield (t/ha) in kharif okra.

Treatment	Number of fruits per plant	Yield of fruits per plant (kg)	Fruit yield (t ha-1)
Date of Sowing			
D1 (15th August)	23.03	0.16	9.45
D2 (1st September)	21.08	0.13	8.25
D3 (15th September)	17.54	0.13	7.61
D4 (1st October)	15.38	0.10	6.71
S.Em.±	0.53	0.00	0.34
C.D. at 5%	1.84	0.02	1.17
C.V. %	9.60	13.09	1.47
Spacing			
S1 (30cm x30cm)	21.60	0.11	12.72
S2 (45cm x 30cm)	19.80	0.13	9.10
S3 (45cm x 45cm)	18.54	0.15	6.91
S4 (60cm x45cm)	17.08	0.13	3.32
S.Em.±	0.46	0.00	0.18
C.D. at 5%	1.33	0.01	0.53
Interaction (D x S)			
S.Em. ±	0.91	0.01	3.63
C.D. at 5%	NS	NS	10.57
C.V. %	8.22	9.68	7.85

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Impact Analysis of Trainings and Front Line Demonstrations in Black Gram (*Vigna mungo*) Cultivation

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ABSTRACT

The impact assessment with reference to increase in knowledge levels of farmers regarding scientific package of practices, extent of adoption of selected technology and percent adoption of production technology was carried out in four adopted villages. The data about knowledge level of scientific package of practices of blackgram indicated that low, medium, and high level of knowledge after intervention of Krishi Vigyan Kendra was found to be 7, 51 and 42 per cent, respectively. Highest knowledge regarding selected scientific innovations was found for irrigation management (63 %), weed management (57 %), integrated nutrient management (54 %) integrated pest management (35 %) and pest, disease control (30 %), respectively. The technology index indicated there was feasibility of evolving technologies at the farmer's field.

Keywords: Adoption, Integrated nutrient management, Integrated pest management, Technology index.

INTRODUCTION

Pulses on account of their vital role in nutritional security and soil ameliorative properties have been integral part of sustainable agricultural since ages. Black gram (*Vigna mungo*) is a widely grown legume, belongs to the family fabaceae and assumes considerable importance from the point of food and nutritional security in the world. It is a short duration crop and thrives better in all seasons either as sole or as intercrop. India is the world's largest producer as well as consumer of black gram. It produces about 1.5–1.9 MT of black gram annually from about 3.5 m ha .of area, with an average productivity of 600 kg/ha. Black gram output accounts for about 10 per cent of India's total pulse production. It is therefore, necessary to assess the technological gap in production and also to know the problems and constraints in adopting modern black gram production technologies Islam *et al* (2011). Keeping this in view, the present investigation was undertaken to study the level of knowledge of farmers regarding black gram cultivation, extent of adoption of improved practices, to find out the yield gap in black gram production technology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted in Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh . One hundred farmers from 4 villages *viz.*, Karlapudi, Kuragallu, Kantheru and Morampudi of Guntur district were selected. The data were collected through personnel interview, tabulated and analyzed to find out the findings and draw the conclusion. The statistical tool like percentage was employed to analyze the data. The constraints as perceived by respondents were scored on the basis of magnitude of the problem as per Meena and Sisodiya (2004). The responses were recorded and converted in to mean per cent score and ranked accordingly as per Warde *et al* (1991).The extension gap, technology gap and the technology index were work out with the help of formulas given by Samui *et al* (2000) as mentioned below:

Extension gap = Demonstration yield- farmers' yield (control)

Technology gap = Potential yield- demonstration yield

Technology index = $\frac{\text{Technology gap}}{\text{Potential Yield}} \times 100$

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Table 1. Overall knowledge of scientific package of practices of blackgram.

Category	Before intervention of KVK	After intervention of KVK
Low level of knowledge	47	07
Medium level of knowledge	40	51
High level of knowledge	13	42

Table 2. Knowledge regarding different technologies for black gram cultivation.

Sr. No	Technology	Low	Medium	High
1	Integrated nutrient management	8	38	54
2	Pest and disease control	23	47	30
3	Integrated pest management	20	44	35
4	Irrigation management	17	20	63
5	Weed management	10	33	57

Table 3. Overall adoption of scientific package of practices of blackgram (percentage)

Category	Before intervention of KVK	After intervention of KVK
Low level of adoption	24	4
Medium level of adoption	58	20
High level of adoption	18	76

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of overall knowledge of integrated nutrient management (INM) indicated that the low, medium and high level of knowledge before intervention by the KVK was 47, 40, 13 per cent, respectively which increased up to 07, 51 and 42 per cent, after intervention of KVK through training programmes and front line demonstrations (FLDs) (Table 1). Javat *et al* (2011) and Das *et al* (2010) reported the similar results.

With respect to selected scientific innovations for blackgram production, sixty three per cent of farmers were possessing high level of knowledge regarding irrigation management followed by weed management (57.0 %), integrated nutrient management (54.0 %), IPM (35.0 %) and pest, disease control (30.0 %) (Table 2).

Majority of the farmers had medium level of knowledge (58.0%) before intervention of KVK and after intervention of KVK, 76 per cent of the farmers had high level of knowledge regarding scientific

cultivation of black gram (Table 3). Integrated nutrient management scored highest adoption percentage (88.0 %) in black gram production technology followed by weed management (82.0 %), pest and disease control (73.0 %), IPM (70.0 %) and irrigation management (62.0 %), respectively (Table 4).

Yield gap analysis of blackgram cultivation:

The data (Table 5) indicated that the highest yield (15.6 q/ha) was found in FLD plots and lower yield (13.3 q/ha) under farmers' plots. The cost benefit ratio was higher in FLD plot (1 :2.52) than

Table 4. Adoption of technologies

Sr. No.	Name of technology	Adoption (%)
1	Integrated nutrient management	88
2	Pest and disease control	73
3	Integrated pest management	70
5	Irrigation management	62
6	Weed management	82

Impact Analysis of Trainings and Front Line Demonstrations

Table 5. Exploitable productivity, extension gap, technology gap and technology index of black gram as grown under FLDS and existing package of practices.

Year	Area (ha)	No of demon	Yield q/ha		Per cent increase in yield	Cost : Benefit Ratio		Extension Gap q/ha	Technology Gap q/ha	Technology index
			Demon	Control		Demon	Control			
2013	10	25	15.6	13.2	13.49	3.0	2.4	2.06	6.9	22
2014	10	26	12.7	10.5	17.11	2.47	1.8	2.26	7.3	36.5
2015	10	25	18.7	16.2	13.36	2.1	1.5	2.25	1.3	16.5
			15.6	13.3	14.85	2.52	1.9	2.12	5.16	25

control (1: 1.9). The results clearly showed that due to knowledge and adoption of scientific practices, the yield of black gram could be increased by 13.49 per cent, 17.71 per cent and 13.36 per cent over the yield obtained under farmers' practices. The above findings were in line with the findings of Dubey *et al* (2010). Yield of the front line demonstration trials and potential yield of the crop was compared to estimate the yield gaps which were further categorized into technology and extension gaps (Hiremath and Nagaraju, 2009). Average extension gap was 2.12 q/ha, which emphasized the need to educate the farmers through various extension means like FLD. The technology gap ranged between 1.3 q/ha to 7.3 q/ha. The average technology gap from three year of FLDs programme was 25 q/ha. The average technology gap observed may be attributed to dissimilarity in soil fertility status, agricultural practices and local climate conditions. The technology index indicated the feasibility of evolved technology at the farmer field. Lower the value of technology index, more is the feasibility of technology demonstrated, (Sagar and Chandra, 2004; Arunachalam, 2011 and Kumar *et al*, 2014). As such reduction of technology index from 22.0 per cent (2013) to 16.5 per cent (2015) exhibited the feasibility of technology demonstrated. Similar yield enhancement in different crops in front line demonstration has amply been documented by Haque (2000), Mishra *et al* (2009) and Kumar *et al* (2010). The FLD obtained a significant positive results and also provided researcher an opportunity to demonstrate the productivity potential and

profitability of INM under real farm situation which they have advocating for a long time. Similar findings were reported by Kirar *et al* (2005) and Chauhan and Pandya (2012) in gram.

CONCLUSION

Knowledge level and adoption level of farmers in four adopted villages were amplified after imparting training and conducting FLD by KVK scientists in Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh. The productivity achieved under FLD over farmers practices created awareness and motivated the other farmers to adopt critical innovations for blackgram cultivation viz., integrated nutrient management, integrated pest management and other technology of black gram in the district.

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Improving Growth, Yield and Profitability in Apple through Mulching in Rainfed Condition in Hilly Region of Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

Apple (*Malus domestica* Borkh.) has become pride of hill farmers for appreciably improving their economy. In rainfed area of hilly regions, where the orchards are mainly established on medium to steep slopes, make the plants prone to water stress as well as nutrient loss from the soil. In spite of no assured irrigation in the hills, the moisture conservation techniques are not in practice. Under such condition, mulching may be practiced during crop cultivation which can be a substitute of irrigation to minimize moisture and nutrient loss as well as cost of production. Considering the above factors, on farm trials were conducted at Harshil area of Uttarkashi district of Uttarakhand at 2530 ft above mean sea level during the year 2010-11 and 2011-12. The trial consisted of four treatments viz., T1, mulching with black polythene, T2, mulching with dry grasses, T3, mulching with straw and T4, clean cultivation as control. Total four treatments were replicated five times. The maximum annual growth was observed under black polythene mulch, while minimum was found under clean cultivation. The highest fruit yield was recorded in mulching with black polythene followed by mulching with dry grasses, however, lowest fruit yield was observed under clean cultivation during both the years. It can be concluded that the plastic mulch has been found efficient for enhancing growth, productivity and profitability of apple crop under rainfed condition.

Key Words: Apple, Economic analysis, Growth, Mulching, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

The major apple growing states in India are Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh and Uttarakhand, which covers 95.4 per cent of total area under apple and 98.7 per cent of the total apple production. In India, it is cultivated on 3.20 lakh ha with production of 18.85 lakh MT and productivity of 5.89 t/ha. The overall productivity is quite low (below 6 t/ha) as compared to standard world average of 16 t/ha. In Uttarakhand alone, the apple was cultivated on 0.29 lakh ha. of land yielding 0.77 lakh MT of fruit annually (National Horticulture Board, 2014-15). It is successfully grown at an elevation range of 1600-2800 m above mean sea level (MSL) and needs chilling requirement of 1000-1600 hr at >7°C (45°F) to overcome the dormancy for flower bud development and flowering (Awasthi, 2001). The area under apple cultivation has increased

manifold during the last four decades, however, the increase in production could not keep pace with the expansion in area (Gautam *et al*, 2005).

In recent years, there has been a gradual decline in its productivity. Several factors are attributed to this declining trend in productivity, like expansion of apple cultivation to marginal areas, supply of nutrient and availability of moisture, declining standard of soil water management, prevalence of diseases and pests, and major climatic shifts (Nautiyal and Dimri, 2009). Among various factors responsible for higher yield, supply of nutrient and availability of moisture play vital role in the production and quality of apple. Moisture is, therefore, essential for its successful production but additional irrigation causes increased cost of production. Under such conditions, mulching may be practiced in crop cultivation which can be a substitute of irrigation

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to minimize cost of production. Mulch is again highly effective in checking evaporation and is hence recommended for most crops. Mulching also suppresses weed infestation effectively. There are several benefits of using mulch, including soil temperature modulation, enhanced fruit quality, improved soil and water management by reduced evaporation and soil erosion, reduced fertilizer leaching and suppression of weed growth which leads to better plants growth and yield.

Considering the above factors, the present On Farm Trial was undertaken to know the effect of mulching on growth and yield of apple production and identify the best mulch in respect to economic production of apple.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present On Farm Trial (OFT) was carried out at village Jhala (harshil area) of district Uttarkashi (Uttarakhand) during the year 2010-11 and 2011-12. The 11 to 12 yr old trees of apple cv. Royal Delicious were selected for the study. The trial consisted of four treatments viz., mulching with black polythene (100 gauge), through dry grasses (15 cm thick), straw (15 cm thick) and clean cultivation (control). The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with five replications. The growth and vigor were measured as annual extension growth of shoot. The yield attributes were obtained in terms of initial fruit set, final fruit set, yield (kg/ plant) and yield (q/ha) at the time of fruit harvesting. The economic analysis was also calculated in terms of cost of cultivation, gross return, net return and benefit cost ratio. The data were analyzed according to the procedure of analysis for Randomized Block Design. The significance of variation among the treatments was observed by applying 'F' test and critical difference at 5 per cent probability was calculated to compare the mean values of treatments for all the characters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Growth Parameters

The perusal of data (Table 1 and Fig. 1 & 2)

indicate that the mulching significantly affected the growth of the plants. The annual growth of the plant was found highest (29.62 and 35.44 cm) in treatment T1 (mulching with black polythene) while treatment T4 (clean cultivation) showed the lowest annual growth during both the years of experiment. The availability of soil moisture and nutrient with less weed growth associated with mulch material can be attributed to maximum annual growth of the plant. Similar findings have also been reported by Pande *et al* (2005) and Granatstein and Mullinix (2008).

Yield attributes

The data revealed that the mulching affected the fruit yield non-significantly in first year (2010-11), while significantly affected during second year (2011-12). The highest fruit yield (kg/plant) was obtained with treatment T1 i.e. black polythene mulch (43.40 and 54.57 kg/plant) followed by dry grasses (40.62 and 50.26 kg/plant). However, the lowest fruit yield (35.31 and 37.08 kg/plant) was found with control treatment T4 (clean cultivation) during both the years of investigation. The similar trend was also observed during both the years of trial (2010-11 and 2011-12) in fruit yield in terms of q/ha. The highest fruit yield (88.53 and 110.57 q/ha) was obtained with black polythene mulch while the minimum yield (72.03 and 75.62 q/ha) was found under clean cultivation.

The maximum fruit set and highest fruit yield under black polythene mulch followed by dry grasses may probably due to the increase in soil moisture, higher nutrient availability and lesser weed infestation, however in clean cultivation less soil moisture retention and nutrient losses resulted low fruit set and fruit yield. These results were in accordance with Wiman *et al* (2009) and Neilsen *et al* (2014).

Economic Analysis

The data pertaining to economic analysis of trial presented in Table 2 and Fig.3 & 4, reveal that the various mulches also effect on benefit cost ratio. The highest cost of treatment per hectare per year

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Table 1: Effect of various mulches on growth and yield of apple cv. Royal Delicious

Treatment	Annual extension growth (cm)		Yield (kg/plant)		Yield* (q/ha)		Yield Increase %	
	2010-11	2011-12	2010-11	2011-12	2010-11	2011-12	2010-11	2011-12
T1- mulching with black polythene	29.62	35.44	43.40	54.25	88.53	110.57	22.90	46.21
T2- mulching with dry Grasses	28.02	31.94	40.62	50.26	82.87	102.50	15.04	35.54
T3- mulching with straw	24.77	28.75	38.78	49.56	79.12	101.07	09.84	33.65
T4- clean cultivation as control	21.81	25.37	35.31	37.08	72.03	75.62	-	-
CD at 5 %	2.59	2.25	NS	4.20	NS	8.55	-	-
SE(m)	0.79	0.69	2.02	1.29	4.13	2.63	-	-
CV (%)	6.13	4.56	10.24	5.41	10.24	5.40	-	-

*Plant spacing 7x7 m

(Rs. 16580 and Rs. 18150.00) accord with treatment T1 *i.e.* mulching with black polythene during both the years. However the cost of cultivation during both the years (excluded the cost of treatment) were equal to all treatments (Rs. 76,500.00/ha/year and Rs. 78,550.00/ha/year). Therefore, the cost of cultivation during both the years included cost of treatment per ha (Rs. 93,080.00/ha and 96,700.00/ha) were in accord with the treatment T1 (Black Polythene Mulching).

The maximum gross return (Rs. 3.09 lakh and 3.96 lakh/ha/year) and net return (Rs. 2.16 and Rs. 2.99 lakh/ha/year) were recorded with treatment T1 *i.e.* mulching with black polythene during both the years of investigation. However, the minimum gross return (Rs. 2.52 lakh and Rs. 2.6 lakh/ha/year) and net return (Rs. 1.75 lakh and 1.82 lakh/ha/year) were obtained with treatment T4 (Clean cultivation as control). The maximum benefit cost ratio (2.32 and 3.09) were obtained with black polythene mulch (T1) followed by clean cultivation (T4) during first year and dry grasses mulches (T2) during second year of trial. However, minimum benefit cost ratio (2.08) was found with the treatment T3 (Mulching with straw) during first year, while T4 (clean cultivation) in second year of experiment. The highest B:C ratio was found with black polythene

mulch might due to highest fruit yield fetches higher market prices. Ghosh and Bera (2015) also reported that the maximum net return was obtained with polythene mulch in pomegranate fruit.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of On Farm Trial, it can be concluded that under hill area of Uttarakhand the apple cv. Royal Delicious recorded significantly higher annual extension growth and fruit yield with black polythene mulching. The use of black polythene mulch material can be maintained high profitability and recorded high benefit: cost ratio due to high fruit yield. Thus, for maximum return and high productivity of apple, mulching may be recommended for temperate zone of Uttarakhand and other hilly states.

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Table 2: Economic analysis of use of various mulches in apple cv. Royal Delicious

Treatments*	Cost of Treatment (₹/ha) (a)		Cost of cultivation (₹/ha) (b)		Total cost of cultivation (₹/ha) (c=a+b)		Gross Return (₹/ha) @35/kg (d)		Net Return (₹/ha) (e=d-c)		B:C Ratio (d/c)	
	2010-11	2011-12	2010-11	2011-12	2010-11	2011-12	2010-11	2011-12	2010-11	2011-12	2010-11	2011-12
T1	16580	18150	76500	78550	93080	96700	309855	396200	216775	299500	2.32	3.09
T2	12100	13220	76500	78550	88600	91770	290045	366100	201445	274330	2.27	2.98
T3	13200	14480	76500	78550	89700	93030	276920	357700	187220	264670	2.08	2.84
T4	-	-	76500	78550	76500	78550	252105	260750	175605	182200	2.29	2.31

(*T1- mulching with black polythene, T2- mulching with dry Grasses, T3- mulching with straw and T4-clean cultivation as control)

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Inheritance of Some Quantitative Characters in Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) under Normal and Saline Sodic Soils

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ABSTRACT

Six populations viz., P1, P2, F1, F2, B1 and B2 of four crosses involving eight parents were evaluated following compact family block design during kharif season in 2008 to 2011 to study the mode of inheritance by using simple (A, B, C and D) and joint scaling tests. The nature and magnitude of gene effects for yield and its components in Barley was also studied using six parameters model of generation mean analysis. The presence of epistasis was detected in 64 cases by simple as well as joint scaling test and inadequacy of additive-dominance model was established. Additive (d), dominance (h) gene effects along with one or more type of non-allelic interaction (i, j, l) contributed significantly towards the inheritance of all the quantitative characters in majority of the crosses. Duplicate type of epistasis was also prevalent in most of the cases with few exceptions. Thus, biparental mating may be suggested for improvement of Barley populations.

Key Words: Barley, Epistasis, Gene action, Generation mean. analysis,

INTRODUCTION

Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L., $2n = 14$), a member of sub-family Poaceae is considered as crop of winter cereal in India and grown in Northern Hills, plains and Central India for food, feed forage and industrial purposes. The crop is inherited with better tolerance to problematic soils, like salinity, alkalinity. It requires less water and fertilizers than the wheat. Thus, in most breeding programme, major emphasis is placed on the improvement of yield and related component traits of polygenetic nature. An understanding of the mode of inheritance of complex quantitative traits in different cropping seasons is essential for formulation of an effective breeding program for improvement of a particular trait. Epistasis is a universal phenomenon in the inheritance of yield and components in crop plants. Detection of epistasis becomes essential not only for obtaining unbiased estimates of additive and dominance gene effects but it also facilitates the breeders to decide about the specific breeding methods to bring about improvement in the crop.

Thus, present investigation was undertaken to detect the epistasis and adequacy of additive dominance/non-allelic model by using simple (A, B, C and D) scaling test (Mather 1949, Hayman and Mather 1955), as well as by Joint Scaling Test (Cavalli 1952) and to estimate the nature and magnitude of gene effects for yield and its components during rabi in four crosses of barley.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Eight genetically diverse and homozygous varieties of barley namely NDB 943, NDB 1173, DL 88, K 890, DWR 57, PL 762, Azad and K 750 were selected for building up the experimental material. These barley genotypes were crossed to produce four F1's i.e. NDB 943 x NDB 1173 (cross I), DL88 x K 890 (cross II), DWR 57 x PL 762 (cross III), Azad x K 750 (cross IV). These F1's were backcrossed to their respective parents (P1 and P2) to produce B1's and B2's as well as selfed to produce F2 seeds. Thus, six genetic populations namely, P1, P2, F1, F2, B1 and B2 were raised in a

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compact family block design with three replications during rabi 2008 under normal and saline sodic soils at the Genetics and Plant Breeding Research Farm, N.D. University of Agriculture and Technology, Kumarganj, Faizabad. The F1's and parents were sown in a single row plot of each whereas, back cross and F2 populations were sown in a three and six rows plot, respectively in five meter length at a row spacing of 22.5 cm. The present investigation was undertaken to test the adequacy of 'additive-dominance model' using simple scaling test and joint scaling test, work out nature and magnitude of gene effects for yield quality and its component traits, study heterosis and inbreeding depression for yield quality and its component traits and work out heritability and genetic advance in per cent of mean. Sixteen quantitative characters namely, initial seed germination, plant height, number of effective tillers, peduncle length, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/spike, grains weight/spike, days to maturity, harvest index, grain yield/plant, grain size, 1000-grain weight, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content were studied in both experiments.

The data on sixteen metric traits from two environments were subjected to analysis of variance of Compact Family Block Design, separately, simple and joint scaling tests and six parameter models of generation mean were used to study the nature and magnitude of gene effects for sixteen traits of four crosses in normal and saline sodic soils.

Heterosis was estimated over standard variety (Azad), better parent and inbreeding depression was studied for understanding the manifestation of heterosis in different crosses. Heritability in broad sense, narrow sense and expected genetic advance in per cent were computed to assess the efficiency of selection in improving the characters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean sum of squares due to differences among generations or progenies within each cross family were significant or highly significant in all the characters under both conditions (normal and

Table -1: Simple scaling tests, gene effects and type of epistasis for 16 metric traits under normal soil.

Crosses	Gene effects											Scales				Type of epistasis
	m	d	h	i	j	i	A	B	C	D						
Initial seed germination (%) in field																
NDB-943xNDB1173	82.220** ±0.20	2.220** ±0.53	14.440** ±1.64	4.440** ±1.33	2.220* ±0.94	15.560** ±2.96	-7.780** ±1.00	-12.220** ±1.81	-24.440** ±2.08	-2.220** ±0.67	C					
DL-88 x K-890	85.553** ±0.54	-3.330** ±0.53	-0.562 ±2.62	-6.673** ±2.41	-0.552 ±0.85	14.457** ±3.65	-4.443** ±1.42	-3.340* ±1.43	-1.110 ±2.97	3.337** ±1.20	--					
DWR-57 x PL-762	85.553** ±0.74	1.110** ±0.95	-5.558 ±3.63	-11.113** ±3.51	-2.225 ±1.23	15.557** ±5.15	-4.447* ±2.05	0.003 ±1.54	6.670 ±3.50	5.557** ±1.75	--					
Azad x K-750	85.550** ±0.20	1.110* ±0.47	8.893** ±1.59	6.673** ±1.25	0.000 ±0.92	-4.453 ±2.85	-1.110 ±1.34	-1.110 ±1.50	-8.893** ±2.12	-3.337** ±0.63	--					
Plant height (cm)																
NDB-943xNDB1173	77.680** ±0.14	-0.437** ±0.26	-5.657** ±0.81	-7.860** ±0.77	-0.613** ±0.35	6.433** ±1.29	0.100 ±0.37	1.327* ±0.61	9.287** ±0.76	3.930** ±0.39	D					

Inheritance of Some Quantitative Characters in Barley

DL-88 x K-890	83.640** ±0.07	-4.873** ±0.24	-11.478** ±0.64	-14.920** ±0.57	-2.698** ±0.32	16.850** ±1.18	-3.663** ±0.47	1.733** ±0.54	12.990** ±0.68	7.460** ±0.28	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	62.747** ±0.14	-0.287** ±0.17	-4.807** ±0.74	-6.333** ±0.65	0.153** ±0.30	6.387** ±1.13	0.127 ±0.48	-0.180 ±0.50	6.280** ±0.90	3.167** ±0.32	D
Azad x K-750	73.173** ±0.14	-4.460** ±0.19	-9.217** ±0.77	-12.653** ±0.68	-1.850** ±0.29	15.713** ±1.20	-3.380** ±0.41	0.320 ±0.59	9.593** ±0.93	6.327** ±0.34	D
Number of effective tillers											
NDB-943xNDB1173	10.267** ±0.06	-0.980** ±0.11	-4.870** ±0.35	-6.467** ±0.32	0.057 ±0.12	15.047** ±0.58	-4.233** ±0.23	-4.347** ±0.197	-2.113** ±0.37	3.233** ±0.16	D
DL-88 x K-890	11.540** ±0.04	-0.280** ±0.08	-11.727** ±0.24	-14.453** ±0.23	0.427** ±0.10	25.827** ±0.40	-5.260** ±0.18	-6.113** ±0.12	3.080** ±0.23	7.227** ±0.11	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	10.847** ±0.03	-1.153** ±0.13	-4.853** ±0.30	-5.800** ±0.27	-0.853** ±0.15	14.720** ±0.58	-5.313** ±0.21	-3.607** ±0.26	-3.120** ±0.28	2.900** ±0.14	D
Azad x K-750	9.867** ±0.08	-0.767** ±0.08	9.587** ±0.38	8.333** ±0.36	-0.687** ±0.13	-10.960** ±0.51	0.627** ±0.20	2.000** ±0.18	-5.707** ±0.39	-4.167** ±0.18	D
Peduncle length (cm)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	9.333** ±0.11	-3.367** ±0.09	-10.617** ±0.52	-9.667** ±0.47	-1.083** ±0.13	7.900** ±0.71	-0.200 ±0.26	1.967** ±0.29	11.433** ±0.63	4.833** ±0.24	D
DL-88 x K-890	5.500** ±0.03	0.333** ±0.08	-0.670** ±0.25	1.600** ±0.21	1.430** ±0.12	-5.327** ±0.45	3.293** ±0.20	0.433* ±0.18	2.127** ±0.30	-0.800** ±0.12	C
DWR-57 x PL-762	4.900** ±0.06	-2.967** ±0.09	1.100** ±0.32	0.333 ±0.30	-2.533** ±0.12	2.467** ±0.48	-3.933** ±0.16	1.133** ±0.21	-3.133** ±0.31	-0.167 ±0.15	C
Azad x K-750	5.733** ±0.03	3.600** ±0.05	6.440** ±0.18	4.800** ±0.15	4.733** ±0.08	13.280** ±0.31	-4.307** ±0.15	-13.773** ±0.13	-22.880** ±0.23	-2.400** ±0.07	C
Spike length (cm)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	8.900** ±0.04	-0.467** ±0.11	1.475** ±0.28	1.467** ±0.27	0.075 ±0.12	-3.617** ±0.49	1.150** ±0.20	1.000** ±0.14	0.683** ±0.19	-0.733** ±0.13	D
DL-88 x K-890	8.867** ±0.04	0.600** ±0.08	-0.667** ±0.23	-1.600** ±0.22	0.567** ±0.10	1.067** ±0.38	0.833** ±0.09	-0.300 ±0.19	2.133** ±0.21	0.800** ±0.11	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	10.600** ±0.06	0.600** ±0.04	-8.050** ±0.25	-9.067** ±0.24	0.117** ±0.06	19.033** ±0.32	-4.867** ±0.12	-5.100** ±0.10	-0.900** ±0.27	4.533** ±0.12	D
Azad x K-750	10.100** ±0.04	-0.233** ±0.08	-4.123** ±0.23	-5.667** ±0.25	0.177 ±0.12	14.913** ±0.50	-4.447** ±0.19	-4.800** ±0.25	-3.580** ±0.38	2.833** ±0.12	D
Chlorophyll content (mg/100g)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	2.267** ±0.00	0.077** ±0.00	-0.570** ±0.01	-0.700** ±0.02	0.033** ±0.01	1.140** ±0.03	-0.187** ±0.01	-0.253** ±0.01	0.260** ±0.02	0.350** ±0.01	D

DL-88 x K-890	1.727** ±0.00	0.147** ±0.01	-0.647** ±0.03	-0.693** ±0.02	0.167** ±0.01	1.000** ±0.05	0.013 ±0.01	-0.320** ±0.02	0.387** ±0.02	0.347** ±0.01	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	2.553** ±0.00	-0.107** ±0.00	-0.567** ±0.01	-0.693** ±0.02	-0.047** ±0.01	1.253** ±0.03	-0.327** ±0.01	-0.233** ±0.01	0.133** ±0.02	0.347** ±0.01	D
Azad x K-750	2.160** ±0.00	-0.123** ±0.00	-0.503** ±0.02	-0.687** ±0.02	-0.057** ±0.01	0.940** ±0.03	-0.183** ±0.01	-0.070** ±0.01	0.433** ±0.02	0.343** ±0.01	D
Number of grains/spike											
NDB-943xNDB1173	52.000** ±0.21	-5.78** ±0.56	57.667** ±1.08	50.667** ±1.00	-3.000** ±0.45	-63.333** ±1.57	3.333** ±0.60	9.333** ±0.71	-38.000** ±1.16	25.333** ±0.50	D
DL-88 x K-890	45.000** ±0.21	-3.333** ±0.45	17.167** ±1.34	18.667** ±1.24	-3.833** ±0.65	-25.000** ±2.23	-0.667 ±0.76	7.000** ±1.09	-12.333** ±1.32	-9.333** ±0.62	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	31.667** ±0.27	-35.000** ±0.35	20.000** ±1.38	35.333** ±1.28	-26.000** ±0.42	-8.000** ±2.04	-39.667** ±0.64	12.333** ±0.50	-62.667** ±2.24	-17.667** ±0.41	D
Azad x K-750	62.000** ±0.21	-1.000** ±0.35	-52.833** ±1.15	-42.000** ±1.10	-0.500** ±0.38	72.333** ±1.78	-15.667** ±0.62	-14.667** ±0.62	11.667** ±1.10	21.000** ±0.55	D
Grains weight/spike (g)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	3.007** ±0.00	0.002** ±0.00	-2.529** ±0.01	-2.647** ±0.01	-0.198** ±0.01	2.403** ±0.02	-0.076** ±0.02	0.320** ±0.01	2.891** ±0.02	1.323** ±0.01	D
DL-88 x K-890	1.804** ±0.00	-0.555** ±0.01	0.956** ±0.03	1.393** ±0.03	-0.468** ±0.01	-0.962** ±0.04	-0.684** ±0.01	0.253** ±0.02	-1.824** ±0.03	-0.696** ±0.01	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	1.908** ±0.01	-1.172** ±0.02	-2.484** ±0.05	-1.056** ±0.05	-0.659** ±0.02	2.865** ±0.08	-1.564** ±0.02	-0.245** ±0.04	-0.753** ±0.05	0.528** ±0.02	D
Azad x K-750	2.811** ±0.00	-0.435** ±0.01	-2.342** ±0.03	-2.407** ±0.03	-0.230** ±0.01	3.903** ±0.05	-0.978** ±0.01	-0.518** ±0.03	0.911** ±0.03	1.204** ±0.01	D
Days to maturity											
NDB-943xNDB1173	136.000** ±0.12	1.000** ±0.17	1.667** ±0.58	6.000** ±0.55	1.333** ±0.21	-7.333** ±0.91	2.000** ±0.36	-0.667* ±0.31	-4.667** ±0.58	-3.000** ±0.27	D
DL-88 x K-890	138.333** ±0.16	0.333** ±0.26	11.000** ±0.85	6.000** ±0.83	2.333** ±0.30	-23.333** ±1.29	11.000** ±0.56	6.333** ±0.30	11.333** ±0.78	-3.000** ±0.41	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	139.333** ±0.12	5.000** ±0.27	-3.000** ±0.78	-6.000** ±0.72	3.333** ±0.36	0.667 ±1.30	6.000** ±0.53	-0.667** ±0.53	11.333** ±0.75	3.000** ±0.36	--
Azad x K-750	133.000** ±0.10	1.667** ±0.22	12.333** ±0.65	15.333** ±0.62	0.667** ±0.27	-28.667** ±1.08	7.333** ±0.46	6.000** ±0.36	-2.000** ±0.61	-7.667** ±0.31	D
Harvest index (%)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	35.383** ±0.20	-1.760** ±0.34	-6.293** ±1.11	-7.467** ±1.07	-5.280** ±0.40	14.760** ±1.70	-8.927** ±0.69	1.633** ±0.52	0.173 ±1.01	3.733** ±0.53	D

Inheritance of Some Quantitative Characters in Barley

DL-88 x K-890	47.910** ±0.15	-5.320** ±0.27	-29.947** ±0.86	-37.013** ±0.81	-5.587** ±0.36	56.920** ±1.36	-15.540** ±0.67	-4.367** ±0.36	17.107** ±0.83	18.507** ±0.41	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	36.183** ±0.14	-2.433** ±0.27	1.707** ±0.83	-3.867** ±0.77	-3.723** ±0.39	1.520 ±1.36	-2.550** ±0.65	4.897** ±0.46	6.213** ±0.80	1.933** ±0.39	--
Azad x K-750	43.080** ±0.10	4.947** ±0.29	-0.035 ±0.75	-1.200 ±0.72	7.788** ±0.34	9.310** ±1.32	3.733** ±0.39	-11.843** ±0.59	-6.910** ±0.60	0.600 ±0.36	D
Grain yield/plant (g)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	23.000** ±0.13	-0.857** ±0.23	-8.260** ±0.73	-11.953** ±0.49	-0.450** ±0.07	25.133** ±3.21	-7.040** ±0.41	-6.140** ±0.40	-1.227 ±0.66	5.977** ±0.35	D
DL-88 x K-890	16.767** ±0.05	-3.927** ±0.10	-7.135** ±0.32	-8.813** ±0.29	-5.048** ±0.14	22.137** ±0.53	-11.710** ±0.27	-1.613** ±0.16	-4.510** ±0.35	4.407** ±0.14	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	12.667** ±0.05	-6.067** ±0.08	-3.028** ±0.28	-4.533** ±0.25	-5.775** ±0.15	15.257** ±0.46	-11.137** ±0.23	0.413* ±0.20	-6.190** ±0.33	2.267** ±0.12	D
Azad x K-750	21.540** ±0.05	0.247 ±0.14	-3.510** ±0.37	-5.187** ±0.36	0.937** ±0.16	18.940** ±0.64	-5.940** ±0.15	-7.813** ±0.29	-8.567** ±0.28	2.593** ±0.18	D
Grain size (L:B ratio)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	3.325** ±0.00	-0.639** ±0.01	-2.814** ±0.03	-3.281** ±0.02	-0.318** ±0.01	3.450** ±0.04	-0.402** ±0.01	0.233** ±0.02	3.112** ±0.03	1.641** ±0.01	D
DL-88 x K-890	3.633** ±0.00	0.651** ±0.00	-1.287** ±0.01	-1.503** ±0.00	0.774** ±0.00	2.097** ±0.01	0.477** ±0.01	-1.071** ±0.00	0.909** ±0.01	0.751** ±0.00	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	3.308** ±0.00	-1.031** ±0.00	-0.255** ±0.00	-0.413** ±0.00	-1.169** ±0.00	3.209** ±0.00	-2.567** ±0.00	-0.229** ±0.00	-2.383** ±0.00	0.207** ±0.00	D
Azad x K-750	3.903** ±0.00	-0.447** ±0.00	-2.356** ±0.00	-2.495** ±0.00	-0.129** ±0.00	2.365** ±0.01	-0.064** ±0.01	0.193** ±0.00	2.624** ±0.01	1.247** ±0.00	D
1000-grain weight (g)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	42.007** ±0.01	1.147** ±0.05	-7.732** ±0.24	-10.347** ±0.12	-0.012 ±0.18	12.837** ±0.48	-1.257** ±0.14	-1.233** ±0.38	7.857** ±0.43	5.173** ±0.05	D
DL-88 x K-890	40.113** ±0.09	-8.293** ±0.27	5.542** ±0.80	12.600** ±0.65	-5.978** ±0.47	3.730* ±1.47	-14.143** ±0.63	-2.187** ±0.79	-28.930** ±1.01	-6.300** ±0.33	C
DWR-57 x PL-762	60.357** ±0.22	9.043** ±0.54	-74.553** ±1.41	-74.953** ±1.36	6.927** ±0.55	100.667** ±2.39	-5.930** ±0.89	-19.783** ±0.75	49.240** ±1.06	37.477** ±0.69	D
Azad x K-750	45.357** ±0.08	-8.293** ±0.44	-5.732** ±0.95	-13.840** ±0.94	-6.555** ±0.45	25.077** ±1.82	-12.173** ±0.84	0.937* ±0.37	2.603** ±0.45	6.920** ±0.47	D
Protein content (%)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	9.750** ±0.00	-1.067** ±0.01	2.183** ±0.04	1.467** ±0.03	-1.217** ±0.03	-2.300** ±0.07	-0.800** ±0.03	1.633** ±0.05	-0.633** ±0.06	-0.733** ±0.07	D

DL-88 x K-890	9.167** ±0.02	0.433** ±0.01	2.042** ±0.07	2.267** ±0.07	-0.192** ±0.02	-6.750** ±0.09	2.050** ±0.03	2.433** ±0.03	2.217** ±0.08	-1.133** ±0.03	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	11.150** ±0.00	0.400** ±0.01	-2.200** ±0.03	-2.800** ±0.03	0.750** ±0.01	5.800** ±0.05	-0.750** ±0.02	-2.250** ±0.02	-0.200** ±0.04	1.400** ±0.01	D
Azad x K-750	9.550** ±0.00	1.767** ±0.01	-2.558** ±0.03	-0.333** ±0.03	1.042** ±0.01	4.717** ±0.06	-1.150** ±0.03	-3.233** ±0.02	-4.050** ±0.03	0.167** ±0.01	D
Grain hardness (kg pressure)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	11.600** ±0.02	-0.800** ±0.03	4.900** ±0.12	4.800** ±0.11	-0.100** ±0.05	-5.800** ±0.18	0.400** ±0.07	0.600** ±0.07	-3.800** ±0.12	-2.400** ±0.05	D
DL-88 x K-890	13.600** ±0.02	-2.533** ±0.06	-10.767** ±0.15	-10.667** ±0.14	-3.033** ±0.06	15.933** ±0.26	-5.667** ±0.11	0.400** ±0.07	5.400** ±0.12	5.333** ±0.07	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	10.600** ±0.02	-1.000** ±0.03	9.700** ±0.12	8.400** ±0.11	-0.900** ±0.05	-16.200** ±0.18	3.000** ±0.07	4.800** ±0.07	-0.600** ±0.12	-4.200** ±0.06	D
Azad x K-750	12.000** ±0.02	2.000** ±0.03	-6.600** ±0.12	-7.200** ±0.11	2.400** ±0.05	6.000** ±0.18	3.000** ±0.07	-1.800** ±0.07	8.400** ±0.12	3.600** ±0.05	D
Amylose content (%)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	10.250** ±0.00	0.217** ±0.01	1.025** ±0.04	0.833** ±0.031	0.125 ±0.02	-8.450** ±0.07	3.933** ±0.03	3.683** ±0.04	6.783** ±0.05	-0.417** ±0.01	D
DL-88 x K-890	9.750** ±0.00	1.433** ±0.01	3.720** ±0.03	2.467** ±0.03	1.587** ±0.01	-5.040** ±0.05	2.873** ±0.02	-0.300** ±0.02	0.107** ±0.03	-1.233** ±0.01	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	9.487** ±0.01	-0.220** ±0.01	4.547** ±0.03	3.480** ±0.03	-0.163** ±0.01	-8.373** ±0.05	2.283** ±0.02	2.610** ±0.02	1.413** ±0.04	-1.740** ±0.01	D
Azad x K-750	10.613** ±0.01	-0.173** ±0.01	1.530** ±0.03	0.827** ±0.03	0.330** ±0.01	-6.580** ±0.04	3.207** ±0.02	2.547** ±0.02	4.927** ±0.03	-0.413** ±0.01	D

Inheritance of Some Quantitative Characters in Barley

Table -2: Simple scaling tests, gene effects and type of epistasis for 16 metric traits under saline sodic soil

Characters	Gene effects											Scales				Type of epistasis
	m	d	h	g	i	j	l	A	B	C	D					
Initial seed germination (%) in field																
NDB-943xNDB1173	78.887** ±0.20	2.223** ±0.47	13.887** ±1.45	8.887** ±1.25	3.890** ±0.67	3.333 ±2.52	-2.220* ±1.00	-10.000** ±1.21	-21.107** ±1.66	-4.443** ±0.63	--					
DL-88 x K-890	83.330** ±0.71	-4.447** ±0.33	-12.222** ±3.03	-13.333** ±2.91	-3.335** ±0.74	24.443** ±3.55	-8.890** ±1.31	-2.220* ±1.00	2.223 ±3.29	6.667** ±1.46	D					
DWR-57 x PL-762	82.220** ±0.74	-4.443** ±0.74	-3.893 ±3.36	-4.447 ±3.31	-6.110** ±0.91	21.107** ±4.37	-14.440** ±1.48	-2.220 ±1.13	-12.213** ±3.18	2.223 ±1.65	--					
Azad x K-750	83.330** ±0.35	1.110* ±0.47	6.110** ±1.87	2.220 ±1.70	-1.557* ±0.70	-3.327 ±2.83	-0.003 ±1.04	1.110 ±1.24	-1.113 ±2.10	-1.110* ±0.55	--					
Plant height (cm)																
NDB-943xNDB1173	74.093** ±0.15	0.437 ±0.29	-4.825** ±0.92	-5.167** ±0.85	0.498 ±0.41	-3.017* ±1.48	4.590** ±0.51	3.593** ±0.69	13.350** ±0.92	2.583** ±0.43	C					
DL-88 x K-890	82.000** ±0.13	-4.773** ±0.20	-18.152** ±0.71	-17.040** ±0.67	-1.445** ±0.28	5.503** ±1.07	4.323** ±0.33	7.213** ±0.45	28.577** ±0.70	8.520** ±0.34	D					
DWR-57 x PL-762	70.000** ±1.18	-0.233 ±0.26	-31.683** ±4.75	-31.533** ±4.75	0.183 ±0.36	27.233** ±4.86	2.333** ±0.62	1.967** ±0.36	35.833** ±4.74	15.767** ±2.37	D					
Azad x K-750	71.967** ±0.18	-3.973** ±0.24	-6.767** ±0.95	-10.187** ±0.87	-1.193** ±0.34	12.227** ±1.44	-2.213** ±0.49	0.173 ±0.64	8.147** ±1.06	5.093** ±0.44	D					
Number of effective tillers																
NDB-943xNDB1173	9.267** ±0.06	-1.003** ±0.11	-1.457** ±0.34	-2.940** ±0.32	0.133 ±0.13	9.127** ±0.54	-2.960** ±0.20	-3.227** ±0.20	-3.247** ±0.33	1.470** ±0.16	D					
DL-88 x K-890	9.753** ±0.04	-0.100 ±0.08	-6.057** ±0.26	-6.467** ±0.23	0.930** ±0.11	9.660** ±0.43	-0.667** ±0.20	-2.527** ±0.16	3.273** ±0.29	3.233** ±0.12	D					
DWR-57 x PL-762	10.933** ±0.03	-0.993** ±0.12	-4.243** ±0.27	-5.347** ±0.24	-0.577** ±0.13	13.900** ±0.51	-4.853** ±0.18	-3.700** ±0.24	-3.207** ±0.26	2.673** ±0.12	D					
Azad x K-750	9.733** ±0.07	-0.667** ±0.06	8.983** ±0.32	7.733** ±0.30	-0.417** ±0.12	-11.033** ±0.44	1.233** ±0.23	2.067** ±0.13	-4.433** ±0.37	-3.867** ±0.15	D					
Peduncle length (cm)																
NDB-943xNDB1173	9.000** ±0.05	-3.533** ±0.06	-10.983** ±0.29	-9.733** ±0.24	-1.450** ±0.12	7.300** ±0.44	-0.233 ±0.17	2.667** ±0.23	12.167** ±0.37	4.867** ±0.12	D					
DL-88 x K-890	5.433** ±0.02	0.167 ±0.11	0.083 ±0.28	1.933** ±0.24	1.017** ±0.15	-4.567** ±0.55	2.333** ±0.24	0.300 ±0.24	0.700* ±0.32	-0.967** ±0.12	D					

DWR-57 x PL-762	5.333** ±0.04	-3.233** ±0.07	1.950** ±0.25	1.133** ±0.22	-2.883** ±0.11	-0.700 ±0.39	-3.100** ±0.15	2.667** ±0.18	-1.567** ±0.27	-0.567** ±0.11	--
Azad x K-750	5.667** ±0.03	3.167** ±0.05	8.817** ±0.19	6.733** ±0.16	4.217** ±0.09	10.233** ±0.33	-4.267** ±0.16	-12.700** ±0.15	-23.700** ±0.26	-3.367** ±0.08	C
Spike length (cm)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	8.800** ±0.03	-0.167** ±0.06	1.733** ±0.17	1.667** ±0.16	0.433** ±0.08	-4.000** ±0.29	1.600** ±0.12	0.733** ±0.10	0.667** ±0.16	-0.833** ±0.08	D
DL-88 x K-890	8.900** ±0.04	0.767** ±0.06	-0.950** ±0.21	-1.533** ±0.20	0.650** ±0.09	1.100** ±0.33	0.867** ±0.10	-0.433** ±0.15	1.967** ±0.21	0.767** ±0.10	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	10.533** ±0.05	0.900** ±0.06	-7.050** ±0.25	-8.067** ±0.24	0.483** ±0.07	18.367** ±0.33	-4.667** ±0.11	-5.633** ±0.07	-2.233** ±0.22	4.033** ±0.12	D
Azad x K-750	10.367** ±0.07	-0.367** ±0.09	-4.708** ±0.39	-6.600** ±0.36	0.125 ±0.12	15.283** ±0.59	-4.217** ±0.18	-4.467** ±0.25	-2.083** ±0.44	3.300** ±0.18	D
Chlorophyll content (mg/100g)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	2.247** ±0.00	0.070** ±0.00	-0.597** ±0.02	-0.713** ±0.02	0.027 ±0.01	1.140** ±0.03	-0.187** ±0.01	-0.240** ±0.01	0.287** ±0.02	0.357** ±0.01	D
DL-88 x K-890	1.733** ±0.00	0.160** ±0.00	-0.710** ±0.02	-0.773** ±0.02	0.203** ±0.01	1.127** ±0.03	0.027** ±0.01	-0.380** ±0.01	0.420** ±0.02	0.387** ±0.01	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	2.543** ±0.00	-0.140** ±0.01	-0.563** ±0.02	-0.693** ±0.02	-0.070** ±0.01	1.273** ±0.05	-0.360** ±0.02	-0.220** ±0.01	0.113** ±0.01	0.347** ±0.01	D
Azad x K-750	2.110** ±0.01	-0.107** ±0.01	-0.303** ±0.03	-0.453** ±0.03	-0.057** ±0.01	0.567** ±0.05	-0.113** ±0.02	0.71** ±0.21	0.340** ±0.03	0.227** ±0.02	D
Number of grains/spike											
NDB-943xNDB1173	51.000** ±0.21	2.667** ±0.22	51.333** ±1.03	45.333** ±0.96	0.052 ±0.04	-53.333** ±1.43	4.000** ±0.62	4.000** ±0.47	-37.333** ±1.11	-22.667** ±0.48	D
DL-88 x K-890	44.333** ±0.16	-2.000** ±0.47	20.833** ±1.23	20.000** ±1.14	-3.167** ±0.59	-19.000** ±2.20	-3.667** ±1.01	2.667** ±0.74	-21.000** ±1.13	-10.000** ±0.57	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	32.667** ±0.27	-35.000** ±0.36	19.500** ±1.33	34.000** ±1.29	-26.833** ±0.41	-8.333** ±1.90	-39.667** ±0.74	14.000** ±0.49	-59.667** ±1.23	-17.000** ±0.65	D
Azad x K-750	61.000** ±0.11	1.000** ±0.27	-52.500** ±0.88	-42.000** ±0.70	1.833** ±0.36	78.333** ±1.60	-16.333** ±0.70	-20.000** ±0.70	5.667** ±1.15	21.000** ±0.35	D
Grains weight/spike (g)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	2.969** ±0.01	-0.001** ±0.00	-2.763** ±0.03	-2.876** ±0.03	-0.124** ±0.00	2.646** ±0.03	-0.009* ±0.00	0.239** ±0.00	3.106** ±0.03	1.438** ±0.01	D
DL-88 x K-890	1.759** ±0.01	-0.567** ±0.00	1.062** ±0.06	1.476** ±0.06	-0.479** ±0.01	-0.945** ±0.06	-0.745** ±0.01	0.213** ±0.01	-2.007** ±0.06	-0.738** ±0.03	D

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DWR-57 x PL-762	1.909** ±0.01	-1.223** ±0.01	-2.258** ±0.05	-0.875** ±0.04	-0.748** ±0.01	2.447** ±0.06	-1.534** ±0.02	-0.039* ±0.02	-0.698** ±0.04	0.437** ±0.02	D
Azad x K-750	2.804** ±0.00	-0.425** ±0.01	-2.053** ±0.03	-2.420** ±0.02	-0.424** ±0.01	3.361** ±0.05	-0.895** ±0.01	-0.047* ±0.02	1.479** ±0.02	1.210** ±0.01	D
Days to maturity											
NDB-943xNDB1173	134.000** ±0.11	-2.000** ±0.17	5.667** ±0.58	12.000** ±0.55	-1.667** ±0.21	-15.333** ±0.91	0.171 ±0.10	3.333** ±0.31	-8.667** ±0.58	-6.000** ±0.27	D
DL-88 x K-890	139.000** ±0.10	-0.333* ±0.14	3.833** ±0.57	0.667 ±0.51	1.833** ±0.24	-11.667** ±0.87	7.333** ±0.44	3.667** ±0.30	10.333** ±0.66	-0.333 ±0.26	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	137.000** ±0.12	6.000** ±0.17	1.500* ±0.59	1.89* ±0.90	3.500** ±0.23	-7.000** ±0.92	7.000** ±0.36	3.23** ±0.50	7.000** ±0.61	5.30** ±0.79	D
Azad x K-750	135.000** ±0.12	2.000** ±0.17	4.500** ±0.59	8.000** ±0.55	0.500** ±0.23	-25.000** ±0.92	9.000** ±0.36	8.000** ±0.36	9.000** ±0.61	-4.000** ±0.27	D
Harvest index (%)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	32.620** ±0.13	-6.387** ±0.26	13.620** ±0.80	3.840** ±0.74	-8.940** ±0.30	2.267 ±1.32	-11.993** ±0.58	5.887** ±0.41	-9.947** ±0.81	-1.920** ±0.37	--
DL-88 x K-890	32.867** ±0.17	0.053 ±0.31	5.332** ±0.97	6.507** ±0.92	1.992** ±0.42	5.523** ±1.54	-4.023** ±0.61	-8.007** ±0.59	-18.537** ±0.92	-3.253** ±0.46	C
DWR-57 x PL-762	32.630** ±0.09	-2.360** ±0.35	-3.727** ±0.84	6.187** ±0.80	-1.113** ±0.41	4.493** ±1.55	-6.453** ±0.72	-4.227** ±0.45	-16.867** ±0.65	-3.093** ±0.40	D
Azad x K-750	38.973** ±0.09	-5.163** ±0.13	-5.152** ±0.49	-10.953** ±0.45	-4.858** ±0.17	39.850** ±0.77	-19.307** ±0.27	-9.590** ±0.30	-17.943** ±0.51	5.477** ±0.23	D
Grain yield/plant (g)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	21.207** ±0.08	-3.833** ±0.16	-0.857** ±0.49	-4.227** ±0.46	-3.163** ±0.18	5.153** ±0.80	-3.627** ±0.34	2.700** ±0.25	3.300** ±0.49	2.113** ±0.23	D
DL-88 x K-890	16.433** ±0.08	-3.513** ±0.22	-2.355** ±0.61	-1.160* ±0.56	-0.725** ±0.29	11.323** ±1.07	-5.807** ±0.47	-4.357** ±0.42	-9.003** ±0.60	0.580** ±0.28	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	18.507** ±0.15	-10.227** ±0.24	-22.112** ±0.79	-14.773** ±0.77	-8.905** ±0.26	35.357** ±1.19	-19.197** ±0.36	-1.387** ±0.43	-5.810** ±0.70	7.387** ±0.38	D
Azad x K-750	23.387** ±0.06	-5.040** ±0.08	-1.463** ±0.030	-2.693** ±0.28	-4.790** ±0.12	11.380** ±0.46	-9.133** ±0.18	0.447* ±0.18	-5.993** ±0.32	1.347** ±0.14	D
Grain size (L:B ratio)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	3.343** ±0.00	-0.599** ±0.01	-2.871** ±0.02	-3.339** ±0.02	-0.276** ±0.01	3.483** ±0.04	-0.348** ±0.01	0.204** ±0.02	3.195** ±0.03	1.670** ±0.01	D
DL-88 x K-890	3.559** ±0.00	0.639** ±0.00	-1.163** ±0.02	-1.216** ±0.01	0.723** ±0.01	1.337** ±0.03	0.663** ±0.01	-0.783** ±0.03	1.095** ±0.03	0.608** ±0.00	D

DWR-57 x PL-762	3.305** ±0.00	-1.031** ±0.00	-0.249** ±0.00	-0.414** ±0.00	-1.178** ±0.00	3.201** ±0.00	-2.571** ±0.00	-0.216** ±0.00	-2.373** ±0.00	0.207** ±0.00	D
Azad x K-750	3.909** ±0.00	-0.452** ±0.00	-2.385** ±0.00	-2.531** ±0.00	-0.127** ±0.00	2.391** ±0.01	-0.057** ±0.00	0.197** ±0.00	2.670** ±0.01	1.265** ±0.00	D
1000-grain weight (g)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	42.137** ±0.03	1.473** ±0.13	-7.272** ±0.45	-7.787** ±0.29	-0.105 ±0.31	-7.603** ±0.89	7.590** ±0.37	7.800** ±0.58	23.177** ±0.71	3.893** ±0.15	C
DL-88 x K-890	38.373** ±0.16	-8.260** ±0.24	8.383** ±0.84	13.373** ±0.80	-6.570** ±0.27	-10.980** ±1.26	-7.767** ±0.55	5.373** ±0.30	-15.767** ±0.83	-6.687** ±0.40	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	47.087** ±0.09	6.633** ±0.27	-33.537** ±0.67	-22.413** ±0.66	5.817** ±0.29	16.567** ±1.18	8.740** ±0.50	-2.893** ±0.31	28.260** ±0.44	11.207** ±0.33	D
Azad x K-750	45.300** ±0.03	-2.073** ±0.10	-13.187** ±0.27	-17.800** ±0.25	-1.327** ±0.12	23.280** ±0.49	-4.067** ±0.11	-1.413** ±0.25	12.320** ±0.24	8.900** ±0.13	D
Protein content (%)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	9.640** ±0.01	-1.063** ±0.01	2.053** ±0.04	1.367** ±0.03	-1.197** ±0.02	-1.947** ±0.07	-0.907** ±0.03	1.487** ±0.04	-0.787** ±0.06	-0.683** ±0.01	D
DL-88 x K-890	9.283** ±0.01	0.217** ±0.05	2.318** ±0.12	2.633** ±0.10	-0.335** ±0.05	-7.423** ±0.20	2.060** ±0.04	2.730** ±0.09	2.157** ±0.06	-1.317** ±0.05	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	11.050** ±0.00	0.433** ±0.01	-2.317** ±0.03	-2.867** ±0.03	0.783** ±0.01	5.833** ±0.05	-0.700** ±0.02	-2.267** ±0.02	-0.100** ±0.03	1.433** ±0.01	D
Azad x K-750	9.500** ±0.00	1.750** ±0.01	-2.777** ±0.04	-0.500** ±0.03	1.110** ±0.02	4.553** ±0.07	-0.917** ±0.04	-3.137** ±0.03	-3.553** ±0.05	0.250** ±0.02	D
Grain hardness (kg pressure)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	11.400** ±0.02	-0.333** ±0.04	4.233** ±0.14	3.867** ±0.12	0.167** ±0.06	-4.200** ±0.23	0.333** ±0.08	0.220 ±0.10	-3.533** ±0.14	-1.933** ±0.06	D
DL-88 x K-890	13.800** ±0.02	-1.600** ±0.03	-10.500** ±0.12	-10.400** ±0.11	-2.100** ±0.05	15.400** ±0.18	-4.600** ±0.07	-0.400** ±0.07	5.400** ±0.12	5.200** ±0.05	D
DWR-57 x PL-762	10.200** ±0.02	-1.000** ±0.03	9.767** ±0.11	8.400** ±0.11	-0.800** ±0.05	-14.867** ±0.18	2.433** ±0.07	4.033** ±0.07	-1.933** ±0.11	-4.200** ±0.05	D
Azad x K-750	11.800** ±0.02	1.633** ±0.03	-6.033** ±0.12	-6.467** ±0.10	1.867** ±0.05	4.867** ±0.18	2.667** ±0.09	-1.067** ±0.06	8.067** ±0.13	3.233** ±0.05	D
Amylose content (%)											
NDB-943xNDB1173	10.200** ±0.02	0.117** ±0.02	0.742** ±0.10	0.633** ±0.09	0.025 ±0.03	-8.683** ±0.14	4.050** ±0.06	4.000** ±0.06	7.417** ±0.12	-0.317** ±0.05	D
DL-88 x K-890	9.900** ±0.01	1.400** ±0.02	3.275** ±0.06	2.200** ±0.05	1.575** ±0.02	-4.550** ±0.09	2.750** ±0.05	-0.400** ±0.03	0.150* ±0.06	-1.100** ±0.03	D

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DWR-57 x PL-762	9.500** ±0.01	-0.183** ±0.01	3.192** ±0.05	3.167** ±0.05	-0.158** ±0.02	-10.383** ±0.08	3.450** ±0.03	3.767** ±0.03	4.050** ±0.05	-1.583** ±0.03	D
Azad x K-750	10.550** ±0.05	-0.200** ±0.02	1.343** ±0.05	0.547** ±0.04	0.330** ±0.02	-5.873** ±0.09	2.993** ±0.03	2.333** ±0.04	4.780** ±0.05	-0.273** ±0.02	D

*, ** Significant at 5% and 1% level of probability, respectively; C = complementary epistasis and D = Duplicate epistasis.

Table- 3: joint scaling test for 16 characters of four crosses under Normal and saline sodic soil

Characters	Chi-square values											
	Normal soil						Saline sodic soil					
	Cross I	Cross II	Cross III	Cross IV	Cross I	Cross II	Cross III	Cross IV	Cross I	Cross II	Cross III	Cross IV
Initial seed germination (%) in field	0.075	0.422	3.267	2.523	1.751	2.805	1.805	2.043	1.805	2.805	1.805	2.043
Plant height (cm)	3.385	69.220**	0.268	40.758**	2.964	25.696**	3.737	12.520**	3.737	25.696**	3.737	12.520**
Number of effective tillers	0.238	16.869**	12.679**	0.613	1.023	69.447**	19.008**	5.431*	19.008**	69.447**	19.008**	5.431*
Peduncle length (cm)	70.325**	60.526**	1.240	263.512**	154.509**	36.916**	3.257	9.262**	36.916**	3.257	3.257	9.262**
Spike length (cm)	0.396	0.264	3.523	2.042	31.740**	3.649	53.827**	1.106	3.649	53.827**	3.649	1.106
Chlorophyll content (mg/100g)	27.348**	17.998**	53.184**	68.353**	17.957**	34.794**	34.306**	26.288**	34.794**	34.306**	34.306**	26.288**
Number of grains/spike	44.630**	1.125	15.308**	1.724	0.000	11.065**	19.187**	13.462**	11.065**	19.187**	19.187**	13.462**
Grains weight/spike (g)	521.332**	172.820**	465.870**	260.326**	2407.624**	249.771**	385.923**	7.509**	249.771**	385.923**	385.923**	7.509**
Days to maturity	6.995**	52.581**	0.263	5.981*	6.995**	1.699	0.000	4.620*	1.699	0.000	0.000	4.620*
Harvest index (%)	49.053**	1.280	0.008	2.767	2.938	0.006	10.794**	6.471*	0.006	10.794**	10.794**	6.471*
Grain yield/plant (g)	2.896	118.102**	5.170*	35.335**	25.003**	4.293*	205.781**	8.656**	4.293*	205.781**	205.781**	8.656**
Grain size (L:B ratio)	540.761**	1400.493**	7018.194**	1425.036**	528.376**	37.151**	255720.375**	2346.878**	37.151**	255720.375**	255720.375**	2346.878**
1000-grain weight (g)	0.004	0.725	159.070**	126.702**	0.142	76.390**	66.432**	113.549**	76.390**	66.432**	66.432**	113.549**
Protein content (%)	37.799**	80.991**	2054.500**	115.961**	30.760**	45.145**	2061.345**	206.686**	45.145**	2061.345**	2061.345**	206.686**
Grain hardness (kg pressure)	4.621*	262.518**	10.500**	168.006**	9.344**	262.500**	41.998**	34.297**	262.500**	41.998**	41.998**	34.297**
Amylose content (%)	17.290	477.487**	32.628**	774.986**	0.506	93.560**	4.201*	172.709**	93.560**	4.201*	4.201*	172.709**

*, ** Significant at 5% and 1% level of probability, respectively.

saline sodic soil). Thus, these characters in different cross combinations as stated above were utilized for further statistical analyses.

Significance of epistasis was detected by either one or both type of scaling tests in four crosses for all the characters under both (normal and saline sodic soil) condition (Table 1, 2 & 3). Out of 64 cases (4 crosses, 16 characters in both condition, all cases showed significance of epistasis which was detected by either one or both type of scaling tests in normal and saline sodic soil for all the characters. Both tests, simple and joint scaling tests led to similar inferences in respect of presence or absence of epistasis in majority of cases for sixteen characters in four crosses in normal and saline sodic soils. Out of 128 comparisons, forty results of two type of tests differed across the sixteen characters in four crosses under both conditions. Presence of epistasis by simple scaling test with absence by joint scaling test was observed in 40 cases, while, its opposite case i.e. absence of epistasis by simple scaling test with presence of epistasis by joint scaling test was not found. Importance of epistasis in inheritance of yield and yield components in barley has been reported by Singh *et al* (1988) and Jezowski *et al* (2000).

The generation mean analysis revealed importance of additive (d) and or dominance (h) gene effects as well as one or more of the epistatic interactions (i, j, l) for all the sixteen traits of four crosses in normal and saline sodic soils. However, nature and magnitude of gene effects and epistatic interactions for a character exhibited considerable variation across the four crosses under two soil situations.

The significance of additive gene effects for most of the traits in four crosses under both soil situations suggested that substantial improvement in yield status can still be achieved in barley by using breeding procedures exploiting fixable components of genetic variance leading to development of pure line varieties in barley under both soil situations. Significance of dominance gene effects and

epistatic interactions for most of the traits in four crosses under both soil situations indicated that exploitation of heterosis through hybrid varieties may be explored as potential alternative in future. Lone (1985), Prakash *et al* (2005) and Singh *et al* (1988) recorded importance of additive as well as non-additive gene effects for plant height. In absence of exploitation of heterosis through commercial hybrids, non-additive gene effects may be utilized for facilitating development of pure line cultivars by involving population improvement methods.

Duplicate type of epistasis was detected for plant height, number of effective tillers, peduncle length, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/spike, grains weight/spike, days to maturity, harvest index, grain yield/plant, grain size, 1000-grain weight, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content in cross NDB 943 x NDB 1173, plant height, number of effective tillers, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/spike, grains weight/spike, days to maturity, harvest index, grain yield/plant, grain size, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content in cross DL 88 x K 890, plant height, number of effective tillers, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/spike, grains weight/spike, grain yield/plant, grain size, 1000 grain weight, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content in cross DWR 57 x PL 762, for plant height, number of effective tillers, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/spike, grains weight/spike, days to maturity, grain yield/plant, grain size, 1000-grain weight, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content in cross Azad x K 750 under normal soil.

In saline sodic soils, duplicate type of epistasis was detected for number of effective tillers, peduncle length, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/spike, grains weight/spike, days to maturity, grain yield/plant, grain size, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content in cross NDB 943 x NDB 1173, initial seed germination, plant height, number of effective tillers, peduncle length, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/

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spike, grains weight/spike, days to maturity, grain yield/plant, grain size, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content in cross DL 88 x K 890, plant height, number of effective tillers, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/spike, grains weight/spike, grain yield/plant, grain size, 1000-grain weight, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content in cross DWR 57 x PL 762, for plant height, number of effective tillers, spike length, chlorophyll content, number of grains/spike, grains weight/spike, days to maturity, grain yield/plant, grain size, 1000-grain weight, protein content, grain hardness and amylose content in cross Azad x K 750 .

Further, Out of 128 , all the crosses showing epistasis for different traits revealed manifestation of duplicate type of epistasis in 108 cases while, 09 cases showed complementary type of epistasis over the both soil conditions. Thus, presence of duplicate epistasis slows down the selection procedure of additive and or non-additive genetic variance (Gupta, 2005).

CONCLUSION

It may be suggested that the normal breeding methods would not solely work. Some forms of recurrent selection namely diallel selective mating or bi parental mating in early segregating generations might prove to be effective approaches. The restricted recurrent selection of desirable segregates followed by selection might also be a useful breeding strategy for exploitation of both additive as well as non-additive type of gene action (Chakraborty et al, 2010). It is apparent that

information obtained will help in improving the existing barley varieties for its yield and quality traits.

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Innovations Developed by Farmers in Erode District of Tamil Nadu

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted in Erode district of Tamil Nadu in order to identify the grass root level farmer led innovations by using personal interview method and observations in order to know location specificity of the innovations. A total of nine innovations were selected for this study namely land preparation, cultivation aspects, harvesting technology and varietal development in acid lime, organic liquid manure preparation and pest management. All the innovators were personally interviewed to know the uniqueness and its special features. This study revealed that, two innovations on land preparation machineries having the potential of covering 2 ha in a day, other two innovations in relation to cultivation aspects reduced the cultivation cost on an average of Rs. 2,800/- and Rs. 5,000/- per ha. Two more innovations on harvesting technology were used for timely harvesting and saved Rs. 6,250/- and Rs. 18,750/-ha. The average yield potential of acid lime variety was up to 2000 fruits /tree / season. By adopting liquid manure preparation technique and pest management technique, a farmer saved Rs. 12,000/- and Rs. 2,500/- against the purchase of fertilizers and pesticides, respectively.

Key Words: Innovation, Indigenous knowledge, Liquid manure, Machinery.

INTRODUCTION

Development of agricultural sector is driven by innovations at all levels. In the ancient times when there was no formal system of research and documentation, even then the people used to devise some modes in order to preserve such things, such peoples who developed these technologies passed away like “unsung heroes” but their innovations are still being practiced under the domain of Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK). Indigenous knowledge requires very low external inputs and are suitable for local conditions and sustainable in nature, moreover, these are environment friendly than the modern technologies. Therefore, it is necessary to focus on documenting and validating the various innovations developed by the local people or farmers at the grass root level (Ramdatt *et al*, 2014).

Until recently, little attention was given to the farmer led innovations, including technological, management and institutional. It is now realized that there are numerous innovations, which yielded

higher return and made farming more economical and sustainable. Local innovation refers to dynamics of indigenous knowledge i.e., knowledge that grows within a social group, incorporating learning from own experiences over generations but also external knowledge internalized within the local ways of thinking and doing (Brigidletty *et al*, 2012).

Farmer innovations are also a way of life for the resource poor farmers who are being challenged by ever changing environmental, policy and market situations. Farmer led innovations in developing countries would lead to increase in production, thereby reducing the poverty among the rural people (Spielman, 2009 and Mariam *et al*, 2011). Farm innovation has always been happening but quite slowly and has seldom been recognized by communities and scientist also. The innovation process at farmers could be speed up giving opportunity to bring in their ideas and skills. Krishi Vigyan Kendra - MYRADA, Erode district is in the process of identifying and documenting

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such innovations in collaboration with farming community in order to properly validate and popularize the innovations among the farming communities through various extension methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The case study method was employed to undertake this study. These cases were selected purposively on the basis of the data base compiled by the Krishi Vigyan Kendra. Out of various innovations documented by Kendra, a total of nine cases namely clod breaker, pebble stone remover, acid lime variety, tapioca sett cutter, rotary power weeder cum ridger, fermented castor solution trap, organic liquid manure preparation technique, turmeric harvester and groundnut pod stripper were selected for the study. All nine innovators were personally interviewed vis a vis attributes of selected grass root innovations. In addition to the personal interview method, the observation method was also used for recording of attributed of the selected innovations. Data were collected twice with a gap of six months.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Clod Breaker

Mr. G RSakthivel hailed in Talavadi block of Erode district doing farming for the past 30 years. Ragi was the major crop cultivated in this region for that fine field preparation is required. Normally the crops are sown immediately after receiving the monsoon. Due to the improper field preparation, the farmers couldn't get the optimum plant population. Clod formation was the common problem faced by the farmer at the time of field preparation. To tackle this problem, he developed animal drawn clod breaker which was made up of wooden log with 10 mm iron pokes. The equipment needs to be driven two times in an acre field for breaking clods and the time consumption for the operation was five hours for a hectare area. Many farmers in this region are effectively using this equipment for the fine field

preparation. The cost of innovation is Rs.3,000/- per equipment. Attributes of the equipments are given in Table 1.

Pebble stone remover

In hilly regions and rainfed areas, the fields are dotted with a number of pebbles and stones hindering the farm activities such as land preparation and inter-cultivation practices. Generally women labourers are engaged for removing the stones before starting of the season. Now a day's labour shortage was the crucial problem faced by the farmers to carry out the farming operations in time. Mr K Viswanathan from Gobichettipalayam taluk of Erode District developed a tractor drawn stone remover. It consist of a conveyor chain driven gear box, shaft connected to the digger and a tipper. The machine has the potential of picking of both small and big stones from a depth of 25 cm in the field. In a day it can be used to clear two hectare area. It can also be modified for harvesting of tuber crops. This innovation helps the farmer to remove the pebbles and harvest the crop without additional involvement of labour.

The special features of pebble stone remover revealed that there are number of benefits like removal of pebbles, stones, leads to fine tilth preparation and harvesting of tuber crops like potato, ginger, turmeric etc. .This innovation was very useful to the hilly and rainfed region farmers who are facing the acute labour shortage.

Acid lime variety

Acid lime is a major crop cultivated in Puliampatti region of Erode district. Die back and canker are the major diseases causing yield loss and quality of the harvested produce. Mr. A Devaraj from Erode district developed an acid lime variety by using the selection technique from the wild species. The special features of this particular variety were enlisted in Table 1. Now the innovation is in the process of multiplication of seedlings by using air layering technique.

Innovations Developed by Farmers

Tapioca sett cutter

Tapioca is the major crop cultivated in the hilly regions of Erode district. Setts are the planting material used for cultivation. Non availability of skilled labour in time forces the farmer to go for planting the whole setts in to the field which leads to the huge requirement of planting materials. Mr.V Viswanathan from Gobichettipalayam taluk of Erode district developed a sett cutter which requires 0.5 HP power. By using the cutter, a farmer can cut 750 setts per hour and it reduces the wastages of setts. By adopting this technology the cost of cultivation was drastically reduced from Rs. 4,000/- to Rs. 1,200/-ha.

Rotary power weeder cum ridger

The major cost involved in tapioca cultivation are weeding and earthing up operation. This operation alone consumes Rs.7,000/-ha area. Mr. V Viswanathan of Erode district invented the rotary weeder cum ridger exclusively for hilly regions. By using this machine the farmer can reduce the cost of cultivation drastically from Rs. 7,000/- to Rs.2,000/-ha. This is the gender friendly, self starter machine requires 7.5 HP power and by using this machine the farmers can do the weeding and earthing up operation simultaneously in one hectare area in a day. The study revealed that tapioca sett cutter and rotary power weeder cum ridger developed by Mr.V Viswanathan was having the better performance in the hilly regions. Both the equipments were gender friendly, easy to handle and operate by the farmers themselves. This finding was in line with Soedjana *et al* (2015).

Fermented castor solution trap

Root grub, the major pests in the crops like sugarcane, cotton, groundnut, coconut and areca nut. The serious infestation of the pest leads to heavy yield reduction. Mr.G R Sakthivel farmer from Talavadi region of Erode district invented the fermented castor solution trap to attract the grubs. Use 5 kg of castor seeds and pulverize it thoroughly. Add 5 l of water and keep this solution undisturbed 10 d for fermentation process. In the

mean time place the 5 mud pots with the capacity of 5 l each where placed in 1 acre field. Add 2 l of fermented solution to each pot and fill the remaining portion with water. Fermented castor solution trap was effectively used for controlling the pests like white grub, stem weevil and Rhinoceros beetle. It also caused the non-entry / re-infestation of rats into the field. The cost of entire process comes to Rs. 500/- only per year and it is eco-friendly too. The feasibility and sustainability of this trap were enlisted in Table 1. It has been reported that fermented castor solution trap was a technology having higher utility among all type of farmers for controlling rhinoceros beetle and other coleopteron pests (Saravana and Alagesan 2015).

Organic liquid manure preparation technique

In the modern farming system, farmers heavily rely on external inputs such as synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, fungicides, etc., for the crop cultivation process. Continuous usage of these inputs leads to poor soil fertility and returns from the crop. This will trigger the interest of the farmers to find the alternate solution. Mr. G R Sakthivel from Talavadi region of Erode District developed a filtering system consists of four compartments. The first section was meant for collection of cow dung and urine mixing. After thorough mixing, the solution was being sent to second compartment for first filtration. In this compartment the sedimented solid matter called slurry was used for biogas production and the supernatant solution was then allowed for next compartment where jaggery was added for fermentation. In the fourth compartment the clear enriched filtrated medium was collected and used for field through drip system. By adopting this technology the farmer can save Rs.15,000/-ha by reduction of labour and fertilizers through application of recycled cow dung and urine solution by filtration techniques. Field application with drip irrigation instead of manual operation also adds advantage to the innovation. By adoption of this technology water holding capacity of the soil is increased, the earth worm multiplied well in the field.

Turmeric harvester

Mr. P Ramaraj from Anthiyur taluk of Erode district was involved in farming practices since 1980. He cultivates crops like Turmeric, Vegetable, Banana and Sugarcane. Turmeric is one of the major crops in his field. This crop is annual and remunerative but highly labour oriented crop. Due to the scarcity of labourer in agriculture activities, farming work could not be carried out in time especially during harvesting season. If it was not harvested in time, crops can be infected with fungal diseases, which results in yield loss. Turmeric which can be easily operated with the support of power tiller. Though it was small, adaptability and transportation of the machine is easy. During machine operation, less consumption of fuel was observed. By using the harvester for harvesting turmeric rhizome, we can reduce the female labour for harvesting. By using of harvester, approximately Rs.18,000/-ha.can be saved in terms of labour. It can also be used for harvesting the tuber crops like potato, ginger in nearby districts.

Groundnut Pod Stripper

Portable groundnut pod stripper in affordable process for the small and medium farmers was developed by the innovative farmer Mr. K Mohanasundaram, Nasiyanur of Erode district. The stripper was run with a help of electrical motor with 0.5 HP power. The cylindrical type machine was closed in all the sides with three openings. One for feeding channel, the other one for pod collection delivery point and the remaining one was dust removing or blowing point. The machine was designed in such a way that two men can work simultaneously.

By using this machine, a farmer can strip the pods from an acre area of groundnut in two or three days by engaging the family labourers alone. 99 percent stripping efficiency was found and the harvested pods are clean and it was notified that there were no broken pods. Winnowing operations can also be done at a time of harvest with the support of special attachment in this machine called

blower. It also reduces the drudgery of the women labourers and can easily transport even with the help of bicycle. The cost saving for stripping operation is Rs.2,500/-acre.

It was found that the groundnut pod stripper was more effective in stripping of pods since it saves labour and time. The cost for designing the machine is only Rs.25000/-. This is also a cost effective one, which can be easily operated and gender friendly in nature. The findings were in conformity with Olga and Ustyuzhantseva (2015).

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that the innovations developed by the innovators were mostly in response to the field level problem faced by the farming community. The in-depth study reveals that five innovations namely clod breaker, organic liquid manure preparation, fermented castor solution trap, turmeric harvester and groundnut pod stripper have been commercialized. While the other innovations are popularized within the district level by the Krishi Vigyan Kendra.

Two innovations namely organic liquid manure preparation and turmeric harvester was notified by ICAR as a best innovation and the famers were awarded during the national level farmer innovators meet. The other innovations like acid lime variety, tapioca sett cutter, rotary power weeder cum ridger was notified by National Innovation Foundation as the best innovation. It was also found that all the farmer led innovations were having cost effective, greater utility and more sustainable rather than the available technology.

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Innovations Developed by Farmers

Table 1: Farmer led innovation and its attributes.

FARM INNOVATIONS									
Attributes	Clod breaker	Pebble stone remover	Acid lime variety	Tapioca sett cutter	Rotary power weeder cum ridger	Fermented castor solution trap	Organic liquid manure	Turmeric harvester	Groundnut pod stripper
Utility	Animal drawn. Covers 1.5 ha/day.	Tractor drawn. Remove pebbles up to 25 cm depth. Covers 2 ha/day	It produces 2000 fruits /season/ tree.	0.5 HP power is required to operate. Cut 750 setts/hr	Power tiller drawn. 7.5 HP power is required. Covers 1 ha/day	Managing root group in sugarcane, groundnut and cotton.	Contains rich of nutrients, sediments used for bio gas production	Power tiller drawn. Covers 1.2 ha/day	Requires 0.5 HP power. Covers. 0.5 ha / day
Cost	Rs. 3,000/-	Rs.2.0 lakh	Rs. 50 / seedling	Rs. 8,000/-	Rs. 35,000/-	Rs. 500/-	Rs. 30,000/-	Rs. 35,000/-	Rs. 25,000/-
Advantages	Gender friendly. Cost of operation: Rs.1500/ha Ensures fine tilth	Cost of operation: Rs. 2000/ha. also used for harvesting tuber crops like potato, onion, garlic, etc.,	Resistant to citrus canker and die-back. Useful for value addition	labour saving. Cost of operation for cutting setts: Rs. 1200/ha	Time and labour saving. Cost of operation Rs.2000/ha.	Eco friendly. Reduces chemical application costs up to Rs.1500/ha	Increases the microbial population in the soil, water holding capacity and suitable for drip irrigation	Easy to transport. Time and labour saving. Cost of operation: Rs. 6250/ha.	Stripping and winnowing done on a single time. Cost of operation: Rs. 2500/ha
Demonstrability	No specific skills required for operation.	This is designed for reducing the labour dependency. The farmers can save Rs. 12000/ha towards labour cost.	Developed this variety by using selection process. Produces more fruits / tree over a long period of time.	Gender friendly and easy to operate. This can be detachable and move to any place.	Designed according to the need of rainfed farmers. Weeding and earthing up can be done at single operation	There is no specific skill required for preparation.	Organic and eco friendly. Non harmful to the soil and plants.	Easy to operate. Single man labour is enough to harvest 1.2 ha against the 110 male labour in manual harvest.	Easy to transport. Gender friendly.

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Sustainability	Easy to multiply. Rainfed millet cultivators are using this for long time.	This is the cost effective labour saving equipment.	This can be multiplied by using air layering technique.	This is the cost effective machine. Chance to go for trans-planting techniques in Tapioca.	Cost effective labour saving equipment. Dual operations carried out in a single mode	Cost effective. Eco friendly in nature. It also controls the rhinoceros beetle	Cost effective. Farmers can save Rs. 25000 in annual crops and Rs.15000 / acre in short duration crop.	Cost effective, gender friendly. It can also be used for harvesting potato, ginger and garlic.	easy to multiply and cost effective one. Labour saving equipment. 99 per cent efficiency was noticed
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Management Practices Followed by Dairy Farmers in Rural and Urban Areas of Bathinda District in Punjab

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ABSTARCT

A field study was concluded to note down the various animal husbandry practices followed by the dairy farmers in rural and urban areas in Bathinda district of Punjab. It was found that about 75 per cent of respondents kept the animals in commercial type of housing system whereas 69 per cent animal sheds were nearby to the dwelling of the farmers and 83 per cent of the farmers provided concrete manger. Majority of the respondents (58%) followed the individual feeding system, cultivated fodder crops (68%) for feeding to dairy animals throughout the year and only 25 per cent of farmers produce non-legume fodder. Similarly, while use of mixed fodder (both legume and non-legume) restricted to only 15 per cent. The health status was maintained by using regular vaccination (91%), veterinary facilities (81%) and artificial insemination (65%) by the respondents. Majority of respondents in the study area felt the constraints of lack of capital, high cost of shed construction, high feed costs and occurrence of repeat breeding in cross bred cattle.

Key Words: Bathinda, Dairy farmers, Management, Rural, Urban area

INTRODUCTION

Management is a key factor for the success of any business and in dairy farming, the role of management is very important. Feeding, housing and health management plays a very significant role in exploiting the full potential of dairy animals. The management practices constitute about 75-80 percent of total cost incurred on milk production in dairy business (Verma and Sastry, 1994). Insufficient feeding of dairy cows results in poor growth, delayed maturity, late conception and poor production. Provision of comfortable and proper spacing is helpful in reducing the energy in maintaining thermo-neutral zone and also provides ideal, comfortable and hygienic conditions, which reduce the incidence of diseases, lower the pathogenic load, reduces the ecto and endo parasites and provides good environment for optimum milk production.

Dairy farm management should be sophisticated, particularly in the tropics with the added environmental stresses. However, smallholder and small dairy co-operatives often lack the necessary

management skills. Co-operatives are not usually strong enough to manage proper health control and services for members.

Herd management practices in cow handling, nutrition, milking procedures, sanitation and housing play major role in predisposing the individual animal as well as herds to diseases. Health management improves the conditions of dairy animals by reducing the disease load and proper health status. Therefore, understanding of livestock management (feeding, housing, health) practices followed by the farmers is the key factors in identification of strength, weakness, opportunity and threat in livestock rearing. This helps in identification of appropriate intervention policy to optimize the production of dairy animals to benefit the farming community.

However, records from smallholders are seldom comparable to those of western dairy nations. In the tropics, climatic and environmental stress, particularly heat stress, could affect animal productivity (Matthewman, 1993). According to Akers (2002), a well-known lactation physiologist,

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the investment in milking management at farms where feed, breed and care for animal obviously are wasted if milking procedures and milk handling are not satisfactory. This means that attention must be focused on milking practice to promote optimal milk production and good udder health. The present study was designed to collect the information regarding the existing management practices i.e., feeding management, housing management and health management adopted by the rural and urban farmers of the Bathinda district of Punjab.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the Bathinda district of Punjab. District Bathinda is lying at Latitude of 30.2300 N and Longitude of 74.9519. This district constituted of seven blocks. For this study, one hundred farmers each from four blocks were selected randomly, thus making a sample size of 400. It is a known fact that the distribution of dairy units is scattered in both rural as well as urban areas, so the selection for rural:urban was based on 3:1 ratio. A well structured pre-designed and pre-tested questionnaire was used to collect the information on array of different management practices (feeding, housing and health) followed by dairy owners through personal interview. The collected data were classified by using appropriate statistical tools like percentage and frequency etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Housing Management Practices

It was revealed that all the respondents (rural and urban) provided almost the same condition of rearing /housing to their dairy animals. Similar findings were reported by Swaroop and Prasad (2009). In rural areas, farmers keeping small to medium scale of dairy unit provided conventional type of housing (75%) and in urban areas (79%) which gives controlled environment for rearing the dairy cows. These sheds were built up with cheap and easily available local material. In some places, bamboo, sheets, local structure plastered with mud mixed with cow dung were also found.

Similar findings have been reported by Sabapara *et al* (2010) and Sharma *et al* (1996).

Table 1. Housing Management Practices followed by the farmers.

Sr. No.	Particular	Rural area (Percent)	Urban area (Percent)
1.	Conventional type	75	79
2.	Sharing of residential housing	69	39
3.	Concrete floor	53	91
4.	Wooden type	17	09

Rural families (69%) share their residence with the dairy cows and value is lower in urban areas (39%). Similar findings were reported by Rathore *et al* (2010) and Sohane *et al* (2004). Purpose of studying this practice was to see the cost of construction of sheds because of low income factor. In the rural areas, 53 per cent of the respondents provides concrete floor while 47 per cent used katcha area for rearing the dairy animals whereas these values in urban area were 91 and 9 per cent, respectively. However contradictory findings were reported by Sabapara *et al* (2010) and Singh *et al* (2009) where mainly katcha type of floor was observed. This was because of the reason that the dairy farmers are now more concerned about the hygiene and cleaning of dairy sheds which is achieved only by providing the concrete floor. It is general observation that the concrete floor is better than the katcha floor to keep the shed / animals worm free and hygienic point of view.

Further, the asbestos sheets, thatched material and galvanized iron sheets were used for construction of the dairy sheds by majority of the commercial dairy units and the respective values were 75, 10 and 15 per cent in rural areas and 80, 8, and 12 per cent in urban areas. In fact, prevailing climatic conditions, temperature, standard cost, economical condition of the farmers play a vital role in the selection of building material. Similar finding were reported by Patel *et al* (2005) and Singh *et al* (2009). Pucca and wooden assisted type of mangers were provided by 83 and 17 percent of

Management Practices Followed by Dairy Farmers

the respondents in rural areas, respectively whereas, this value was 91 and 9 percent in urban areas of the district.

Feeding Management Practices

The data (Table 2) show that around 85 per cent respondents of rural area and 58 per cent of urban areas preferred individual feeding system in conventional system of rearing while 15 per cent of the respondents of rural areas and 42 per cent of urban areas adopted group feeding in loose housing system. Similar findings were reported by Gupta et al (2008) and Singh et al (2007). However lesser number of individual feeding was observed in urban area because of common feeding manger to feed the animals.

Table 2. Feeding Management Practices followed by the farmers.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Rural area (Per cent)	Urban area (Per cent)
1.	Feeding system- individual	85	58
2.	Conventional system of rearing	15	42
3.	Leguminous feeding	25	22
4.	Leguminous + non-leguminous feeding	16	10
5.	Dry matter feeding- paddy straw	11	08
6.	Mixture of green fodder + dry fodder	94	89
7.	Local available feed ingredients	55	36

The legume fodder data revealed that 25 percent in rural areas and 22 percent in urban areas cultivate and purchase legume fodder for feeding to dairy animals. A small proportion of respondents used mixture of leguminous and non-leguminous green fodder for feeding to the dairy animals. The study showed that 15 per cent of respondents from rural areas and 39 percent of urban areas did not have land for cultivation of green fodder. They purchased the green fodder from local market to fulfill their green fodder requirement.

It was found that the dry matter requirement of dairy animals met out by feeding the wheat straw in whole district of Bathinda. Eighty nine percent of respondents in rural areas and 92 percent in urban areas used wheat straw to fulfill the requirement of dry matter. Rest of the respondents (11 percent from rural area and 8 percent of urban areas) used paddy straw and other brans to fulfill the dry matter requirement. Similar findings were reported by Deoras et al (2004). Majority of the farmer (94%) in rural area and 89 per cent in urban areas offer chopped green fodder mix with dry fodder for feeding to the dairy animals. Only 6 percent from rural area and 11 percent from urban area offer the fodder as such. This finding was in agreement with earlier findings of Chaudhary et al (2006) and Sabapara et al (2010). This may be due to lack of adequate knowledge of efficient utilization of feed and fodder

In rural areas, 55 per cent respondents used feed ingredients locally available while 36 per cent used the commercial cattle feed available in local markets and 9 per cent used the combination of both. In urban areas, 41 per cent farmers used the local feed input while 39 per cent used the compound cattle feed, 20 per cent used both. Rathore et al (2010) and Sabapara et al (2010) reported that dairy farmer feed concentrates to their dairy animals made from home produced ingredients along with the compound cattle feed in various proportion in different parts of the country. As for as the feeding of concentrates on the milk production basis was concerned, it was adopted by 65 per cent dairy farmers from rural areas and 85 per cent in urban areas while 35 per cent and 15 per cent respondents in rural and urban fed the animals without taking into consideration of milk produced.

HEALTH MANAGEMENT

To exploit the optimum potential of the livestock, it is essential to keep neat and clean, sanitation and health care management facility at the farm. About 91 per cent in urban and 87 per cent in rural areas, regularly vaccinate the stock while 9 per cent in

urban areas and 13 per cent dairy farmers in rural areas did not follow (Table 3).

Table 3. Health management practices followed.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Rural area (Per cent)	Urban area (Per cent)
1.	Regular vaccination	91	87
2.	Vaccination facility	63	81
3.	Artificial insemination	65	85

Around 85 per cent of urban respondents and 65 per cent of rural respondents used artificial insemination while 15 per cent of urban and 35 per cent of rural preferred the natural mating system.

CONCLUSION

Majority of respondents in the study area feels the constraints of lack of gross capital, high shed construction cost, high feed costs, incidence of repeat breeding, respectively. The co-operative milk union and animal husbandry department can provide financial credit with the help of banks / NABARD to the trainees of dairy farming through societies, dairy departments, KVK's and other agencies to uplift the socio economic status of these dairy farmers.

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Manifestation of Heterosis in Indian Mustard: Through Physiological characters for Seed Yield

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ABSTRACT

Half diallel F1 crosses and parents of Indian mustard [*B. juncea* (L.) Czern & Coss.] genotypes were evaluated for canopy temp. (OC) at 40 DAS, 50 DAS, 60 DAS, 70 DAS and chlorophyll fluorescence at 40 DAS, 50 DAS, 60 DAS, 70 DAS, seedling mortality (%) and seed yield per plant (g). Mean squares due to parent v/s crosses were significant for all the traits, except for canopy temperature at 50 DAS, chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 40 DAS, chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 50 DAS and chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 60 DAS in timely sown condition and canopy temperature at 50 DAS and canopy temperature at 70 DAS in late sown condition. For seed yield and physiological traits, crosses RH8814 x RH0555A, RH0644 x BPR543-3 and BPR349-9 x RH0644 in timely sown condition and crosses RH0555A x RH0644, RH0735 x RH0116 and BPR349-9 x RH0644 in late sown were identified as promising on the basis of their high per se performance with positive and negative heterotic effects. From the component character analysis, it was concluded that characters canopy temperature, chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) and seedling mortality contributed significantly towards heterosis in seed yield. These crosses could be further used to select superior segregants.

Key words: Brassica juncea, half diallel, heterosis breeding, seed yield, yield components.

INTRODUCTION

Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*) is a naturally autogamous species, yet in this crop frequent out-crossing occur which varies from 5 to 30% depending upon the environmental conditions and random variation of pollinating insects. In India, the area of rape and mustard is 61.90 lakh/ha, with production of 58.03 lakh tons and yield 0.94 tons/ha in 2015-16.

The success stories of hybrid breeding are the reason for its expansion in all most all major fields of agricultural plants. For developing a hybrid, genetic analysis of important characters and their combination in a single hybrid is essential. It has become a common practice of the plant breeders to obtain genetic information from diallel analysis of progenies and desirable parental combination which can reflect a high degree of heterotic response for its commercial exploitation in future breeding programs. Heterosis has been earlier explored and

utilized for boosting various quality traits in Brassica and other crops (Hassan et al. 2006). According to Pal and Sikka, (1956) heterosis is a quick, cheap and easy method for increasing crop production. Therefore, present study was conducted to explore the role of some physiological traits in expression of heterosis (mid-parent and better-parent) on F1 generation of mustard genotypes using diallel analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Eight diverse mustard genotypes namely RH8814, RH0735, RH0116, BPR349-9, RH0952, RH0555A, RH0644, BPR543-3 were selected as parents on the basis of their origin, adaptability, diversity and yield potential. Crosses were attempted during Rabi, 2013-14 in a diallel fashion (excluding reciprocals). Eight parents along with 28 F1s were evaluated during Rabi, 2014-15 in randomized block design with three replications

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having plot size of two row of three meter length under timely and late sown conditions. The data were recorded on ten characters (Table 1), from five competitive plants excluding border plants in each F1s and parents which were randomly selected from each replication. All the recommended cultural practices were followed throughout the crop season to raise a good crop. Standard formulas were used for estimation of heterosis. Table value of 't' at error d.f. corresponding to 5% or 1% level of significance. Negative direction of heterosis was considered for canopy temp. at 40 DAS, 50 DAS, 60 DAS, 70 DAS and seedling mortality, whereas, positive direction was considered for rest of the traits.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of variance showed that mean sum of squares were significantly different for most of the physiological traits in both the environments, indicating presence of adequate genetic variation among the genotypes (F1+ parents). except for Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 40 DAS in late sown condition among parents. Mean squares due to parent v/s crosses were also significant for all the traits which depicted presence of variations for different traits. Superiority of F1s in mustard was also reported by Vaghela *et al.* (2011), Patel *et al.* (2012) and Arifullah (2013). The results on heterosis for different traits are detailed below:

Canopy temperature (°C) at 40,50,60,70 DAS- Minimum canopy temperature was treated as desirable attribute and accordingly negative estimates of heterosis were considered to be desirable. Five crosses exhibited significant negative heterosis over better parents and mid-parents for this trait. in both the environments Minimum magnitudes of heterobeltiosis was observed for the cross i.e. RH0555A x BPR543-3 (-14.80), followed by RH0644 x BPR543-3 (-14.42) and RH0735 x RH0952 (-13.92). Differential magnitude of mid parent heterosis over mid-parent and better parent for canopy temperature (°C) at 50 DAS recorded by crosses viz., RH8814 x RH0116, RH8814 x

BPR349-9, RH8814 x RH0644, RH8814 x BPR543-3, RH0735 x BPR543-3 and BPR349-9 x RH0644 in both the environments. Similarly, negative and significant heterosis over better parents in both the environments was exhibited by crosses ; RH8814 x RH0116, RH8814 x RH0952, RH8814 x RH0644, RH8814 x BPR543-3, RH0735 x RH0952, RH0116 x RH0952 and BPR349-9 x RH0952 for canopy temperature (°C) at 60 and 70 DAS. Similar results was also reported earlier by Kumar *et al.* (2007) and Nasrin *et al.* (2011) in Brassica juncea. Negative and significant heterosis over better parent expressed by the seven cross combinations viz., RH8814 x RH0116, RH8814 x BPR349-9, RH8814 x BPR543-3, RH0735 x RH0116, RH0116 x RH0952, BPR349-9 x RH0952 and BPR349-9 x RH0555A in both the environments. Therefore, it is suggested that these crosses may be used in the development of high temperature tolerant hybrids after converting CMS lines or restorer lines for low canopy temperature (°C). The same results were also reported earlier by Vaghela *et al.* (2011) and Verma *et al.* (2011) in mustard.

Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 40,50,60,70 DAS -For chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 40 DAS five cross in both the environments manifested significant positive heterosis over mid-parent. Three crosses RH8814 x RH0555A, RH0735 x RH0952 and RH0952 x BPR543-3 manifested significant positive heterosis over better-parent in both environments. Significant heterobeltiosis for chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 50 DAS was noticed in six crosses in both the environments namely; RH8814 x BPR349-9, RH0735 x RH0952, RH0735 x RH0555A, RH0735 x BPR543-3, RH0116 x BPR349-9, RH0116 x RH0952. Similar results were revealed by Singh *et al.* (2005), Sadanand *et al.* (2009), Patel *et al.* (2012), Yadava *et al.* (2012), Singh *et al.* (2013) and Gami and Chauhan (2013). Heterobeltiosis for chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 70 DAS was significant and positive manifested by only one cross i.e. RH0116 x RH0952 in both the environments. **These traits can be improved by**

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Table: 1 Analysis of variance for different physiological characters under normal and late sown condition in Indian mustard

Source	d.f.	Canopy temperature at 40 DAS (OC)	Canopy temperature at 50 DAS (OC)	Canopy temperature at 60 DAS (OC)	Canopy temperature at 70 DAS (OC)	Chlorophyll fluorescence at 40DAS (Fv/Fm)	Chlorophyll fluorescence at 50DAS (Fv/Fm)	Chlorophyll fluorescence at 60DAS (Fv/Fm)	Chlorophyll fluorescence at 70DAS (Fv/Fm)	Seeding mortality (%)	Seed yield/plant(g)
Timely sown condition											
Replications	2	0.909	2.810 **	0.032	0.316	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.051	3.538
Genotypes	35	24.961 **	6.746 **	3.012 **	12.165 **	0.001 **	0.003 **	0.004 **	0.004 **	35.332 **	28.864 **
Parents	7	19.507 **	4.870 **	1.911 **	12.018 **	0.002 **	0.004 **	0.008 **	0.008 **	25.280 **	16.508 **
Crosses	27	27.045 **	7.482 **	3.144 **	11.988 **	0.001 **	0.002 **	0.003 **	0.002 **	39.204 **	27.100 **
Parents v/s crosses	1	6.881 **	0.001	7.153 **	17.962 **	NA	NA	NA	0.005 **	1.145	162.971 **
Error	70	0.971	0.506	0.586	0.407	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.970	1.714
Late sown condition											
Replications	2	0.078	6.168 **	2.155	0.111	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.108	1.718
Genotypes	35	2.927 **	2.405 **	6.289 **	4.226 **	0.002 **	0.002 **	0.004 **	0.002 **	41.531 **	29.562 **
Parents	7	3.419 **	1.497 *	4.794 **	5.085 **	NA	0.002 **	0.002 **	0.001 **	19.281 **	14.995 **
Crosses	27	2.618 **	2.703 **	6.700 **	4.063 **	0.002 **	0.002 **	0.005 **	0.003 **	44.424 **	31.759 **
Parents v/s crosses	1	7.815 **	0.720	5.671 *	2.608	NA	0.005 **	0.010 **	0.006 **	119.180 **	72.198 **
Error	70	0.832	0.620	1.204	1.017	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.822	2.546

*, ** significant at P=0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table: 2 Mean (%) and range of heterosis (MP) and heterobeltiosis (BP) for yield and different physiological traits in Indian mustard

Traits	Environment	MP		BP	
		Mean	Range	Mean	Range
Canopy temperature at 40 DAS	Normal	-2.76	-25.4-28.5	-9.30	-28.26-25.08
	Late	-4.20	-19.06-10.33	-7.85	-20.83-7.92
Canopy temperature at 50 DAS	Normal	0.14	-21.22-36.80	-5.28	-24.15-35.83
	Late	-1.27	-12.56-12.61	-3.67	-13.15-11.67
Canopy temperature at 60 DAS	Normal	-3.28	-11.87-7.74	-6.29	-15.41-0.98
	Late	-3.11	-19.87-15.55	-6.40	-24.14-7.21
Canopy temperature at 70 DAS	Normal	-5.43	-32.33-19.52	-11.99	-36.21-8.59
	Late	-2.79	-19.27-19.19	-7.61	-22.35-12.74
Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 40 DAS	Normal	0.49	-4.73-4.86	-1.36	-2.87-2.61
	Late	-0.61	-8.85-6.65	-1.08	-9.54-6.12
Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 50 DAS	Normal	0.09	-5.79-9.15	-2.37	-11.69-6.28
	Late	2.13	-4.15-10.44	0.39	-4.63-9.76
Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 60 DAS	Normal	-0.37	-11.56-10.57	-4.05	-12.56-4.26
	Late	-2.89	-15.54-4.46	-4.93	-17.80-4.46
Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 70 DAS	Normal	2.22	-9.38-13.29	-1.57	-11.86-6.72
	Late	-2.16	-11.37-4.33	-3.59	-13.53-3.66
Seeding mortality (%)	Normal	-0.77	-38.28- 53.26	-10.05	-45.49-31.8
	Late	-11.13	-43.74- 32.85	-17.03	-46.64-24.53
Seed yield/plant (g)	Normal	21.555	-16.29-73.19	11.287	-25.61-62.31
	Late	17.476	-51.18-68.47	6.897	-53.73-66.02

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Table: 3 Extent of heterosis (%) for canopy temp. at 40 DAS, 50 DAS, 60 DAS, 70 DAS and chlorophyll fluorescence at 40 DAS in Indian mustard

Crosses	Environment	Canopy temperature at 40 DAS Heterosis (%) over		Canopy temperature at 50 DAS Heterosis (%) over		Canopy temperature at 60 DAS Heterosis (%) over		Canopy temperature at 70 DAS Heterosis (%) over		Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 40 DAS Heterosis (%) over	
		M.P.	B.P.	M.P.	B.P.	M.P.	B.P.	M.P.	B.P.	M.P.	B.P.
RH8814 x RH0735	Normal	4.24	-5.09	0.77	-6.43	0.44	-0.44	19.52**	5.05	0.46**	-1.78
	Late	4.20	2.41	-6.64	-10.39**	-1.94	-6.84	1.61	-2.00	-7.68	-8.48
RH8814 x RH0116	Normal	-23.89**	-28.26**	-14.25**	-15.83**	-4.69	-10.22**	0.22	-16.73**	3.50**	2.025**
	Late	-1.65	-2.65	-12.56**	-13.15**	-9.17*	-9.65*	-12.38**	-18.79**	-8.86	-9.54
RH8814 x BPR349-9	Normal	-8.20*	-16.62**	-8.88*	-10.55*	-5.87	-9.45*	8.68**	-7.75*	3.25**	2.07**
	Late	-19.06**	-20.83**	-8.84**	-9.02*	-6.82	-7.72	-8.46	-12.70*	-2.58	-3.43
RH8814 x RH0952	Normal	-1.96	-3.51	3.23	-4.76	-5.36	-10.18**	16.82**	8.59*	-3.38	-5.88
	Late	0.22	-5.83	-0.72	-5.49	-15.23**	-19.75**	-4.66	-6.89	-4.70	-4.94
RH8814 x RH0555A	Normal	-1.11	-9.59**	3.54	-2.62	7.68*	0.97	7.02*	-8.64**	2.43**	1.14**
	Late	5.19	4.75	5.09	1.18	4.97	2.68	1.85	-0.42	1.73**	1.59**
RH8814 x RH0644	Normal	-23.98**	-27.43**	-10.28**	-11.93**	-9.39**	-15.41**	10.03**	-5.92	-0.71	-3.97
	Late	-8.74*	-10.91*	-11.35**	-11.96**	-14.53**	-17.13**	2.50	0.43	-0.54	-1.41
RH8814 x BPR543-3	Normal	-25.39**	-27.01**	-14.55**	-16.40**	-7.60*	-13.11**	7.02*	-8.64**	1.09**	-1.75
	Late	-6.45	-10.63*	-8.18*	-9.80*	-16.31**	-17.66**	-9.03*	-14.62**	0.00	-0.13
RH0735 x RH0116	Normal	-7.65*	-19.41**	-7.29	-15.37**	-4.28	-9.82**	-32.23**	-36.21**	3.52**	-0.21
	Late	-11.20**	-12.94**	-7.92*	-11.22**	3.72	-1.24	-6.44	-15.94**	0.79**	0.66**
RH0735 x BPR349-9	Normal	-14.43**	-27.79**	23.62**	12.84**	-8.00*	-11.50**	-1.41	-4.84	0.50**	-0.62
	Late	-10.42*	-14.90**	-8.50*	-11.02**	-0.84	-5.19	-6.55	-13.71**	-2.4	-2.44
RH0735 x RH0952	Normal	10.85**	3.62	36.78**	35.83**	-8.73*	-13.37**	8.34**	1.46	1.15**	0.78**
	Late	-5.79	-13.92**	-0.74	-2.71	-12.37**	-2.116**	-3.42	-4.43	6.65**	6.12**
RH0735 x RH0555A	Normal	5.14	-10.76**	13.42**	11.89*	6.02	-0.58	-5.36	-8.06*	1.29**	0.41**
	Late	0.60	-1.96	12.61**	11.67**	15.55**	7.21	9.32	3.40	-2.72	-3.68
RH0735 x RH0644	Normal	-0.45	-12.12**	26.38**	15.37**	7.74*	0.58	-4.36	-6.90*	0.00	-1.09
	Late	-6.51	-7.06	8.24*	5.77	4.39	-3.95	3.49	-1.92	2.81**	2.81**
RH0735 x BPR543-3	Normal	7.25	-3.19	-16.65**	-24.15**	-4.47	-10.18**	-4.75	-7.47*	-3.74	-4.33
	Late	-11.48**	-12.90**	-8.44*	-9.55*	-0.64	-7.30	2.47	-6.82	-2.58	-3.18
RH0116 x BPR349-9	Normal	-7.08*	-11.60**	-2.26	-3.78	-1.71	-3.92	1.52	-0.74	4.8**	2.20**
	Late	10.33*	7.92	0.20	0.00	2.21	1.23	-4.83	-8.70	-2.56	-2.69

RH0116 x RH0952	Normal	-11.68**	-17.14**	-9.81*	-19.33**	-11.57**	-12.35**	-16.16**	-25.56**	3.97**	0.00
	Late	-5.32	-11.04*	-4.43	-9.02*	-5.46	-10.50*	-10.63*	-19.81**	-2.41	-2.78
RH0116 xRH0555A	Normal	-8.65**	-12.50**	6.59	-2.89	-4.30	-4.67	5.05	2.04	-0.48	-3.12
	Late	-0.21	-0.62	-1.63	-5.29	-1.03	-3.19	1.29	-5.19	3.93**	3.03**
RH0116 x RH0644	Normal	-9.31**	-9.52*	-19.64**	-20.89**	-4.96	-5.78	4.68	1.48	-0.76	-5.23
	Late	-6.91	-9.13*	1.88	1.18	-7.22	-10.05*	4.86	-2.04	0.91**	0.79**
RH0116 xBPR543-3	Normal	28.55**	25.08**	-8.89*	-10.00*	-3.62	-3.72	-0.67	-3.52	1.15**	-3.06
	Late	-8.04*	-12.14**	4.19	2.35	-7.16	-8.66	-8.07	-10.37*	1.63**	1.12**
BPR349-9 xRH0952	Normal	-15.46**	-23.91**	-9.57*	-19.11**	-6.42	-8.38*	-0.75	-9.61**	-1.08	-2.43
	Late	6.42	3.11	-2.16	-6.86	-19.87**	-24.14**	-10.54*	-17.65**	-0.87	-1.49
BPR349-9xRH0555A	Normal	-16.98**	-17.10**	-15.12**	-22.67**	-11.87**	-14.79**	-18.94**	-19.02**	0.72**	0.59**
	Late	0.00	-3.51	-2.44	-6.08	8.40*	6.04	-19.27**	-22.35**	-1.04	-2.15
BPR349-9 xRH0644	Normal	-22.40**	-25.94**	-21.22**	-22.44**	-8.11*	-11.56**	-26.25**	-26.47**	-0.83	-2.88
	Late	-4.40	-9.52*	-7.60*	-8.24*	-4.16	-7.08	-5.82	-9.61	0.25**	0.12**
BPR349-9xB-PR543-3	Normal	-6.07	-12.46**	-1.01	-2.22	0.91	-2.15	-19.53**	-19.61**	2.33**	0.57**
	Late	-3.99	-11.01*	-3.79	-5.49	8.20*	6.45	-0.49	-0.78	-3.12	-3.84
RH0952 xRH0555A	Normal	-5.05	-15.26**	11.78**	10.27*	-0.39	-0.78	-7.64*	-15.72**	-1.54	-2.75
	Late	-2.88	-9.30*	4.34	1.91	1.96	-0.79	19.19**	12.74*	-1.59	-1.97
RH0952 x RH0644	Normal	7.46*	0.00	20.35**	9.86*	-1.07	-1.93	-19.96**	-26.82**	-4.73	-5.43
	Late	-3.68	-11.71*	7.24*	1.59	-2.67	-4.44	3.49	-1.92	-2.33	-2.81
RH0952 xBPR543-3	Normal	15.67**	10.23*	-5.63	-14.12**	-0.88	-0.98	-23.79**	-30.45**	2.99**	2.61**
	Late	-2.43	-12.33**	2.34	-2.03	-4.35	-7.46	-4.18	-12.87**	0.71**	0.59**
RH0555A xRH0644	Normal	16.93**	11.59**	13.57**	3.67	-1.46	-2.31	-29.40**	-29.61**	-1.07	-2.99
	Late	-1.63	-3.97	1.32	-0.99	-4.89	-5.44	-2.00	-3.13	5.72**	4.67**
RH0555AxB-PR543-3	Normal	16.49**	8.55*	11.64**	1.59	-0.88	-0.98	-28.75**	-28.82**	-0.62	-2.20
	Late	-10.82**	-14.80**	8.44*	7.11	-0.76	-1.67	-7.96	-10.92*	0.88**	0.75**
RH0644 xBPR543-3	Normal	19.90**	16.67**	-2.59	-3.78	1.08	0.98	-1.08	-1.18	-0.53	-0.89
	Late	-13.02**	-14.42**	4.59	2.75	-0.93	-1.83	-3.52	-6.63	2.95**	2.32**
CD at 5 %	Normal	1.38	1.60	1.01	1.15	1.07	1.24	0.89	1.03	0.016	0.019
	Late	1.28	1.48	1.11	1.28	0.77	0.89	1.42	1.64	0.012	0.014
CD at 1 %	Normal	1.84	2.13	1.33	1.53	1.43	1.65	1.19	1.37	0.022	0.025
	Late	1.70	1.97	1.47	1.70	1.54	1.78	1.88	2.18	0.016	0.018

*, ** significant at=0.05 and 0.01, respectively

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Table: 4 Extent of heterosis (%) for Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 50 DAS, 60 DAS, 70 DAS, seedling mortality and seed yield in mustard

Crosses	Environment	Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 50 DAS Heterosis (%) over		Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 60 DAS Heterosis (%) over		Chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) at 70 DAS Heterosis (%) over		Seedling mortality Heterosis (%) over		Seed yield/plant(g) Heterosis (%) over	
		M.P.	B.P.	M.P.	B.P.	M.P.	B.P.	M.P.	B.P.	M.P.	B.P.
RH8814 x RH0735	Normal	0.34**	-0.17	2.04**	1.53**	5.83**	-4.77	-22.0**	-22.41**	6.29	-10.11
	Late	5.49**	3.35**	1.52**	0.88**	-0.12	-1.09	-9.75**	-20.48**	24.49*	5.57
RH8814 x RH0116	Normal	3.44**	3.05**	2.72**	0.92**	2.47**	-3.47	16.15**	6.19	55.19**	54.99**
	Late	-0.58	-2.41	0.13**	-1.12	-2.23	-2.83	-39.15**	-44.71**	17.25	8.17
RH8814 x BPR349-9	Normal	1.43**	0.79**	-5.88	-6.11	10.32**	1.72**	8.97	5.33	-1.56	-7.45
	Late	4.762**	2.63**	1.36**	-1.36	-9.06	-10.16	-1.54	-8.43*	58.15**	56.35**
RH8814 x RH0952	Normal	1.83**	1.06**	-2.86	-4.85	13.29**	6.72**	31.39**	11.00**	8.24	5.01
	Late	-2.44	-3.17	-4.58	-5.06	-6.51	-8.26	32.85**	24.53**	21.32**	14.5
RH8814 x RH0555A	Normal	0.95**	-1.25	4.26**	1.13**	8.61**	-1.54	36.52**	25.60**	70.49**	56.90**
	Late	1.89**	0.87**	2.54**	-0.21	-6.47	-7.64	-9.75**	-20.48**	34.20**	10.02
RH8814 x RH0644	Normal	-3.09	-8.74	-1.06	-3.08	9.36**	0.25**	-34.26**	-43.61**	5.15	-6.75
	Late	-2.92	-3.16	-4.06	-4.30	-1.86	-2.10	-13.69**	-26.78**	8.37	6.80
RH8814 x BPR543-3	Normal	2.95**	-0.12	10.58**	2.13**	9.90**	0.96**	-3.37	-8.51	73.19**	62.31**
	Late	-1.80	-3.14	-1.04	-3.44	-0.25	-1.99	-28.80**	-39.86**	-7.61	-21.04*
RH0735 x RH0116	Normal	0.08**	-0.67	-3.72	-5.87	3.96**	-0.99	-14.32*	-21.67**	-1.35	-16.84**
	Late	4.88**	0.89**	-1.00	-1.61	0.82**	0.45**	1.25	-1.52	46.06**	34.76**
RH0735 x BPR349-9	Normal	-0.96	-1.21	-11.57	-11.78	-0.94	-3.54	17.70**	13.78*	-16.29**	-25.61**
	Late	6.23**	6.23**	0.734**	-2.56	-8.44	-8.67	23.38**	17.12**	-32.05**	-41.19**
RH0735 x RH0952	Normal	5.59**	4.40**	-6.63	-8.09	-3.29	-7.91	2.82	-13.14**	-8.16	-17.02**
	Late	5.14**	2.25**	-10.35	-10.47	-1.72	-4.48	-27.27**	-31.52**	9.23	-1.43
RH0735 x RH0555A	Normal	2.97**	1.09**	3.13**	-0.45	-2.76	-3.57	-6.52	-14.00**	-12.57*	-20.70**
	Late	3.26**	0.17**	3.83**	0.29**	-3.83	-5.94	-15.58**	-16.14**	-51.18	-53.73**
RH0735 x RH0644	Normal	5.57**	-0.11	-0.32	-1.88	1.05**	-0.99	1.69	-12.78**	-9.31	-14.56*
	Late	1.81**	-0.51	-4.37	-5.34	0.00	-0.73	-21.26**	-25.14**	45.68**	26.43**
RH0735 x BPR543-3	Normal	9.15**	6.28**	3.19**	-5.13	0.94**	-1.47	-30.34**	-34.04**	20.75**	-3.51
	Late	5.34**	1.82**	-0.95	-2.64	-3.09	-5.69	-17.86**	-22.30**	-4.39	-4.73
RH0116 x BPR349-9	Normal	1.64**	0.62**	0.38**	-1.75	4.76**	2.39**	3.70	-6.67	7.80	1.35
	Late	6.03**	2.00**	1.60**	-2.45	-4.93	-5.51	-3.68	-6.51	13.94	5.56

RH0116 x RH0952	Normal	1.49**	0.98**	-6.21	-9.82	3.43**	3.43	16.20**	-7.55	20.94**	11.74
	Late	3.38**	2.37**	-0.71	-1.58	3.75**	1.06	10.31**	6.19	41.26**	36.94**
RH0116 x RH0555A	Normal	0.08**	-2.47	-3.16	-4.42	1.77**	-2.31	53.26**	31.80**	30.21**	19.83**
	Late	-2.10	-2.94	0.09**	-3.90	1.71**	-0.16	15.47**	12.11**	-6.39	-17.21**
RH0116 x RH0644	Normal	-5.77	-11.47	-5.83	-9.44	4.01**	1.04	-29.67**	-43.27**	-7.91	-9.44
	Late	-1.45	-3.02	-10.72	-12.16	-2.55	-2.91	-36.42**	-40.85**	-5.96	-10.67*
RH0116 x BPR543-3	Normal	-3.49	-6.72	4.11**	-2.25	5.10**	2.34	11.33*	-1.70	-3.13	-5.56
	Late	10.44**	9.76**	-7.43	-8.55	0.71**	-1.64	-35.18**	-40.00**	-1.75	-6.67
BPR349-9 x RH0952	Normal	0.42**	-0.96	-3.99	-5.73	2.75**	0.419	-5.95	-18.23**	-28.50**	-35.00**
	Late	4.55**	1.54**	-6.71	-9.66	1.84**	-1.38	-8.20*	9.50*	5.26	2.36
BPR349-9 x RH0555A	Normal	-1.60	-3.03	-6.44	-9.47	-0.78	-2.47	27.79**	21.40**	-0.50	-9.17*
	Late	2.78**	-0.29	4.46**	4.46**	-11.37	-13.53	-43.74**	-46.64**	28.74**	19.15**
BPR349-9 x RH0644	Normal	-5.79	-10.65	-10.96	-12.56	1.54**	0.91	-38.28**	-45.49**	-14.69**	-16.11**
	Late	1.86**	-0.59	3.86**	1.46**	0.69**	-0.28	-8.11**	-16.39**	2.75	-2.96
BPR349-9 x BPR543-3	Normal	-2.73	-4.93	9.20**	0.62**	-1.13	-1.38	4.57	2.34	-13.96**	-16.11**
	Late	5.47**	1.94**	-3.28	-8.11	-2.08	-4.94	2.39	-7.30*	0.39	-5.19
RH0952 x RH0555A	Normal	0.12**	-2.75	-6.11	-10.74	1.22**	-2.71	-16.36**	-23.33**	-14.95**	-16.51**
	Late	-0.83	-0.95	3.22**	-0.04	4.33**	3.66	3.15	-4.48	14.94**	6.38
RH0952 x RH0644	Normal	-5.52	-11.69	-3.12	-3.24	-9.38	-11.86	-29.23**	-30.00**	-30.73**	-36.67**
	Late	-2.14	-2.75	1.45**	0.67**	0.00	-2.11	-23.96**	-32.38**	-21.57**	-25.93**
RH0952 x BPR543-3	Normal	3.18**	-0.59	6.68**	-3.32	1.63**	-0.92	-37.01**	-43.83**	-26.51**	-33.33**
	Late	-4.15	-4.63	-12.57	-14.27	1.34**	1.075	-16.34**	-25.95**	-16.08**	-20.74**
RH0555A x RH0644	Normal	-2.87	-6.58	2.52**	-2.52	-2.33	-3.52	-14.13**	-19.76**	-5.21	-13.33**
	Late	1.38**	0.62**	-10.36	-12.44	-3.94	-5.37	-6.61*	-11.20**	-3.86	-8.67
RH0555A x BPR543-3	Normal	-4.05	-4.85	9.67**	4.27**	-8.74	-10.07	15.10**	10.59*	-10.76**	-19.05**
	Late	2.32**	2.06**	-12.12	-16.50	-4.62	-5.11	-36.14**	-39.59**	-5.96	-10.67*
RH0644 x BPR543-3	Normal	-2.89	-5.83	9.02**	-1.32	-0.29	-0.66	12.71**	0.50	-19.09**	-21.11**
	Late	1.09**	-0.04	-15.54	-17.80	-2.48	-4.42	2.60	1.22	-10.59	-15.56**
CD, at 5 %	Normal	0.012	0.014	0.013	0.015	0.017	0.020	1.38	1.60	0.51	0.58
	Late	0.017	0.020	0.012	0.014	0.013	0.016	1.27	1.47	0.46	0.53
CD at 1 %	Normal	0.017	0.019	0.017	0.020	0.023	0.027	1.84	2.12	0.67	0.77
	Late	0.023	0.027	0.016	0.019	0.018	0.021	1.69	1.96	0.61	0.69

*, **, significant at=0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

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advancing these crosses through pedigree selection in successive segregating generation. These results for chlorophyll fluorescence were also reported earlier by Shanthi *et al* (2011) in rice.

Seedling mortality (%)- Significant and negative heterosis over mid-parent for seedling mortality was manifested by eight crosses namely; RH8814 x RH0735, RH8814 x RH0644, RH0735 x BPR543-3, RH0116 x RH0644, BPR349-9 x RH0644, RH0952 x RH0644, RH0952 x BPR543-3 and RH0555A x RH0644 in both the environments. Negative and significant heterosis over better parent was expressed by the seven cross combinations viz., RH8814 x RH0735, RH0116 x RH0644, BPR349-9 x RH0952, BPR349-9 x RH0644, RH0952 x RH0644, RH0952 x BPR543-3 and RH0555A x RH0644 in both the environments. Similar results for seedling mortality were also reported earlier by Sio-Se *et al* (2006), Sharma *et al* (2011, 2012), Sharma and Sardana (2013).

Seed yield/plant (g)- Maximum significant positive heterosis was exhibited by cross RH8814 x BPR543-3 (73.19%) followed by RH8814 x RH0555A (70.49%) and RH0644 x BPR543-3(67.80%) in timely sown condition where as six crosses exhibited significant and positive mid-parent heterosis and maximum heterosis was exhibited by cross RH8814 x BPR349-9 (58.15%) followed by the cross RH0116 x RH0644 (57.85%) and RH0735 x RH0116 (46.06%) in late sown condition. Heterosis over mid-parent for seed yield/plant ranged from -16.29 (to 73.19 in timely sown condition and -51.18 to 68.47 in late sown condition. Significant and positive heterosis over better parent was manifested by three crosses namely; RH0116 x BPR543-3, BPR349-9 x RH0644 and RH0555A x RH0644 in both the environments and the cross RH8814 x BPR543-3(62.31%) recorded maximum positive heterosis over better parent followed by RH8814 x RH0555A (56.90%) and RH8814 x RH0116(54.99%) in timely sown condition. The significant and maximum positive heterosis over better parent in late sown condition manifested by

the crosses namely; RH8814 x BPR349-9(56.35%) followed by RH0116 x RH0644 (46.67%) and RH0116 x RH0952 (36.94%). Heterobeltiosis for seed yield/plant ranged from -25.61 (RH0735 x BPR349-9) to 62.31 (RH8814 x BPR543-3) in timely sown condition and -53.73 (RH0735 x RH0555A) to 66.02 (BPR349-9 x RH0644) in late sown condition. These high yielding crosses may be exploited for developing superior genotypes and the parents involved may be converted to well adapted cytoplasmic male sterile or restorer lines to develop commercially viable hybrids. Positive significant heterosis for seed yield in late sown condition was also reported earlier by different workers; Kumar *et al.* (2007), Aher *et al.* (2009), Nasrin *et al.* (2011), Vaghela *et al.* (2011) and Verma *et al.*(2011).

CONCLUSION

From the present investigations it is concluded that crosses RH8814 x RH0555A, RH0644 x BPR543-3 and BPR349-9 x RH0644 in timely sown condition and crosses RH0555A x RH0644, RH0735 x RH0116 and BPR349-9 x RH0644 in late sown condition were identified as promising on the basis of their high per se performance, average heterosis, heterobeltiosis may used in future breeding programmes for improving the seed yield and related traits in Indian mustard.

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Table: 5 Top five heterotic hybrids for seed yield/plant and its physiological component traits in Indian mustard

Environment	Superior heterotic hybrids for seed yield/plant over mid and better parent	Heterosis for its component traits
Normal	RH8814 x BPR543-3	CT 40 DAS, CT 50 DAS, CT 60 DAS, seed yield per plant
Late	RH8814x BPR349-9	CT40 DAS, CT 50 DAS, CF 50 DAS, seed yield per plant
Normal	RH8814 x RH0555A	CF 40 DAS, CF 60 DAS, seed yield per plant
Late	BPR349-9 x RH0644	CT 50 DAS, CF 40 DAS, CF 60 DAS, seedling mortality, seed yield per plant
Normal	RH8814 x RH0116	CT 40 DAS, CT 50 DAS, CF 40 DAS, CF 50 DAS, CF 60 DAS, seed yield/plant
Late	RH0555A x RH0644	CF 40 DAS, CF 50 DAS, seedling mortality, seed yield/plant
Normal	BPR349-9 x BPR543-3	CT 70 DAS, CF 40 DAS, CF 60 DAS, seed yield per plant
Late	RH0116 x RH0644	Seedling mortality, CF 40 DAS, Seed yield/plant
Normal	RH0644 x BPR543-3	Seed yield per plant
Late	RH0735 x RH0116	CT 40 DAS, CT 50 DAS, CF 40 DAS, CF 50 DAS, CF 70 DAS, Seed yield per plant

CT: Canopy temperature, CF: Chlorophyll fluorescence, DAS: Days after sowing

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Nutrient Management in Wheat through Front Line Demonstrations in Hingoli District

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ABSTRACT

The FLD's of wheat were conducted during the *rabi* season at twelve farmers' field to demonstrate production potential and economic benefit of recommended technologies consisting of recommended nutrient management (100:50:50:20 NPKS kg/ha + *Azotobacter* + PSB @ 25 g/kg seed) over existing farmers practices of (local check 64:46:30:00 NPKS kg ha⁻¹) at Hingoli district of Maharashtra during *rabi* season 2011-2012 and 2014-2015. Each front line demonstration was laid out on 0.40 ha area with farmers practices were considered as existing farmer practice for comparison. Recommended nutrient management technologies recorded mean yield of 25.12q/ha which was 21.33 per cent higher than that obtained with farmer's practice. The average technology gap and index were found to be 4.38 q/ha and 16.25 per cent. Improved soil fertility status at the time of harvest in demonstration plot as compared to farmer practice (local check) will save the fertilizer doses due to its judicious use of fertilizers.

Key words: Front Line Demonstration, wheat, Lok-1, BC ratio

INTRODUCTION

Wheat is the second most important winter cereal in India after rice contributing substantially to the national food security. The wheat programme in India has released 399 wheat varieties, comprising bread wheat (335), durum (54), dicoccum, (5) and triticale (5) for cultivation under different production in all the wheat growing zones (Anonymous, 2012). The growing situations vary from harsh conditions in peninsular and central regions to the favourable conditions of northern India. Wheat grown in rain fed and dry land area is faced with water scarcity, temperature extremes and minimal use of nutrients that limit the yield potential and also results in irregular production. The productivity of wheat per unit area could be increased by adopting recommended scientific and sustainable management production practices using suitable high yielding varieties. Front line demonstrations (FLD) were carried out in a systematic manner at farmers' field to convince farmers to adopt improved production management practices for enhancing wheat productivity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participatory rural appraisal (PRA), group discussion and transect talk were followed to explore the detail information of study area. Twelve FLD's were conducted during *rabi* season of 2011-2012 and 2014-2015 in two villages namely Sukali vir and Bhategaon, respectively. The area under each demonstration was 0.4 ha. The soil was medium black to black cotton soil with low to medium organic carbon (0.20 to 60 %), low to medium in available phosphorus (8.20 to 17.00 kg/ha); very high in available potassium (up to 500 kg/ha) and soil pH was slightly alkali in nature. The treatment comprise of recommended practice (100:50:50:20 NPKS kg /ha + *Azotobacter* + PSB @ 25 g/kg seed). Fifty per cent dose of nitrogen, full P and K was applied as basal at time of sowing, remaining quantity of nitrogen applied 30 day after of sowing. The seeds were treated with *Azotobacter* and Phospho-solubilizing bacteria bio-fertilizer each 25 g/kg seed. Farmer's practice include imbalance fertilizer application (64:46:30:00 NPKS kg/ha) without seed treatment. All the participating

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Table 1: Production, technology gap, extension gap and technology index of wheat as affected by recommended practice as well as farmers practice under irrigated condition

Year	Area (ha)	No. of farmers	Grain yield (q/ha)				Per cent increase over FP	Technology gap (q/ha)	Extension gap (q/ha)	Technology index
			Potential	Recommended Practice		FP average				
				Highest	Lowest					
2011-12	4.8	12	30	26	20	23.58	19.00	4.58	21.4	
2014-15	4.8	12	30	28.50	24.30	25.67	22.49	4.18	11.1	
Total/mean	4.8	12	30	27.25	22.15	25.12	20.74	4.38	16.25	

Table 2: Economics and fertility status of front line demonstrations of wheat as affected by recommended practices as well as farmers practices under irrigated conditions

Year	No. of Farmers	Gross expenditure (Rs./ha)		Gross returns (Rs./ha)		Net returns (Rs./ha)		Additional net return (Rs./ha)	B:C Ratio		Fertility status							
		RP	FP	RP	FP	RP	FP		RP	FP	RP	FP	OC (%)		P (kg/ha)		K (kg/ha)	
													RP	FP	RP	FP	RP	FP
2011-12	12	20,860	20,950	27,096	22,800	6,236	1,850	4,386	1.29	1.12	0.35	0.33	16	10.50	536	463		
2014-15	12	27,750	28,150	45,333	38,236	17,583	10,086	7,497	1.63	1.36	0.43	0.37	13.50	15.70	433	461		
Total/mean	12	24,305	24,550	36,214	30,518	11,909	5,968	5,941	1.46	1.24	0.39	0.35	14.75	13.10	484.5	462		

Nutrient Management in

farmers were trained on all aspects of wheat production management before implementing the FLDs at their field. To study the impact of frontline demonstration, data from FLDs and local practices were collected and analyzed. The extension gap, technology gap and technology index along with benefit cost ratio were calculated using the formula as suggested by Samui *et al* (2000).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Technology Gap} &= \text{Potential yield} - \text{Demonstration Yield} \\ \text{Extension Gap} &= \text{Demonstration Yield} - \text{Farmers Yield} \\ \text{Technology Index} &= \frac{\text{Potential Yield} - \text{Demonstration Yield}}{\text{Potential Yield}} \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seed yield

Wheat productivity was 25.12 q/ha under recommended practice (100:50:50:20 NPKS kg/ha + *Azotobacter* + PSB @ 25 g/kg seed) on farmers field as against a yield 20.74 q/ha under existing farmers practice (64:46:30:00 NPKS kg/ha) with an increase of 21.33 per cent following recommended practices (Table 1). Similar results have been reported by Joshi *et al* (2015).

Economics

The inputs and outputs prices of commodities prevailed during both the year of demonstrations were taken for calculating cost of cultivation, net returns and benefit cost ration show in table 2. The investment on production by adopting recommended practices was Rs. 24,305/- ha against the traditional farmers practices (Rs. 24,550/- ha). The additional net income ranged from Rs. 4,386 to Rs. 7,497/- ha with mean value 5,941/- ha over farmers practice. The average benefit cost ratio of recommended practices was 1.46 and that of farmers practice was 1.24, this may be due to higher yields obtained under recommended practices compared to farmers practice. Similar results have been reported earlier on wheat by Tiwari *et al*, (2003).

Extension and technology gap

The extension gap ranged between 4.58-4.18 q/ha emphasized the need to educate the farmers through various mean for adoption of improved

agricultural production to reverse the trend of wide extension gap (table 1). The trend of technology gap ranged between 4.18-6.42 q/ha reflected the farmer's cooperation in carrying out such demonstration with encouraging results in both the years. The technology index of 21.4 to 11.1 per cent showed the feasibility of the evolved technology at the farmer's field. The reduction in technology index exhibited the feasibility of the demonstrated technology in this region.

Soil Fertility Status

The soil fertility status was increased during both the year of demonstrations soil sample were taken at the time harvesting for soil analyzing data are presented in table 2. The data revealed that increase the mean organic carbon 0.39 per cent in demonstration plot as compared to 0.35 per cent by farmer's practice. Similar is the case with available phosphorus and potassium. This also save the fertilizer as well as soil fertility status could be maintained due to judicious use of fertilizers.

CONCLUSION

FLD is playing one of the important roles in motivation the farmers for adoption of based on soil test nutrient management in wheat production. Favorable benefit cost ratio is self explanatory of economic viability of the demonstration and convinced the farmer balance fertilizer use in wheat production. The technology suitable for enhancing the productivity of wheat, calls for conduct of such demonstrations under the transfer of technology programme by KVKs.

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Performance of Different Genotypes of Chilli (*Capsicum annum*) under Allahabad Agro-Climatic Condition

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ABSTRACT

The investigation was carried out at the Vegetable Research Farm in the Department of Horticulture, Allahabad Agricultural Institute-Deemed University, Allahabad to evaluate the performance of 20 genotypes under Allahabad agro-climatic conditions. All twenty genotypes were tested in a randomized block design with 3 replications. The observations were recorded on 14 quantitative traits and 3 qualitative traits i.e. plant height at 100 d, 120 d, days to 1st flowering, days to 50 per cent flowering, days to 1st green fruit harvest, average fruit length, average fruit diameter, average green fruit yield/plant, days to 1st red ripe fruit harvest, average weight of red ripe fruit yield, number of seeds/fruit, weight of seeds/ fruit, ascorbic acids, oleoresin (%) and capsaicin content (%). The earliest day to 1st flowering amongst genotypes was recorded with the Pusa Jawala (31.66) followed by LCA 301 (32), JCA 9(32.33) and the maximum days to 1st flowering were noticed in LCA 333 (41.66). Days to 50 per cent flowering was also observed significant among genotypes. The minimum days to first green fruit harvest was recorded in LCA 357 (79.00) followed by LCA 404 (80.66) and Pusa Jawala (81.33) while genotype LCA 301 (96.33) took maximum days to first green fruit harvest. There were significant differences among genotypes for capsaicin (%) content. The maximum capsaicin (%) was found in IC 413702 (0.62%) followed by Pbc 1438 (0.51%) and IC-383079(0.47%), while JCA 9(0.16%) was found with minimum capsaicin.

Key words: : Ascorbic acid, Chilli, Correlation, Path coefficient, Flowering , Green fruit yield, Oleoresin.

INTRODUCTION

Chilli (*Capsicum annum*) is one of the most important vegetable as well as spice crop, belongs to family Solanaceae. It is a self pollinated crop bearing a pod like fruit (berry) and has a predominant position among the spices grown all over India. It is being grown for green/red chillies in Uttar Pradesh during summer, rainy and winter seasons. The important chemical constituents of chilli fruits include vitamins, pungency, colouring matter oleoresin contents, which are particularly important for food and spice industries. Chillies are mostly used as spices but sometimes it is also used as vegetables. Fruits are used in pickles, sauces, ketchups, chutneys and oleoresin. The

present investigation was carried out to evaluate the performance of 20 genotypes under Allahabad agro-climatic conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was conducted during August-December, 2006 at the Vegetable Research Farm in the Department of Horticulture. It is situated at 25.750 latitude and 81.500E longitude and 98 m above mean sea level (MSL). The experimental field has an even topography with a gentle slope and good drainage. The soil samples were drawn from each replication of experimental plot at 15 cm depth before the sowing of the crop and a composite sample was prepared to determine the physical and

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chemical properties of soil. The Allahabad region has a sub-tropical and semi-arid climate and the temperature rise up to 45°C to 48°C in summer and goes down to as low as 2.50°C during winter. The present investigation was carried out to find out the variation in different stage and growth in Chilli. The different genotypes tested were Pusa Jawala, SM 20, JCA 9, IC 413702, IC 383079, Japani long, Pbc 1438, LCA 206, LCA 301, LCA304, LCA 312, LCA 324, LCA 333, LCA 334, LCA 357, LCA 404, CO56861, Kashi Anmol, EC 492576 and Utkal Ragini taken from Indian Institute of Vegetable Research, Varanasi.

Observations were recorded with respect to Plant height (days), 1st flowering (days), 50 per cent flowering (days), 1st green fruit harvest (days), average weight of green fruits (g), average fruit length (cm), average fruit diameter (cm), average green fruit yield/plant (g), 1st ripe fruit harvest (days), average weight of red ripe (g), average red ripe fruit yield (g), number of seed/fruit, weight of seeds/fruit (g), ascorbic acid (mg/100g), Oleoresin (%), Capsaicin (%) and qualitative parameters. Ascorbic acid was estimated titrimetrically using 2-6 dichlorophenol indophenols method (Sadasivam and Manickam, 1992). Oleoresin and Capsaicin content (%) was determined by Folin-Dennis method (Mathew *et al*, 1971) in chilli powder.

The data were pooled and statistically calculated for analysis of the R.B.D. design, mean, Range and Analysis of variance described by Panse and Sukhatme (1967).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The perusal of data (Table 1) showed that a large amount of variability was present in plant height. The maximum plant height was observed in LCA 206 (51.83cm) and the minimum in Kashi Anmol (37.53cm) against the population mean of 41.96 cm. All the genotypes under study exhibited higher mean values as compared to general mean (41.96), while Pusa Jawala (39.76cm) and LCA 304 (42.9CM) showed lower mean values. Significant

differences were found for days to 1st flowering amongst different genotypes.

The earliest day to 1st flowering amongst genotypes was recorded with the Pusa Jawala (31.66) followed by LCA 301 (32), JCA 9(32.33) and the maximum days to 1st flowering were noticed in LCA 333 (41.66). Days to 50 per cent flowering was also observed significant among genotypes. Japani Long (58.00) and LCA 334 (57.33) took maximum days to 50 per cent flowering and the minimum days were recorded with the genotype SM 20 (51.66).

Significant differences were found for days to first green fruit harvest among various genotypes. The minimum days to first green fruit harvest was recorded in LCA 357 (79.00) followed by LCA 404 (80.66) and Pusa Jawala (81.33) while genotype LCA 301 (96.33) took maximum days to first green fruit harvest. Significantly the maximum weight of green fruit was recorded in EC 492576 (22.93g), followed by LCA 206 (18.88g), IC 38079 (18.65g) and JCA 9 (11.69g), while genotype Pusa Jawala (8.22g) was found to be with minimum weight of green fruit. Maximum fruit length was observed significant in IC 413702 (12.16cm) followed by SM 20 (11.50 cm), Pusa Jawala (10.5 cm) and LCA 206 (9.56cm) and the minimum fruit length was recorded in Pbc 1438 (4.33cm).

There were significant differences amongst different genotypes for the diameter. The maximum fruit diameter was observed in LCA 206 (2.63cm) followed by SM 20 (2.46cm) and LCA404 (2.40cm), while LCA 312(1.23cm) was found with minimum fruit diameter. Significantly the maximum average green fruit yield was found in SM 20 (168.42g) followed by Pusa Jawala (143.98g) and Utkal Ragani(140.43g), while LCA 301 (34.72G) was found with minimum green fruit yield. Days to first ripe fruit harvest was also recorded significant. LCA 404 took maximum days (130.00) followed by SM 120.00) and Kashi Anmol (120.00), whereas CO 5686 1 took minimum days for first ripe fruit harvest (103.00).

Performance of Different Genotypes of Chilli

Table 1. Mean performance of different genotypes for various characters in Chillies.

Genotype	Plant height at 120 d	Days to 1st flowering	Days to 50% flowering	Days to 1st green fruit harvest	Av. wt. of green fruits (g)	Av. fruit length (cm)	Av. fruit diameter (cm)	Av. green fruit yield/plant (g)	Days to 1st ripe fruit harvest	Av. wt. of red ripe	Av. red ripe fruit yield	No. of seed/fruit	Wt. of seeds/fruit	Ascorbic acid (mg/100g)	Oleoresin (%)	Capsaicin (%)
Pusa Jawala	39.76	31.66	55.00	81.33	8.22	10.5	1.60	143.98	110.66	11.50	125.55	31.66	0.616	52.51	16.52	0.23
SM-20	40.33	36.33	51.66	85.00	9.75	11.5	2.46	168.42	120.00	10.81	102.89	31.33	0.633	42.55	14.50	0.33
JCA-9	39.16	32.33	51.66	85.00	9.75	11.5	2.46	168.42	116.66	12.48	91.57	64.00	0.713	19.49	16.92	0.16
LCA-206	51.83	38.66	53.66	83.33	18.88	9.56	2.63	97.74	49.10	37.33	52.33	80.66	9.66	8.16	2.40	0.67
LCA-404	49.10	37.33	52.33	80.66	9.60	8.16	2.40	65.67	130.00	26.78	68.47	39.00	0.563	38.05	13.60	0.43
IC-413702	47.76	36.66	52.66	84.66	9.60	8.3	1.86	53.083	115.00	20.63	49.80	40.00	0.676	33.92	16.91	0.62
Japani long	40.20	40.33	58.00	90.00	5.37	9.5	2.33	71.30	111.33	11.87	68.61	52.66	0.523	19.32	13.51	0.41
Pbc-1438	48.33	40.66	58.00	90.00	5.37	9.5	2.33	71.33	104.00	23.52	95.99	55.66	0.738	40.95	9.30	0.51
IC-383079	48.03	39.00	54.66	85.00	18.65	12.16	2.06	69.21	111.00	19.79	57.37	38.66	0.84	28.10	11.17	0.47
LCA-333	51.73	41.66	64.66	83.66	8.09	8.83	2.26	39.42	116.66	12.48	33.17	33.66	0.670	32.85	14.62	0.25
LCA-334	50.66	39.00	57.33	80.66	18.16	9.16	1.33	49.63	117.33	16.35	46.57	41.66	0.813	26.10	13.20	0.35
CO-5686-1	42.00	39.33	52.00	81.66	8.32	8.66	1.73	68.20	103.00	13.01	63.28	111.0	1.056	28.21	15.11	0.32
Kashi Anmol	37.53	40.33	55.00	89.66	8.24	9.66	1.76	133.42	120.00	10.52	101.14	51.00	0.756	25.10	13.54	0.20
LCA-357	42.00	39.66	55.00	79.00	12.05	8.33	2.36	35.39	119.00	11.69	34.05	51.33	0.703	46.18	10.53	0.20
EC-492576	45.46	40.66	56.66	84.21	22.93	9.16	2.03	42.93	122.33	13.20	41.29	86.00	1.010	104.82	14.94	0.23
Utkal Ragini	40.23	41.33	56.00	86.21	9.79	4.73	1.53	140.43	111.33	13.42	116.18	31.00	0.640	24.71	15.35	0.22
LCA-324	41.00	35.00	52.66	94.33	9.85	5.00	1.63	39.42	116.33	11.27	102.21	40.33	0.710	25.19	13.48	0.31
LCA-312	44.66	40.33	55.33	94.66	9.93	4.73	1.23	44.30	111.66	13.06	91.50	37.66	0.630	46.49	11.25	0.25
LCA-301	39.33	32.00	52.66	96.33	9.10	5.63	1.63	34.72	115.33	18.99	80.30	41.66	0.713	37.41	13.49	0.20
LCA304	42.66	33.00	51.66	93.66	8.75	6.90	2.30	53.88	15.49	77.17	47.95	0.71	36.73	13.95	16.23	0.62
Grand mean	44.09	37.76	54.83	86.24	11.40	8.06	77.65	114.53	15.49	77.17	47.95	0.71	36.73	13.95	16.23	0.62
F-test	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
SEm(+)	1.34	0.87	0.96	1.96	0.47	0.29	1.58	1.78	0.74	1.08	1.37	0.02	0.58	0.58	0.26	0.52
C.D.at 5%	4.12	3.83	2.50	2.77	3.03	1.37	2.13	4.55	5.11	2.13	3.11	3.95	0.06	0.06	0.48	2.31

Significant differences were found for red ripe fruit weight. The maximum average weight of red ripe fruit was observed in LCA 404 (26.78g), followed by Pbc 1438 (23.52g) and IC 413702 (20.63g), while Kashi Anmol (10.52g) was found minimum weight of red ripe fruit. Significantly the maximum red ripe fruit yield was found in Pusa Jawala (125.55g) followed by Utkal Ragini (116.18g) and SM 20(102.89g), while LCA 333 (33.17g) was found with minimum red ripe fruit yield.

The number of seeds/fruit was also found significant. The maximum average number of seeds/fruit was observed in CO 5681 1 (111.00) followed by EC 492576 (86.00) and JCA 9 (64.00), while Utkal Ragini(31.00) was recorded with minimum average number of seeds/fruit. Significantly maximum average weight of seeds/fruit was recorded in CO 5681 1 (1.05g) followed by EC 492576 (1.010g) and LCA 334 (0.813g), while Japani Long((0.523) recorded minimum average weight of seeds/fruit. There were significant differences among genotypes for ascorbic acid contents. The maximum ascorbic acid 104.82mg/100g was found in EC 492576 (104.82mg), followed by Pusa Jawala (52.51mg) and LCA 312 (46.49), while LCA 206 was found with minimum ascorbic acid (16.71mg). For Oleoresin (%) content there were significant differences. The maximum oleoresin (%) content was recorded I JCA 9(16.92%) followed by IC 413702(16.91%) and Pusa Jawala (16.52%), while LCA 357 was observed with minimum oleoresin content. There were significant differences among genotypes for capsaicin (%) content. The maximum capsaicin (%) was found in IC 413702 (0.62%) followed by Pbc 1438 (0.51%) and IC-383079(0.47%), while JCA 9(0.16%) was found with minimum capsaicin.

Varietal variation in capsaicin content in hot chilli (*Capsicum chinense*) have been reported by Cherian (2000).

CONCLUSION

Based on performance SM 20, JCA 9, Pusa Jawala, Utakal Ragini and Kashi anmol exhibited high fruit yield per plant. Among all the genotypes SM 20 was found to be highest yielder i.e. 168.42 g/plant. There were significant differences among genotypes for capsaicin (%) content and the maximum capsaicin was found in IC 413702 followed by Pbc 1438 and IC 383079, while JCA 9 was found with minimum capsaicin. The maximum ascorbic acid was found in EC 492576 followed by Pusa Jawala and LCA 312, while LCA 206 was found with minimum ascorbic acid. LCA 404 took maximum days followed by SM 20 and Kashi Anmol whereas CO 5686 1 took minimum days for first ripe fruit harvest.

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Performance of Mechanical Reaper for Ragi (*Eleusine coracana* L.) Harvesting

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ABSTRACT

A study on Front line demonstration of power tiller mounted mechanical reaper was conducted at farmers' field in Magadi taluk of Ramanagar district by Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK), Ramanagara. Demonstrations were carried out at 25 farmers field covering an area of 11 há during kharif 2013-14 and 2014-15 seasons. The Results of the study showed that harvesting of ragi using reaper had reduced time of operation by 72 per cent, total labour dependency by 92 per cent and cost of cultivation by 81 per cent as compared to manual operation. Field capacity of ragi reaper was found to be 0.23 ha/hr in comparison to manual operation. This demonstration helped the farmers in creating awareness and inculcating the knowledge of the mechanization, which in turn help them to get more returns. Farmer opined that mechanical reaper was easy to operate, can reduce drudgery and overcomes labour scarcity during crucial stage of operation.

Key words: Demonstration, Field capacity, Labour, Mechanization, Ragi reaper,

INTRODUCTION

Mechanization plays an important role to carry out timely operation, reducing labour and drudgery in agriculture. Ramanagara district is predominantly oriented with ragi (*Eleusine coracana* L.) crop covering an area of 62326 ha. One of the important operations in ragi cultivation is harvesting. This operation is carried using locally available sickle which is time consuming and needs more number of labours per unit area. Non-availability of labour during peak periods also accounts for more expenditure. Majority of the farmers come under small and marginal category. These fragmented lands have lower productivity due to the inadequate operation and merger use of the precise farm machineries (Srivastava, 2004). The timeliness of operations has assumed greater significant in obtaining optimal yields from different crops, which is possible by way of mechanization.

Reaper harvesters on the other hand are other alternative for harvesting purpose, provided straw is considered as economic by-product for animal feed and/or industrial applications. Therefore, KVK,

Ramanagara demonstrated use of ragi reaper with the objective to evaluate its field performance over conventional method of harvesting and compare the cost of operation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Front line demonstrations were carried out at 25 farmers' field covering 11 ha in villages namely Dhonehalli, Gollaratti, Srigiripur of Magadi taluk of Ramanagara district. Reaper cum harvester was hired from custom hiring centre and harvesting was carried out consecutively for two years 2013-14 and 2014-15. In addition to that, awareness about the importance of mechanization was also created through various extension activities like on campus and off campus training programmes, demonstrations, group discussions, literatures and other extension activities. Harvesting of ragi using labourers was studied in comparison to mechanized harvesting of ragi using ragi reaper. Data regarding time and cost of operation, labour charges and number of labourers required in harvesting were recorded.

Field evaluation

The specification of the mechanical reaper has been given in Table 1.

Table 1. Technical specifications of Ragi reaper.

Sr. No	Particular	Specification
1	Width of cut (m)	1.0
2	Row spacing (m)	0.3
3	Number of blades	24
4	No. of persons required for operation	1
5	Forward Speed of travel (km/hr)	2.20
6	Width of machine (m)	1.45
7	Length of machine (m)	2.40
8	Height of machine (m)	0.87
9	Weight of machine (kg)	120
10	Power source	Petrol engine, 5 H.P
11	Cost of the machine (Rs)	1,07,000/-

To evaluate the efficacy of the reaper, following performance criteria were considered.

- Field capacity of the machine
- Field efficiency of the machine
- Harvesting losses
- Savings in labour, time and cost of operation over conventional method of harvesting.

Actual Field capacity

Field capacity is the actual area covered by the machine or implement under actual time usually expressed in ha/hr. It is the quantum of work turned out by the machine. Field capacity should be the maximum with least effort for minimizing field losses.

$$\text{Actual Field capacity (ha/hr)} = \frac{\text{Actual area covered, ha}}{\text{Time taken, hr}}$$

Theoretical Field capacity

Theoretical field capacity was calculated based on the forwarded speed and the width of the equipment. It was calculated as

$$\text{Theoretical field capacity} = \frac{W \times S}{10}$$

Where, W = Width of the implement, m and S = Speed of operation (km/hr).

Field efficiency

The field efficiency of the machine indicates the efficacy of the machine and operator, in reducing the time taken in turning and stoppage for adjustments.

$$\text{Field efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Actual field capacity (ha/hr)}}{\text{Theoretical field capacity (ha/hr)}} \times 100$$

A rectangular type of field helps in achieving higher field efficiency. Higher field efficiency reduces the cost of operation.

Speed of travel (Forward speed)

For measuring forward speed of reaper while harvesting of crop, the distance reaper travelled in 15 seconds was measured and speed of travel was recorded in terms of km/hr (Alizadeh *et al*, 2007)

Harvesting losses

In order to estimate harvesting losses in manual and reaper harvesting, the losses that occurred before harvesting (pre-harvest) must be measured. To do this, in four parts of each plot with the use of wooden frame with 1m×1m dimensions, all grains fallen within the frame are collected and weighed and the mean of the four measured values are recorded. Harvesting losses include shattering and uncut losses and were determined by the following equation (Pradhan *et al*, 1998)

$$W_{gt} = W_{g1} + W_{g2} + W_{g3}$$

Where, Wgt = Total losses (g/m²),
Wg₁ = Pre harvest losses (g/ m²)

Wg² = Shattering losses (g/ m²) Wg³ = Uncut losses (g/ m²)

After measuring the amount of losses at different stages, the percentage of harvest losses were determined by the following equation

$$H = \frac{W_{gt} - W_{g1}}{Y_g} \times 100$$

Where,

H = Percentage of harvest losses (%)

Wg₁ = Pre-harvest losses (g/m²)

Wgt = Total harvesting losses (g/m²)

Y_g = Grain yield (g/m²)

Stubbles left in the field was also measured using scale and expressed in metric unit.

Performance of Mechanical Reaper

Table 2. Comparative economics of operations between Ragi reaper and manual harvesting.

Operation	Total time taken(hr/ha)			Total number of labours /ha			Total cost of cultivation (Rs/ha)		
	Mechanization	Manual	Efficiency over Manual (%)	Mechanization	Manual	Efficiency over Manual (%)	Mechanization	Manual	Efficiency over Manual (%)
Harvesting	5	18	72	2	25	92	3000	15625	81

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results (Table 3) revealed that overall time taken for harvesting of ragi by reaper was reduced by 72 per cent compared to manual harvesting. Similar results were found by Shelke (2011). Labour dependency to harvest one hectare area of ragi using mechanical reaper was reduced by 92 per cent while cost of cultivation was reduced by 81 per cent over manual operations, Thus there was a saving an amount of Rs.12, 625/ha.

The effective width of reaper was 1.0 m and forward speed of machine was 2.20 km/hr for. The cost of the fuel was included to work out the cost of cultivation. The average fuel consumption recorded was 1.2 l/hr.

The Actual field capacity of the reaper was found to be 0.23 ha/hr whereas, theoretical field capacity was recorded 0.31 ha/hr, but these values differ with crop condition, labourers ability and climate conditions. Field efficiency was found to be 74.1 per cent (Table 2).

The measured values of pre harvest losses were found to be 3.54 per cent whereas post harvest losses under manual and ragi reaper conditions were 4.21 and 5.30 per cent, respectively.

The harvesting losses were more than pre-harvest and manual harvesting but were in acceptable limit (Kumar, *et al*). This may be due to mechanical action of harvester and physiological maturity of crop. The stubble height left over in the field after harvesting was 130 mm and in manual harvested plots, it was 55mm. the cost of cultivation under ragi reaper was found to be Rs. 3000/-ha against

Rs. 15,625/-ha under manual harvesting. Therefore, it was evident that harvesting with ragi reaper was the most economical.

CONCLUSION

Scarcity of manual labours and drudgery to carry out field operation calls for different power sources. Time and labour are crucial resources in cultivation of field crops. Adoption of mechanization in cultural operations not only reduces drudgery but also saves time considerably resulting in lower cost of cultivation and increased returns. Farmers opined that adoption of mechanization not only reduces the drudgery, reduces cost of cultivation but also increases more returns per unit time and area.

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Popularization of Horse Gram (*Macrotyloma uniflorum*) in Vellore District of Tamil Nadu

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ABSTRACT

Horse Gram, *Macrotyloma uniflorum* (Fabaceae) although rich in proteins (20 %) but due to less acceptable taste and flavour of cooked products, it is consumed only by the farming community and low-income groups. In Tamil Nadu, total area cultivated under horse gram crop is 48,000 ha and covering an area of 8,000 ha in Vellore district. It is mostly grown under rainfed conditions during the month of October after the receipt of north east monsoon. In order to introduce new potential horse gram varieties, on farm trials were conducted through Krishi Vigyan Kendra during 2014-15. It was found that 32.35 per cent higher yield was obtained in the recommended variety CRIDA 18R over the local variety with higher BCR of 2.4. In the succeeding year 2015-16, front line demonstrations were conducted and found that variety CRIDA 18R of horse gram gave higher grain yield over the local variety Paiyur 2, with a net return of 29.7 per cent higher than the local variety. Thus, the study clearly revealed that the variety CRIDA 18R has more potential than the local variety under rainfed conditions of Vellore district.

Key Words: Horse gram, Number of fruits/plant, Grain yield, Net returns.

INTRODUCTION

The horse gram, *Macrotyloma uniflorum* (Fabaceae) is normally used to feed horses, though it is also commonly used in dishes. It is rich in proteins (20 %) but due to less acceptable taste and flavour of cooked products, it is consumed only by the farming community and low-income groups. Thus, it has remained an underutilized food legume (Aiyer, 1990). The district of Vellore comes under the North Eastern zone of Tamil Nadu wherein pulses are grown in a large area next to paddy and groundnut. In Tamil Nadu, total area cultivated under horse gram crop is 48,000 ha and in Vellore district, among the pulses red gram is grown in an area of 14,270 ha followed by horse gram covering an area of 8,000 ha.

In Vellore district, horse gram is mostly grown under rainfed conditions during the month of October

after the receipt of north east monsoon. Farmers get poor yield as they use age old their own stored seeds for cultivation and do not have awareness on high yielding varieties. Quality seeds contribute 10-15 per cent increase in yield in any crop. Other reasons for getting lower yield in case of pulse production are no adoption of seed treatment, non-application of micronutrient spray and no foliar spray of 2 per cent of diammonium phosphate (DAP) twice during flowering. Hence, to introduce and assess new horse gram varieties suitable for Vellore district, on farm trials were undertaken during 2014-2015 through Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Vellore and found that CRIDA 18R variety gave higher yield compared to local varieties. In the succeeding year 2015-16, the same variety was demonstrated and popularized to the farmers of Vellore district through frontline demonstrations.

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Table 1. Yield parameters of the OFT conducted during 2014-15.

Sr. No.	Parameter	CRIDA 18R	Local Paiyur 2
1	Plant population/ m ²	29.3	26.7
2	Grain yield (kg /ha)	900	680
3	Gross cost (Rs.)	7530	7370
4	Gross returns (Rs.)	18068	13671
5	Net returns (Rs.)	10538	6301
6	BCR	2.4	1.86

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the year 2014-15, an on farm trial (OFT) was conducted in the Anaicut block of Vellore district to assess the potential horse gram variety suitable under rainfed conditions. Seven farmers' fields were selected in the Anpoondi village and were provided with the seeds of horse gram variety CRIDA 18R purchased from Central Research Institute for Dryland Agriculture, Hyderabad along with bio-fertilizers like *rhizobium* and *phosphobacterium*. Sowing was taken up during *Rabi* season under rainfed situation. Based on the results of OFT, the variety CRIDA 18R was found to be promising and suitable under drought conditions for Vellore district in comparison with local horse gram variety. Hence, in the succeeding year 2015-16, the variety was popularized through Frontline demonstrations by distributing seeds of CRIDA 18R for 0.4ha land to 10 farmers in the villages of Kanagasamudram, Edapalyam, Kamatchiammanpettai and Rengampet coming under K. V. Kuppam block of Vellore

district. The seeds were sown during the first week of Nov 2015.

In the village of Edapalayam, an off campus training was conducted to enrich the knowledge on critical technologies to be followed in horse gram cultivation. In the training, farmers were advised about the importance of land preparation, selection of quality seeds, seed treatment with bio fertilizers and bio control agents, soil test based fertilizer application and foliar spray of pulse wonder during flower initiation stage. Farmers took up the cultivation of CRIDA 18R horse gram variety as per the advisory of scientists of Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Vellore. The frontline demonstrations were conducted by comparing the CRIDA 18R variety with local horse gram variety Paiyur 2. A demonstration plot was also laid out at the KVK farm premises for research comparison.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the results of the on farm trial conducted

Table 2. Yield parameters of FLD conducted during 2015-16

Sr. No.	Parameter	CRIDA 18R	Local Paiyur 2
1	Number of fruits/plant	47.5	38.1
2	Number of branches/plant	5.8	3.7
3	Plant height (cm)	35.7	59.6
4	Plant population/ m ² *	16.7	15.1
5	Grain yield (kg /ha)*	343	273
6	Gross cost (Rs.)	5249.1	5249.1
7	Gross returns (Rs.)	9421.5	7234.5
8	Net returns (Rs.)	4172.4	1985.4
9	BCR	1.79	1.38

Popularization of Horse Gram

during 2014-15, it was found that the plant population maintained in the demonstration plot was 29.3 as compared to 26.7 in farmers' practice plot. This in turn gave 32.35 per cent higher yield in the recommended horse gram variety CRIDA 18R over the local variety with higher BCR of 2.4. It was clearly revealed (Table 1) that the variety CRIDA 18R was having more potential than local variety under rainfed conditions.

It was pertinent to mention that during Nov 2015, unexpected heavy rainfall led to loss of crop stand at farmers' field who took up sowing in first week of Nov 2015 and hence there was a decline in grain yield as compared to yield obtained during 2014-15.

Growth parameters / Plant attributes

- **Plant type:** Horse gram variety CRIDA 18R is short bushy bunch type of plants while the local variety are spreading tall climbing habit plants
- **Plant height:** It is recorded a height of 59.6 cm in local horse gram variety of Paiyur 2 while CRIDA 18R plants were shorter with a height of 35.7 cm
- **Branching habit:** CRIDA 18R horse gram variety has more number of branches and nodes (56.8%) than the local variety which contributed to higher grain yield. (Table 2)
- **Maturity:** CRIDA 18R variety matures in 85-87d about 15-20d earlier than local variety
- **Non-shattering pods:** One of important character impressed the farmers is that pods of CRIDA 18R horse gram do not shatter after maturity and/or even on delayed harvest

Yield parameters

- CRIDA 18R horse gram variety bears more number of fruits per plant (24.7%) than local variety.

- In comparison with local Paiyur 2 horsegram variety, CRIDA 18R gave 25.6% higher yield.
- CRIDA 18R horse gram variety gave away net returns of 29.7% higher than the local variety.
- CRIDA 18R horse gram variety seeds are brownish red in colour and are bold seeded which fetched the farmers about Rs.50 per kg in the market compare to Rs.40 per kg in case of local variety.

The findings were in line with CRIDA research achievements 2010 where it was found that CRIDA's new horse gram varieties, CRIDA 18R and CRHG 4 performed better (up to 33% higher grain yield and 10-25d early maturity) than local checks in Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Kerala.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of on farm trial and frontline demonstrations conducted during 2014 to 2016, it was found that 32.35 per cent higher yield was obtained in the recommended variety CRIDA 18R over the local Paiyur 2 variety with higher BCR of 2.4. Further CRIDA 18R variety bear on an average 47.5 fruits per plant (24.7% more than local) and its seeds are brownish red in colour and are bold seeded fetching the farmers' higher price (Rs.10 per kg more than local variety). Thus the study clearly revealed that the variety CRIDA 18R has more potential than local variety under rainfed conditions of Vellore district.

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Problems of Lac Growers in Chhatisgarh

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ABSTRACT

This study has been undertaken to identify the nature of problems faced by the Lac growers with objectives to identify the socio-economic and psychological profile along with the problems of lac growers in the district and provide suggestions for improving income through lac cultivation. The Kanker district was selected purposively due to maximum area coverage. Total 60 lac growers from four villages of two blocks were randomly selected. The study shows the awareness among farmers as they do plantation of short-cycled host plants of Semialata rather than Kusum tress. The understanding of farmers is quite high about diseases, pest control, pruning, and other farming practices. Absence of organized market, Price fluctuation, Lack of training in harvesting, handling and processing of Lac was found to be major challenge for the farmers. Climatic changes and broodlac availability was reported as other issues. Organized effort from the government line departments, KVKs and forest department for capacity building of farmers are urgent requirements.

Key Words: Lac growers, , Lac industry, Forest, NTFP, Problems

INTRODUCTION

Lac is a natural heritage of our country has been associated with tribal and poor people providing regular income in absence of other cash crops. India is the major producer of lac, accounting for more than 50 per cent of the total world production (15,200 MT) followed by Thailand (8,000 MT), Indonesia (8,000 MT), China (1,000 MT) and Vietnam (400 MT) during the year 2010. About 85 per cent of the country's production is exported to various countries. Due to its wide variety of applications in industries and in various uses the demand for lac is increasing day by day. So there is a need of promoting lac cultivation. Chhattisgarh has immense potential in terms of favourable climate, soil type, geography and natural conditions. Government is also promoting lac cultivation through new policies and schemes like SGSY and MSP.

Lac industry makes vital contribution to the economic well being of about 3 M tribal population of the country. Unfortunately over the last three decades the production of stick lac has registered a continuous decline mainly due to natural causes like unfavorable weather conditions, pest attack etc. Rao and Singh (1990) studied that about 85 per cent of the annual lac production in this country is exported. Industrially advanced countries like U.S.A., U K West Germany and USSR etc. use lac in large quantities (61.65%). During the past several years, however, there has been a gradual drop in the world demand for lac, the largest single factor, which is responsible for such decline in the demand for Indian lac is the wide and violent fluctuation in prices. The countries with advanced chemical technology like USA, UK, and West Germany have developed methods for utilizing the cheaper Thai Seed lac and started importing more lac from

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Thailand and the demand for better quality high priced Indian lac have gone down. Lac production in India has shown wide fluctuations in yield in the past, seriously affecting the export potential of the country. One of the major factors responsible for this is the heavy loss of crop due to pests. The situation can be retrieved to a large extent, if effective and economic control of the pests could be achieved. It may thus be concluded that the judicious use of this insecticide can not only result in doubling / tripling the lac yield but also in producing healthy and even pest free broodlac, without harming the lac insect (rather in improving its performance), beneficial biota, and mammals etc.

Recent studies carried out by Indian Lac Research Institute in Ranchi district of Jharkhand and several lac growing villages of other regions have revealed that income generated from lac cultivation is next only to cultivation of paddy. The income from lac cultivation is about 8 per cent of their total agricultural income. Lac cultivation requires good technical knowledge. Lack of communication may hamper the production process and supply chain later on. The other major problem of this sector in the recent past has been the instability of the prices and frequent price crash in the local market. This has led to lack of interest among farmers to take up lac cultivation and the production has come down drastically in the recent past. Experts in this field say that the Indian lac industry is totally dependent on the export market and the uncertainty of production leading to the uncertainty of prices make foreign buyers worry to enter.

Given huge prospects of lac-industry in Chhattisgarh, this study has been undertaken to identify the nature of the problems faced by the lac growers and also to suggest remedial measures for the revival of lac cultivation

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Kanker district of Chattisgarh plains. Kanker district was selected purposively because the maximum area under the lac in Chhattisgarh plains comes under this district.

Narharpur and Charma block were selected for the study. Total 4 villages, two from each block were selected randomly. 15 respondents from each village who were engaged in lac production were selected randomly for the present study.

A detailed questionnaire was designed which covered all the aspects of profile with special focus on lac cultivation. Focused group discussion was another method which was used to identify key challenges faced by farmers in lac cultivation and their view on possible solutions. Detailed interview with forest officials and informal interaction were other tools which used to collect data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the respondents

Age

The data indicates that maximum numbers of respondents (76.67 %) were from the age group 37-53 yr followed by above 54 yr (18.33%) and below 36 yr (3 %). Mean age was found to be 46.75 + 7.35 yr. In conformity of the study Pal (2011) showed that on an average, the age of 39 per cent family heads was more than 50 yr and 61 per cent family heads were less than 50 yr.

Education

It was evident that most of the respondent's population was illiterate (58.3%). Only Tilkadand block had somewhat even distribution of literacy with people from different education levels. However, no one from the respondent's population has attended college. About 18.3 per cent people had attended primary schools. Similar percentage of people attended middle school as well. Only 5 per cent people had gone to high school. In contradiction of the present findings Mohammad (2012) revealed that the literacy of total family members of lac growers observed high in large (89.29%) category. He also added that the people having the education level up to primary school, middle school, higher secondary school and above higher secondary school was 44.91, 28.53, 11.29 and 3.38 per cent, respectively.

Problems of Lac Growers

Family Size

Maximum number of households had 6+ members i.e., 29 families as such (48.33%). However, families with 2-4 members were also close enough i.e., 20 households as such (33.33%). Male population was 95 while female population was 90 from the surveyed sixty households. The results revealed that mostly extended family concept prevails in the locale of the study. In line with the study Pal (2011) showed that lac grower's families having up to 5 members and more than 5 members were 54 and 46 per cent, respectively, with an average family size of 5.92.

Annual Income

In Tilkadand all the farmers had annual income from lac above Rs.1 lakh. If we compare it with the income from agriculture below we will come to know lac has become the primary source of income for the farmers in this region. Overall 28.33 per cent farmers had income from lac between Rs 50000-100000 annually. About fifty three per cent farmer had income from Rs100000-1, 50,000. This explains that lac is a primary source of sustainable livelihood for the farmers in this region. Likewise, 18.33 per cent farmers had income of Rs 1, 50,000 & above. Every household have 10 to15 Ber trees and from these lac host trees each of the village get around 8 to10 thousand rupees from lac cultivation. Pal et al (2009) reported similar findings.

Land Holding

Most of the farmers (93.33%) were marginal, with less than 2 ha. of cultivable land. This makes it clear that why lac cultivation is preferred over agriculture in this region. The scarcity of land and lack of irrigation facilities among these marginal farmers increases their orientation towards forest based products as they require natural rain and less effort and time. Only 1 per cent had more than 4 ha. of land. Five per cent farmers had between 2 to 4ha. of land. In line with the study Pal (2011) showed that 18.0 per cent lac growers had marginal land holding of average size 0.64 ha. Twenty five

per cent had small land holding with average size of 1.04 ha. Thirty nine per cent had medium land holding with average size 2.82 ha. Sixteen per cent had semi-medium land holding with average size 6.45 ha and 2.0 per cent had large land holding with average size 13.0ha.

Understanding of lac cultivation

The understanding level has been judged on various parameters like knowledge about the disease, crop cycle and harvesting instruments, tools and techniques involved in lac cultivation. On the basis of these knowledge levels, points have been assigned accordingly. It was found (Table 1) that majority of the famers (71.66 %) have complete understanding of lac cultivation practices followed by moderate (28.33%).

Table 1. Understanding level of a farmer with respect to lac cultivation practices N=60

Sr. No.	Village	Complete	Moderate	Low
1.	Chihro	7	8	0
2.	Kapaskoti	13	2	0
3.	Dhanesara	11	4	0
4.	Tilkadand	12	3	0
	Frequency	43	17	0
	Per cent	71.66	28.33	0

Problems related with lac cultivation

Problem of transport

It was noticed that Chihro Village had maximum transport problem as it is in the interiors of Kanker district. Lack of infrastructure problems in road transport was major reason for the higher marking in "5" and "4" categories (Table 2). Out of 60 respondents, 22 checked in the "high" category of problems in transportation and 21 checked in for "very high" category. So it was evident that this problem needs to be taken care of for consistent supply of raw material. Thirty six per cent farmers say high level of problem of transport whereas 35 per cent say it's a very high level problem while 28.3 consider it moderate.

Table 2. Categorisation of problem of transport

N = 60

Sr. No.	Village	Transport				
		(Very high) 5	(High) 4	(Moderate) 3	(Low) 2	(Negligible) 1
1.	Chihro	8	7	0	0	0
2.	Kapaskoti	2	5	8	0	0
3.	Dhanesara	4	5	6	0	0
4.	Tilkadand	7	5	3	0	0
	Total Frequency	21	22	17	0	0
	Per cent	35	36.66	28.33	0	0

Problem of Broodlac availability

The availability of Broodlac is not a severe problem, however the quality is. Poor quality Broodlac doesn't give proper yield. However Broodlac is available in government centres at the season time. Hence, data (Table 3) reveals that most of the respondents (53.33%) categorised it as a moderate problem followed by low (36.66%).

Problem of markets

The availability of market again depends on the location and accessibility of the Village. Chihro has problems because of its remote location in Bhanupratappur block of Kanker district. Tilkadand farmers had problems of accessing the market at the right time because they needed transport facility. It was evident (Table 4) that majority of the respondent categorised it as a moderate problem followed by

Table 3. Categorisation of problem of Broodlac availability on time.

N=60

Sr. No.	Village	Broodlac Availability				
		(Very high) 5	(High) 4	(Moderate) 3	(Low) 2	(Negligible) 1
1.	Chihro	0	0	8	7	0
2.	Kapaskoti	0	0	7	8	0
3.	Dhanesara	0	0	8	7	0
4.	Tilkadand	0	6	9	0	0
	Total frequency	0	6	32	22	0
	Per cent	0	10	53.33	36.66	0

Table 4. Categorisation of problem due to market conditions.

N= 60

Sr. No.	Village	Markets				
		(Very high) 5	(High) 4	(Moderate) 3	(Low) 2	(Negligible) 1
1.	Chihro	0	8	7	0	0
2.	Kapaskoti	5	6	4	0	0
3.	Dhanesara	4	8	3	0	0
4.	Tilkadand	1	2	12	0	0
	Total Frequency	10	24	26	0	0
	Per cent	16.66	40	43.33	0	0

Problems of Lac Growers

Table 5. Categorisation of problem because of climatic factors.

N=60

Sr. No.	Village	Climate				
		(Very high) 5	(High) 4	(Moderate) 3	(Low) 2	(Negligible) 1
1.	Chihro	0	1	9	5	0
2.	Kapaskoti	0	0	13	2	0
3.	Dhanesara	0	0	12	3	0
4.	Tilkadand	0	5	10	0	0
	Total frequency	0	6	44	10	0
	Per cent	0	10	73.33	16.66	0

40 per cent of the respondent who rated it as a high. Similar findings by Pal *et al* (2009) confirm the above findings.

Problem related to climatic factors

The problem of climate is persistent in every Village. It refers to global warming and unexceptional rises in temperature in summer season. Lac insect dies in excessive heat. Therefore, the farmers doesn't get proper yield. Every experienced farmer is accepting the fact that this problem due to climate has increased in recent times. It was evident (Table 5) that most of the farmers (73.33%) perceived it as a moderate factor in lac production. Everybody had production related problem in recent years due to climate change. The productivity quality-wise has decreased. Though, the government support lac cultivation by including it in MSP. However, during the quality check most of the lac rejected by the government depending on its quality. So it has

issues supporting marginal farmers because they don't have bulk production. If government rejects their lac, they had to sell it in local market for cheap prices. Similar findings by Pal *et al* (2009) confirm the above findings.

Problem of theft

Previous researchers have mentioned the problem of theft in their researches. However, now it's not so common now in the region because government has declared it under Minimum Support Price (MSP) policy, and collecting it through SHG's in designated collection centres. Hence, problem of theft has been reduced. Only few instances of theft have been observed in Chihro Village due to its separated tree location in and around the village.

CONCLUSION

Lac is a highly remunerative cultivation. A hectare of Ber plantation with Kusmi lac cultivation

Table 6. Categorisation of problem of theft of lac crop.

N = 60

Sr. No.	Village	Theft				
		(Very high) 5	(High) 4	(Moderate) 3	(Low) 2	(Negligible) 1
1.	Chihro	0	0	0	9	12
2.	Kapaskoti	0	0	0	4	8
3.	Dhanesara	0	0	0	7	9
4.	Tilkadand	0	0	0	0	11
	Total frequency	0	0	0	20	40
	Per cent	0	0	0	33.33	66.66

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can produce net return of 3-5 lakh/yr. It is like an insurance crop especially during drought year as the crop is very good during such adverse climate. Lac cultivation involves significant women participation and helps ecosystem development. A good number of lac host trees like Kusun, Palash, Ber etc. naturally occurring in forest and sub forests in Chhattisgarh are available for commercial exploitation.

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Production Technologies of Red Gram (*Cajanus cajan* L.) Adopted by Farmers of Karimnagar District of Telangana

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ABSTRACT

In order to study the adoption of production technologies of red gram by the KVKs adopted versus non-adopted farmers, a questionnaire was developed consisting of 21 technologies measured on 3 point continuum i.e. fully adopted, partially adopted and non adopted with the scores of 3,2,1, respectively. It was observed that, majority (40.0%) of the KVK adopted red gram farmers had medium extent of adoption followed by high (36.67%) and low (23.33%) whereas, majority (43.33%) of the KVK non-adopted farmers had medium extent of adoption followed by low (40.00%) and high (16.67%). Further, calculated 'Z' Value (2.25) was greater than table 'Z' value at 0.01 level of probability. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and hence it could be concluded that there exists a significant difference between mean scores of KVK adopted and non adopted farmers.

Key Words: Adopted and Non Adopted Farmers, Red Gram, Production, Technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Red gram (*Cajanus cajan* L.) requires average rainfall of 600-650 mm with moist conditions for the first eight weeks and drier conditions during flowering and pod development stage, rains during flowering results in poor pollination. However, the critical growth stages are branching, flowering and pod filling where moisture stress causes adverse effect therefore in the absence of rains, heavy irrigation is required. Red gram needs a moist and warm weather i.e. 30 – 35 °C during germination and slightly lower temperature (20 -25°C) during active vegetative growth and at maturity it needs higher temperature of around 35 – 40°C. Water logging, heavy rains, frost are very harmful to the crop. Hailstorm or rain at maturity damages the entire crop. It has a good drought tolerant capacity because of its deep tap root system.

This crop grows well on all types of soils but loam to sandy loam soil is suitable. This crop also

does well in sloppy lands in the mid-hills. It can be grown successfully on neutral soils having a pH range of 6.5 to 7.5. Land is prepared by at least one ploughing during the dry season followed by 2 or 3 harrowing and disc ploughing. The seed rate is 15 kg/ha. Red gram should be sown in rows at a distance of 50 cm with seed to seed spacing of 15-20 cm. The crop gives much higher yield if, it is sown in last week of May.

Treat the seeds with Carbendazim or Thiram @ 2 g/kg of seed 24 hours before sowing (or) with powder formulation of *Trichoderma viride* @ 4g/kg of seed (or) *Pseudomonas fluorescens* @ 10 g/kg seed. Apply 15 kg N and 45 kg P₂O₅ per hectare is sufficient for this crop. The crop grows very slowly during their early growth period of 45 – 50 days. This makes it less competitive with weeds and If not controlled in time, it can cause up to 90 per cent reductions in seed yield. Red gram should be harvested when 75-80 per cent of the pods turn

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Table 1. Extent of adoption of red gram production technologies.

Category	Adopted red gram farmers (n=60)			Non adopted red gram farmers (n=30)		
	Low (33-55)	Medium (56-78)	High (79-100)	Low (33-55)	Medium (56-78)	High (79-100)
Frequency	14	24	22	12	13	5
Percentage	23.33	40.00	36.67	40.00	43.33	16.67

brown and are dry. Delayed harvesting, during bad-weather, may increase the risk of damage to mature seed. Traditionally red gram plants are harvested by cutting the stem at the base with a sickle, but occasionally machines are used for cutting and followed by drying and threshing. The harvested plants are bundled and placed upright to dry for a week depending on the weather conditions. Pods and grain are separated by beating the dry plants with sticks or by using a thresher.

Being red gram is one of the important crops of Karimnagar district, it was felt to understand the adoption levels of the farmers regarding various production technologies of red gram.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

KVK Jammikunta of Telangana State along with its 15 adopted villages was selected for the study. A sample of 60 red gram growing farmers who were adopting the KVK technologies and another 30 red gram farmers who were not covered under KVK production technologies were selected from the adopted villages. A schedule was developed consisting of 21 technologies to assess the adoption level by the farmers, measured on 3 point continuum i.e. fully adopted, partially adopted and

non adopted with the scores of 3,2,1, respectively. Accordingly the respondents were grouped on the basis of frequency and percentage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extent of adoption of red gram production technologies by the farmers

It was observed (Table 1) that, majority (40.0%) of the KVK adopted red gram farmers had medium extent of adoption followed by high (36.67%) and low (23.33%) whereas, majority (43.33%) of the KVK non-adopted farmers had medium extent of adoption followed by low (40.00%) and high (16.67%). These results were in agreement with the findings of Rao *et al* (2012).

Comparison between KVK adopted and non adopted red gram farmers in terms of extent of adoption of red gram production technologies

It was evident (Table 2) that, calculated 'Z' Value (2.25) was greater than table 'Z' value at 0.01 level of probability. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and hence it could be concluded that there exists a significant difference between mean scores of KVK adopted and non adopted farmers. These findings were in agreement with Rao *et al* (2017).

Table 2. Comparison between KVK adopted and non adopted red gram farmers in terms of extent of adoption of red gram production technologies.

Sr. No.	Respondent category	Size of the sample(n)	Mean	S.D.	'Z' value
1.	Adopted farmers	60	52.98	7.89	2.25*
2.	Non -adopted farmers	30	25.46	4.32	

*Significant at 0.01 level of probability

Production Technologies of Red Gram

Table 3. Item wise analysis of extent of adoption of red gram production technologies by KVK adopted farmers in Karimnagar district. n=60

Sr. No.	Production technologies	Extent of adoption						Total score	Mean score	Rank
		Fully adopted		Partially adopted		Not adopted				
		F	%	F	%	F	%			
1	Optimum seed rate, more profitable as sole crop	60	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	180	3.00	I
2	Growing of wilt tolerance varieties PRG 158 and Laxmi in wilt prone area, application of Trichoderma viridi culture (Trichoderma viridi 2 kg in 100 kg FYM) at the time of sowing under optimum moisture conditions	52	86.7	8	13.3	0	0.0	172	2.86	II
3	Growing of LRG 41 is tolerant for helioverpa	50	83.3	10	16.7	10	16.6	170	2.83	III
4	Providing irrigation at critical stages is important	49	81.9	10	16.6	1	1.5	168	2.80	IV
5	Deep ploughing during summer and destruction of crop residues help to reduce pest / disease incidence	50	83.4	5	8.3	5	8.3	165	2.75	V
6	Sowing of red gram with a spacing of 120 cm x 120 cm	46	76.7	10	16.7	4	6.6	150	2.70	VI
7	Seed treatment with Trichoderma viridi @ 8 gm/kg of seed	42	70.0	12	20.0	6	10.0	156	2.60	VII
8	Soil samples collected up to 15-20cm depth for soil testing	42	70.0	8	13.3	10	16.7	152	2.53	VIII
9	Soil test based fertilizer application is economical	41	68.3	9	15.0	10	16.7	151	2.51	IX
10	Incorporation of FYM into the soil during last ploughing, square plantation leads to higher yields, application of chemical pesticides on ETL levels gives good control of insect pests, spraying of neem oil at 50% flowering,	40	66.6	10	16.7	10	16.7	150	2.50	X
11	Use of Rhizobium bio-fertilizer reduce the usage of nitrogenous fertilizer, spraying of pre emergence herbicide pendimethalin @ 2.5 l/ha	33	55.0	12	20.0	15	25.0	138	2.30	XI
12	Application of biological pesticides controls insect pest, under limited irrigation facilities good net returns	30	50.0	15	25.0	15	25.0	135	2.25	XII

Table 4. Item wise analysis of extent of adoption of red gram production technologies by KVK non adopted farmers in Karimnagar district. n=30

Sr. No.	Red gram production technologies	Extent of adoption						Total score	Mean score	Rank
		Fully adopted		Partially adopted		Not adopted				
		F	%	F	%	F	%			
1	Growing of red gram variety LRG 41 is tolerant for helioverpa Optimum seed rate is important	20	66.6	5	16.7	5	16.7	75	2.50	I
2	Square plantation facilitates good crop canopy, more profitable as sole crop, spraying of neem oil at 50% flowering	15	50.0	10	33.3	5	16.7	70	2.33	II
3	Application of culture (Trichoderma viridi) 2 kg in 100 kg FYM) at the time of sowing will reduce the wilt incidence, application of chemical pesticides is economical, IPM in red gram reduces the pod borer incidence.	10	33.3	19	63.4	1	3.3	69	2.30	III
4	Growing of red gram variety PRG 158 and Laxmi in wilt prone area gives higher yields.	13	43.3	12	40.0	5	16.7	68	2.26	IV
5	Incorporation of FYM into the soil during last ploughing, square plantation leads to higher yields, application of chemical pesticides on ETL levels gives good control of insect pests.	12	40.0	12	40.0	6	20.0	66	2.20	V
6	Deep ploughing during summer and destruction of crop residues help to reduce pest / disease incidence	16	53.3	0	0.0	14	46.7	62	2.16	VI
7	Spraying of pre emergence herbicide pendimethalin @ 2.5 l/ha will reduce weed infestation.	5	16.7	10	33.3	15	50.0	50	1.66	VII
8	Use of Rhizobium bio fertilizer will reduce the usage of nitrogenous fertilizer	6	20.0	8	26.7	16	53.3	40	1.33	VIII

Production Technologies of Red Gram

The data (Table 3) indicates the item analysis of the KVK adopted farmers in red gram crop on extent of adoption possessed by them on red gram technologies. It was noted that the technologies on which the respondent had high adoption were usage of optimum seed rate, more profitable as sole crop, ranked 1st followed by growing of PRG 158 variety, wilt management with *Trichoderma viridi* (2nd), growing of LRG 41 variety (3rd), providing irrigation at critical stages (4th), deep summer ploughing (5th), square plantation (6th). The adopted farmers had lowest extent of adoption on usage of biological pesticides. On the other hand, most of the non adopted KVK farmers adopted practices like growing of LRG 41 variety, use of optimum seed rate, were ranked 1st followed by square plantation, spraying of neem oil, more profitable as sole crop (2nd), wilt management with *Trichoderma viridi*, providing irrigation at critical stages, adoption of IPM practices (3rd), growing of PRG 158 variety (4th), seed treatment (5th), deep summer ploughing (6th) etc.

Adopted farmers of red gram crop had high extent of adoption on usage of optimum seed rate, profitability of red gram as a sole crop, growing of LRG-41 and PRG-158 varieties, wilt management with *Trichoderma viridi*, square plantation etc. The reasons could be that KVK scientists conducted series of demonstrations at the farmers' fields of adopted village. In these demonstrations, the farmers were practically seen the performance of the technologies. KVK also taken up seed production of improved varieties at the KVK farm and supplied to the farmers which facilitated high extent of adoption. KVK scientists conducted several

method demonstrations, group discussions, farmer – scientist interactions, front line demonstrations which paved way for high extent of adoption of these technologies. The adopted farmers had lowest adoption of usage of biological pesticides due to non availability of quality inputs in the local market.

Similarly, most of the non adopted farmers had high extent of adoption on usage of LRG-41 variety, use of optimum seed rate, square plantation, red gram as sole crop, wilt management, seed treatment etc. The reasons could be the non adopted farmers were motivated by the adopted farmers experience in achieving higher net returns by adopting more technologies. These non adopted farmers learnt by participating in extension activities and also shared the experiences of adopted farmers.

CONCLUSION

High extent of adoption of red gram production technologies was seen among the farmers adopted by the KVK Jammikunta compared to the non adopted farmers. This could be due to the multiplicity of the transfer of technology mechanisms followed by the KVK scientists in the adopted villages especially for the benefit of farmers adopted by the KVK.

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Productive and Reproductive Performance of Vanaraja Birds Reared by Tribal Community of Dhemaji District of Assam

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ABSTRACT

Productive and reproductive performances in terms of body weight, age at first egg, egg production, egg weight, fertility, hatchability and mortality of Vanaraja and Desi chicken of Assam were studied under traditional system of rearing and their respective values were compared between two varieties. The Vanaraja birds were given to rear under the demonstration programme of the Dhemaji KVK to the farmers of tribal communities like Bodo, Mising and Sonowal tribes of the district. The overall mean body weight was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher in Vanaraja than Desi chicken. The mean age at first egg was recorded as 181.05 ± 1.52 in Vanaraja and in Desi chicken it was 203.31 ± 3.13 d which was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) different. The mean egg production up to 32, 40, 52 and 72 wk of age in Vanaraja were recorded as 32.13 ± 0.11 , 50.08 ± 0.32 , 89.29 ± 1.02 and 181.12 ± 1.53 numbers, respectively and in case of Desi chicken, the corresponding values were recorded as 11.21 ± 0.03 , 25.82 ± 0.18 , 42.57 ± 0.72 and 76.27 ± 0.85 , respectively. The mean egg weight of Vanaraja at 32, 40 and 52 wk of age was also significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher than Desi birds. However, there was no significant difference in mortality rates between two groups during 6 to 30 and 31 to 52 wk of age. There was also no significant ($P \leq 0.05$) difference in fertility and hatchability percent between two genetic groups. Therefore, it may be concluded that Vanaraja birds were adapted well under traditional backyard rearing system among the tribal communities in Dhemaji district of Assam.

Key Words: Body weight, Desi chicken, Egg production, Hatchability, Traditional system, Vanaraja.

INTRODUCTION

Livestock and poultry rearing is an imperative factor for improving the nutritional security of rural poor in India. The tribal population of Dhemaji district rear Desi type chicken in backyard system of rearing for household consumption and to meet the day to day daily expenses to some extent and these birds are low in egg and meat production.

To meet the growing demands of the population and to improve the per capita consumption among tribal people, backyard poultry farming with improved varieties of poultry in tribal areas is the best alternative. Traditionally Desi varieties are used for backyard poultry production whose production potential is very low, which is around 70-80 eggs per year. Vanaraja is a dual purpose bird developed at Directorate of Poultry Research (DPR), Hyderabad

having indigenous look with good growth and egg production performance. Keeping this fact in mind, a demonstration was planned for developing the rural poultry farming with improved poultry *viz.* Vanaraja as free range/ backyard farming to see the suitability of these birds in backyard system of rearing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted during the period July, 2013 to December, 2014 by KVK, Dhemaji. For this study, 15 numbers of tribal farmwomen were selected randomly from the Silapathar Block and were given each with 15 nos. of month old Vanaraja birds. The farmwomen were selected on the basis of their experience on Desi poultry keeping and who possessed at least 15 nos.

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Table1. Monthly mean (\pm SE) body weights of the Vanaraja and Desi birds under backyard system.

Age (month)	Mean body weight (g)					
	Vanaraja Male	Vanaraja Female	Vanaraja Overall	Desi Male	Desi Female	Desi Overall
1	343.06 \pm 2.07	301.23 \pm 1.06	326.02 \pm 1.52a	203.26 \pm 1.03	179.21 \pm 0.98	163.04 \pm 0.87 b
2	911.11 \pm 3.45	692.04 \pm 2.11	797.13 \pm 2.73 a	383.52 \pm 2.32	357.12 \pm 2.74	361.01 \pm 2.53 b
3	1452.03 \pm 5.08	1153.07 \pm 4.18	1293.16 \pm 4.51 a	512.07 \pm 4.04	467.16 \pm 3.01	496.12 \pm 3.48 b
4	1951.09 \pm 6.01	1533.11 \pm 4.97	1743.01 \pm 5.06 a	663.07 \pm 4.35	597.22 \pm 4.12	648.07 \pm 4.09 b
5	2413.33 \pm 8.06	1772.05 \pm 5.23	2087.28 \pm 6.26 a	801.34 \pm 5.12	739.14 \pm 5.03	762.03 \pm 5.12 b
6	2965.01 \pm 10.24	2109.13 \pm 7.34	2521.07 \pm 8.67 a	903.05 \pm 5.91	827.65 \pm 5.87	853.14 \pm 5.73 b

Means with different superscripts within a row differ significantly ($p < 0.05$)

of Desi birds at their house. Thus a total of 225 numbers of Vanaraja birds were distributed under the programme procured from the Government Duck & Poultry Farm, Jaysagar, Sivasagar, Assam. Each of the farmers was given with 13 female and 2 male birds to rear under backyard rearing system like their local poultry.

The body weight of all the birds were recorded before distribution to the farmers and also at monthly intervals up to maturity at an average of six month age, average age at the point of lay, mean egg weight at 32, 40 and 52 wk of age, mean egg production 32, 40, 52 and 72 wk of age. The mortality rates of birds at 6th to 30th and 31st to 52nd wk of age, fertility and hatchability percentage of eggs were also recorded for a period of one and half year. Data on above mentioned parameters were also recorded for the local indigenous poultry. Both types of poultry were reared in the farmers' backyard. Vaccination (F1 and R2B strain of RD) was done in both varieties and health status of the birds was monitored throughout the period.

The data were analyzed as per standard statistical methods (Snedecor and Cochran, 1994). The effect of genetic group on the different growth and production traits was studied. The individual means among genetic groups were tested by Duncan's New Multiple Range Test (DMRT) for their significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The overall mean body weights of Vanaraja birds at 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 months of age recorded as 797.13 \pm 2.73, 1293.16 \pm 4.51, 1743.01 \pm 5.06, 2087.28 \pm 6.26 and 2521.07 \pm 8.67g respectively, whereas 361.01 \pm 2.53, 496.12 \pm 3.48, 648.07 \pm 4.09, 762.03 \pm 5.12 and 853.14 \pm 5.73g respectively for the Desi birds at their respective age under traditional system of management (Table1). The values for body weights of Vanaraja birds were significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher than their corresponding values for Desi chicken might be due to the difference in genetic makeup of the birds. Islam *et al* (2014) also reported a comparable body weights at 8 and 20 wk of age in case of Vanaraja and indigenous chicken in Assam. Deka *et al* (2014) recorded much lower mean body weights in Vanaraja and almost similar mean body weight in indigenous chickens at 24 wk of age. In contrast to the present findings, Kumar *et al* (2005) and Zuyie *et al* (2009) recorded the body weights at 8 and 20 wk of age, which were much lower in Vanaraja in comparison with the present study. The higher body weights recorded in the present study might be due to the higher access of nutrients during the study period.

The mean ages at first egg was recorded in Vanaraja and Desi chicken as 181.05 \pm 1.52 and 203.31 \pm 3.31 d, respectively (Table 2). The significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower age at first egg in case of Vanaraja might be due to the superiority in

Performance of *Vanaraja* Birds

Table 2. Certain productive and reproductive parameters of Vanaraja and Desi birds.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Bird varieties		Changes over Desi bird (%)
		Vanaraja	Desi bird	
1	Age at first egg (days)	181.05±1.52	203.31±3.31	(-) 11 %
2	Mature hen weight (g)	2137.26 ±22.13	1361.53 ±21.43	(+) 31.25 %
3	Mean egg production (no.)			
	Up to 32 wk of age	32.13±0.11a	11.21±0.03 b	(+) 190 %
	Up to 40 wk of age	50.05±0.32a	25.82±0.18 b	(+) 94 %
	Up to 52 wk of age	89.29±1.02a	42.57±0.72 b	(+) 110 %
	Up to 72 wk of age	181.12±1.53a	76.27±0.85b	(+) 137 %
4	Mean Egg weight (g)			
	Up to 32 wk of age	47.31±0.21a	37.85±0.04b	(+) 25 %
	Up to 40 wk of age	54.07±0.24a	42.06±0.07b	(+) 28.54 %
	Up to 52 wk of age	58.32±0.26a	46.08±0.13b	(+) 26.56 %
5	Survivability (%)			
	0 to 5th week	90.74±1.01a	93.93±1.05 a	
	6th to 30th week	96.05±0.09a	98.39±0.43a	
	31st to 52nd week	98.53±0.08a	99.13±0.53a	
6	Fertility (%)	91.02±3.92a	92.40±4.97a	
7	Hatchability (%) on TES	86.14±3.26a	88.52±3.95a	

Means with different superscripts within a row differ significantly ($p < 0.05$)

germplasm and nutritional status of the birds. Islam *et al* (2014) also recorded the similar findings in Vanaraja and indigenous chicken of Assam under backyard system. The present findings of Vanaraja were also comparable with the findings of Zuyie *et al* (2009) and Deka *et al* (2014). In contrast to the findings, Pathak & Nath (2013) recorded much lower values for Vanaraja and Desi chicken in Sikkim. The differences in the findings might be due to the better management and nutrition of the birds. The mean egg production values up to 32, 40, 52 weeks of age in Vanaraja birds were significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher than the corresponding values of Desi birds, which were also supported by the findings of Islam *et al* (2014) and Kumaresan *et al* (2008).

The mean egg weights of two genetic groups at 32, 40 and 52 wk of age are presented in the Table 2. There was significant ($P \leq 0.05$) difference between the values at different ages. The lower

values might be due to inferior genetic makeup in indigenous chicken of Assam. The findings were also corroborated with the findings of Islam *et al* (2014). Kalita *et al* (2012) also recorded the mean egg weight as 35.27±0.15g in case of indigenous chicken of Assam. There were no significant ($P \leq 0.05$) differences in survivability between the two genetic groups at different ages. The findings were also supported by Islam *et al* (2014). The main cause of mortality during early part of their life were cold shock, yolk sac infection etc. The percent mortality was showing similar trends in both types of birds as with the advancement of age, it was decreased. No significant differences were observed in respect of survivability between two varieties of birds, which might be due to better resistance to many of the diseases. Islam *et al* (2014) also reported similar trends of mortality in Vanaraja and indigenous chicken of Assam. The values for fertility (%) and hatchability (%) on TES

recorded in case of Desi birds was higher than the Vanaraja birds. However, there was no significant difference in fertility and hatchability of the eggs of Vanaraja and indigenous birds. Almost similar types of findings were also reported by Kalita *et al* (2012).

CONCLUSION

From the study, it was concluded that Vanaraja birds adapted well under traditional backyard rearing system among the tribal communities in Dhemaji district of Assam.

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Ready-to-Serve Beverage from Spray Dried Pomegranate Juice Powder

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ABSTRACT

The pomegranate juice is considered as the one of the nature's most powerful antioxidants. Excellent flavour, nutritive value and medicinal properties of pomegranate fruit indicates its good potentiality for processing into value added products. In India and other countries of the world the demand of fruit beverages are increasing regularly due to its nutritional, medicinal and calorific properties. Present investigation was undertaken to develop RTS beverage using spray dried pomegranate juice powder with added sugar and citric acid. Spray dried powder of pomegranate (Cv. Bhagwa) juice obtained with 154°C inlet air temperature, 87.5 mL/h feed flow rate and 37 per cent malto dextrine concentration were used to prepare the RTS premix. For standardization, pomegranate RTS was prepared with various levels of powder quantities (6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 g powder per 100 mL RTS), TSS (12, 13, 14, 15 and 16°Brix) and acidity (control, 0.20, 0.25, 0.30 and 0.35 %). The results of sensory score indicated that the RTS developed using 8 g spray dried pomegranate juice powder per 100 mL RTS having 15°Brix total soluble solids and 0.30 per cent acidity was found to be best among all the levels.

Key Words: Pomegranate, Spray dried powder, Ready-to-Serve, Beverages, Sensory analysis

INTRODUCTION

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) is one of the oldest known edible fruit crops which belong to the family Punicaceae. Among arid and semiarid fruits of India, pomegranate ranks first in area and production of 1.28 lakh ha and 12.86 lakh tonnes, respectively with productivity of 10.04 t/ha (Anonymous, 2016). Among different varieties of pomegranate cultivated in Maharashtra, Bhagawa and Super Bhagawa varieties become popular because of a glossy red coloured fruit with soft seeds and more acceptable TSS-acidity blends.

Fruit is well known for its medicinal properties due to high level of antioxidant activity and high total phenolic content (Bagci, 2014; Vardin and Yasar,

2012 and Horuz *et al*, 2012). Apart from its demand as fresh fruit and juice, the processed products such as anardana, carbonated drinks, syrup, concentrate, wine, candy, frozen, canned and minimally processed arils are also gaining importance in world trade (Dhumal, 2012; Barman *et al*, 2013 and Dak *et al*, 2014). In spite of numerous health benefits, fresh consumption of pomegranate is still not wide spread due to difficulty in extracting arils from the fruit and staining of hands and it is also a time consuming process. Product diversification in the context of increased pomegranate production is the need of time. Therefore, there is great demand for value added products of pomegranate due to their convenience and unique sensory characteristics.

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Drying of fruit juice produces a stable, easy handling form of the juice powder that reconstitute rapidly to a good quality product resembling the original juice as close as possible (Vikram Simha *et al*, 2012). Juice powders are used mainly as convenience foods and have long storage shelf life at ambient temperatures (Horuz *et al*, 2012 and Muzaffar *et al*, 2016). Spray drying has been adopted to manufacture powders due to its ability to generate a product with precise quality specifications in continuous operation. In India and other countries of the world, the demand of fruit beverages is increasing regularly. This increasing trend is mainly due to the higher content of nutritional, medicinal and calorific properties over the non-fruit based beverages. Ready-to-Serve (RTS) is one of the best and commonly acceptable beverages.

The numerous health benefits and huge production provide a solid basis for the development and utilization of pomegranate as both pharmaceuticals and dietary supplement. Therefore, this is very important to standardize the suitable powder quantity, TSS and acidity for the preparation of RTS with good sensory properties. Thus, present investigation was undertaken to develop pomegranate RTS beverage using spray dried pomegranate juice powder with addition of sugar and citric acid.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Raw materials

Fresh, well matured, uniform size and coloured pomegranate fruits of Cv. Bhagawa were procured from the local market, Rahuri, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra and used for the experimentation.

Extraction of juice

After weighing, fruits were carefully cut at the equatorial zones with sharp knife to minimize damage to arils. The arils were separated manually and defective and damaged arils were discarded. The juice from arils was extracted manually and filtered through four layered muslin cloth.

Preparation of spray dried powder

Spray dried powder of pomegranate juice was produced at 154°C inlet air temperature, 87.5 mL/h feed flow rate and 37 per cent maltodextrine concentration and used to prepare the RTS premix (Roustapour *et al*, 2012; Vardin and Yasar, 2012; Vikram Simha *et al*, 2012).

Standardization of RTS premix from pomegranate juice powder

Powder obtained by spray drying was used to prepare the RTS premix. The RTS normally contain minimum 10 per cent juice, 10°Brix TSS and 0.3 per cent acidity (Malav *et al*, 2014). The RTS premixes were prepared to maintain these standards. Standardization was carried out in three steps *i.e.* standardization of powder quantity, standardization of TSS level and standardization of acidity level. The RTS was standardized on the basis of sensory scores. The independent and dependent parameters for standardization of RTS premix are as given in Table 1.

Table 1. Independent and dependant parameters for standardization of pomegranate RTS premix.

Independent parameters	Powder quantity (6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 g /100 mL RTS) TSS levels (12, 13, 14, 15 and 16°Brix) Acidity level (Control, 0.20, 0.25, 0.30 and 0.35%)
Dependent parameters	Sensory attributes

Standardization of powder quantity

Pomegranate RTS was prepared with five levels of powder *i.e.* 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 g powder per 100 mL RTS. Sugar and citric acid was added to adjust the 15°Brix TSS and 0.30 per cent acidity of RTS. Premixes were prepared by mixing the required quantities of powder, sugar and citric acid. Sensory evaluation of RTS was done to obtain optimized quantity of pomegranate juice powder.

Standardization of TSS level

Five RTS premixes were prepared from pomegranate juice powder, sugar and citric acid to

Ready-to-Serve Spray Dried Pomegranate Juice Powder

vary the TSS of RTS from 12 to 16°Brix. The RTS was prepared from these premixes. Pomegranate powder quantity as standardized was kept constant for each treatment. Sugar was added in varying proportion to get the required TSS levels of RTS. Acidity of RTS was adjusted to 0.30 per cent with required quantity of citric acid. Sensory evaluation of RTS was done to obtain best TSS level.

Standardization of acidity level

Five premixes were prepared to adjust the acidity of RTS to 0.20, 0.25, 0.30 and 0.35 per cent with required quantity of citric acid. The control sample was prepared without addition of citric acid. The quantity of pomegranate juice powder and TSS as standardized was used for all the treatments. Sensory evaluation of RTS was done to obtain best acidity level.

Sensory evaluation

The sensory evaluation of pomegranate RTS was carried out by the procedure given by Amerine *et al* (1965) on nine point hedonic scale. The sensory evaluation was performed by a panel of semi trained judges for colour, flavour, taste and overall acceptability.

Statistical analysis

The data obtained on sensory characteristics of the RTS was analyzed to determine the statistical significance of the treatments using method of analysis of variance described by Panse and Sukhatme (1985).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Standardization of RTS premix from pomegranate juice powder

The present investigation was an attempt to develop RTS beverage by varying quantity of pomegranate juice powder, TSS and acidity. The premixes were prepared to maintain the RTS standards. The levels of ingredients were finalized on the basis of sensory scores and presented in Table 2 to 7.

Standardization of powder quantity

For standardization of powder quantity, the five premixes were prepared by using different levels of pomegranate juice powder, sugar and citric acid. The ingredients for preparation of RTS premix were finalized by performing several experiments based on a trial-and-error method to maintain the RTS standards i.e. 15°Brix TSS and 0.30 per cent acidity and were given in Table 2. The RTS were prepared by using the premixes, were analyzed for sensory evolution and presented in Table 3.

The data revealed that the sensory scores of RTS varied significantly with increase in the quantity of pomegranate juice powder from 6 to 14 g. The scores for all the sensory parameters were increased up to 8 g powder quantity and afterword decreased. RTS prepared with 8 g pomegranate powder (Tp2) had maximum acceptability (8.33) among the treatments followed by treatment Tp3 (7.50) while minimum acceptability (6.33) was observed in treatment Tp4 and Tp5. Higher sensory score for treatment Tp2 was observed which may be due to the proper blend of sugars and citric acid. Sugars and citric acid had statistically significant effect on sensory parameters of RTS. Thus the acceptable quantity of the pomegranate juice powder was found to be 8 g per 100 mL RTS.

Table 2. Treatment details for standardization of pomegranate juice powder quantity for preparation of RTS premix.

Treatment	Powder quantity (g)	Sugar (g)	Citric acid (mg)
Tp1	6	9.5	255
Tp2	8	8.0	230
Tp3	10	6.5	210
Tp4	12	5.5	190
Tp5	14	4.5	180

Bawne (2000) prepared tamarind RTS from 10, 12 and 14 per cent levels of juice reported that the acceptability of RTS increased significantly with increasing the juice level from 10 to 12 per cent and decreased at 14 per cent.

Table 3. Effect of powder quantity on sensory parameters of pomegranate RTS

Treatment	Col-our	Taste	Flavour	Overall acceptability
Tp1	6.62	7.50	7.87	7.33
Tp2	8.00	8.50	8.50	8.33
Tp3	7.50	7.50	7.50	7.50
Tp4	7.00	6.00	6.00	6.33
Tp5	7.00	6.00	6.00	6.33
SE(m)±	0.087	0.035	0.037	0.045
CD at 5%	0.277	0.113	0.117	0.142
CV (%)	2.077	0.863	0.884	1.079

Standardization of TSS level

The five premixes were prepared by using different concentrations of sugar and citric acid to maintain TSS levels of RTS in between 12 to 16°Brix. The powder quantity of 8 g per 100 mL and acidity of 0.30 per cent was maintained for all prepared RTS. The treatment details for preparation of RTS premixes and their sensory scores with varying TSS levels are presented in Table 4 and 5, respectively.

From Table 5, it was observed that TSS had significant effect on taste, flavour and overall acceptability scores of RTS whereas non-significant effect on colour scores. The sensory scores for pomegranate RTS were increased up to 15°Brix TSS, afterwards sensory scores were decreased with increasing the TSS levels. This may be because of improper TSS-acidity blend with increasing the TSS level. Taste, flavour and overall acceptability scores of pomegranate RTS varied significantly from 5.86 to 8.28, 6.89 to 7.92 and 6.92 to 8.09, respectively with varying levels of TSS whereas colour scores varied non-significantly from 7.73 to 8.06. The treatment Ts4 (15°Brix TSS) received maximum score for colour, taste, flavour and overall acceptability as 8.06, 8.28, 7.92 and 8.09, respectively followed by treatment Ts5 (16°Brix TSS). Thus, the acceptable RTS was prepared with 15°Brix TSS. Similar results were reported by Sandhan *et al* (2009) for carbonated pomegranate

RTS, Akhtar *et al* (2013) for pomegranate juice based drink, Dhumal (2012) for pomegranate RTS and Sree (2012) for sweet orange RTS.

Table 4. Treatment details for standardization of TSS level for preparation of RTS premix

Treat-ment	TSS, °Brix	Powder quantity (g)	Sugar (g)	Citric acid (mg)
Ts1	12	8	4.8	215
Ts2	13	8	5.9	220
Ts3	14	8	7.0	225
Ts4	15	8	8.1	230
Ts5	16	8	9.2	235

Table 5. Effect of TSS levels on sensory parameters of pomegranate RTS.

Treatments	Colour	Taste	Flavour	Overall acceptability
Ts1	7.81	5.86	7.10	6.92
Ts2	7.73	6.36	7.33	7.14
Ts3	7.75	7.00	7.47	7.41
Ts4	8.06	8.28	7.92	8.09
Ts5	8.00	7.50	6.89	7.46
SE(m)±	0.1	0.142	0.040	0.099
CD at 5%	N/A	0.454	0.129	0.317
CV (%)	2.2	3.518	0.950	2.324

Standardization of acidity level

For preparing RTS with varying acidity levels, the powder quantity and sugar quantity were kept constant at 8 and 8.1 g per 100 mL RTS, respectively as per previous results. The quantities of ingredients used for preparing RTS premixes with varying acidity level are as shown in Table 6. The results for sensory score are presented in Table 7.

The data shown in Table 7 depicts that acidity levels had statistically significant effect on the sensory parameters of pomegranate RTS. The score for all the sensory parameters of pomegranate RTS except colour were increased with increased acidity levels up to 0.30 per cent and afterward decreased. At constant powder quantity and TSS level, prepared RTS with lowest acidity content had sweeter taste which was disliked by most of

Ready-to-Serve Spray Dried Pomegranate Juice Powder

the panelist. Higher score for overall acceptability was recorded for treatment Ta3 i.e. for RTS with 0.30 per cent acidity due to proper blend of sugar and citric acid. Thus 0.30 per cent acidity (Ta3) was selected as the optimum acidity level for preparation of pomegranate RTS.

Similar findings were observed by Sandhan *et al* (2009) for carbonated pomegranate RTS, Maheswarlu *et al* (2010) for whey based pomegranate beverage, Sree (2012) for sweet orange RTS, Rejeti (2012) for sapota RTS blended with papaya, pineapple, grape, carrot and beetroot in different proportions

Table 6. Treatment details for standardization of acidity level for preparation of RTS premix.

Treatment	Acidity (%)	Powder quantity (g)	Sugar (g)	Citric acid (mg)
Control	0.12	8	8.1	-
Ta1	0.20	8	8.1	185
Ta2	0.25	8	8.1	205
Ta3	0.30	8	8.1	230
Ta4	0.35	8	8.1	260

Table 7. Effect of acidity levels on sensory parameters of pomegranate RTS.

Treatments	Colour	Taste	Flavour	Overall acceptability
Control	5.50	5.50	6.00	5.67
Ta1	6.90	6.80	6.80	6.83
Ta2	7.50	7.30	7.30	7.37
Ta3	8.20	8.00	7.90	8.03
Ta4	8.40	7.10	7.20	7.57
SE(m)±	0.026	0.041	0.046	0.027
CD at 5%	0.082	0.132	0.147	0.086
CV (%)	0.612	1.035	1.13	0.657

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that sensory properties of pomegranate RTS were significantly influenced by powder quantity, TSS and acidity levels. The acceptable quality RTS can be prepared using 8 g spray dried pomegranate juice powder per 100 mL

by adding sugar and citric acid to maintain 15°Brix total soluble solids and 0.30 per cent acidity, respectively.

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Role of Cluster Frontline Demonstrations in Enhancement of Chickpea Production

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ABSTRACT

The cluster frontline demonstration (CFLDs) on chickpea was conducted by Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Malegaon in two villages namely Vadel and Ajang of Malegaon tehsil during the rabi season of 2015-16. The results revealed that improved seed of Digvijay + seed treatment (Trichoderma viridi 5 g/kg + Rhizobium sp. 25 g/kg + PSB 25 g/kg) + plant protection (Pheromone trap 3 no./acre+ insecticide) recorded average highest yield 21.16 q/ha followed by 16.25 q/ha in control plot. The same trend was found in case of gross and net monetary returns, which was Rs. 84636/- and Rs. 51545/-ha and for control Rs. 64992/- and Rs. 28392/-ha, respectively. Benefit cost ratio for demonstration and control was 2.56 and 1.78, respectively. It can be concluded that the pulses production could be enhanced by encouraging the farmers through adoption of recommended technologies which were followed in the CFLDs.

Key words: CFLDs, Chickpea, Grain yield, IPM

INTRODUCTION

Chickpea is one of the most important pulse crop and occupies a major position among pulses in Maharashtra state. Output of pulses was 17.06 MT during 2015-16 (Anonymous, 2017). Chickpea is an important rabi crop mainly sown in September-November and harvested in February. Crop duration is 90-120 d depending on the variety. It is best suited to areas having low to moderate rainfall and a mild cold weather. Indian government imports large quantity of pulses to fulfill domestic requirement of pulses. In this regard, to sustain this production and consumption system, the Department of Agriculture, Cooperation and Farmers Welfare had sanctioned the project "Cluster Frontline Demonstrations on Rabi Pulses 2015-16" to ICAR-ATARI, Hyderabad through National Food Security Mission. This project was implemented by Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Malegaon of Zone-V with main objective to boost the production and productivity of pulses through CFLDs with latest and specific technologies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation of CFLDs was conducted during rabi season 2015-16 by the KVK Malegaon, District Nashik of Maharashtra state. Two villages namely Vadel and Ajang of Malegaon tahsil were selected for this project. Total 50 farmers were selected for the project. Farmers were trained to follow the package and practices for chickpea cultivation as recommended by the State Agricultural Universities and need based input materials provided to the farmers (Table 1).

The farmers followed the full package of practices like soil testing, seed treatment with bio-fertilizer, Trichoderma viride, fertilizer application, weed and water management, IPM practices etc. In case of local check, the traditional practices were followed in existing varieties like Chafa, local by the farmers. The yield data were collected from both CFLD and farmers practice plot (local check) and compiled results has been given in (Table 2).

Table 1. Details of need based input material given on CFLDs of chickpea

Cluster	Number of demonstrations	Variety	Technology Demonstrated	Need based inputs
Vadel	38	Digvijay	Improved variety, IPM	Improved Seed, Soil testing, Rhizobium spp., PSB, Trichoderma viride, pheromone traps, insecticide (Chloropyriphos 50% + Cypermethrin 5%)
Ajang	12			

Table 2. Details of yield and economics of cluster frontline demonstration on chickpea

Treatment	Yield (q/ha)	Gross Cost (Rs./ha)	GMR Rs./ha)	NMR (Rs./ha)	B:C ratio
T1: Farmers practice	16.25	33090.91	64992.73	28392.84	1.78
T2: Improved Seed Digvijay + seed treatment (<i>Trichoderma viridi</i> 5 g/kg + <i>Rhizobium sp.</i> 25 g/kg + PSB 25 g/kg) + plant protection (Pheromone trap 3 no./acre)	21.16	36599.89	84636.36	51545.45	2.56

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cluster Frontline demonstrations on chickpea were conducted by using variety Digvijay in an area of 10 ha at 50 farmer's field in Vadel and Ajang villages of Malegaon block. The need based inputs provided to farmers per hectare were variety Digvijay seed 75 kg, *Rhizobium spp.* @ 1875 g, PSB @1875 g, *Trichoderma viride* @ 375 g, pheromone traps 3 no., insecticide (Chloropyriphos 50% + Cypermethrin 5%) @ 250 ml. Results concluded that average highest yield 21.16 q/ha found in demonstration plot followed by 16.25q/ha in control plot. The same trend found in case of CFLDs gross and net monetary returns, was Rs. 84636/- and Rs. 51545/- ha and for control Rs. 64992/- and Rs. 28392/-ha, respectively. Benefit cost ratio for demonstration and control was 2.56 and 1.78 respectively. This improvement in yield might be due to the application of seed treatment, use of fertilizers, timely weed and water management and integrated pest management practices.

Constraints Observed During CFLDS

The farmers' yields were affected by various environmental and socio-economic factors like non-availability of quality seed, load shedding of power for irrigation, unawareness of latest

technology, causes severe yield loss, delayed sowing, lack of improved seed-cum-fertilizer drill, use of recommended dosage of fertilizers etc. High losses in yield observed due to heavy infestation of *Helicoverpa armigera* due to improper method and time of application of pesticide.

CONCLUSION

Cluster frontline demonstrations on pulses (Chickpea) conducted in two villages in Malegaon tehsil and result concluded that average highest yield 21.16q/ha found in demonstration plot followed by 16.25 q/ha in control plot. There was 23.20 per cent increase in yield observed in demonstration plot over farmers' practice. It was observed that potential yield can be achieved by imparting scientific knowledge to the farmers, providing the quality need based inputs and proper application of inputs. Horizontal spread of improved technologies may be achieved by the successful implementation of frontline demonstrations and various extensions activities like training programme, field day, exposure visit organized in CFLDs programmes in the farmer's fields. For wide dissemination of technologies recommended by SAUs and other research institute, more number of FLDs should be conducted.

Role of Cluster Frontline Demonstrations

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Socio-economic Characteristics and Constraints Faced by Horticultural Growers of East Sikkim

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ABSTRACT

Farmers in Sikkim have an aversion to commercial production of horticultural crops as this requires high initial investment. Low educational level coupled with improper technical training/extension services leading to low adoption of new technologies has been a problem area. Farmer's perception in case of seasonal training revealed that about 39.3 percent farmers preferred 2-3 days training followed by 5-7 days training (22%), one day training (18%), less than 7 days training (12.7%) and no training (8%). Regarding demonstrations, 65.3 per cent of the respondents preferred off campus while 4.7 per cent preferred on campus demonstrations. The study revealed twenty six major constraints and difficulty in using bio control agents, non-availability of bio pesticides and bio-fertilizers were most predominant among all for horticulture growers of East Sikkim.

Key Word: Constraints, Enterprise, Extension, Socio-economic, Technology.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture will play a dominant role in the growth of Indian economy in the foreseeable future. The share of horticulture in agriculture which was 3.9 per cent during Ninth Plan increased to 4.6 per cent during the current Twelfth Plan. Interestingly, this share was 11.6 per cent during the Eleventh Plan. The area under horticulture crops was 23.69 million hectares during 2012-13 (Anonymous, 2014a). The total horticultural production and food grain production in India during 2012-13 was 268.85 MT and 257.13 MT. During 2013-14, the production and productivity under vegetables, fruits and flowers are 162897 MT, 17.3 MT/ha followed by 88977MT, 12.3MT/ha and 1754MT and 543MT/ha (Anonymous, 2014b).

Sikkim, the 22nd State of Indian Union is based upon an agrarian economy. More than 64 per cent of the population depends on agriculture for their livelihood. Agricultural land in Sikkim is estimated to be around 1, 09,000 ha, i.e. 15.36 percent of the total geographical area. Sikkim has a net cultivable area of about 79,000 ha (11.13 %); with irrigated area of 15 per cent of the total operational holdings of 110000 ha (Mohanty *et al*, 2013). Overwhelming

contribution of horticulture sector to the state's GDP needs priority attention for higher levels of rural prosperity. Farmers in Sikkim have an aversion to commercial cultivation of horticultural crops as this requires high initial investment. Poor quality of seeds and other planting material available affect the yield of crops and thereby also in attaining the returns to the farmers. With low educational level of the farmers coupled with improper technical training/extension services available to them, adoption of new technologies has always been a problem. These result in non-uniform quality of commercial horticultural crops produced in Sikkim. Presently, agriculture in Sikkim needs focus on eco-friendly farming including bio-pesticides, farmers' practices to promote sustainable agriculture with the objectives to make organic farming profitable, sustainable and environmentally acceptable.

The present study was carried out with the objective to study the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents in the context of scientific vegetable cultivation, identification of appropriate, sustainable best organic practices and identify the constraints faced by the horticultural growers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted in Gangtok, Ranka and Pakyong blocks of East Sikkim during 2015. A sample of 150 respondents was selected from the identified 15 villages (five villages from each block) following the purposive and random sampling procedure. Data collection was done with the help of well constructed and pre-tested interview schedule and analysis was done with suitable statistical techniques. The percentage, cumulative frequency, mean score and preference ranking were preferred for analyzing the data. In order to understand farmers' knowledge and practices related to sustainable horticulture, face-to-face in-depth interviews were conducted with cross-section of farmers under horticultural crops.

The constraints were classified with the help of a 5 points continuum scale as Strongly Agreed Farmers (5), Agreed Farmers (4), Neutral Farmers (3), Disagreed Farmers (2) and Strongly Disagreed Farmers (1) and accordingly each respondent was given score as per their preference to various constraints and mean weighted score was worked out for each statement under above mentioned five categories.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Age, education, marital status and land holding

The study revealed that the highest proportion (46.7%) of the respondents was in young age group (21-40 yr) as compared to 30 per cent in the less than 20 yr and only 23.3 percent in old age category (Table 1). It also showed that most of the respondents were male (63.3%), unmarried (17.3%) and married (82.7%). The data (Table 1) indicated that 11.3 per cent respondents were illiterate, 48.7 per cent had primary education, 14.7 per cent secondary education, 18.7 per cent higher education and 6.6 per cent were graduates and above. Sharma (2016) reported that adoption of various practices was found to be higher for high and secondary education level than primary, middle and college level dairy farmers.

Ninty per cent of respondents were residing as nuclear family and the rest 10 per cent were in joint family. In case of land holding status, it was found that the values for marginal, small, medium and large farmers were 20, 50, 24.7 and 5.3 per cent, respectively, along with moderate (55.3%) followed by high (28%) and low (16.7%) extension contacts of the respondents.

Farmer's perception on sustainable organic practices

According to the farmers' perception on sustainable organic practices and marketing strategies, the knowledge on market for selling organic produce ranked first with mean score of 3.02 and knowledge on different bio control agents ranked second with mean score of 2.86 (Table 2). The reason behind the perception was the adoption of organic farming to promote Sikkim as an organic state. Hence, it is very important to create or develop markets for organic food produce along with the evolvement of related strategies and to control diseases and insect pests by biological means. The results also depicted that knowledge on use of organic manures and pesticides, perception on profitability of organic farming, perception on environmental degradation were ranked as third, fourth and fifth with mean score of 2.67, 2.63 and 2.01, respectively.

Constraints faced by the horticultural farmers

The data (Table 3) revealed that 26 different types of constraints faced by the horticultural growers of East Sikkim for successful adoption of organic farming which resulted non-profitable enterprise. The relevant constraints included; difficulty in using bio control agents, non-availability of bio pesticides and non-availability of bio-fertilizers which ranked as first, second and third important constraint respectively. Inadequate training in plant protection measures for dissemination of modern agricultural technologies was considered as the fourth important constraint. Susceptibility of existing varieties to pests and diseases was encountered one of the major constraints for successful cultivation

Constraints Faced by the Horticultural Growers

of high value horticultural crops in the region (fifth rank).

Other important constraints of the farmers for successful horticultural crops production were lack of adequate technical guidance from extension workers, difficulty in using botanical pesticides, lack of knowledge and skill about the use of pesticides, limited contact between farmers and extension workers, low price for horticultural products, higher cost of bio-inputs (bio-fertilizers, bio-pesticides and bio-fungicides) Inadequate credit facilities, knowledge on name of specific bio-pesticide, non-availability of resistant varieties, lack of diagnostic skill in identifying the major pests, higher labour wages, lack of clarity of information, exploitation by middlemen, knowledge on mode and method of application, knowledge on ITKs, cost for crop insurance, lack of adequate information, seasonal fluctuations in market, lack of knowledge about the beneficial insects, knowledge on prevailing pest, knowledge on disease and non-availability of bio control agents.

Rolle (2006) indicated fresh produce losses ranged between 10 to 40 per cent globally, with losses in India at the high end. Chikkasubbanna (2006) has reviewed some of the issues and priorities for improving the post harvest sector for vegetable handling. Pant and Singh (2014) stated that farmers need updated information on the source, quality and cost of agricultural inputs. They required information which is strategically relevant that can ultimately enhance their quality of livelihood with the winds of global liberalization and global marketing.

CONCLUSION

The higher education helps farmers to respond to challenges, innovation and organic technology. The farmer's perception on sustainable organic practices and marketing strategies, the knowledge regarding market for selling organic produce and of different bio control agents were the major aspects. It was found that major constraints like difficulty in using bio control agents, non-availability of bio

pesticides and bio-fertilizers which ranked as first, second and third important constraint, respectively were leading factors for non sustainable agriculture development. To strengthen the rural farming community, agricultural extension must play an important role by providing them the best extension services as well as connecting the farming community with market directly. Extension approach needs to be restructured to make technology dissemination responsive as per the needs of farmers.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents by their personal characteristics. (N=150)

Parameter	Frequency (Percentage)
Age group (Yr)	
<20	45(30.0)
21-40	70(46.7)
41-60	35(23.3)
Sex	
Male	95(63.3)
Female	55(36.7)
Marital Status	
Single	26(17.3)
Married	124(82.7)
Education level	
Illiterate	17(11.3)
Primary education	73(48.7)
Secondary education	22(14.7)
Higher secondary	28(18.7)
Graduate and above	10(6.6)
Family size	
Nuclear	135(90.0)
Joint	15(10.0)
Land holdings	
Marginal (<1 ha)	30(20.0)
Small (1-2 ha)	75(50.0)
Medium (2-5 ha)	37(24.7)
Large (>5 ha)	8(5.3)
Extension contact	
Low	25(16.7)
Moderate	83(55.3)
High	42(28.0)

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Table 2. Perception on sustainable organic practices and marketing strategies.**(N=150)**

Sr. No	Statements	SDA	DA	UD	A	SA	Mean Score	Rank
1	Knowledge on market for selling organic produce	25	49	-	56	20	3.02	I
2	Knowledge on different bio control agent	22	35	21	44	28	2.86	II
3	Knowledge on use of organic manures and pesticides	12	46	6	53	33	2.67	III
4	Perception on profitability of organic farming	18	24	19	63	26	2.63	IV
5	Perception on environmental degradation	-	22	12	62	54	2.01	V

Table 3. Constraints faced by the farmers for adoption of organic practices of horticultural crops. (N=150)

Sr. No	Constraints	SDF	DF	NF	AF	SAF	MS	Rank
1	Difficulty in using bio control agents	45(30)	27(18)	-	78(52)	-	3.26	I
2	Non-availability of bio pesticides	24(16)	60(40)	15(10)	20(13.3)	31(20.7)	3.17	II
3	Non-availability of organic manures	31(20)	25(15.3)	13(8.7)	44(29.3)	39(26)	3.15	III
4	Inadequate training	32(21.3)	44(29.3)	16(10.7)	22(14.7)	36(24)	3.09	IV
5	Susceptibility of varieties to pests and diseases	53(35)	20(13.3)	-	37(24.7)	40(26.7)	3.06	V
6	Lack of adequate technical guidance	28(18.7)	34(22.7)	9(6)	52(34.6)	27(18)	2.89	VI
7	Difficulty in using botanical pesticides	31(20)	26(17.3)	29(19.3)	25(16.7)	39(26)	2.86	VII
8	Lack of skill about the use of pesticides	-	50(33.3)	25(16.7)	75(50)	-	2.83	VIII
9	Limited contact with extension workers	22(14.6)	39(26)	12(8)	43(28.7)	34(22.7)	2.81	IX
10	Low price for horticultural products	27(18)	32(21.3)	12(8)	33(22)	46(30.7)	2.74	X
11	Higher cost of bio-inputs	-	45(30)	28(18.7)	65(43.3)	12(8)	2.70	XI
12	Inadequate credit facilities	12(8)	25(15.3)	40(26.7)	55(36.7)	20(13.3)	2.68	XII
13	Knowledge on name of specific bio-pesticide	20(13)	34(22.7)	8(5.3)	54(36)	34(22.7)	2.68	XII
14	Non-availability of resistant varieties	30(20)	22(14.7)	13(8.7)	32(21.3)	53(35.3)	2.62	XIII

Constraints Faced by the Horticultural Growers

15	Lack of diagnostic skill in identifying the major pests	29(19)	15(10)	19(12.7)	42(28)	45(30)	2.60	XIV
16	Higher labour wages	22(14)	29(19.3)	6(4)	51(34)	42(28)	2.58	XV
17	Lack of clarity of information	20(13)	26(17.3)	22(14.7)	36(24)	46(30.7)	2.58	XV
18	Exploitation by middle-men	12(8)	39(26)	-	69(46)	30(20)	2.56	XVI
19	Knowledge on ITKs	19(12)	23(15.3)	11(7.3)	54(36)	43(28.7)	2.47	XVII
20	Cost for crop insurance	18(12)	24(16)	13(8.7)	49(32.7)	46(30.6)	2.46	XVIII
21	Lack of adequate information	10(6.7)	28(18.7)	18(12)	55(36.6)	39(26)	2.43	XIX
22	Seasonal fluctuations in market	19(12)	22(14.6)	8(5.3)	55(36.7)	46(30.7)	2.42	XX
23	Knowledge about the beneficial insects	16(10)	27(18)	11(7.3)	34(22.7)	62(41.3)	2.34	XXI
24	Knowledge on prevailing pest	14(9.3)	9(6)	25(16.7)	62(41.3)	40(26.7)	2.30	XXII
25	Knowledge on disease	-	15(10)	-	89(59.3)	46(30.7)	1.89	XXIII
26	Non-availability of bio control agents	-	-	14(9.3)	61(40.7)	75(50)	1.59	XXIV

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Socio-economic Characterisation and Dairy Production System Maintained by Women Milk Producer Cooperative Societies in Indian Sundarban Region

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ABSTRACT

The present study was undertaken to characterise socio economic pattern of WMPCS members and analyse small holder dairy production system including its constraints in the Indian Sundarban. A total of 160 respondents from six development blocks were interviewed with a pre tested questionnaire. 74.4 per cent of the farmers had age between 20-45 yr and 88 per cent of them were married, which reflects young and energetic attitude of the farmers. 46.9 per cent of the farmers had only primary level of education. 63.5 per cent of the WMPCS members belonged to low income group (Rs 2500/- – 5000/-), evidently, net income from sale of milk by WMPCS members was found to be significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than that of informal dairy farmers. Herd size per household varied between 1.46 to 1.87 total livestock units (TLU); non-descript Indian zebu was the pre-dominant breed. 37.6 per cent respondents used artificial technique for breeding purpose. FEAST computer program was used to analyse feed resources of the area and it was found that the small holder dairy production system entirely depend upon grazing with little supplementation of concentrates. In the lean months of winters, residues of leguminous crops as well as mangrove leaves were used as fodders. Milk production of different cattle breeds varied significantly ($P < 0.01$) and milk yield from cross-bred Jersey was maximum (1652 l/lactation). Principal constraint was lack of green fodder production for dairy farming.

Key Words: FEAST, Sundarban, Milk production, Small holder, Dairy, Women Milk Producers' Cooperative Society.

INTRODUCTION

Sundarban region is a conglomerate of tropical mangrove islands bordering *Bay of Bengal*, and is a special ecological zone due to habitat of large numbers of threatened flora and fauna. Various researchers had observed that the area became increasingly vulnerable and unstable owing to serious threats from climate changes, population explosion, extreme poverty and lack of infrastructure (Danda *et al*, 2011 and FAO, 2011). Scope of crop based agriculture is also very limited due to salinity of soil in the area and thus local people principally depend upon animal husbandry and fishery based alternative livelihood systems.

Homestead dairy with indigenous zebu cattle is a common avenue for livelihood in the area. Recently, dairy cooperative societies formed and managed exclusively by village women has opened up vast possibilities of holistic development in the villages and women empowerment using homestead dairy as a tool. Present study was undertaken with the objective of characterising socio-economic status of the members of Women Milk Producers' Cooperative Societies (WMPCS) working under 'Sundarban Co-Operative Milk & Livestock Producers' Union Ltd (SMLU)' and analysing small holder dairy production systems maintained by WMPCS in Indian Sundarban region and their constraints.

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Table 1. Village wise distribution of respondents.

Sr. No.	Name of Block	Name of Village	Name of WMPCS	Number of Respondents
1	Mathurapur I	RamjibonPur	Ramkrishna WMPCS	20
2	Mathurapur II	Purbajata	Purbajata WMPCS	20
3	Namkhana	Fatikpur	FatikpurWMPCS	40
4	Kakdwip	14 number plot	RabindraWMPCS	20
		Gangadharpur	Radhakrishna WMPCS	20
5	Kulpi	Bajberia	Laxmipasa WMPCS	20
6	Basanti	Nafargunj	Nafarganj WMPCS	20

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling procedure

The present study was conducted during March-July 2016 in eighteen 'Women Milk Producers' Cooperative Societies' (WMPCS) in selected areas of Sundarban region of West Bengal, India. Six development blocks namely Mathurapur-I, Mathurapur-II, Namkhana, Kakdwip, Kulpi and Basanti were selected purposively. A total of 160 respondents were chosen randomly from the 7 WMPCS for present survey (Table1).

Data Collection and Analysis

A semi structured and pre-tested interview schedule on socio-economic parameters and prevalent dairy production system, maintained by WMPCS members, was developed for the present survey. Data were collected by personal interview, compiled and tabulated. Milk production data were collected from secondary sources like record books of each WMPCS. All the data were statistically analysed (SPSS V.20) for construction of frequency table, paired t-test (for comparing two groups of observations) and one way ANOVA (for comparing more than two groups of observations).

Evaluation of existing feed and fodder resources for small holder dairy farming in the concerned region was done using FEAST (Feed Assessment Tool) software program developed by International Livestock Research Institute (Duncan *et al*, 2012). Quantitative and qualitative information required

on different aspects of feed and fodder resources for FEAST program were gathered by (i) a Focus Group Discussion with minimum 20 women farmers at each milk collection unit in the village and (ii) by face to face individual interviews.

Constraints of homestead dairy farming as perceived by women members of the milk cooperatives were analysed by *Henry Garret ranking*. In this technique, percentage position of ranks associated with small dairy farming was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage position} = 100 (R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_j$$

Where, R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} variable by j^{th} respondents and N_j = Number of variable ranked by j^{th} respondents.

Using Garrett table, the percentage position of each rank was converted into scores. For each constraint, scores of individual respondents were added and then divided by the number of respondents. The factors with highest mean value were considered to be the most important.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characterisation of WMPCS members

Age

Age is an important factor that directly influences attitude of dairy farmers. WMPCS farmers according to their age were categorized

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Table 2. Socio-economic attributes of WMPCS members, n=160

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age	<20 years	3	2
	20-45 years	119	74.4
	>45 years	38	23.6
Marital Status	Married	143	89.40
	Un-married	5	3.1
	Widow	8	5
	Separated	4	2.5
Level of education	Up to Class IV	75	46.9
	Class V-VIII	54	33.7
	Class IX - XII	29	18.1
	Above XII	2	1.3
Average land holding	Up to 0.5 acre	101	63.1
	More than 0.5 acre	29	18.1
	Only Home-stead land	30	18.8
Gross monthly income of household	< Rs.2500.00	30	18.75
	Rs.2500.00 - 5000.00	102	63.5
	>Rs.₹ 5000.00	28	44.8

into 3 groups, viz. < 20 yr, 20-45 yr, and > 45yr (Table 2). The study revealed that 74.4 per cent of respondents belong to age category of 20-45 yr. Similar results were obtained in a dairy production area in South Ethiopia (Yigrem *et al*, 2008). Results indicated that dairy farming was being operated by famers who were young, energetic and physically capable. Sharma (2016) also reported that the farmers in the age group of 20-30 yr were found to be more interested in acquiring trainings, demonstrations and exposure visits and acquired high level of knowledge as compared to the elder group of more than 40 years of age.

Marital status

WMPCS members were exclusively women and married (88 %) followed by widow (4 %), unmarried (3 %) and separated (2 %). This indicated that most of the members involved in dairy farming were responsible, caring individuals with good mothering ability which is required in maintaining a good managerial standard in dairy farming.

Level of education

Education plays an important role in overall progress of human life. It drives farmers to adopt and implement newer technologies more successfully. Our study categorized WMPCS members into four groups up to class IV, class IV-VIII, class IX-XII, and above class XII. Present study showed (Table 2) that majority of the women farmers (46.9 %) had an education label up to class IV (primary level) followed by class V to VIII (33.7%), class IX to XII (18.1%) and above XII (1.3%). The present research finding showed that one of the major limitations for growth of the WMPCS was lack of education. Therefore, through suitable education programs, the overall betterment of WMPCS members could be achieved.

Average land holding

For dairy farming, owning a land is an important factor for sustainability of the farming. Various surveys (Skunmun, 2000 and Mubiru *et al*, 2007) in Asia and Africa indicated that larger the farm land/

household more was the milk production. The data (Table 2) showed 63.1 per cent of dairy owners have land holding up to 0.5 acre, followed by more than 0.5 acre (18.1 %) and only residence compound (18.8 %). This fragmented and smaller land profile was typical to the area and demonstrated vulnerable situation of the small holder dairy farming of the region.

Gross monthly income of household

The study indicated that majority (63.5 %) of farm women belonged to low income group (Earning Rs.2500-5000/month) families and 18.75 per cent members belonged to less than Rs. 2500/month group (Table 2). This result reflected poor socio economic condition of people of Sundarban and was in consistent with the findings of Dumrya *et al* (2016).

Comparison of net monthly income from milk sale between WMPCS members and informal women dairy farmers

The study revealed that the net income from milk sale of WMPCS members was significantly ($P < 0.05$; paired t-test) high as compared to that of informal milk producers (Fig.1). Net income of WMPCS members from milk sale is on average Rs.1050/- month whereas the informal growers receive average price of Rs.865.82/-month. This indicated that formation of WMPCS had a direct role on income optimisation for dairy farmers. This comparison clearly gave evidence that support from district level milk union in terms of technical inputs, trainings etc. was very much helpful for WMPCS members to consolidate their profit margin.

Small Holder Dairy Production System under WMPCS

Herd Size per household and cattle breeds

Herd size refers the numbers of cattle per household and presented in Table 3. In this study three cattle breeds were documented namely local, cross bred Jersey (CBJ) and cross bred Gir (CBG). Herd size was expressed in Tropical Livestock Unit (TLU). When calculating Tropical Livestock

Units (TLU), following conversion factors were used (Staal *et al*, 1997) adult male cattle: 1.0, adult female cattle: 0.7, post weaner cattle: 0.5 (heifer), pre-weaners cattle: 0.2 (calf).

Highest (1.87 TLU) and lowest (1.46 TLU) herd size was observed respectively in Ramkrishna WMPCS (Mathurapur I block) and Fatikpur WMPCS (Namkhana block). Majority of dairy herds were small, typical to the concerned area. Chand *et al* (2015) opined that economic viability of small holder dairy farming decreases with small herd size. It was also evident that low productive non-descript (indigenous zebu) cows were predominant breeds in the area. Farmers prefer local breeds due to many positive attributes like better disease resistant capability, suitability in low input farming and low cost of maintenance. As a result, although facility for artificial insemination with better cattle genotype was available in the area, small farmers were reluctant to avail that facility. During the interview, it was also reported that repeated failures of AI techniques was a cause of frustration for the farmers.

Cattle breeding programme in the area

It was evident that natural pure breeding among indigenous zebu was common in the study area. Various stakeholders like WMPCS, state departments and non-government organisations were working for years to produce cross-bred genotypes by implementing cross breeding policy for better production. Attempts were being made to popularise cross breeding of indigenous cows with improved sires like Jersey, Sahiwal or Girbreed using artificial insemination (AI) techniques with frozen semen. Odend'hal (1988) described the poor impact of cattle crossbreeding program in West Bengal. Situation has not changed much; present study showed that only 37.6 per cent farmers adopt AI technology, while rest of the farmers prefer natural service with local bulls. AI service is mainly provided by private AI workers (55%), followed by government agencies (35%) and veterinary field assistants (10%).

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Table 3. Cattle Herd size in different WMPCS, n= 160.

Sampling area of Households	Herd Size in TLU (Mean± SE)			
Name of WMPCS	CBG	CBJ	Local	Total
Radhakrishna MPCS	0.24±0.125	0.145±0.006	1.335±0.213	1.72±0.21
Rabindra MPCS	0.14±0.064	0.185±0.07	1.39±0.222	1.715±0.24
Fatikpur MPCS	0.1±0.055	0.22±0.08	1.14±0.139	1.461±0.14
Ramkrishna WMPCS	0.16±0.054	0.14±0.071	1.57±0.221	1.87±0.205
Purbajata MPCS	0.05±0.03	0.24±0.102	1.185±0.176	1.48±0.190
Nafarganj WMPCS	0.05±0.03	0.285±0.081	1.325± 0.18	1.665±0.201
Laxmipasa WMPCS	0.19±0.117	0.24±0.077	1.115±0.166	1.545±0.179

Housing of cows

Present study noticed that three types of cattle housing namely cemented floor, partly cemented floor and earthen floor in the region. Majority (43%) of the farmers used earthen floor followed by semi partly cemented floor (39%) and cemented floor (18%) for keeping their animal. It was also observed that most of the cow shed had poor ventilation and lacked proper waste management practices.

Feed and Fodder availability

FEAST program revealed that grazing was the main source (36.81 %) of dry matter followed by crop residues (27.93 %) purchased feed (13.59 %), collected fodder (12.72 %) and cultivated fodder (8.95 %). Dairy cows get maximum feed during rainy season when there are plenty of greens. Typically large numbers of dairy cows are kept in grazing on a small pasture. This was in consistent with several earlier reports (Devendra, 2000 and Kasirye, 2003). In this system of feeding, cows consume grasses and weeds with little nutritive values. When greens became scanty in winter, straws of leguminous crops (e.g., *Lathyrus*) were used as animal feed. However, Paddy straw remains as the principal crop residue that is extensively used as dry fodder throughout the year. It was reported that in the lean season of winter months, farmers used even some mangrove leaves, particularly of *Avicennia sp.* as fodder. This finding was in consistent of Ghosh *et al* (2015). Common feed ingredients used for cattle ration were mainly wheat bran, sunflower cake, mustard cake and grass pea pods. Most of the time, a

concentrate mixture consisting of these ingredients is given to animals with paddy straw. It was observed that cultivation and production of green forage for animal feeding was only limited to some pockets only. Majority of farmers were not at all aware for fodder cultivation practices. Maize (var. *African tall*) was the principal fodder cultivated by some progressive farmers. It was evident, however, that there were no scientific feeding management programs among WMPCS members, which might be due to the fact that extension machinery is still very weak in the region.

Milk Production

Milk production of different breed differed significantly ($P < 0.01$; One way Anova). Among the three breeds, CBJ was the most productive (1652.25 l/lactation) followed by CBG (949.35 l/lactation) and indigenous zebu (414.82 l/lactation). Although CBJ appeared to be the most productive in this agro-climatic area, it was clear that production of CBJ was still far below from national average of 2400 l/lactation. This might be attributed to nutritional insufficiency of dairy cows as evidenced by acute shortage of greens in lean periods.

Constraints of small holder dairy farming

Henry Garret ranking analysis (Table 4) from 160 respondents showed that the primary constraint for small holder dairy farming was lack of green fodder cultivation, followed by lack of extension contacts, high price of cattle feed, distantly located veterinary hospital etc. Respondents reported non-availability

Table 4. Ranking of constraints in small holder dairy in India Sundarban, n=160.

Constraints	Total Score	Average	Rank
Lack of green fodder cultivation	13740	85.8	1
Lack of extension contacts	12380	73.3	2
High price of cattle feed	11500	71.8	3
Distantly located veterinary hospital	10800	67.5	4
Frequent failure of artificial insemination in cows	10180	63.6	5
High incidence of calf mortality	9900	61.8	6
Distantly located milk collection centres	9420	58.8	7

of quality fodder seeds in the region. Limited feed resource remained as a major constraint in small holder dairy farming in South Asia for many years as reported by several authors (Devendra, 2000). Present study revealed that they did not also have the adequate knowledge regarding cultivation practices of fodders. Further, it had been identified that farmers were more inclined to cultivation of cash crops than fodder. In this background it was observed that scanty fodder supplementation might lead to various metabolic and reproductive diseases and as a result warrant subsequent financial loss to farmers.

CONCLUSION

Present study identified a mixed crop-livestock system in Indian Sundarban region where homestead dairy farming is an integral part of livelihood. Analysis on socio-economic aspects of WMPCS members clearly showed that small dairy farmers still belonged to poor class with minimum exposure to modern dairy farming that needs to be addressed. For sustainable dairy farming in the concerned region, it was strongly recommended that- i) re-evaluation of present breeding policy with cross-breeding; phenotypic and genotypic characterisation of local zebu cattle should be started for using them in future breeding programs and, ii) promoting fodder maize cultivation in the region. If steps could be taken up by district milk union (SMLU) to frame a suitable strategy covering the above stated recommendations, small holder dairy farming in the region may witness a new dimension in near future.

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Socio-economic Impact of Livestock in Tribal Areas of Leh

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ABSTRACT

Livestock is not only an important source of food and income but also the sign of assets in rural areas for poor people. In order to estimate how social-economic factors influence livestock production and income with the help of empirical model, the authors used the data collected from 100 household selected from 24 villages of 6 localities in Leh region of Jammu and Kashmir. In Ladakh region overall 70 per cent people are dependent on livestock especially in areas of Zaskar and Nyoma, out of which about 80 per cent are women. Hence, it is strongly suggested that stakeholders should look forward to the livestock production system in Leh region of Jammu and Kashmir to have clear strategy and good policies.

Key Words: Empirical model, Household, Leh region, Livestock, Socio-economic factors

INTRODUCTION

Ladakh, land of high passes, is the largest in area among the three main regions of the Jammu and Kashmir State. It is a biogeographic region with extremely harsh climatic conditions. It is the coldest and most elevated inhabited region in the country with altitudes ranging from 2300 m to 5900 m above mean sea level. The temperature fluctuates from 30° C in summer to -30° C in winter. Average precipitation is very low i.e. around 9 to 10 cm. Majority of people (77%) live in villages and depend primarily on agriculture and livestock rearing. Being unique agro-climatic and biogeographic region on earth which is bestowed with rich natural animal biodiversity having unique characteristics features which can withstand harsh climatic conditions of this cold dry arid region. This contributes the uniqueness of livestock species in true sense.

The cold desert of Ladakh has huge barren lands where even agriculture is uncertain, therefore, people mainly depend on livestock resources. Because of unique animal biodiversity and

ecosystem integrity of this region it has been found that livestock contributes in income generation and poverty alleviation by means of multiple values which are associated with livestock. Direct value for example livestock sales, meat and milk, employment, transport, knowledge and indirect values such as inputs for agriculture, wildlife and tourism. The native livestock breeds are multipurpose with unique genetic characteristics and exhibit a distinct superiority over other breeds of the India which include adaptation to harsh or extremely cold arid dry climatic conditions, utilization of poor quality feed and better resistance to tropical diseases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data Collection and Sampling Techniques

Both primary and secondary data were collected from three blocks namely Nyoma, Durbok and Leh of Ladakh region. Structured questionnaire based primary data were collected from a total of 100 randomly selected households in the year 2013-14. The data were verified from the Dept. of Animal

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Husbandry and Sheep Husbandry Govt. of J & K. In each of the villages sampling was done with the help of local authorities. List of all households in a village was taken as a sampling frame during assignment of primary data source (PDS). From the list the starting point was chosen at random using lottery technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact of livestock on the economy of Ladakh

The estimated livestock Population of the state is 155.867 lakh comprising 31.185 lakh cattle, 37.788 lakh sheep, 7.704 lakh Buffalo, 16.748 lakh goat, 57.195 lakh fowl and 5.247 lakh duck. Out of the total livestock population 48.47 and 47.42 per cent is present in Jammu and Kashmir region, respectively. The contribution of Ladakh region depicts that livestock population of these two districts includes 0.964 lakh cattle, 2.081 lakh sheep, 2.900 lakh goats and 0.461 lakh fowls. The Total livestock Population of Ladakh Region is 6.406 lakh. Out of which 3.222 lakh in Leh and 3.184 lakh in Kargil district respectively. Ladakh Region contributes 3.83 per cent to the total estimated milk production of the State which is about 1609.247 thousand MT, total estimated meat production of State was worked out to be 309 lakh kg consisting of 80.30 per cent of red meat and 19.70 per cent of white meat. The Jammu region accounted for 51.45 per cent , Kashmir region (41.55%) while Ladakh Region (7.00%) of total meat production (Integrated sample survey 2010-11).

The agriculture including livestock contributes 25.94 per cent to the Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) at constant prices of which livestock has a contribution of 11 per cent, which is about 40 per cent of the agriculture and allied activities. This contribution is excluding the draught power of the livestock used for ploughing and other transport. In absolute terms the sector contributes Rs. 3240/- crore to the state economy at current price as per GSDP. The contribution of livestock to the state economy is higher than horticulture and crop sector.

Major livestock resources found in Ladakh region

The agro-climatic conditions in the state are conducive for wool and mutton production. This is a primary occupation of migratory tribes. The contribution of livestock to the state economy is quite significant and the sheep and goat population constitutes about 56 per cent of the total livestock. The local Kashmiri wool which was primarily used for manufacturing of Namdas and coarse blankets obtained from cross breed sheep finds its way into the market for making of fine quality tweeds, pullovers and blankets etc. The estimated sheep and goat population of the Ladakh Region is 2.081 lakh sheep, 2.900 lakh goats. The main sheep breeds of this region are: Malluk breed and Merino-Malluk hybrids that produce better quality clothing wool. Changluk breed is prevalent in Changtang area which provide wool preferred for the carpet industry. Ladakh Region contributes 2.697 lakh kg to the total wool production estimated for the State (73.819 lakh kg) which consisted of 59.764 lakh kg (80.96%) from Cross-breed Sheep and 14.055 lakh kg (19.04%) of Local-breed Sheep. (Integrated sample survey 2010-11)

Goats

The biggest advantage of the Indigenous goat is its resistance to diseases and its adaptability in unfavourable grazing circumstances. Because of their small size, adaptive feeding behaviour and easy management, goats are a viable option in improving the household cash flow of rural people tribal communities which resolve the issue of food security. Apart from cash income from the sales of pashmina wool products, goats could also be a valuable source of milk ,meat , manure and skin for considerable number of rural people and tribal pastoral communities of Ladakh.

Changtangi goat primary raised for its valuable pashmina wool which is the costliest fiber on earth. Other breeds of goats are raised for meat and wool. Their hair is used for making ropes, baskets and coarse blankets, the skin used for garments in poorer

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households. The present scenario shifting towards livestock integrated farming based economy is the most burning issue of Ladakh and it is the high time to take livestock integrated farming system seriously so that we could cherish the dream of a sustainable, prosperous and a developed Ladakh.

Yak (*Bos grunniens*)

Yak is a unique bovine species of economic importance in high hill and snow bound areas of Indian Himalayas. This versatile bovine is a major source of livelihood for the highlanders living in difficult terrains. The range of products and services provided by yak include: meat, milk, wool and leather, draught power and soil nutrients besides serving as financial asset and security.

Yak a hardiest bovine species called as ships of snow that easily survives cold temperatures and require minimal care. It is the only animal which lives on the mountains at an altitude of 2500 to 6000 m above mean sea level with temperature well below 50°C kept for multipurpose uses such as meat, fibre, fuel, and transport. Yak-cattle cross (dzo and dzomo), the dzo kept for draught power and dzomo for milk production. Dzo are preferred for ploughing because they are much harder than the local bull or the cattle-jersey bull; The female yak (Dzomo) is better milch animal as compared to local cow, milk is very rich having 7 – 12 per cent fat & 5 -6 per cent protein. Milk is golden white in colour. The dressing percentage varies from 40 to 45 per cent. Produce undercoat of fine diameter (400 g/yr). In some areas, where the Dzomo cannot withstand the summer heat the cows are preferred. Here cows are of different breed than of plains and they can very well withstand the biting cold of winter months. With the very little grazing pastures open, hand feeding becomes must. The lactation period of cow and Dzomo is six and nine months respectively. Cows give three to four kg milk/day while as Dzomo produce five to six kg of milk/day. The calving period of cows is greater than Dzomo, in case of cows it is more than eighteen months but Dzomo reproduces almost every year. Jersey-local

cattle hybrids kept by families for increased milk yield provided they have fodder.

Out of six blocks of Leh district, Leh block has highest number of exotic breed of cows which determines that it produces maximum milk in the district in spite of least cultivable land. Durbok has got least number of exotic breed of cows. Khaltsi, kharuand Leh has highest number of indigenous breed of cows. The dairy production of Leh is the main sector of economy in the rural side. It fulfills their domestic needs and the surplus is sold in market. Out of total livestock 43.42% are cows and bulls only. It clearly indicates the importance of dairy production in arid region of Ladakh.

Asiatic double-humped camels (*Camelus bactrian*)

This is a unique animal species of economic importance in high hill and snow bound areas of Indian Himalayas. This versatile animal is a major source of livelihood for the highlanders living in difficult terrains. The range of products and services provided by camel include meat, milk, wool and leather, draught power and soil nutrients besides serving as financial asset and security. They are hairy double humped animals having historic importance of Central Asian trade capable of carrying 600 pounds. Bactrian camels can go a week without water and a month without food and they can endure extreme harsh climatic conditions and travel long periods of time without water has made them ideal caravan animals of cold dry arid region. Bactrian camels move on an average at about 5 km/hr and produce 5 kg of hair, 600 l of milk and 250 kg of dung a year. Camels serve humans as beasts of burden, transportation, desert companion, source of pride, measure of wealth and now kept for tourism purpose which plays a significant role in the rural economy of this region. It provides milk and for the occasional feast meat. From its wool women weave blankets and rugs, its hide is turned into sandals, candles, buckets. Camel dung fires are a source of heat and used for cooking during coldest nights of the winter.

Zanskari horse

This horse is a symbol of wealth and used in local polo matches and donkeys used along the upper Indus river for transport.

Estimated economic value of livestock produces during 2013-14) for Leh Region .(Total Rs. 29.314 Crores

CONCLUSION

It can be said that livestock sector plays an important role in socio-economic development as animals provide nutrient-rich food products, draught power, dung as organic manure and domestic

fuel, hides & skin, ensure food and nutritional security and are a regular source of cash income for rural households. It acts as natural capital which can be easily reproduced to act as a living bank with offspring as interest and an insurance against income shocks of crop failure and natural calamities. Rearing of livestock helps in women empowerment and the livelihoods of major chunk of poor rural households of cold arid dry region of Ladakh where livestock rearing are an integrated part of the smallholder production systems and play a significant role in poverty alleviation, socio-economic development particularly important to women, who often supplement family incomes and generating gainful advantages of employment in the tribal areas of this region. Therefore, livestock industry in the state has vast scope for development rendering quick economic returns and has been identified as critical to the overall economic and social development of this region.

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Socio-Personal, Communication Characteristics and Information Needs of Vegetable Growers of Hill Region of Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to identify the relationship between socio-personal & communication characteristics and information needs for designing distance learning modules for farmers of hill districts of Uttarakhand. One hundred and twenty vegetable growers of four hill districts of Uttarakhand state comprising of Kumaon and Garhwal region were selected for the study. Data were analyzed by using percentage, frequency and chi-square analysis. It was observed that vegetable growers of hill regions of Uttarakhand had moderate to high need for information as well as knowledge. The most important areas in which respondents had high information needs were seed treatment, weed management, disease and pest control, chemical fertilizer application, harvesting, post harvesting and marketing. The findings revealed there were no direct meaningful relationship between information needs and Socio-personal profiles.

Key Words: Information needs, Socio-economic, Vegetable growers, Relationship.

INTRODUCTION

Farmers of hill region are engaged in growing of different in different altitudinal zones and in all the geographical location. In terms of production, some areas are producing high quality and quantity of vegetables but the production is not as much as can be desired keeping favourable geo-environmental conditions in view. The villages, which are located in the highland, are exporting vegetables, particularly potato, tomato cabbage, pea in the regional market and earning high income. At the same time, most of the regions in the mid-slopes are producing vegetable domestically while the agro-ecological conditions are quite suitable for high production. It is because farmers are still unaware about the new cultivation practices and technologies available with the research institutes. Hence, it is essential to disseminate information about new technologies so that farmers can make use of these technologies. There also existed a gap between research findings and the need of the farmers. It has been reported by Raut (2005) that about 73 per cent respondents need information related to agriculture followed

by horticulture (59 %) and animal husbandry (18 %). Different extension agencies like Krishi Vigyan Kendras, District Horticulture Officers and other non government organizations are providing information about agriculture to the farmers in closer proximity but still the information gap is prevailing in the hilly region. Hence, the present study was undertaken to find out relationship between personal, socio-economic and communication characteristics and information needs of vegetable growers in hill regions of Uttarakhand..

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Out of the six districts of the Kumaon region, Nainital and Champwat and from seven districts of the Garhwal region, Rudraprayag and Tehri Garhwal district on the basis of productivity of vegetables were selected for the study. Out of these districts KVK of each district was selected purposively and one adopted vegetable growing village from each KVK was selected purposively. Thirty farmers from four selected villages each who were engaged in vegetable cultivation were

selected by using census method. The data for the investigation were collected from 120 respondents with the help of semi structured interview schedule and knowledge test. The relationship among the selected characteristics (includes personal, socio economic and communication characteristics) and information needs of vegetable growers as perceived by the respondents were determined by computing the correlation coefficients (r value). The data collected were coded, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted with the help of appropriate procedures and statistical techniques.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio personal characteristics

The data (Table 1) showed that majority of the respondents (70.00%) belong to middle age group followed by old (15.84%) and young (14.16%) age group. Raut (2005) also found that majority of the respondents belonged to middle age followed by young and old. Regarding educational status of the farmers, it was observed that 30.83 per cent of the respondents were having primary education followed by middle level (26.67%) and intermediate and more (20.00%) where as only 18.33 per cent of the respondents have education up to high school. Some of the farmers (4.17%) were found illiterate (Table 1).

Majority of the respondents (48.34%) were having medium level of experience in the enterprise, followed by high level (38.33 %) and few farmers (13.33%) came under low category. The values for land holdings revealed that a majority of the respondents (53.33%) were small followed by marginal (40%), medium (5%) and large (1.67%) category of land holding. The reason behind this might be that in hilly area, the land is scattered and divided in the families so maximum number of the farmers were marginal and small.

It was noticed that majority of the respondents (78.34%) belonged to general category which included Brahmins and Thakur followed by other backward caste (15.83%) and Scheduled caste

Table1. Distribution of respondents according to their socio personal characteristics.

Parameter	Category	Frequency (N=120)	Percentage
Age Mean=33.71 S.D.=11.41 Middle (22-45 yr) Old (>45 yr)	Young (<22 yr)	17	14.16
		84	70.00
		19	15.84
Education Primary Middle level High school Intermediate and more	Illiterate	05	04.17
		37	30.83
		32	26.67
		22	18.33
		24	20.00
Year of experience Medium (5-9 yr) High (> 9 yr)	Low (<5 yr)	16	13.33
		58	48.34
		46	38.33
Marital status Married Widow	Unmarried	16	13.33
		102	85.00
		2	01.67
Land Holding	Marginal (<1 ha)	48	40.00
	Small (1-2 ha)	64	53.33
	Medium (2-4 ha)	6	05.00
	Large (>4 ha)	2	01.67
Caste	Scheduled Caste	07	05.83
	Other Backward Caste	19	15.83
	General	94	78.34
Source of Earning	Agriculture	120	100.00
	Unskilled	24	20.00
	Skilled worker	71	59.17
	Business	57	47.50
	Service	42	35.00
Social Participation	Cooperative society	28	23.33
	Farmers forum	16	13.33
	Youth club	14	11.67
	Dairy cooperative	06	05.00
	Panchayat membership	38	31.67
	No Membership	46	38.33

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(05.83%) including Gorkhaali and Jatav. The data regarding Source of earning in Table 1 indicate that all the respondents (100 %) were engaged in agriculture followed by skilled workers (59.17%), business (57.50%) and services (35.00%) as their source of earning. Only 20 per cent were found to be unskilled worker. It was evident (Table 1) that regarding social participation that 31.67 per cent of the respondents were involved in socio-political institutions like Panchayat followed by 23.33 per cent in co-operative societies, 13.33 per cent in societies like farmers forum and 11.67 per cent of the respondents were engaged in various Youth clubs like Yuvak Mangal Dal and Yuvati Mangal Dal. Merely five per cent of the respondents were engaged in dairy co-operatives.

Socio economic status (SES)

It refers to the status and the position of the respondents' family in the society. It is relevant from Table 2 that most of the respondents 63.34 per cent had medium level of socio economic status (SES) followed by upper level (23.33%) and lower level (13.33%). Therefore, the analysis of the figures reveals that majority of the respondents were found in medium level of SES.

Communication characteristics

It is apparent from Table 3, that maximum of respondents (63.33%) had medium level of extension agency contact, followed by low (22.50%) and high extension agency contact (14.17%). Majority of the respondents were having contact with extension agencies because these villages were adopted by the Krishi Vigyan Kendras of the respective districts. It was that most of the respondents (65.00%) were having medium level of information seeking behaviour,

followed by low level (23.33%) and high level of information seeking behaviour (11.67%). Singh and Kalra (1993) reported that farmers preferred radio for seeking agricultural information followed by television, newspaper, agricultural magazines, films and audio cassettes. It was evident that most of the respondents (57.50%) were having medium level of information processing behaviour, followed by low level (30.00%) and high level (12.50%). Majority of the farmers processed the information through remembering and documenting the literature. Some farmers also maintained the file for processing the information.

It was pertinent to note that most of the respondents (61.66%) had medium level of information sharing behaviour, followed by low (26.67%) and high level (11.67%). Maximum of the respondents shared the gained information with their relatives, neighbours and with the needy persons of their locality. Donner (2009) shared a number of services that use mobile phones for interaction with rural farmers. Providing market information was the most frequently offered service.

The finding regarding communication characteristics showed that majority of the respondents had medium extension agency contact, information seeking behaviour, information processing behaviour and information sharing behaviour.

Information needs analysis through knowledge test

Information needs of the vegetable growers were analyzed and prioritized. The level of Information need was determined with the help of average mean score and standard deviation (SD). The Information need was identified by various methods

Table 2. Distributions of respondents according to socio economic status.

Parameter	Level of SES	Category	Frequency (N=120)	Percentage
SES Mean=27.85 S.D.=8.57	Lower	Less than 19	16	13.33
	Middle	19-35	76	63.34
	Upper	More than 35	28	23.33

Table 3. Distribution of respondents according to communication behaviour.

Category	Frequency (N=120)	Percentage
1. Extension Agency Contact		
Low	27	22.50
Medium	76	63.33
High	17	14.17
2. Information Seeking Behavior		
Low	28	23.33
Medium	78	65.00
High	14	11.67
3. Information Processing Behavior		
Low	36	30.00
Medium	69	57.50
High	15	12.50
4. Information Sharing Behavior		
Low	32	26.67
Medium	74	61.66
High	14	11.67

viz. knowledge test, interview schedule, focused group discussion and non participant observation. The content of Knowledge test was divided into different segments so that each aspect was covered adequately. It covered the content related to pre-sowing (field preparation, seed treatment), weed management, pest control, insecticide & pesticide application, marketing, infrastructural facilities. The data (Table 4) indicated that majority of the respondents (70%) had medium level of knowledge about their enterprise followed by low (17.50%) and high (12.50%).

Medium level of knowledge was probably due to the reason that most of them were cultivating vegetables for many years and they gained

experience in this sector. They were supported by governmental agencies like Krishi Vigyan Kendras, District Horticulture Board and some NGOs time to time.

Prioritizing of information need on vegetable cultivation practices of respondents

The level of information needs was determined with the help of average mean score and standard deviation. It was evident (Table 5) that most of the farmers possessed moderate and high level of information need. The areas like field preparation, seed treatment, seed sowing, weed control, organic farming, harvesting, post harvest management and marketing information of the respondents categorized under moderate level of information needs categories whereas insect & pest control and chemical fertilizer application were found to be in high level of information need.

The salient issues which emerged during focused group discussion were farmers needed more information on disease and pest identification and its control. They did not know the exact method of application of pesticides and insecticides. Most of the time the crop get damaged due to the infestation of any pest or any disease and if they apply the insecticides and pesticides again by improper use the remaining crop also get damaged. Some of the farmers opined that they needed information regarding better quality and variety of seeds. They told that many times extension personnel provided seeds but they did not germinate or get destroyed. It might be because they were not told about the appropriate sowing methods of the particular variety. Besides vegetable cultivation practices they stressed that they lack information on marketing of their product.

Table 4. Distribution of respondents according to information need.

Variable	Category	Frequency (N=120)	Percentage
Knowledge level Mean=28.28 S.D=5.40	Low (less than 23)	21	17.50
	Medium (23-33)	84	70.00
	High (more than 33)	15	12.50

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Table 5. Prioritization of information need on vegetable cultivation practices (N=120)

Sr. No.	Major information need areas	Percentage of re-spondents	Level of information need
1.	Field Preparation	56.50	Moderate
2.	Seed Treatment	62.50	Moderate
3.	Seed Sowing	45.50	Moderate
4.	Weed Control	48.33	Moderate
5.	Insect & Pest Control	83.17	High
6.	Chemical Fertilizer Application	85.00	High
7.	Organic Farming	62.33	Moderate
8.	Harvesting	43.66	Moderate
9.	Post Harvest Management	66.50	Moderate
10.	Marketing	68.66	Moderate

It was clear from Table 3 that there is no significant relationship of socio personal and communication characteristics with information needs. In contrary to the findings Yadav (2008) found that training need or knowledge level had positive and significant relationship with personal and socio economic characteristics, viz. education ($r=0.2895$), social participation($r=0.1795$) and overall socio economic status($r=0.2994$). Sharma (2016) also reported that the farmers in the age group of 20-30 yr were found to be more interested in acquiring trainings, demonstrations and exposure visits and acquired high level of knowledge as compared to the elder group of more than 40 years of age.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the major findings of the study it was concluded that vegetable growers of hill regions of Uttarakhand had moderate to high need for information/ knowledge. The most important areas in which respondents had high information needs were seed treatment, weed management, disease control, insect-pest control, chemical fertilizer application, harvesting, post harvesting

Table 6. Relationship of socio personal and communication characteristics with information needs.

Sr. No.	Variable	Correlation coefficient (r)
1	Age	0.067
2	Years of experience	-0.078
3	Education	0.121
4	Social participation	0.033
5	Extension agency Contact	-0.011
6	Information seeking behaviour	-0.042
7	Information processing behaviour	-0.112
8	Information sharing behaviour	-0.002
9	Marital status	0.038
10	Earning source	0.032
11	Land holding	-0.038
12	Caste	0.125
13	SES	0.064

* *Significant at 0.05 level of probability*

and marketing. The results depicted that majority of the respondents dominated by middle age group, married, under middle level of experience in the enterprise, skilled workers, small farmers, belonged to general caste and had primary and middle level of education. Maximum number of the respondents was involved in social and political institutions with and without holding any post, belonged to medium family size possessed agricultural instruments/ electrical instruments/ animals and had pucca house. Majority of the respondents came under the medium level of socio economic status (SES) group. The findings revealed there were no direct meaningful relationship between information needs and Socio-personal profiles.

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Soil Fertility Status as Influenced by Cropping System in Submountain Zone of Lower Shiwalik Hills in Punjab

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to access the effect of cropping system under irrigated and rainfed condition on fertility status of the soil. The soil samples (0-15 cm) were collected from four villages, i.e. Jhandiankalan, Mehndrikhurd, Samlah and fatehgarhviran. The results from chemical analysis of samples revealed that the pH of 100% samples from was lied between 6.5-8.7 and EC from 100% samples lied below 0.8 dS/m. Soil samples in irrigated system were high in SOC category, whereas none of the soil sample in rainfed system had SOC in this category. Similarly, available P, K and DTPA extractable available Cu, Zn and Fe were low in soils from maize-wheat system as compared to rice-wheat system soils.

Key Words: Maize-wheat, Nutrient content, Micro-nutrient status, Rice-wheat.

INTRODUCTION

The sub mountain zone of Punjab consist parts of Hoshiarpur, Ropar, Nawanshaheer, Pathankot and Patiala. This zone is characterized with undulating topography and hilly terrain with problems such as soil erosion, lack of soil moisture, frequent floods, droughts, low fertility status of soil and deep underground water. The maize-wheat is the second dominant cropping system after rice-wheat cropping system. Rice-wheat cropping system was cultivated over an area of ~2.6 mha that constituted ~78% of gross cropped area of the Punjab (Benbi and Brar, 2009), on the other hand, maize-wheat cropping sequence was followed over an area of about 0.126 mha area.

Benbi *et al* (2012) reported that the contrasting moisture regimes under rice-wheat and maize-wheat cropping systems lead to decomposition of organic matter at variable rates. The soil organic carbon pool was also affected by the indigenous carbon input in the form of root and leaf biomass and farmyard manures. The magnitude of carbon sequestration and nutrient release in soil after its mineralization was mainly driven by the quality of the soil organic

matter (SOM). The climate, cropping system and soil management interventions such as manures and fertilizer application, extent of soil tillage and soil moisture also affected the soil organic carbon status of the soil (Regmi *et al*, 2002). The present investigation was carried out to access the effect of cropping system on fertility status of the soils under rice-wheat and maize-wheat cropping systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study region is situated in villages Jhandian, Samlah, Mehndrikhurd and Fatehgarhviran of district Ropar (Punjab). The soil of villages Jhandiankalan, Mehndrikhurd and Samlah are under Maize-wheat cropping system with rainfed condition, while soil of the village Fatehgarhviran is under rice-wheat cropping system with irrigated condition. Rice crop was fertilized with 125-160 kg N ha⁻¹, 30-40 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹, 20-30 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ (in soil with low potassium status), while maize crop was fertilized with 90-130 kg N and 25-35 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and farmyard manure was applied at 6 Mg ha⁻¹ before transplanting rice or seeding maize, once in two years. Wheat was fertilized at 90-130 kg N and 50-65 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 20-30 kg K₂O

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Table 1. Effect of cropping systems on chemical properties, available macro-nutrients and DTPA extractable micro-nutrient status of soil.

Cropping system	pH	EC (dS m ⁻¹)	OC (%)	Available (Kg/Acre)		DTPA extractable micro-nutrient (mg/kg)			
				P	K	Mn	Cu	Fe	Zn
Rainfed Eco-system (Maize-wheat system)	7.54a	0.21b	0.42b	10.90b	126.38b	6.48a	0.72b	5.61b	0.96b
Irrigated Eco-system (Rice-wheat system)	7.82a	0.39a	0.64a	13.31a	138.28a	4.90b	1.35a	16.92a	1.53a

Different letters in each column show significant differences at < 0.05 probability level.

ha⁻¹ (in soil with low potassium status). In addition 25 kg Zinc sulphate (21% Zn) was also applied to rice in Zinc deficient soils and 10 kg Zinc sulphate (21% Zn) was applied to maize in Zinc deficient soils.

Surface soil samples (0-15 cm depth) were collected from 100 sites under different land-uses at four villages. Soil samples were collected in the month of May after the harvesting of wheat. Soil samples were collected randomly from 4-5 places with the help of soil augur and then composited. Soil samples were air dried and sieved through 2 mm sieve for chemical analysis. The soil samples were analyzed for pH (1:2 soil: water suspension), electrical conductivity (EC, 1:2 soil: water supernatant), soil organic carbon (SOC) (rapid titration method of Walkley and Black (1934)), available P (Olsen et al, 1954), available K (Mervin and Peech, 1950) and micro-nutrients viz. zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), iron (Fe) and manganese (Mn) were determined using DTPA (Diethylene Tri-amine Penta Acetic acid) extract (Lindsay and Norvell, 1978). Mean comparison was made using Duncan Multiple Range Test when the F-test was found significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results revealed that pH and EC were higher in the irrigated rice-wheat system as compared to rainfed system (Table-1). The soil organic carbon was significantly higher in the rice-wheat system as compared to rainfed system; it might be due to addition of higher root biomass in irrigated

system. Similarly, available P and available K were significantly higher in the irrigated system than rainfed system. This was mainly due to higher use of phosphoric and potassic fertilizers. In case of Mn, higher number of soil samples lied under Mn deficient category (less than 3.5 mg kg⁻¹) in rice-wheat cropping than that in maize-wheat, but Mn deficiency in wheat depends upon the permeable nature of soils coupled with greater solubility of Mn (Singh et al, 2006). The higher uptake under intensive cultivation in case of rice-wheat system might be another reason for the low Mn content in Irrigated system.

All the soil samples had DTPA-Cu above critical value of 0.2 mg kg⁻¹ representing optimal Cu supplying capacity of soils for optimal crop growth. The data further revealed that irrigated rice-wheat system has higher number of soils under sufficient Zn category as compared to rainfed system might be due to addition of Zn fertilizers. The maize-wheat and rice-wheat cropping system had DTPA-Fe concentration more than critical value of 4.5 mg kg⁻¹, but the concentration was significantly higher in rice-wheat system as compared to maize-wheat system. The higher soil moisture in the irrigated rice-wheat system provides favourable micro environment for higher solubility and availability of DTPA extractable Fe.

CONCLUSION

The pH, EC and SOC were higher in the irrigated rice-wheat system as compared to rainfed system. The available P, K, DTPA extractable Fe,

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Zn and Cu were higher in the irrigated system than rainfed system, while available Mn content was lower in irrigated system than rainfed system. It has also been observed that intensive cultivation has led to build up of SOC in soils under irrigated system.

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Technological Gain in Sugarcane Cultivation through Contract Farming in Odisha

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ABSTRACT

Contract farming, an agreement between farmers and processing firms for the production and supply of agricultural products under forward agreements, at predetermined prices. It also transfer technological knowledge and skills in a way that is profitable for both the contracting firms and contracted grows. This study was conducted in Dhenkanal and Nayagarh district of Odisha with a sample size of 90 contract sugarcane growers selected randomly from each selected districts aggregating 180 samples for the purpose of investigation. The study revealed that the contract sugarcane growers had deficiency on disease, pest and nutrient management. Low level of adoption was observed on use of implements, application of recommended dose of fertilizers, use of herbicides and management of ratoon crops. Socio-economic attributes such as education, social participation, extension contact, cosmopolitans, land holding had positive influence in increasing the knowledge level of the respondents. It was therefore, suggested that the contracting sugar industries should organize capacity building programmes to enrich the knowledge and adoption level of the sugarcane growers for quality production benefiting both the contracted farmers and contracting firms.

Key Words : Adoption, Contract farming, Knowledge, Sugarcane.

INTRODUCTION

Contract farming is an agreement between the farmers and a sponsor established ahead of the growing season for the production and supply of agricultural produce with a specific quantity, quality and date of delivery at a price fixed in advance. The contract assured farmers for sale of produce, extending credit, services and inputs from the purchaser or contracting agency (Kiresur *et al*, 2002). It develops markets and brings the transfer of technological skills in a way that has to be profitable for both the purchaser and farmers (Ponnusamy and Gupta, 2003). This approach would have considerable potential in countries where small scale agriculture continued to be wide spread. It facilitates the introduction of production factors like seeds, inputs, technological package and guidance by the contracting farms (Kumar and Kumar, 2008) and has immense potential in farm diversification and employment opportunity (Biswas *et al*, 2011). Contract farming in sugarcane cultivation

undertaken by various sugar factories in Odisha during early nineties is gaining popularity year after year. Quality production is the main intervention for the sustainability of contract farming. Therefore, the growers should have a knowledge and skill competency on latest developments to ensure quality production (Kumar, 2002). Hence, an attempt was made to assess the technological gain of the sugarcane growers through contract farming.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sakti Sugar Ltd. Dhenkanal has introducing contract farming approach on sugarcane cultivation in the districts of Dhenkanal, Anugul, Jajpur and Kendraparain in Odisha. Similarly; Nayagarh Sugar Complex Ltd., Nayagarh has enrolled sugarcane growers under contract farming in the district of of Nayagarh, Khurda, Puri and Jagatsinghpur. The district Nayagarh under Nayagarh Sugar Complex Ltd and Cuttack under Shakti Sugar Ltd, Dhenkanal were selected randomly for the study.

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Table 1. Involvement in sugarcane cultivation under contract farming.

Sr. No.	Period	Nayagarh District (n = 90)		Cuttack District (n = 90)		Total (n = 180)	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Last 3 year	20	22.22	21	23.33	41	22.78
2	Last 5 year	62	68.89	56	62.22	118	65.56
3	Last 7 year	6	6.67	9	10.00	15	8.33
4	Last 10 year	2	2.22	4	4.45	6	3.33

The list of farmers involved under contract farming in sugarcane cultivation was collected from both the sugarcane factories. A sample of 90 sugarcane growers from each selected districts were randomly selected covering total sample size of 180 for the purpose of investigation. Preference of cultivating sugarcane, numbers of years under contract farming, area under contract farming, important agronomic practices, knowledge level and extent of adoption were selected as the variables for the study. The data were collected personally with a semi-structure schedule pretested earlier. Appropriate statistical measures such as percentage, mean score and regression analysis were employed to analyze the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Odisha, Nayagarh Sugar Complex Ltd. established during 1989 and Shakti Sugar Ltd. in 1994. Both the sugar factories introduced contract farming in sugarcane cultivation since their establishment. It was observed (Table 1) that majority of respondents in Nayagarh (66.89%) and in Cuttack (62.22%) districts were under contract farming since last five years i.e. from 2008 onwards. Only 22.22% in Nayagarh district and 23.33%

in Cuttack district were involved under contract farming since 2010. It was, therefore, apprehended that the respondents had good association for contract farming. Contract farming system usually motivates farmers for more coverage due to assured procurement with remunerative price. The data (Table 2) revealed that 69.45 per cent of the respondents were cultivating sugarcane in an area of within 0.20 ha. Since the respondents were mostly marginal (50.56%) and small farmers (49.44%), it is concluded that the respondents were covering good area under sugarcane which indicate the benefits of the contract farming.

Preference of the respondents in cultivating sugarcane under contract farming

The data collected on scale point of less, same and better than other crops were analyzed with score value of 1, 2 and 3, respectively. As observed from (Table 3), the respondents of both Nayagarh and Cuttack district were almost of similar opinion. Relative advantage, profitability, compatibility sustainability, simplicity and predictability were the most preferred criteria in cultivating sugarcane in comparison to other crops. It indicate that the respondent had affinity towards cultivation of sugarcane may be due to contract farming system.

Table 2. Area covered on sugarcane under contract farming.

Sr. No.	Area (ha)	Nayagarh district (n = 90)		Cuttack district (n = 90)		Total (n = 180)	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Less than 0.20	60	66.67	65	72.22	125	69.44
2	Up to 0.40	20	22.22	16	17.78	36	20.00
3	Up to 0.60	7	7.78	6	6.67	13	7.23
4	Up to 0.80	3	3.33	3	3.33	6	3.33

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Table 3. Preference of cultivating sugarcane.

Sr. No.	Preference	Nayagarh District (n = 90)		Cuttack District (n = 90)		Total (n = 180)	
		Mean Score	Rank	Mean Score	Rank	Mean Score	Rank
1.	Relative advantage	2.91	I	2.96	I	2.94	I
2.	Compatibility	2.57	IV	2.60	II	2.59	III
3.	Simplicity	2.62	II	2.32	V	2.47	V
4.	Divisibility	1.89	VII	1.92	VIII	1.91	IX
5.	Observability	1.84	IX	1.87	IX	1.86	X
6.	Predictability	2.28	V	2.24	VI	2.26	VI
7.	Profitability	2.61	III	2.59	III	2.60	II
8.	Stability	1.99	VI	1.92	VIII	1.96	VII
9.	Sustainability	2.57	IV	2.49	IV	2.53	IV
10.	Equitability	1.88	VIII	2.00	VII	1.94	VIII

(Maximum Obtainable Score – 3)

Knowledge Level

The data collected on scale point of fully known, partially known and not known on various aspects of sugarcane cultivation were analyzed with score value of 3, 2 and 1, respectively. It was observed (Table 4) that the respondents of both Nayagarh and Cuttack district had better knowledge about suitability of soil type and selection of seed cane. Significant gaps observed in time of planting (47.33%), diseases of sugarcane (38.33%), pests of sugarcane (34.67%), variety (30.00%), method of planting (27.00%), nutrient management (25.33%) and treatment of seed cane (25.33%) indicating that the respondents had not adequate knowledge about sugarcane cultivation.

Extent of adoption

Practices were also collected on scale point of regularly, occasionally and not adopted and analyzed by putting score value of 3, 2 and 1, respectively. The findings revealed (Table 5) that the respondents of both the districts had better adoption of except use of implements, recommended fertilizers and manures, herbicide application, removal of water shoots, post-harvest management for ratoon crops and proper time of harvest.

It indicates the respondents of both the district were continuously growing sugarcane; they might have adopted these practices with their past experience.

Regression analysis

It is basically an approach to analyze the causal relationships between a set of causal factors and set of consequent factors. It has been observed that the best fitted regression equation could explain only 15.40% of the total variance in influencing the knowledge level of the respondents. Therefore, stepping wise regression analysis was made to locate the causal factors enhancing the knowledge level. It was observed (Table 6) that education, social participation, extension contact, cosmopolitans, holding size and use of implements exhibited positive influence in enhancing knowledge level of the respondents on sugarcane cultivation under contract farming. Sharma (2016) also reported that the farmers in the age group of 20-30 yr were found to be more interested in acquiring trainings, demonstrations and exposure visits and acquired high level of knowledge as compared to the elder group of more than 40 years of age.

Table 4. Knowledge about Sugarcane cultivation

Sr.No.	Knowledge	Nayagarh District (n = 90)		Cuttack District (n = 90)		Total (n = 180)	
		Mean Score	Gap (%)	Mean Score	Gap (%)	Mean Score	Gap (%)
1	Suitable soil type	2.90	3.33	2.87	4.33	2.89	3.67
2	Variety	2.13	29.00	2.07	31.00	2.10	30.00
3	Time of planting	1.64	45.33	1.52	49.33	1.58	47.33
4	Method of planting	2.21	26.33	2.17	27.67	2.19	27.00
5	Selection of seed cane	2.92	2.67	2.90	3.33	2.92	2.67
6	Treatment of seed cane	2.42	19.33	2.42	19.33	2.42	19.33
7	Fertilizer and manure	2.23	25.67	2.25	25.00	2.24	25.33
8	Pests of sugarcane	2.03	32.33	2.01	33.00	1.96	34.67
9	Diseases of sugarcane	1.86	38.00	1.84	38.67	1.85	38.33
10	Management practices	2.96	1.33	2.96	1.33	2.96	1.33

(Maximum obtainable score-3)

Table 5. Extent of adoption of practices in sugarcane cultivation.

Sr. No.	Practice	Nayagarh district (n=90)		Cuttack district (n=90)		Total (n=180)	
		Mean Score	Gap (%)	Mean Score	Gap (%)	Mean Score	Gap (%)
1	Use of implements	2.02	32.67	2.08	30.67	2.05	31.67
2	Good varieties	2.93	2.33	2.90	3.33	2.92	2.67
3	Seed cane treatment	2.73	9.00	2.80	6.67	2.77	7.67
4	Proper planting	2.86	4.67	2.90	3.33	2.88	4.00
5	Optimum plant population	2.74	8.67	2.73	9.00	2.74	8.67
6	Recommended fertilizers and manure	2.23	25.67	2.30	23.33	2.27	24.33
7	Herbicide application	1.63	45.67	1.61	46.33	1.62	46.00
8	Earthing up	3.00	0.00	3.00	0.00	3.00	0.00
9	Plant protection measure	2.76	8.00	2.80	6.67	2.78	7.33
10	Tying of canes	2.87	4.33	2.91	3.00	2.89	3.67
11	Proper time of harvest	2.50	16.67	2.51	16.33	2.51	16.33
12	Post harvest management	2.19	27.00	2.30	23.33	2.25	25.00
13	Removal of water shoots	1.30	56.67	1.84	38.67	1.57	47.67
14	Water management	2.90	3.33	2.90	3.33	2.90	3.33

(Maximum obtainable score-3)

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Table 6. Stepping wise regression analysis of socio-economic variables influencing knowledge level.

Sr. No.	Variable	Beta	Adj R2	R2	t Value	Probability
1.	Education X3	5.742	0.408	0.694	3.726	0.001
2.	Social participation X7	7.148	0.492	0.701	3.641	0.011
3.	Extension Contact X8	3.679	-0.504	0.723	4.607	0.005
4.	Cosmopolitaness X9	6.914	-0.571	0.806	2.912	0.011
5.	Holding size X11	7.646	-0.610	0.703	2.925	0.001
6.	Use of implements X12	2.164	0.519	0.604	3.458	0.016

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that respondents stated cultivation advantage, profitability, compatibility, sustainability and predictability as the benefits of sugarcane over other crops. Most of the respondents were cultivating sugarcane since last five years with average area of around 0.20 ha. They have better knowledge about suitable soil and selection of seed cane. Considerably deficiencies were observed towards knowledge on time and method of planting, disease and pest management, variety, seed cane treatment and nutrient management. Similarly, low adoption were observed on use of implements, recommended fertilizers and manure, herbicide application, removal of water shoots and management of ratoon crops. Education, social participation, extension contact, cosmopolitans, holding size and use of implements used by the respondents had positive influence in increasing their knowledge level. The findings, therefore suggested that the contracting sugar industries have to organize adequate capacity building programmes to enrich the knowledge and adoption level of the farmers for better production for the benefit of the contracting firms and contracted growers.

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Tissue Culture Protocol for In-vitro Propagation of Papaya (*Carica papaya* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Papaya is slowly emerging from the status of a homestead crop to that of commercial crop due to increasing awareness of multifold uses of papaya. Its cultivation is encountered with the problem of its dioecious nature. Micro propagation represents the only economic way of continuously producing uniform planting material of known sex. The studies on *in-vitro* propagation of papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) was carried out at the Department of Pomology and Floriculture, College of Agriculture, Vellayani. The propagation studies were carried out by enhanced release of axillary buds in Papaya variety Pusa Nanha. Apical buds and lateral buds from seedlings and mature plants were used as explant. Explants were subjected to different treatments of plant growth substances for culture establishment and shoot proliferation. The study revealed that full strength MS medium supplemented with sucrose 30.0 g/l and agar 6.5 g/l under light condition produced highest shoot number and longest shoot in papaya. Application of BA 0.50 mg/l along with NAA 0.1mg/l was found to be better for initial culture establishment and proliferation. Application of amino acid, glycine, 100.00 mg/l resulted in highest shoot proliferation rate, while highest shoot length was obtained from arginine 100.0 mg/l. Addition of activated charcoal 0.05 per cent and Cobalt chloride 5.0 mg/l increased the shoot proliferation rate and shoot length in papaya. *In vitro* rooting was more in full strength MS medium supplemented with IBA 3.0 mg/l, sucrose 30.0 g/l and activated charcoal 0.05 per cent.

Key Words : Explant, Micropropagation, Medium, Papaya, Shoot proliferation.

INTRODUCTION

Papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) is one of the major tropical fruit crops suited for both nutrition gardens and commercial orchards. Nutritive value, high yielding potential, year round fruiting behaviour and short pre-bearing period make papaya unique among fruit crops. Due to its multifold uses it is slowly emerging from the status of a homestead crop to that of commercial crop.

Papaya cultivation is encountered with the problem of its dioecious nature. The majority of plantations are established from seeds using dioecious cultivars. Hence seed propagation results in seedlings which are either male or female. However, the setback of propagating by seeds is the production of non-true-to-type planting materials due to the segregation of off springs at the second

filial generation, the inherent heterozygosity and dioecious nature of the plant, and the seeds of open-pollinated flowers exhibit considerable variation in shape, size and flavour and susceptibility to diseases. Moreover, as sex cannot be determined until the mid development stage, three seedlings are established in each planting position, till flowering. Then they are thinned, retaining only the most vigorous female plant with one male to every 10 to 20 female plants. This results in wastage of inputs. With a requirement to renew plantations every three year to ensure quality fruit production propagation by seed represents a significant cost to the producer.

The multiplication rates are low in the vegetative propagation methods like mound layering. Similarly asexual reproductions are also often tedious and impractical when carried out on

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large scale. Therefore to minimize these problems, efficient micro propagation of papaya has become critical for the multiplication of specific sex types of papaya. This field level problem necessitated the substitution of seedling progeny with tissue culture propagules developed from female or bisexual plants. Micro propagation represents the only economic way of continuously producing uniform planting materials of known sex (Chan and Teo, 2002) However, suitable protocols for tissue culture of papaya are to be developed to suit specific situations. Hence the present experiment was conducted with an objective of refining the existing tissue culture protocol of papaya.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The studies on *in vitro* propagation of papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) were carried out at the Department of Pomology and Floriculture, College of Agriculture, Vellayani using papaya variety Pusa Nanha. Apical buds and lateral buds from seedlings and mature plants were used as explant for *in vitro* propagation. The explants were collected from mature plants and one month old seedlings. For surface sterilization apical buds were treated with mercuric chloride (0.08 %) for 10 min. and lateral buds for 12 min. with intermittent shaking.

Explants from papaya were subjected to different treatments of plant growth substances for culture establishment. In order to standardize a suitable hormone combination for better culture establishment, studies were carried out using BA, Kinetin and NAA at various concentrations. The treatments involved were different levels of cytokinins, viz; BA (0.2 -5.0mg/l) and Kinetin (0.5-5.0mg/l) alone or in combination with auxin, viz., NAA (0.01, 0.1 and 0.5 mg/l). Six replications were kept for each treatment. The basal media used for the study were MS and half strength MS. Observations were recorded on the number of surviving cultures (percentage), number of cultures showing initial growth, number of days for bud initiation and number of buds per culture, after four weeks of culturing in the establishment media. Plant growth

substances like BA (0.2-5.0 mg/l) and Kinetin (0.5-5.0 mg/l) alone or in combination with NAA (0.01, 0.1 and 0.5 mg/l) were tried for shoot proliferation. Six replications were also kept for each treatment. The number of cultures survived (percentage), number of shoots per culture and length of the longest shoot and abnormalities in shoot growth if any, were recorded after six weeks of culturing in the shoot proliferation media.

The cultures were kept in light or in darkness in order to assess the effect of light on multiple shoot proliferation. Trials on the *in vitro* rooting were conducted in full MS medium. Individual shoots measuring 2.50-3.50 cm length, excised from shoot proliferating cultures were subjected to different rooting treatments with varying levels of IBA (0.5 - 4.0 mg/l), IAA (0.1- 2.0 mg/l) and NAA (0.1 – 3.0 mg/l). Each treatment was replicated six times. Observations on the number of cultures initiating roots, number of days for root initiation, number of roots, root length and abnormality in root growth, if any, were recorded four weeks after culturing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Various workers reported micro-propagation in papaya by enhanced release of axillary buds (Lai *et al*, 2000; Chan and Teo, 2002 and Hidaka *et al*, 2008). Explants used in the present study were apical buds and lateral buds of mature plants and one month old seedlings. Panjaitan *et al* (2007) also used similar method by using shoot tips from seedlings and lateral buds from female plants for *in vitro* propagation of papaya. Anandan *et al* (2011) also reported that establishment of seedling explants were highest when apical tips of four week old seedlings of papaya were used as explants.

Forty treatments were tried to assess the effect of plant growth substances on culture establishment of papaya. Significant difference was noticed among these treatments. Among the different plant growth substances used in the establishment medium, the earliest bud break was obtained with the application of Kinetin 1.0 mg/l in combination with NAA

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Table 1. Effect of plant growth substances on culture establishment medium of papaya.

Treatment	Plant growth substances (mg l ⁻¹)	Initial growth (%)	Survival (%)	Number of days taken for bud initiation	Number of buds initiated per culture
CE1	BA 0.00 + NAA 0.01	66.67	50.00	8.50	1.00
CE2	BA 0.00 + NAA 0.10	100.00	66.67	10.33	1.00
CE3	BA 0.00 + NAA 0.50	33.33	33.33	13.33	1.00
CE4	BA 0.20	33.33	33.33	11.00	1.00
CE5	BA 0.20 + NAA 0.01	50.00	50.00	9.17	1.17
CE6	BA 0.20 + NAA 0.10	83.33	50.00	7.33	1.00
CE7	BA 0.20 + NAA 0.50	83.33	83.33	14.83	1.17
CE8	BA 0.50	50.00	33.33	10.17	1.00
CE9	BA 0.50 + NAA 0.01	100.00	83.33	6.33	1.50
CE10	BA 0.50 + NAA 0.10	100.00	100.00	13.67	3.50
CE11	BA 0.50 + NAA 0.50	66.67	50.00	10.33	1.17
CE12	BA 1.00	66.67	33.33	7.00	1.00
CE13	BA 1.00+ NAA 0.01	50.00	50.00	13.83	1.67
CE14	BA 1.00 + NAA 0.10	83.33	83.33	11.50	1.17
CE15	BA 1.00+ NAA 0.50	83.33	50.00	15.17	1.00
CE16	BA 3.00	100.00	100.00	7.83	1.00
CE17	BA 3.00 + NAA 0.01	66.67	66.67	6.33	1.00
CE18	BA 3.00 + NAA 0.10	100.00	83.33	11.00	1.83
CE19	BA 3.00 + NAA 0.50	100.00	100.00	9.50	1.33
CE20	BA 5.00	50.00	50.00	15.33	1.00
CE21	BA 5.00 + NAA 0.01	100.0	66.67	9.67	1.00
CE22	BA 5.00 + NAA 0.10	83.33	83.33	12.17	1.00
CE23	BA 5.00 + NAA 0.50	66.67	50.00	16.33	1.17
CE24	Kinetin 0.50	33.33	33.33	8.17	1.00
CE25	Kinetin 0.50 + NAA 0.01	50.00	33.33	11.17	1.00
CE26	Kinetin 0.50 + NAA 0.10	50.00	50.00	14.67	1.83
CE27	Kinetin 0.50 + NAA 0.50	100.00	100.00	11.67	2.00
CE28	Kinetin 1.00	66.67	66.67	8.50	2.17
CE29	Kinetin 1.00 + NAA 0.01	100.00	66.67	10.83	1.00
CE30	Kinetin 1.00 + NAA 0.10	50.00	50.00	4.33	1.17
CE31	Kinetin 1.00 + NAA 0.50	66.67	33.33	11.50	1.00
CE32	Kinetin 3.00	66.67	66.67	15.67	1.33
CE33	Kinetin 3.00 + NAA 0.01	66.67	50.00	6.50	1.17
CE34	Kinetin 3.00 + NAA 0.1	83.33	50.00	15.17	1.17
CE35	Kinetin 3.00 + NAA 0.50	66.67	66.67	9.00	1.00
CE36	Kinetin 5.00	83.33	83.33	16.67	1.00
CE37	Kinetin 5.00 + NAA 0.01	83.33	50.00	13.33	1.00
CE38	Kinetin 5.00 + NAA 0.10	50.00	50.00	10.17	1.00
CE39	Kinetin 5.00 + NAA 0.50	100.00	83.33	15.00	1.00
Control		83.33	83.33	21.67	1.00
CD(0.05)				0.98	0.36

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Table 2. Effect of plant growth substances on multiple shoot proliferation of papaya.

Treatment	Plant growth substances (mg l-1)	Days for bud initiation	Number of shoots per culture	Length of longest shoot (cm)
MSP1	BA 0.00 + NAA 0.01	8.67	1.00	2.18
MSP2	BA 0.00 + NAA 0.1	5.00	1.17	1.28
MSP3	BA 0.00 + NAA 0.5	5.00	1.50	1.93
MSP4	BA 0.20	4.50	1.00	0.70
MSP5	BA 0.20 + NAA 0.01	8.17	1.00	2.15
MSP6	BA 0.20 + NAA 0.10	6.17	3.17	2.63
MSP7	BA 0.20 + NAA 0.50	3.17	1.67	1.68
MSP8	BA 0.50	4.67	2.17	2.90
MSP9	BA 0.50 + NAA 0.01	10.83	1.33	0.85
MSP10	BA 0.50 + NAA 0.10	8.67	6.50	5.78
MSP11	BA 0.50 + NAA 0.50	4.50	3.50	4.08
MSP12	BA 1.00	3.83	1.50	1.18
MSP13	BA 1.00 + NAA 0.01	7.00	1.17	2.15
MSP14	BA 1.00 + NAA 0.10	10.83	4.33	3.72
MSP15	BA 1.00 + NAA 0.50	5.33	1.00	2.05
MSP16	BA 3.00	10.83	1.50	1.53
MSP17	BA 3.00 + NAA 0.01	8.00	5.33	3.30
MSP18	BA 3.00 + NAA 0.10	12.33	1.00	0.87
MSP19	BA 3.00 + NAA 0.50	5.83	2.83	2.68
MSP20	BA 5.00	10.33	1.33	1.20
MSP21	BA 5.00 + NAA 0.01	5.83	2.67	2.05
MSP22	BA 5.00 + NAA 0.10	9.50	1.33	2.78
MSP23	BA 5.00 + NAA 0.50	12.17	1.00	1.37
MSP24	Kinetin 0.50	6.33	1.00	2.05
MSP25	Kinetin 0.50 + NAA 0.01	4.00	4.17	3.75
MSP26	Kinetin 0.50 + NAA 0.10	10.00	1.50	1.22
MSP27	Kinetin 0.50 + NAA 0.50	4.50	2.33	3.08
MSP28	Kinetin 1.00	9.67	2.17	2.22
MSP29	Kinetin 1.00 + NAA 0.01	9.67	1.00	1.05
MSP30	Kinetin 1.00 + NAA 0.10	12.83	1.00	1.40
MSP31	Kinetin 1.00 + NAA 0.50	8.50	5.33	2.07
MSP32	Kinetin 3.00	5.67	2.17	2.45
MSP33	Kinetin 3.00 + NAA 0.01	13.50	1.00	3.60
MSP34	Kinetin 3.00 + NAA 0.10	9.67	1.00	0.73
MSP35	Kinetin 3.00 + NAA 0.50	4.50	1.17	1.18
MSP36	Kinetin 5.00	10.00	1.00	1.28
MSP37	Kinetin 5.00 + NAA 0.01	11.50	1.00	2.62
MSP38	Kinetin 5.00 + NAA 0.10	8.50	1.67	1.18
MSP39	Kinetin 5.00 + NAA 0.50	6.00	1.00	3.10
Control		-	1.00	0.55
CD (0.05)		1.09	0.62	0.2

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0.1 mg/l. In a similar experiment, Rohman *et al* (2007) used Kinetin 1.0 mg/l for better establishment of papaya explants. Highest bud initiation was recorded from BA 0.5 mg/l along with NAA 0.1 mg/l (Table 1). The result of the present study was in agreement with the observations of Priyakumari (2001) who observed that MS medium supplemented with BA 0.5 mg/l and NAA 0.1 mg/l gave the highest number of bud initiation in establishment medium. This may be due to the fact that BA and its combination with auxin induced more bud initiation as reported by Suthamathi *et al* (2002). Increase in level of cytokinin than auxin favoured bud initiation in papaya (Kabir *et al*, 2007). The above reports were thus in agreement with the results of the present studies.

Application of BA 0.5 mg/l along with NAA 0.1 mg/l was found to be better for shoot proliferation in papaya (Table 2). The results of the present experiment were in line with the findings of Adigo *et al* (2015) who reported that maximum number of shoots in papaya variety Rajshahi-red was produced from shoots cultured in MS medium supplemented with BA 0.5 mg/l along with NAA 0.1 mg/l. Full strength MS medium produced highest shoot proliferation rate, better survival of plantlets in papaya variety Pusa Nanha. This was in agreement with the findings of Lai *et al* (2000), who reported that MS medium at full strength was used for the micro-propagation of papaya. Similar results as suitability of full MS medium for *in*

vitro propagation of papaya was also reported by Suthamathi *et al* (2002) and Usman *et al* (2002).

Sucrose 30.0 g/l in shoot proliferation medium produced maximum number of shoots and also resulted in better survival and further elongation of shoots.. These results were supported by findings of Fitch and Maureen (2003) who observed that sucrose 30.0 g/l was effective for micro-propagation of papaya. Suthamathi *et al* (2002) also reported that MS medium supplemented with sucrose 30.0 g/l increased multiple shoot proliferation in papaya.

The study revealed that agar 6.0 g/l produced highest shoot number in papaya. The addition of optimum agar concentration creates an osmotic potential favorable for the uptake of nutrients. The probable reason may be the enhanced absorption of nutrients from the media due to the lowered osmotic potential. A change in agar concentration affects the nutrients in culture media as well as over all nutrient concentration in the experiment (Protul *et al*, 2012). The results of the study showed that the highest shoot length was noticed by the addition of agar 6.5 g/l in papaya.

In the present study amino acids arginine and glycine at different concentrations were supplemented to the media, to study the shoot proliferation rate. Maximum shoot proliferation and better survival was noticed with the addition of amino acid glycine, 100.0 mg/l (Table 3). It was observed that at higher concentrations of arginine and glycine, there was a significant reduction in

Table 3. Effect of amino acids on multiple shoot proliferation of papaya.

Treatment	Amino acids	Survival (%)	Shoots per culture	Length of longest shoot (cm)
GL1	Glycine-50.00	66.67	2.67	0.75
GL2	Glycine-100.00	100.00	3.50	2.37
GL3	Glycine-200.00	66.67	1.17	0.27
AR1	Arginine-50.00	83.33	2.33	1.87
AR2	Arginine-100.00	100.00	4.50	0.63
AR3	Arginine-200.00	100.00	2.00	0.35
Control		66.67	3.67	2.05
CD (0.05)			1.01	0.10

shoot number and shoot length. This may be due to antagonistic effect of these amino acids when the concentration exceeds optimum level.

Addition of activated charcoal 0.05 per cent (Table 4) increased shoot proliferation rate and shoot length in papaya. Activated charcoal adsorbs the toxic substances and residual cytokinin from the medium (Ming *et al*, 2007). Shoot elongation occurring by the addition of activated charcoal may be attributed to the adsorption of phytohormones on activated charcoal. The result of the present experiment was in confirmity with findings of Adigo *et al* (2015) also, who observed that activated charcoal 0.05 per cent was ideal for the *in vitro* propagation of papaya. Cobalt chloride 5.0 mg/l increased shoot proliferation rate and shoot length in papaya, while the highest survival percentage was obtained with the addition of Cobalt chloride 10.0 mg/l. Fitch and Maureen (2003) added ethylene inhibitors amino ethoxy vinyl glycine (AVG) and Cobalt chloride (CoCl₂) to the culture medium of papaya and the results indicated that shoot proliferation rates enhanced by 23 per cent and 49 per cent respectively. The present experiment also showed similar results. The present study revealed reduced shoot number and length of shoots in control plants. This finding was in line with the observations of Hidaka *et al* (2008) who observed that ethylene accumulation is deleterious to culture growth and development.

Light had significant influence on shoot proliferation. The trial revealed that cultures under light produced maximum number of shoots and increased shoot length in papaya. Better survival

of plants was also observed under light conditions. The shoots and leaves appeared pale and chlorotic under dark conditions. This can be attributed to the lack of chlorophyll development required for photosynthesis and in turn shoot regeneration, which might have contributed to the reduced rate of shoot proliferation of cultures under dark. The positive effects of light was observed by Kabir *et al* (2007) and Protul *et al* , 2012 .

Among the various plant growth substances tried for *in vitro* rooting, full strength MS medium supplemented with IBA 2.0 mg/l induced early rooting. The above results from the present study are in line with the findings of Rogayah *et al* (2012) who reported that full strength MS medium was ideal for *in vitro* rooting of papaya. Highest number of roots was obtained by the addition of IBA 3.0 mg/l in papaya (Table 5). Anandan *et al* (2011) reported that in papaya under *in vitro* conditions, application of IBA 3.0 mg/l promoted highest number of roots. The present experiment also showed similar result. Highest number of roots was noticed with the addition of sucrose 30.0 g/l to the rooting medium. Similar studies of Fitch and Maureen (2003) showed that highest *in vitro* rooting in papaya was obtained by adding sucrose 30.0 g/l to the rooting medium. This finding was in confirmity with the observations of the present study. The beneficial effect of high sucrose concentration might be because the optimum level of sucrose for root formation depends on a balance between the sucrose and total nitrogen in the medium. Addition of activated charcoal 0.05 per cent to the rooting medium induced early rooting and highest number

Table 4. Effect of activated charcoal on multiple shoot proliferation of papaya.

Treatment	Activated charcoal (%)	Survival (%)	Shoots per culture	Length of longest shoot (cm)
AC1	0.05	100.00	5.50	1.82
AC2	0.10	83.33	3.50	0.27
AC3	0.20	83.33	1.00	0.65
Control		100.00	1.67	1.13
CD (0.05)			0.95	0.13

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of root. Panjaitan *et al* (2007) reported that presence of activated charcoal stimulated rhizogenesis in papaya. Improved rooting response has been observed in many instances when activated charcoal was included in the medium (Rogayah, 2012). This might be because activated charcoal adsorbs the toxic substances and cytokinins inhibitory to rooting.

CONCLUSION

The refined tissue culture protocol of papaya revealed that apical buds and lateral buds from mature plants and seedlings could be used as explants for *in vitro* propagation. However, explant for papaya is apical bud. For surface sterilization of explants, apical buds should be treated in 0.08 per cent mercuric for ten minutes and for lateral buds it is twelve minutes. Application of BA 0.5 mg/l along with NAA 0.1 mg/l was found to be better for initial culture establishment. The culture establishment medium is useful for conditioning of the explant and for stimulating its initial growth.

The study revealed that full strength MS medium supplemented with sucrose 30.0 g/l and agar 6.0 g/l, amino acid arginine 50.0 mg/l, activated charcoal 0.05 per cent, Cobalt chloride 10.0 mg/l was is ideal. For multiple shoot proliferation combined application of BA 0.5 mg/l along with NAA 0.1 mg/l was found to be the best. Cultures placed under light produced maximum number of shoots and increased shoot length in papaya. Better survival of papaya plants also was observed under light conditions. For *in vitro* rooting, full strength MS medium supplemented with IBA 3.0 mg/l and sucrose 30.0 g/l is found promising. Improved rooting response has been observed when activated charcoal 0.05 per cent was included in the medium.

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Table 5. Effect of plant growth substances on *in vitro* rooting of papaya.

Treatment	Plant growth substances (mg l-1)	Rooting (%)	Number of roots	Length of longest root (cm)
R1	IBA 0.50	66.67	-	-
R2	IBA 1.00	33.33	2.00	2.23
R3	IBA 2.00	66.67	1.17	2.70
R4	IBA 3.00	100.00	6.33	3.28
R5	IBA 4.00	-	2.50	1.13
R6	IAA 0.10	50.00	-	-
R7	IAA 0.50	83.33	1.00	0.88
R8	IAA 1.00	66.67	4.17	2.42
R9	IAA 2.00	33.33	2.33	1.60
R10	NAA 0.10	-	-	-
R11	NAA 0.50	83.33	3.17	1.37
R12	NAA 1.00	66.67	1.00	2.85
R13	NAA 2.00	83.33	1.33	2.08
R14	NAA 3.00	33.33	3.50	1.47
Control		-	-	-
CD (0.05)			0.47	0.13

Plate 1. Bud initiation of papaya in culture establishment medium

Plate 2. Multiple shoot formation of papaya in shoot proliferation medium

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Use of Soil Test Crop Response Approach in Direct Seeded Rice

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ABSTRACT

To assess the soil test crop response (STCR) based nutrient management in direct seeded rice (DSR), demonstrations were conducted at five farmer's field during kharif 2015-16 in Tunga Bhadra Command area of Raichur, India. Three technology options (TO) were assessed and were TO1: Farmers' practice (Imbalanced fertilization (250:155:133 kg/ha), TO2: Recommended package of practices (100:50:50 kg/ha) and TO3: STCR equation based application of fertilizers (targeted yield: 75 q/ha). The grain and straw yield of DSR (variety BPT 5204) was found higher in TO3 (70.70 and 79.94 q/ha, respectively) and increase was to the tune of 21.5 and 21.4 per cent over TO2. The higher B:C ratio was recorded in the TO3 (2.97) and was higher by 14.67 per cent over TO1 (2.59). After harvest of crop, it was observed that there was build up of available N, P₂O₅ and K₂O in plots with TO3 in all the five farmers field. These results clearly indicated that application of fertilizers to crops based on soil test values and target yield approach was effective in getting the higher yield.

Key words: Nutrient management, STCR, Direct seeded rice, Target yield.

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa*), the staple food of more than half of the population of the world, is an important target to provide food security and livelihoods for millions. Imminent water crisis, water-demanding nature of traditionally cultivated rice and climbing labour costs ramble the search for alternative management methods to increase water productivity, system sustainability and profitability. Direct seeded rice (DSR) technique is becoming popular nowadays because of its low-input demanding nature. It offers a very exciting opportunity to improve water and environmental sustainability. To get more and more yield farmers tend to use excess and heavy doses of fertilizers but on other hand they are neglecting the soil health deterioration. Also in some cases application of fertilizers by the farmers in the field without knowledge on soil fertility status and nutrient requirement by the crop causes adverse effects on soil and crop regarding both nutrient toxicity and deficiency either by over use or inadequate use.

Soil test crop response (STCR) based N application caused significantly higher nutrient uptake over the rest of treatments and was comparable with 150 kg

N/ha application in four splits plus green manure 6.25 t/ha (Ramesh *et al*, 2008). Application of N based on STCR enhanced significantly the growth and yield attributing characters viz., plant height, leaf area index (LAI), dry matter production, total tillers/ m², panicle length, productive tillers, total number of grains per panicle over other nitrogen management practices. The treatment with N application based STCR realized the target yield (Ramesh and Chandrashekar, 2007). Srinivasan and Angayarkanni (2008b) reported that application of fertilizers based on STCR equation will result in build up of nutrients in the soil. Hence the present investigation was undertaken where STCR approach of fertilizer application was compared with farmers practice and recommended dose of fertilizers application. In this contest, soil test based application and target yield approach will help to provide the required amount of nutrient to the crop and increases the crop uptake and in turn higher yield can be expected.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The investigation was conducted at five farmer's field to assess the STCR based nutrient management

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in DSR during kharif 2015-16 at Manvi taluka of Raichur district of Karnataka (TBP command area). Three technology options (TO) assessed were TO1: Farmers practice (Imbalanced fertilization (250:155:133 kg/ha), TO2: Recommended package of practices (100:50:50 kg/ha) and TO3: STCR equation (targeted yield: 75 q/ha). In each farmers field 0.5 acre plots were made for each technical options. The source for TO2 was University of Agriculture Sciences, Dharwad and Raichur and for TO3 was AICRP STCR, Bengaluru. Initial soil samples from each farmer's field were collected and analyzed for pH, EC, available N, P2O5 and K2O. Based on these soil test values (Table 1) and target yield (75 q/ha) the fertilizers were calculated using STCR equation (Table 2) and added to plot with TO3.

The DSR with variety BPT 5204 (Sona Masuri) was selected for present investigation and seed rate used was 60 kg/ha. Fifty per cent of Nitrogen fertilizer and 100 per cent of phosphorus and potash fertilizers were applied as basal dose and remaining 50 per cent of nitrogen fertilizer was applied in 2 split doses. During the crop growth period, growth and yield parameters were recorded and after harvest of crop soil samples were drawn separately from each TO plots in each farmers field and analyzed for pH, EC, available N, P2O5 and K2O.

Table 1. Initial soil available N, P2O5 and K2O

Farmers	Available N (kg/ha)	Available P2O5 (kg/ha)	Available K2O (kg/ha)
F1	165	38	385
F2	212	32	390
F3	245	36	410
F4	178	39	402
F5	158	36	397

STCR based nutrient application

Based on the soil test available N, P2O5 and K2O, the required quantity of fertilizer to attain the target yield of 75 q/ha was calculated (Table 2). The fertilizer prescription to attain specific yield targets based on soil available nutrient levels for the experimental field were as follows:

Target yield equation

$$FN=3.45T-0.29SN \text{ (KMnO}_4\text{-N)}$$

$$FP2O5=2.82T-1.70SP2O5 \text{ (Olsen's P2O5)}$$

$$FK2O=2.00T-0.09SK2O \text{ (NH}_4\text{OAC-K2O)}$$

Where,

- SN is soil test Nitrogen
- SP2O5 is soil test P2O5
- SK2O is soil test K2O
- T is Target yield here 75 q/ha is used

Table 2. Calculated FN, FP2O5 and FK2O based on soil test values, using target yield equation.

Farmers	Calculated fertilizers for each farmers		
	Urea (kg)	DAP (kg)	MOP (kg)
F1	334	319	192
F2	295	342	191
F3	280	327	188
F4	327	316	190
F5	335	327	190

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the experiment indicated that the number of tillers and panicles per square meter were observed higher in the TO3 (422 and 358, respectively) and was higher by 29 and 19 per cent, respectively over TO1. Similarly, grain and straw yield was found higher in TO3 (70.70 and 79.94 q/ha, respectively) and increase was to the tune of 21.5 and 21.4 per cent over TO2 (Table 3). Singh et al (2014) reported that targeted yield of rice (45 q/ha) and (50 q/ha) was achieved by using the plant nutrients on the basis of targeted yield concept (soil test crop response technology). The present results were in accordance with the study conducted by Singh et al (2017) and revealed that among the treatments, STCR-INM recorded relatively higher yield, benefit: cost ratio and per cent achievement than other treatments. The post-harvest soil organic carbon and soil available N, P and K status indicated the build-up and maintenance of soil fertility due to soil test based fertilizer recommendation under INM.

Use of Soil Test Crop Response Approach

Table 3. Influence of nutrient management on growth and yield of DSR (average of five farmers).

Treatments		No. of tillers/ m ²	No. of panicles / m ²	% BPH incidence	Grain Yield (q/ha)	Straw Yield (q/ha)
T1	Farmers practices (250:155:133 kg/ha)	327	300	14	66.47	75.11
T2	RPP (100:50:50 kg/ha)	375	313	12	58.23	65.80
T3	STCR equation (Targeted yield 75 q/ha)	422	358	12	70.75	79.94

The higher B : C ratio was recorded in the TO3 (2.97) which was higher by 14.67 per cent over TO1 (2.59). The gross and net returns in TO1 were Rs. 1,06,352/- and Rs.65,254/-, respectively (Table 4) where as in TO3 the higher gross and net returns were obtained (Rs.1,13,194/- and Rs.75,064, respectively). Chaubey *et al* (2015) reported that the net returns from the improved practice (STCR technology) were substantially higher than the farmers' practice (GRD) for both the hybrid rice and improved rice. After harvest of crop, soil samples from each TO were collected and subjected to chemical analysis. It was observed that there was buildup of available N, P₂O₅ and K₂O in plots with TO3 in all the farmers filed (Fig 1, 2 & 3). These results clearly indicate that application of fertilizers to crops based on soil test values and target yield approach was effective in getting the higher yield, probably due to balanced application of nutrients to the crop. This results were in accordance with study conducted by Srinivasan and Angayarkanni (2008a). The application of fertilizers based on soil test improved the performance of rice crop along with enhanced soil organic carbon, available macronutrients and soil microbial enzyme activities as compared to the application of general

recommendation of fertilizers (Rajput et al, 2016).

Figure 1: influence of nutrient management on soil available nitrogen status after harvest of crop

Figure 2: influence of nutrient management on soil available phosphorus status after harvest of crop

Table 4: Influence of nutrient management on economics of DSR (average of five farmers)

Treatments		Grain Yield (q/ ha)	COC (Rs./ ha)	GR (Rs./ ha)	NR(Rs./ha)	BC Ratio
T1	Farmers practices (250:155:133 kg/ha)	66.47	41098	106352	65254	2.59
T2	RPP (100:50:50 kg/ha)	58.23	35325	93162	57837	2.64
T3	STCR equation (Targeted yield 75 q/ha)	70.75	38130	113194	75064	2.97

Figure 3: influence of nutrient management on soil available potassium status after harvest of crop

Legend:

T1	Farmers practices (250:155:133 kg/ha)
T2	RPP (100:50:50 kg/ha)
T3	STCR equation (Targeted yield 75 q/ha)
F	Farmer

CONCLUSION

The nutrient requirement by the crop is based on the fact that there is significant linear relationship between nutrient uptake and grain yield. It shows that for required grain yield production, a definite quantity of nutrient must be absorbed by plant. Once the nutrient requirement for a given yield target is known, the fertilizer requirement can be calculated taking in to account the efficiency of soil and fertilizer nutrients. The STCR technology was effective in changing attitude, skill and knowledge of farmers. Further, it can be said that DSR with suitable conservation practices has potential to produce slightly lower or comparable yields as that of transplanted rice (TPR) and appears to be a viable alternative to overcome the problem of labour and water shortage. Despite controversies, if properly managed, comparable yield may be obtained

from DSR compared with TPR. It would be good if the capabilities of farmers to manage natural resources in sustainable manner are enhanced and rice productivity is increased through developing knowledge and technology of direct seeding by way of research and extension activities.

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Varietal Performance of Turmeric (*Curcuma Longa L.*) in Chamarajanagar District of Karnataka

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted during 2012-13 and 2013-14 to evaluate and identify superior and most promising variety of Turmeric suitable for Chamarajanagar district. Five varieties of turmeric viz., Chaitanya, IISR Prabha, IISR Pratibha, IISR Allepy supreme and Chamarajanagar local varieties were evaluated. Average data of two years revealed that the variety IISR Pratibha recorded highest fresh (345.43 q/ha) and cured rhizome (70.36 q/ha) yield followed by IISR Allepy supreme and IISR Prabha, while in curing percentage IISR Allepy supreme (22.3%) was found to be superior followed by IISR Prabha and IISR Pratibha. With regard to rhizome numbers and their length, IISR Pratibha produced more number of rhizome (10.75), maximum length (10.12 cm) and girth (2.13 cm) followed by IISR Allepy supreme. The varieties IISR Prabha, IISR Pratibha and IISR Allepy supreme were found to be early duration types (230.75 to 234.50 d) compared to Chaitanya and Chamarajanagar local, which matured relatively late (265.13 to 269.81 d). IISR Pratibha recorded significantly highest per day productivity (149.11 kg/day) followed by IISR Allepy supreme (134.12 kg/day). With respect to curcumin content, IISR Allepy supreme recorded highest (5.73%) followed by IISR Pratibha (5.20%). Over and all, IISR Pratibha and IISR Allepy supreme excelled.

Key Words: Turmeric, varieties, Cured rhizome, Curcumin content, Fresh rhizome, Productivity, Curing percentage.

INTRODUCTION:

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa L.*) is one of the most important spice crops in India and plays a vital role in national economy. Though wide genetic variability exists in this crop with regard to the yield and yield attributes, however, not much work has been done on crop improvement through the selection of superior types with high yield, high quality and earliness in southern dry zone of Karnataka. Chamarajanagar falls under southern dry agro climatic zone-VI of Karnataka with turmeric as a major spice crop of the district, presently growing in an area of 9000 ha (Anonymous, 2013-14). Most of the Turmeric growers are growing local varieties which are low yielding (15-18 t/ ha of fresh rhizome), long duration (280-290 d) and are low in curcumin content (2-3%). Hence, the present study was carried out to evaluate and identify superior, most promising variety of turmeric suitable for

Chamarajanagar district with regard to yield, yield components, earliness and quality aspects.

MATERIALS METHODS

The field experiments were conducted at farmer's field at Chamarajanagar district during the year 2012-13 and 2013-14. The trials were laid out in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with four replications using five varieties of turmeric namely Chaitanya, IISR Prabha, IISR Pratibha, IISR Allepy supreme and Chamarajanagar local variety. The plot size was 20 m x 10 m (1481 plants) and rhizomes were planted during third week of May during each year on ridge and furrow method with a spacing of 45 cm x 30 cm. The observations on vegetative growth, yield and yield attributes, earliness, curcumin content were recorded during both the years and pooled analysis was done. All agronomic practices viz., irrigation, mulching,

weeding, fertilizer application, manuring were done according to the recommendation of University of Horticulture Science, Bagalakot for turmeric production. The crop was harvested at different periods of the year based on the maturity (maturity indices followed were leaf drying and falling of plants) from January to March. Vegetative growth parameters like plant height, number of leaves, number of clumps, yield parameters like number of rhizomes, length and girth of rhizome, fresh rhizome yield, cured rhizome yield, curing percentage and quality attribute (curcumin content) of different varieties were recorded from five randomly selected and tagged plants in each replication. Mean values were computed. Curcumin content was done by following the procedure outlined by Manjunath *et al* (1991). Curing percentage was computed by considering the loss of weight in rhizome after curing and the difference expressed as percentage. The data obtained were statistically analysed following statistical procedures outlined by Gomez and Gomez (1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Vegetative growth

Significant differences were noticed among the varieties with respect to plant height, number of clumps and number of leaves at different stages of crop growth (Table 1). Variety IISR Pratibha recorded more number of leaves (29.18), number of clumps (7.29) and highest plant height (126.96 cm) at all the stages of crop growth followed by IISR Allepy supreme and IISR Prabha. Chamarajanagar local recorded less number of leaves (21.11) and lowest plant height (105.31 cm) at final stage of the crop growth.

Yield and quality of turmeric

Significant differences were noticed for yield, yield attributes and quality of turmeric (Table 2). Highly significant variations between the cultivars for fresh and cured yield and quality of turmeric were noticed. Further, it was found that yield attributing characters such as rhizome length, girth,

number and curing percentage varied significantly among cultivars.

The most important yield contributing character in turmeric was number of rhizomes and their size. More number of rhizomes per plant were produced by IISR Pratibha (10.75) followed by IISR Allepy supreme (9.43) and IISR Prabha (8.67). However Chaitanya and Chamarajanagar local produced less number of rhizomes per plant (5.73 and 5.85, respectively).

The length of the rhizomes varied from 7.14 cm in Chaitanya to 10.13 cm in IISR Pratibha, whereas rhizome girth at centre varied from 1.57 cm in Chamarajanagar local to 2.13 cm in IISR Pratibha. IISR Allepy supreme and Prabha produced thick and large rhizomes, whereas short and thin rhizomes were observed in Chaitanya and Chamarajanagar local. Choudhary *et al* (2006) reported 5 to 11 rhizomes in variety Sudharshan and Krishna.

The data (Table 2) evidenced highly significant variation among turmeric types with regard to the yield of fresh rhizomes per hectare and percentage recovery of the cured produce. Variety IISR Pratibha produced significantly more fresh rhizomes (345.44 q/ha) than all other varieties followed by IISR Allepy supreme (314.39 q/ha), whereas the variety Chamarajanagar local recorded significantly lower fresh rhizome yield (225.56 q/ha). Similar results were obtained by Venkatesha and Siddalingayya (2016).

It was noted that IISR Pratibha and IISR Allepy supreme produced bold, plumpy, thick and larger rhizomes and attained higher green yield. Length and girth of rhizomes correlated positively with the green yield (fresh rhizome yield) because of higher weight due to higher girth and the plants with longer primary rhizome naturally produced more secondary rhizomes and consequently the yield was high.

Curing percentage is an important factor as the fresh rhizomes are to be cured to obtain marketable turmeric. Maximum recovery of the cured produce was recorded in IISR Allepy supreme (22.3 %)

Varietal Performance of Turmeric

Table 1. Plant height, number of clumps, number of leaves of turmeric varieties at different stages of crop.

Particulars	Plant height (cm)				Number of clumps				Number of leaves						
	45 DAP	75 DAP	105 DAP	135 DAP	Final stage of the crop	45 DAP	75 DAP	105 DAP	135 DAP	Final stage of the crop	45 DAP	75 DAP	105 DAP	135 DAP	Final stage of the crop
Chaitanya	14.53	26.87	56.53	83.84	110.01	3.26	4.40	4.73	5.14	5.48	-	9.92	12.27	15.19	21.19
IISR Prabha	13.64	28.56	69.95	91.96	116.67	3.86	4.81	5.41	6.47	6.73	-	10.05	12.95	18.83	26.19
IISR Pratibha	15.98	30.44	77.28	110.14	126.96	3.80	5.01	6.63	7.04	7.29	-	10.40	13.29	20.92	29.19
IISR Allepy supreme	14.30	28.81	68.89	99.08	121.54	3.65	4.91	6.09	6.67	6.91	-	10.28	13.04	12.12	26.62
Chamarajanagar Local	12.53	26.58	54.19	87.74	105.31	3.06	4.39	4.78	5.23	5.75	-	9.93	12.28	16.05	21.11
SEM	0.32	0.15	0.31	1.40	0.82	0.054	0.061	0.057	0.060	0.070	-	0.07	0.08	0.16	0.33
CD @ 0.05 %	0.93	0.42	0.90	4.05	2.39	0.16	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.20	-	0.21	0.24	0.49	0.99
'F' test	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	-	*	*	*	*

Table 2. Studies on yield and yield attributes of turmeric varieties.

Particulars	Corresponding Author's Email:	Length of the rhizome (cm)	Girth of the rhizome (cm)	Gross yield of fresh rhizome (q/ha)	Curing percentage	Cured turmeric (q/ha)	Crop duration (Days)	Curcumin content	Per day productivity (kg/day)
Chaitanya	5.73	7.14	1.57	22.58	16.91	3.84	265.01	3.11	85.19
IISR Prabha	8.67	8.16	1.71	30.21	21.02	6.36	230.75	4.89	130.96
IISR Pratibha	10.75	10.13	2.13	34.54	20.42	7.04	232.06	5.26	149.11
IISR Allepy supreme	9.42	9.01	1.98	31.43	22.30	6.95	234.37	5.73	134.12
Chamarajanagar Local	5.84	7.61	1.56	22.55	17.31	3.97	269.65	3.11	83.65
SEM	0.08	0.11	0.02	0.19	0.12	0.06	0.48	0.05	0.84
CD @ 0.05 %	0.25	0.33	0.06	0.56	0.36	0.19	1.40	0.17	2.43
'F' test	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

followed by IISR Prabha (21.02 %) and IISR Pratibha (20.42 %). Cured turmeric is also one of the important attributes in grading the turmeric produced for export and domestic market. The yield of cured produce per hectare was found to be maximum in IISR Pratibha (70.4 q/ha) followed by IISR Allepy supreme (69.6 q/ha), whereas comparatively low yield was recorded in Chaitanya (38.4 q/ha) and Chamarajanagara local (39.7 q/ha). The variation in rhizome characters, fresh yield and recovery percentage among various turmeric varieties could be due to genetic factors rather than the environmental conditions as reported by Subharayadu *et al* (1976).

The curcumin content was found to be maximum in variety IISR Allepy supreme (5.73 %) followed by IISR Pratibha (5.21 %), whereas comparatively low curcumin content was recorded in Chaitanya and Chamarajanagar local (both 3.11 %). The varieties IISR Prabha, IISR Pratibha and IISR Allepy supreme were found to be early duration types (230.75 to 234.38 d) compared to Chaitanya and Chamarajanagar local which were matured relatively late (265.06 to 269.66 d, respectively).

Duration of the variety correlated positively with per day productivity because of the earliness and more yield. Variety IISR Pratibha recorded significantly highest per day productivity (149.11 kg/day), followed by IISR Allepy supreme (134.12 kg/day) and IISR Prabha (130.96 kg/day), whereas, comparatively low per day productivity was recorded in Chamarajanagar local (83.65 kg/ha) and Chaitanya (85.19 kg/day).

CONCLUSION

The variation in vegetative characters, rhizome characters, fresh rhizome yield, recovery percentage, cured rhizome yield, curcumin content, earliness among various turmeric varieties could be due to genetic factor rather than the environmental condition. Thus it can be concluded that among the turmeric varieties evaluated under Chamarajanagar condition, the variety IISR Pratibha produced highest fresh and cured rhizome yield, highest number and maximum length and girth of rhizomes, whereas, maximum curing percentage was observed in the variety IISR Allepy supreme. Further, the varieties IISR Prabha, IISR Pratibha and Allepy supreme were found to be early duration types as compared to Chaitanya and Chamarajanagar local. Hence, these three varieties can be recommended for turmeric growers of Chamarajanagar district.

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Yield Realization of Different *Brassica* Cultivars under Central Plain Zone of Punjab

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ABSTRACT

The experiment was laid out using randomized block design with 8 treatments and 3 replications during rabi 2016-17. Treatments comprised of 8 cultivars of Brassica sown at the KVK Kapurthala farm in order to evaluate the yield potential of these cultivars under central plain zone of Punjab conditions. The crop was sown on 10th November 2016 and harvested during 1st fortnight of April 2017. The study revealed that minimum duration was taken by YSH 0401 (141.0 d) and maximum by RH 749 (154.9 d). The data also showed that there was no significant difference in seed yield levels between 4 cultivars (RH 406, NRCDR 2 and NRCHB 101 and GSC 7), whereas, these were significantly higher yielder than other cultivars. Productivity on per day basis was calculated and found that maximum productivity was observed in NRCHB 101 (15.5 kg/ha/d) and lowest in YSH 0401 (9.1 kg/ha/d).

Keywords: Brassica, Cultivars, Maturity, Productivity, Punjab, Seed yield

INTRODUCTION

In India, Rapeseed and mustard (*Brassica* spp.) is the second most important edible oilseed after groundnut sharing 27.8 per cent in India's oilseed economy with 32 per cent of the total oilseed production in the country (Thakur and Sohal, 2014). Brassicaceae family consists of 338 genera and 3709 species. The production and yield of rapeseed and mustard increased from 6.66 MT and 1017 kg/ha in 2000-01, the country witnessed yellow revolution through a phenomenal increase in production and productivity to 7.66 MT and 1185 kg/ha in 2010-11 (Singh and Kothari, 2013).

To meet the ever growing demand of oil in the country, the gap is to be bridged through management techniques. Optimum crop geometry, balanced NPK fertilizers, intercultural operations and inclusion of farmyard manure are the building blocks for achieving the utmost yield targets of rapeseed-mustard. Effective management of natural resources, integrated approach to plant-water, nutrient and pest management and extension of rapeseed mustard cultivation to newer areas under

different cropping systems will play a key role in further increasing and stabilizing the productivity and production of rapeseed-mustard to realize 24 MT of oilseed by 2020 A.D.

Despite the high quality of oil and also its wide adaptability for varied agro-climatic conditions, the area, production and yield of rapeseed-mustard in India have been fluctuating due to various biotic and abiotic stresses coupled with India's domestic price support programme due a vast variability in climatic and edaphic conditions in mustard growing areas of India, so, the selection of appropriate cultivars is important for increasing the productivity (Anjum et al, 2005).

The tremendous increase in oilseed production could be attributed to development of high yielding cultivars coupled with improved production technology, their widespread adoption and good support price. Sometimes, selection depends upon the quality of the produce, as; Gobhi Sarson cultivars such as GSC 6 and GSC 7 became popular among the farmers due to less than 2 per cent erucic acid content. These are a long

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duration cultivars confined to Haryana, Punjab and Himachal Pradesh. It had good yield potential with wide adaptability and possesses high oil content of good quality (Shekhawat *et al*, 2012). Therefore an effort was made to evaluate the yield realization of different *Brassica* cultivars under central plain zone of Punjab.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Six cultivars of Brassica were procured from Directorate of Rapeseed and Mustard, Bharatpur, Rajasthan (DMR) during rabi 2016-17 and two Gobhi Sarson cultivars (GSC 6 and GSC 7) released from PAU, Ludhiana were evaluated at the KVK Kapurthala farm in order to assess the yield potential of these cultivars under Punjab conditions (Table 1). The experiment was laid out using randomized block design with 8 treatments and 3 replications. The seeds were sown on 10th November 2016 at 30 cm row to row spacing by hand drill. Two thinning operations were done at 15 and 30 days after sowing (DAS), whereas, two hand weeding were done at 25 and 40 days after sowing. The fertilizers were applied in quantity @ 225 kg of urea and 187.5 kg of single super phosphate (SSP) per ha. Half amount of the urea and full dose of SSP were applied at the time of sowing and remaining half of the urea was applied at 25 days after sowing. One application of Confidor @ 100ml/ha was done

in 250 of water at 100 DAS in order to control attack of aphid and jassids and Ekalux was sprayed @ 625 ml/ha for control of tobacco caterpillar at 45 and 120 DAS. The experimental plot was harvested on 4 to 14th April 2017, depending upon the maturity of cultivar. The seed yield data were calculated and analyzed by using online OPSTAT software (Sheoran *et al*, 1998).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study revealed that all the cultivars were of different duration varying between 141-155 d. Minimum duration was taken by YSH 0401 (141 d), although GSC 6 was also early maturing cultivar with 145.3 d required for maturity (Table 2). Maximum duration was taken by RH 749 (154.9 d), which was statistically at par with GSC 7 (154 d).

On comparing the yield realized from different cultivars (Table 2), it was observed that maximum seed yield was obtained with RH 406 (23.4 q/ha) followed by NRCDR 2 (22.8 q/ha) and NRCHB 101 (22.8 q/ha). the data also revealed that there was no significant difference between 3 cultivars of DRMC (RH 406, NRCDR 2 and NRCHB 101) and one cultivar of PAU (GSC 7) with 21.4 q/ha, whereas, these were significantly higher yielded than other cultivars namely DRMRIJ 31 (21.2 q/ha), RH 749 (16.1 q/ha), GSC 6 (14.9 q/ha) and YSH 0401 (12.8 q/ha).

Table 1. Information on Brassica cultivars used under study.

Sr. No.	Variety	Common Name	Botanical Name	Developing Institute	Oil content (%)
1	RH 406	Indian Mustard	<i>Brassica juncea</i> L.	CCS HAU, Hisar	40.0
2	NRCDR 2	Indian Mustard	<i>Brassica juncea</i> L.	DRMR, Bharatpur	36.5-42.5
3	NRCHB 101	Indian Mustard	<i>Brassica juncea</i> L.	DRMR, Bharatpur	34.6-42.1
4	GSC 7	Gobhi Sarson	<i>Brassica napus</i> L.	PAU, Ludhiana	40.5
5	DRMRIJ 31	Indian Mustard	<i>Brassica juncea</i> L.	DRMR, Bharatpur	42.0
6	RH 749	Indian Mustard	<i>Brassica juncea</i> L.	CCS HAU, Hisar	39.0
7	GSC 6	Gobhi Sarson	<i>Brassica napus</i> L.	PAU, Ludhiana	39.1
8	YSH 0401	Indian Mustard	<i>Brassica rapa</i> L. var. Yellow Sarson	CCS HAU, Hisar	43.0-45.0

Yield Realization of Different *Brassica* Cultivars

Table 2. Seed yield obtained from different *Brassica* cultivars.

Sr. No.	Variety	Time taken to maturity (Days)	Yield (q/ha)	Productivity (kg/ha/d)
1	RH 406	153.1	23.4	15.3
2	NRCDR 2	148.0	22.8	15.4
3	NRCHB 101	146.7	22.8	15.5
4	GSC 7	154.0	21.4	13.9
5	DRMRIJ 31	152.3	21.2	13.9
6	RH 749	154.9	16.1	10.4
7	GSC 6	145.3	14.9	10.3
8	YSH 0401	141.0	12.8	9.1
	C.D.	0.9	2.1	1.4

As the time taken for maturity varied for 14 days and there was difference in seed yield obtained as well in different cultivars of *Brassica* (Table 2). In order to conclude precisely, productivity on per day basis was calculated and found that maximum productivity was observed in NRCHB 101 (15.5 kg/ha/d) followed by NRCDR 2 (15.4 kg/ha/d), RH 406 (15.3 kg/ha/d), GSC 7 (13.9 kg/ha/d), DRMRIJ 31 (13.9 kg/ha/d), RH 749 (10.4 kg/ha/d), GSC 6 (10.3 kg/ha/d) and lowest in YSH 0401 (9.1 kg/ha/d).

CONCLUSION

Minimum time taken to maturity was with YSH 0401 followed by GSC 6 and maximum by RH 749, GSC 7 and RH 406. Out of 7 cultivars, 3 cultivars of DMR, viz., RH 406, NRCDR 2 and NRCHB 101 was statistically at par with GSC 7 in seed yield. Moreover, GSC 7 variety of *Brassica* is canola type and had higher oil quality which is most suitable for human consumption. These 3 cultivars from DMR were having statistically higher productivity per ha per day as compared to all other cultivars. So, these 3 cultivars can be further evaluated at farmer's field to increase adaptability of these cultivars in central plain zone of Punjab. In order to popularize these cultivars popular among farmers, there is a need to establish mini agro processing units at the village level, so that farmers can sell their raw produce in the village itself. It is worth to mention that infact there is MSP declared by Govt of India for oilseed

crops but there is no purchaser in the market at the prescribed MSP, as a result of which there is great difficulty in convincing the farmer to adopt this crop in place of other rabi crops especially wheat.

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Short Communication

Effect of Demonstration on Use of Paddy Straw Baler in Raichur District

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INTRODUCTION

About 620 MT of rice straw produced in 2008 in Asia and now approximately 731MT per year rice straw is produced globally (Africa: 20.9 million tons, Asia: 667.6 million tons, Europe: 3.9 million tons, America: 37.2 million tons, and Oceania: 1.7 million tons). After China, India is the larger producer of paddy. India produces 98 MT of paddy with roughly 130 MT of straw. Of this, about half is used as animal fodder. The rest is mostly burnt in the fields, though a small amount is also used by brick kilns and paper and packaging industry. However, because of continuous failure of rainfall, the farmers are unable to go for rice-rice cultivation practice, and thus there is heavy demand for the paddy straw as fodder for the animals. In such conditions, transporting the straw in condensed form with lesser cost becomes a challenge. Farmers find that, the transportation of rice straw is very difficult because of bulkiness and cost of transportation.

Paddy is a major crop in Raichur district, cultivated over one lakh ha area including *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. According to the statistics available with the department of Agriculture (2014-15) per ha production of rice is about 6500 kg/ha and average straw production is about 4 t/ha. Collection and management of rice straw is a major challenge for the environmental and economic reasons. Collecting this huge amount of straw manually is a major challenge for the farmers because of the labour shortage and also due to bulkiness. This straw stored as well as stored fodder. Because of the mechanization in rice, when

the rice is harvested by combine harvester, it leaves a significant length of straw in the field. For the preparation of the land for the next season and in a hurry to prepare the land for the next crop farmers find it easy to burn the straw. Increasing labour cost is another reason farmers prefer setting fire to their paddy fields after harvesting the crop. As an answer to these challenges, KVK, Raichur introduced, paddy straw baler in the farmers fields under front line demonstration (FLD) on mechanization of paddy from 2014-15 to 2016-17 with the objectives to study the extent of adoption of paddy baler, to assess the drudgery of women in manual collection of paddy straw and to study the utilization pattern of straw after baling.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Radha Krishna Camp of Harvi village, Gudadinni camp of Manvi taluka and Kasabe camp, Vijayanagar camp of KVK Raichur were selected consecutively during 2014-15 and 2015-16 and 2016-17 for the study. This area was purposively selected because these camps were inhabited by Andra migrants with major area under paddy. During 2014-15, front line demonstration were conducted at 5 farmers' fields in Radha Krishna Camp on mechanization in paddy, during 2015-16, demonstrations on paddy baling using the baler available with the department of Agriculture were conducted at the Gudadinni camp of Manvi Taluka for a group of 100 farmers and during 2016-17, FLDs were carried out in Vijayanagar Camp to popularize the baling of paddy straw. The

Table 1. Impact of demonstration on Horizontal spread of paddy straw baler in Raichur.

Particular	Before demonstration	After demonstration
No. of balers	Available at Yantradhare scheme- a custom hiring centre established in selected hoblis by Karnataka State Department of Agriculture	Seven farmers have purchased apart from custom hiring centre.
Area under straw baling	1-2 ha.	>220 ha.
Compactness	3 trips	1 trip
Cost of baling (Rs/ha)	4100/-	3500/-
Straw recovery (Per cent)	60	90
Labour requirement (hr/ha)	24	4
Knowledge scores (Per cent)	2	95

knowledge of farmers regarding the baling and adoption of densification was assessed using focus group discussion method. The knowledge was imparted on baling through demonstration, group discussion, method demonstration, interactions with department and university scientists.

Similarly, ergonomic assessment was done using Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) scale developed by Hignett and McAtamney (2000) for a group of ten women agricultural labours who constituted control group and were collecting the straw manually. The labour required, time consumed for baling, recovery of the straw with baler and conventional method, extent of adoption of this cost economics were calculated. Same group pre and post tests assessments were compared in adoption of paddy baler.

Drudgery of women in manual collection of the straw was assessed using the pulse rate and

ergonomic assessment by REBA. The pulse rate of the respondent before and after working was recorded by inserting her thumb in the slot provided with the fingertip Pulse oximeter instrument. This simple device was used to assess the respiratory function of individual as influenced by the activity and resulting in fluctuation of pulse beats. Oximetry is a test used to measure the oxygen level (oxygen saturation) of the blood. A clip-like device called a probe is placed on a body part, such as a finger or ear lobe. The probe uses light to measure how much oxygen is in the blood. Information on utilization pattern of the straw was assessed through focus group discussion. The results were compiled and analyzed accordingly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results indicate that, during 2014-15 there was not a single baler in the Raichur district but after conducting the demonstrations, the number of baler

Field views of demonstration of paddy straw baler

Paddy fields after harvesting with combine harvester

Demonstration of round type baler for densification of paddy straw

Field view after baling straw

Use of Paddy Straw Baler in Raichur District

machines increased to 7 numbers. The capacity of each baler during the peak season varied between 5000 bales to 3500 bales. Thus, a total of 28,000 bales were produced. Average bales per hectare varied from 100-150. So, an average of 220 ha of paddy straw was baled. It reduced the cost from Rs. 4100/- to Rs.3500/-ha and the recovery of the straw also increased from 60 to 90 per cent with the use of paddy straw baler. This round type baler yielded about 100-150 bales /ha with average weight of the bale about 15-18 kg.

Table 2. Comparison of Drudgery scores between manual collection and baler

Treatments	Drudgery	
	Pulse rate	REBA Score
Manual collection of paddy straw	77-98	14

The drudgery scores (REBA) revealed that, manual collection of straw was highly drudgery prone activity as compared to baling. Though mechanical work cannot be compared with the manual work, the computation of drudgery scores for manual collection of straw indicated that, highest drudgery was experienced by women in bending, repeated movement of limbs while collecting the straw. This might lead to musculoskeletal disorders among women. Fluctuations in the pulse rate in doing this activity also indicated physical exertion in carrying out this activity. Acceptance of this technology was indicated by increased number of paddy straw balers. However, cost of the straw balers need to be reduced, so that all the farmers can adopt this technique of densification or should be made available on custom hiring basis at the village level.

Table 3. Utilization pattern of paddy straw in Raichur

Sr. No.	Pattern of Utilization	Percentage of utilization
1	Animal feed	98%
2	Puffed rice units and other packaging material	02%

The results of group discussion with the farmers revealed that, about 98 per cent of the straw was used as animal feed and only 2 per cent was used for other purposes like puffed rice units and package material. However, farmers revealed that these bales were sold at the rate of Rs. 2500/- tractor load if harvested by combine harvesters, and Rs. 1500/-tractor load if harvested by chain link machines. In their opinion there is heavy demand for this straw from neighboring districts also.

CONCLUSION

These results imply the need to introduce paddy straw baler in paddy growing areas as one of the components of custom hiring centre. The efforts may also be supplemented by the Department of Animal husbandry and veterinary sciences to enrich the straw before baling so as to enable the cattle to get required nutrients. After animal feed the excess straw may be fully utilized for production of energy.

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*Short Communication***Evaluation of Alternate Rice Variety for Replacement of BPT 5204 Suitable for Samba Season in Southern Zone of Tamil Nadu****M Kathiravan¹ and C Vanitha²**

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ABSTRACT

In Pudukkottai district, Rice is the major crop which is cultivated nearly on 75,000 ha in rabi season (Sep-Oct). In this season, very old and most disease susceptible variety BPT 5204 is predominantly used by Pudukkottai farmers which has become susceptible to attack of insect pest and diseases. To overcome this problem, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pudukkottai conducted on farm testing (OFT) on alternative rice variety for BPT 5204 during 2015-16. Five trials were laid out at different locations in Pudukkottai. Critical inputs of Paddy varieties like CO 50 and TKM 13 were distributed to the farmers. The parameters like per cent disease incidence (PDI), productive tillers and yield (q/ha) were recorded. The results revealed that rice variety TKM 13 recorded the lowest PDI (5.64) compared to control BPT 5204 (18.84), number of productive tillers was also higher (15.6) in TKM 13 and thus higher (60.04 q/ha) yield was recorded compared to control (54.14 q/ha). It was concluded that, farmers were satisfied with Rice TKM 13 variety due to lower pest and disease incidence and higher yield.

Key Words: Percent Disease Incidence, Productive tillers, Rice, Samba season, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L) is the most important grain with regard to human nutrition and caloric intake, providing more than one-fifth of the calories consumed worldwide by humans. Rice is the principal crop extensively cultivated in all the districts of the Tamil Nadu having a unique three-season pattern viz., Kuruvai (April to July), Samba (August to November) and Summer (December to March).

In Tamil Nadu, rice is cultivated in an area of 17.26 lakh ha with the production of 71.15 lakh tonnes. In Pudukkottai district, rice is the major crop which is cultivated nearly in 75,000 ha during samba season. In this season, very old and most disease susceptible variety, BPT 5204 is predominantly grown by Pudukkottai farmers which increase the plant protection cost, leads to reduction in yield and income. To overcome this problem, Krishi Vigyan

Kendra, Pudukkottai conducted an on farm testing (OFT) on assessment of alternative high yielding Samba Rice variety for replacement to BPT 5204.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

On Farm Trails were conducted at Aranthanki, Manamelkudi and Aavudaiyarkovil blocks of Pudukkottai where direct sowing of rice was followed. The trial was conducted at five locations. Three technological options were imposed for this on farm trail and critical inputs of rice varieties viz., CO 50 and TKM 13 were distributed to the farmers.

Table 1. Technological Options.

Technology Option	Variety	Source of technology
TO 1	BPT 5204	Farmers' practice
TO 2	CO 50	TNAU
TO 3	TKM 13	TNAU

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Table 2. Characteristics of Rice varieties selected for On Farm Trial.

Name of the variety	Characters of the variety
Rice CO 50	Parentage : CO 43 / ADT 38, hybridization and pedigree method of selection Duration : 130 – 135 d Season : Late samba / Thaladi Yield : 6338 kg/ha [10.11% increased over ADT(R)46] Moderately resistant to blast, sheath blight, brown spot, bacterial leaf blight and rice tungro disease
Rice TKM 13	Parentage: WGL 32100 /Swarna Duration: 130 days (which is 7-10 d earlier than BPT 5204) Season : Late samba / Thaladi Yield: 5938 kg/ha Moderately resistant to leaf folder, stem borer, green leaf hopper, blast, rice tungro disease, brown spot and sheath rot.

Table 3. Performance of Rice varieties at farmers’ field (Average of five trials).

Sr. No.	Parameter	BPT 5204	CO 50	TKM 13
1.	Percent disease incidence (Blast)	18.84	7.10	5.64
2.	Productive tillers (Nos.)	12	14	15
3.	Yield (q/ha)	54.1	59.0	60.0
4.	BCR	2.43	2.65	2.71

The observations viz., percent disease incidence (PDI), productive tillers (Number), Yield (q/ha) and benefit to cost ratio (BCR) were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result (Table 3) revealed that, among the three varieties evaluated, rice TKM 13 recorded the lowest percent disease incidence (5.64) compared to control BPT 5204 (18.84), more productive tillers (15.6) in rice TKM 13 and lowest in control BPT 5204 (12.0). Similarly, rice TKM 13 recorded the highest yield of 60.04 q/ha which was 10 per cent more over the control BPT 5204 (54.1 q/ha) followed by CO 50 (59.0 q/ha). Among these varieties, rice TKM 13 registered the highest benefit:cost ratio (2.71:1) compared to control BPT 5204 (2.43). The findings were in agreement with Banumathy *et al* (2016)

CONCLUSION

Rice variety TKM 13 recorded more number of productive tillers which is the most important yield contributing parameter, lowest percent disease incidence which reduced the plant protection cost, higher yield and higher BC ratio. Hence, Farmers were satisfied with TKM 13 cultivation. Moreover, it matures in 130 d which is 7-10 d earlier than BPT 5204. Since the grain is of very fine quality; it has more commercial value and high marketable price. Hence, it is concluded that TKM 13 is the suitable rice variety alternate to BPT 5204 during samba season for rice cultivating area of Pudukkottai district.

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Short Communication

Evaluation of Ridge Gourd (*Luffa acutangula* (Roxb) L.) Genotypes for Higher Yield

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INTRODUCTION

Ridge Gourd (*Luffa acutangula* (Roxb.) L.) is a monoecious and highly cross pollinated important tropical cucurbitaceous vegetable crop cultivated throughout India. Every 100g of the edible portion of ridge gourd contains 0.5g of fiber, 0.5 percent of protein, 0.35 percent of carbohydrate, 37 mg of carotene, 5.0 mg of vitamin c, 18 mg of calcium and 0.5 mg of Iron (Hazra and Som, 2005). There are number of cultivars available with wide range of variability in shape of fruits. The yield potential of existing cultivars is low and there are several factors responsible for low yield of ridge gourd in Tamil Nadu. Lack of high yielding variety is one of the main reasons for low yield of ridge gourd. In nut shell, to improve the yield and for developing a new variety, collection and evaluation of germplasm is a pre requisite in a specific crop improvement programme. Hence, an effort was made to identify the potential cultivar with desirable growth and yield parameters.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at Department of Horticulture, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai during November 2013 to Nov, 2015. A total of 20 genotypes collected from different parts of Tamil Nadu were used for this study. The details of the genotypes were LA 1(PKM 1), LA 2 (Co 1), LA 3 (Chekkanurani Local), LA 4 (Usilampatti Local), LA 5(Kallampatti Local),

LA 6 (Melur local), LA 7 (Periyakottai Local), LA 8 (Alagargoil Local), LA 9 (Sivagangai Local), LA 10 (Thirumangalam Local), LA 11(Sedapatti Local), LA 12 (Virudhunagar Local), LA 13 (Kinnimangalam Local), LA 14 (Vedasanthur Local), LA 15 (Ottanchatram Local), LA 16 (Alathur Local), LA 17 (Kannapatti Local), LA 18 (Natham Local), LA 19 (Seranma Devi Local) and LA 20 (Srirampuram Local). These genotypes were evaluated during Nov, 2013, October 2014 and August 2015. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with three replications. The crop was raised by digging pits at a spacing of 2 m between rows and 1.5 m between plants and the vines were trained on trails system. The growth and yield parameters viz., first female flower node, days to first female flower opening, number of fruits per plant, fruit length, fruit diameter, fruit weight, yield per plant were recorded. The data collected in three years were pooled and subjected to statistical analysis adopting standard procedures of analysis (Panse and Sukhatme, 1967).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean performance of different genotypes evaluated for growth and yield characters is presented in table 1. The earliness is one of the important parameters for good variety which is measured in terms of days to first female flower anthesis and node at which first female flower appears. Among the 20 genotypes, LA15 recorded the earliest flowering (52.67 d) followed by LA6

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Table 1. Mean performance of ridge gourd genotypes.

Name of genotypes	First Female flower node	Days taken for first female flowering	Number of fruits / plant	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit diameter (cm)	Individual fruit weight (g)	Fruit yield per plant (kg)
LA1	18.43	119.67	28.58	21.81	24.37	292.00	4.63
LA2	23.17	113.33	31.17	25.83	34.10	576.33	9.37
LA3	20.97	103.70	32.03	24.66	34.97	268.00	4.65
LA4	23.33	113.27	32.27	26.31	35.77	495.33	8.39
LA5	20.73	118.67	30.40	23.96	33.77	482.33	5.88
LA6	17.90	98.33	31.47	22.42	36.67	360.00	7.02
LA7	20.80	110.83	31.57	24.39	28.53	539.33	8.09
LA8	22.80	117.67	30.97	25.52	33.83	422.33	7.19
LA9	22.57	115.07	29.37	24.83	26.00	460.67	7.14
LA10	21.30	109.67	28.37	23.66	35.30	338.00	4.85
LA11	20.23	117.07	29.00	23.16	28.68	252.67	3.91
LA12	18.10	120.33	29.63	21.94	29.70	432.00	8.81
LA13	20.13	110.32	31.00	23.76	29.50	461.67	7.79
LA14	21.27	114.13	29.73	24.09	30.28	486.67	4.49
LA15	11.23	52.67	11.50	11.32	11.53	176.67	2.60
LA16	21.98	124.40	28.93	24.30	36.23	516.00	7.59
LA17	16.57	121.78	29.90	21.01	33.40	215.33	3.45
LA18	19.23	103.07	31.40	23.29	31.63	544.00	6.23
LA19	23.27	117.20	33.47	26.67	29.83	377.67	5.70
LA20	23.47	127.40	29.44	25.46	31.20	525.00	4.09
S Ed	0.55	2.79	0.81	1.84	1.07	18.84	0.46
CD	1.12	5.65	1.65	3.52	2.17	38.13	0.93

(98.33 d) and LA18 (103 d) and late flowering was observed is LA 20 (127 d). Similar results for variability in earliness were reported by Allirani and Jansirani (2014).

The node at which the female flower appears also decides the earliness of the variety. Among the 20 genotypes LA15 recorded the earliest female flowering node (11.23) followed by LA17 (16.57) and LA6 (17.90). The late flowering was observed is by LA20 (23.47). The number of fruits per plant

decides the yield per plant. Among the 20 genotypes the mean value ranged from 11.50 to 33.47. The highest number of fruits per plant was recorded by the genotype LA19 (33.47), followed by LA4 (32.27), LA3 (32.03).

The fruit length is also one of important factor which decides yield as well marketability of the fruits. The maximum fruit length was recorded by the genotype LA19 (26.67 cm) followed by LA4 (26.31 cm), LA2 (25.83 cm) and the least number of

Evaluation of Ridge Gourd

fruits was recorded in LA15 (11.32 cm). The mean fruit diameter ranged from 11.53 to 36.67 cm. The genotype LA6 recorded the maximum fruit diameter (36.67cm) followed by LA16 (36.23 cm) and LA4 (35.77cm). The minimum fruit diameter of 11.53 cm was recorded in LA15. The mean fruit weight varied significantly among the genotypes. The mean fruit weight ranged between 176.67 g to 576.33 g among the genotypes. The genotypes LA1 (576.33 g) recorded the highest value followed by LA 18 (544 g) and LA 20 (525 g). The genotype LA 15 (176.67 g) registered lesser fruit weight among the twenty genotypes. The yield per plant is one of most important factor for yield potential. The fruit yield per plant in the twenty genotypes ranged between 2.60 to 9.37 kg. The genotype LA 2 recorded the highest yield (9.37 kg) per plant followed by LA 12 (8.81 kg) and LA 4 (8.39 kg). The genotypes LA 15 (2.60 kg) recorded lower fruit yield per plant. Similarly variation in yield per plant was reported by Allirani and Jansirani (2014) in ridge gourd.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that among the twenty genotypes evaluated, LA 2 recorded highest yield

(9.37 kg / plant) followed by LA 12 collected from Virbhunagar (8.81 kg / plant). LA 15 collected from Ottanchatram recorded earliness in first female flowering node and first female flowering days (11th node and 52.67 d). The genotype LA 19 collected from Seranmadevi recorded high number of fruits per plant (33.47 Nos.), fruit length (26.67 cm), individual fruit weight (377.67g) with the average yield of 5.7 kg per plant. The genotype LA 1 (PKM 1), LA 18 (Natham Local) and LA 20 (Sreerampuram Local) recorded highest fruit weight (576.33 g, 544 g and 525 g, respectively). The high yielding genotype LA 2 recorded 31.17 number of fruits per plant and individual fruit weight of 576.33 g.

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*Short Communication***Prevalence of Mastitis in Goats****Vandna Bhanot¹, O P Mehla², Kamaldeep³ and Rajnish Kumar⁴**Disease Investigation Laboratory
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Near Court Road, Ambala City -134 003 (Haryana)**INTRODUCTION**

Mastitis is an inflammation in the udder and can occur in any lactating animal. Even non lactating animals can harbour this infection. Goats can have variety of symptoms or none at all. Any abnormality in milk may signal mastitis: clotted, stringy, bloody, off colour, off flavour, and reduced production. Mastitis in goats occurs throughout the year both in clinical and subclinical forms in sporadic outbreaks in livestock farms (Ameh *et al*, 1993). In clinical mastitis, there are changes in milk colour, clots are present in the milk, and there are large numbers of leukocytes in the milk. Swelling, heat, pain, and indurations may be observed in the mammary gland in clinical cases; these symptoms can be detected by visual observation of the udder. In subclinical mastitis, there are no clinical signs of disease other than an increased somatic cell count in the milk, the presence of pathogenic organisms in the milk, and an inflammatory response that can only be detected by screening or laboratory tests. Obviously subclinical mastitis is one of the most important infectious diseases in small ruminants. Furthermore, subclinical mastitis represents a constant risk of infection for the whole stock. As there is a need for higher milk yields and more stringent requirements on milk quality in dairy goat herds, udder infections must be prevented or detected at an early stage not only to protect the farmer but rather the consumer. Moreover, the greatest problem in the treatment

and control of mastitis is the emergence of drug resistance due to indiscriminate use of antibacterial drugs. This paper describes prevalence of clinical and sub-clinical mastitis in goats in Ambala district of Haryana.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Study animal**

The study was undertaken in different villages of district Ambala. The study animals were randomly selected lactating goats in the district. The study involved 186 (65 Beetel cross, 36 Jamunapari and 85 Non-descript) randomly selected lactating goats in the district. Milk samples from animals were collected aseptically. The first few streams of milk were discarded and about 10 ml milk samples were collected in sterile tubes, labelled as L or R (L for left halves and R for right halves). The milk samples were transported in an ice box with ice to the laboratory.

Assessment of clinical and sub-clinical mastitis:

Clinical mastitis was assessed by palpation and visualization of the udder, and diagnosed if the udder was red, hard, or hot to touch. Mild Clinical Mastitis was judged visually by slight or moderate swelling, indurations of one or more quarters, and a visibly abnormal secretion, including clots, revealed by the use of a strip-cup.

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Sub-clinical mastitis

Sub-clinical mastitis was assessed by the California mastitis test (CMT) using 15 per cent Teepol. Briefly, in each well of the test plate, 2 ml of milk was stripped from individual teats and an equal amount (2 ml) of 15 per cent Teepol was added to the milk. A circular motion was made with the plate for 10 seconds to mix the reagent and milk, and after 20 seconds, changes in the milk were observed. The formation of milk clots upon addition of the reagent was recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, overall prevalence of mastitis in goat was recorded 136 (73.1%). Clinical mastitis was detected in 12 (6.4%) of the lactating goats and subclinical mastitis 124 (66.6%) in lactating goats. The low level of clinical mastitis may be partly associated with the fact that dairy goats with clinically observable mastitis are either treated or culled. The results were in close agreement with Bawaskar *et al* (2011). However, in present study, higher incidence were observed than those reported by Yadav *et al* (1982) and White and Hinkley (1999) whereas, these findings were at a lowered degree than those reported by Swarup and Prabhudas (1985) and El-Idrissi *et al* (1994). The observation was further classified as follows: Breed wise 39 (60%) Beetel cross 19 (52%) and Jamunapari 66 (77.6%). Nondescript breeds were found positive for subclinical mastitis. Lactation

wise high prevalence of subclinical mastitis was recorded in third lactation 65 (52.4%) followed by second (28.2%) and first (19.3%).

CONCLUSION

The overall prevalence of mastitis in goat was recorded 136 (73.1%). Non-descript breeds were more prone as compared to Beetel cross and Jamunapari. The occurrence of subclinical mastitis increased with increase in lactation. The maximum incidence of lactation was found in third lactation.

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Short Communication

Technological Intervention for Improving the Breeding and Production Performance of Desi Pigs

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INTRODUCTION

Pig farming in rural villages is mainly in the hands of resource poor and economically weaker sections of society. They are mainly focussed in the rearing of native black pigs which provide them marginal income for their livelihood. Local or indigenous pigs constitute the bulk of pig population in India with poor growth rate and productivity and are reared under extensive and scavenging system and to a lesser extent in a semi-intensive system under subsistence farming, with few or no inputs (Seth et al, 2014) The desi pigs are allowed to roam freely in the villages scavenging on vegetable and human waste and are housed only during night time in the house backyard. These pigs grow at a leisure pace and attain marketing weight of 50 -60 kg at 10-12 months of age thus the productivity of these pigs is low. The expenditure incurred towards the input cost provided to these pigs is comparatively less and the return obtained through sale of desi pigs is also low.

In recent years, due to change in the consumer preference and life style, the demand for the pork and pork products is continuously increasing and has encouraged young entrepreneurs to start pig rearing on a commercial scale as an income generating activity. Therefore, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Kattupakkam conducted an on-farm trial by providing the resource poor pig farmers with Large white Yorkshire boars for improving the breeding

performance and to enhance the productivity of desi pigs.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in two villages of Kncheepuram district of Tamil Nadu. The data on production parameters were collected through direct observation and also through discussion with pig farmers. The farmers who were involved in desi pig rearing using desi boars for breeding for more than a decade were selected for the study. They were provided with Large white Yorkshire boars produced at Piggery unit of Post Graduate Research Institute in Animal Sciences, Kattupakkam, to cross breed the desi sows in the Technology option 1 and the data on the performance indicators were assessed. Similarly, in the Technology option 2 the existing technology of crossing of desi sows with desi boars was carried out to study the breeding and production parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Breeding parameters

With regard to the breeding parameters in the Technology option 1 involving cross breeding of desi sows with Large White Yorkshire boars, the mating percentage and farrowing percentage was observed as 60 and 90 per cent, respectively. The average number of piglets per farrowing was recorded as 8.2. The mating percentage and

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Table 1 . Breeding and Production parameters of the technological options assessed.

Sr. No.	Breeding parameter	Large white Yorkshire boar	Desi boar
1.	Mating percentage	60	55
2.	Farrowing percentage	90	75
3.	Average no of piglets/ farrowing	8.2	8.4
4.	Birth weight of piglets (kg)	0.92	0.56
5.	Weaning weight (kg)	7.80	5.20
6.	B:C ratio	1.92:1	1.84:1

farrowing percentage with regard to the Technology option 2, wherein traditional pig breeding involving desi boars and sows was carried out was found to be 55 and 75 per cent, respectively, and the average number of piglets per farrowing was recorded as 8.4.

Production parameters

In Technology option 1, the birth weight of individual newborn piglets was 0.92 kg, while the weaning weight at eight weeks of age was 7.8 kg, whereas in the case of technology option 2 involving desi pigs, the birth weight and weaning weight of piglets was found to be 0.56 kg and 5.20 kg. Higher body weight was noticed in crossbred followed by Desi pigs (Gopinathan and Usha, 2011). The purebred Yorkshire sows and their crossbred litters are better than purebred Duroc and their cross breeds in terms of litter size at birth, and at weaning, (Arganosa et al, 1991). Higher body weight and average daily gain were noticed in Large White Yorkshire followed by crossbred and Desi pigs throughout the period of study. The data revealed that the breeding performance of poor productive desi pigs were improved considerably by crossing desi sows with Large White Yorkshire boars. The production performance of cross bred piglets was also significantly higher than desi piglets.

The two technological options were also compared on the economic front (BCR) with the parameters gross cost, expenditure and net returns. The results implied that the benefit cost ratio in the technology option 1, where cross breeding technology was employed using LWY boars was found to be 1.92 : 1 while the BCR in technology

option 2 involving desi boar was found to be 1.84 : 1 (Table 1).

CONCLUSION

The results revealed that with regard to the breeding parameters, the mating percentage and farrowing percentage was observed as 60 and 90 per cent, respectively and the average number of piglets per farrowing was recorded as 8.2. The birth weight and weaning weight of piglets was found to be 0.92 kg and 7.80 kg, respectively. The economic analysis of the study revealed that the benefit cost ratio for the technological intervention of cross breeding of desi pigs with Large white Yorkshire boars was higher than pure breeding of desi pigs. To improve the productivity of desi pigs and to improve pork production, cross breeding technology using Large White Yorkshire boar is recommended for large scale adoption due to the factors like easy adoption, cost effectiveness and improved performance parameters like higher individual birth weight and weaning weight of piglets.

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Message

Dear readers,

Ushering this edition in the year 2017 with NAAS rating elevated from 2.77 to 4.41 in a year's span itself is complimentary and commendable to share. From the sidelines of political potpourri the drive which we all Indians, must join being a citizen of India is "Swatch Bharat".

I hereby do not endorse or promote any political agenda but believing that it has become a must, since we are the second most populated nation for the heck of good health of our future - for our children. We must have health and hygiene as our principle responsibility in all its measures.

Do we not need to keep our environment clean! What about unhealthy eating and littering habits! Government is trying through public media about use of toilets and sanitation but how far is its implementation.

Should we not come forward to monitor at least in area where we are working, residing or even commuting. Yes, Please lets be vigilant and police defaulters with bad habits of spitting on roads, puking here and there, throwing eats and surplus out in open. Smoking of cigarettes, bidies, tobacco for that matter must be banned if not possible then at least not be allowed in public. We need to leave a legacy of good habits mainly of clean thoughts , clean mind and clean environment.

I humbly pray that all Indians give it a due thought and make the nation worth living atleast for our future generations.

Wishing you all joining Swatch Bharat Campaign in your own way but to a meaning.

Thanks & Regards

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of stylized loops and a long horizontal stroke.

Shabnam Sharma, Principal,
CBSE Senior Secondary School
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First subheadings are placed in a separate line, begin at the left margin, and are in italics. Text that follows should be in a new paragraph.

Second Subheadings should begin with the first line of a paragraph, indented and in italic. The text follows immediately after the second subheading.

Contents: The contents must be arranged in an orderly way with suitable headings for each subsection. The recommended subdivision of contents is as follows:-

Running head: The running head or short title of not more than 50 characters, in title case and centered should be placed above the main title of the study.

Title: The title must be informative and brief. The initials and name of the author(s), the address of the host institution where the work was done must follow the title.

Superscripts (1,2,3) should be used in cases where authors are from different institutions. The superscript # should be appended to the author to whom correspondence should be addressed, and indicated as such together with an e-mail address in the line immediately following the keywords. The present postal address of authors, if currently different from that of the host institution should also be superscripted appropriately and inserted in the lines following the key words.

Abstracts: It must summarize the major objectives, methods, results, conclusions, and practical applications of the study conducted. The Abstract must consist of complete sentences and use of abbreviations should be limited.

Keywords: The Abstract is followed by three to five keywords from the title to be used for subject indexing. These should be singular (e.g. paper, not papers). The abstract, including key words should be separated by horizontal lines placed before and after the text.

Introduction: This should include a statement of why the subject under investigation is considered to be of importance, a concise indication of the status quo of published work in this field and a declaration of the aims of the experiment or study i.e. the hypothesis.

Materials and Methods: These should be concise but of sufficient detail to enable the experiment to be replicated by an outside party. Particular care should be taken to ensure that the appropriate statistical analyses have been carried out. Specify the design used, factors tested or the statistical model employed. Non significant differences ($P > 0.05$) should not be discussed.

Results and Discussion: Results and discussion should be combined to avoid repetition. It should be presented in a logical sequence in the text, tables and figures. The repetitive presentation of the same data in different forms should be avoided. The discussion should consider the results in relation to any hypotheses advanced in the Introduction and place the study in the context of other work.

Conclusion: The conclusion should consist of a short integration of results that refer directly to the stated aims of the experiment and a statement on the practical implications of the results.

Acknowledgements (optional): A brief and formal acknowledgment section, if desired, should follow the conclusion statement. Do not include titles of persons; such as Dr., Mr., or Ms., use only initials and surnames.

References: The existing relevant literature restricted to those with a direct bearing upon the findings must be appropriately cited.

References appearing in the text – References in the text should be given as : Sharma and Rao (1983). Use “and” and not “&”. A reference by three or more authors should be identified in the text only by the first author followed by *et al* (in italic) and the year.

Where several references are quoted consecutively in the text, the order should be chronological or, within a year, alphabetical (by first author or, if necessary, by first and second author(s)).

Where references are made to several papers by the same author(s) in the same year, the year should be followed by a, b, c, etc.

Personal communications and unpublished work should be cited in the text only and not in the reference list, giving the initials, name: for example (M. S. Gill, unpublished), (M.S. Gill, personal communication).

References to internet sites should be quoted in the normal way in the text e.g. FDA (2008). In the reference list, the full URL must be given, followed by the date that the website was assessed.

References appearing in reference section : All publications cited in the text should be presented in the list under Reference section, in alphabetical order. The title of the article should be given in the reference and journal's name should be cited in *italic* as abbreviated by the journal. It is the full responsibility of the authors to cross check reference in the text of the article with those in the list of references. In all cases, a reference must provide sufficient information to enable the reader to locate it.

Examples of references – (Hanging indent 1 cm)

For journals/periodicals

Mufeed S (1998). Evaluating employee performance: A successful instrument for human resource development. *Indian J Trg and Dev* 28 (2): 72-93.

For books

AOAC (1980). Official Methods of Analysis. 13th edn. Association of Official Analytical Chemists. Washington, DC.

For Chapters in book

Barnabas A P and Lakshmiswaramma M (1980). “Assessment of Evaluation system for Rural development”. In: *Monitoring and Evaluation of Rural Development: Some Asian Experiences*. (eds Kuldeep Mathu and Inayatulloah) Kuala Lumpur U.N. Asian and Pacific Development Centre. Pp: 121-22.

Bray R A (1994). The leucaena psyllid. In: *Forage Tree Legumes in Tropical Agriculture* (eds. R C Gutteridge and H M Shelton). CAB International, Oxford. Pp. 283-91.

For proceedings of conferences/symposia etc.

Vivero J L P (2002). Forest is not only wood: the importance of non-wood forest products for the food security of rural households in Ethiopia. In: *Proceedings of the Fourth, Annual Conference forestry society of Ethiopia* 14-15 January 2002, Ethiopia pp 102.

Elangovan A V ,Tyagi P K, Mandal A B and Tyagi P K (2007). Effect of dietary supplementation of stain on egg production performance and egg quality of Japanese quail layers. *Proceedings of XXIV Annual Conference of Indian Poultry Science Association and National Symposium* , 25-27 April, Ludhiana, India, pp. 158 (Abstr.).

For theses

Fayas A M (2003). Viability of self help groups in vegetables and fruit promotion council Keralam- a multidimensional analysis, MSc (Ag.) thesis, Kerala Agricultural University.

For online (internet site) citation

FDA (2008). Effect of the use of antimicrobials in food producing animals on pathogen load: Systematic review of the published literature. www.fda.gov/cvm/antimicrobial/PathRpt.PDF Accessed January 11, 2012.

Tables/Figures/Illustrations : Tables should be self contained and complement, but not duplicate information contained in the text. The table number (given as an Arabic numeral) should be given at the top, followed by a concise title. Give essential details as footnotes. Keep the number of columns to a minimum. Column headings should be brief, with the units of measurement clearly stated in parentheses. Where one unit applies to all the data in the body of the table include it in the title. Cite all tables in the text, in numerical order at first mention. Significant differences between means in columns or rows should be indicated by superscript letters, and accompanied by a standard statement underneath the table, e.g. “Means in columns not sharing a common superscript differ significantly (P<0.05)”.

Figures: Number all figures/illustrations consecutively, in order of appearance in the text, using Arabic numerals. Keep lettering

on illustrations to a minimum and include essential details in the legend. Tables/Figures/illustrations etc. should be submitted along with the main text of the paper with each on a new page, and should take account of the page size of the journal. Wherever possible, figures should be suitable for subsequent direct photographic reproduction.

Coloured figures : Use of coloured photographs is discouraged. If found necessary, the photographs should be submitted as good quality, glossy colour prints.

Abbreviation and units: Use only standard abbreviations. The word ‘Figure’ should be shortened to Fig. unless starting a sentence. SI units (metre, kilogram etc.) should be used wherever possible. Statistics and measurements should always be given in figures; i.e. 15mm, except where the number begins the sentence. When the number does not refer to a unit measurement (e.g. 15mm), it is spelt out, except where the number is greater than nine.

Style and format of short communications: A short communication should be a maximum of 1500 words. It contains a very brief abstract followed by a brief introduction, text including tables and figures and a brief conclusion followed by references. No subheadings are to be included except for the abstract and reference section. Format, tables and figures must conform to the conventions of the Journal.

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